

**A hermeneutic phenomenological study to explore
postgraduate nursing students' lived experience of
workplace support to apply learning in practice**

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Abstract

Strategic policies were identified from government, professional and healthcare organisations for postgraduate nurse education (PGNE) to support the capacity and capability of the nursing workforce to meet healthcare needs. However, iterative literature reviews throughout my professional doctorate identified limited research and understanding relating to postgraduate nursing students' (PGNS) experiences of workplace support to apply learning in practice (ALiP).

Therefore, the overarching aim of my hermeneutic phenomenological study was to make an original contribution to knowledge relating to PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP. The methodological framework is underpinned by a constructionist ontology, interpretivist epistemology and hermeneutic phenomenology that assume multiple realities and truths. Justification for the framework and methodological decisions is underpinned by the aim of understanding the subjective, lived experiences of PGNS. Following university ethical approval for the study, relevant gatekeeper permissions were sought to purposefully recruit voluntary participants enrolled on a range of postgraduate nursing programmes. The study's inclusion and exclusion criteria aimed to ensure participation of PGNS with experiences of undertaking postgraduate education while working in nursing practice.

Individual audio recorded telephone interviews were undertaken to collect and transcribe an accurate description of the verbal sharing of the participants' PGNS experiences. Data interpretation of parts (individual transcriptions) and the whole (collective transcriptions) was guided by the hermeneutic spiral, frameworks for interpretation and rigour, and my fore-structures of understanding. Within this thesis findings are presented as offerings inclusive of rich, in-depth interpretation and analytical discussion with anonymous crafted extracts to bring to life the participants' subjective lived experiences. The offerings chapters critically explore the phenomena revealed through data interpretation to illuminate further understanding and meaning of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP, and transparently discuss methodological strengths and limitations. The outcomes of my research aim to provide an opportunity for relevant professional colleagues to further understanding, knowledge, research and practice relating to PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP.

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Contents

Abstract.....	ii
Acknowledgement.....	iii
List of Abbreviations.....	1
Chapter 1 - Introduction.....	3
1.1 Initial rationale and context of enquiry.....	3
1.2 Context of thesis.....	7
Chapter 2 - Background Contexts.....	9
2.1 Introduction.....	9
2.2 The context of postgraduate nurse education.....	9
2.2.1 Defining PGNE.....	9
2.2.2 Contemporary factors influencing PGNE.....	11
2.2.3 Understanding how registered nurses may become situated in PGNE.....	16
2.3 Setting the context of postgraduate learning and application of learning in nursing practice.....	18
2.3.1 Pedagogical perspectives influencing the context of learning and application of PG learning in practice.....	18
2.3.2 HEI perspectives influencing the context of learning and application of PG learning in practice.....	21
2.3.3 Strategic nursing perspectives influencing the context of learning and ALiP.....	23
2.4 The context of workplace support to apply learning to practice.....	24
2.4.1 Defining the context of workplace learning.....	24
2.4.2 Understanding context of workplace support for PGNS.....	25
2.5 Chapter synthesis.....	30
Chapter 3 – Iterative Literature Review.....	32
3.1 Contextualising the literature review.....	32
3.2. Part one literature search and review approaches.....	36
3.2.1 Overarching approach.....	36
3.2.2 Part one literature search strategy and findings.....	37
3.3 Part one literature review findings.....	43

3.3.1 The landscape of professional policy literature relating to the concept of workplace support for PGNS to translate learning in practice	43
3.3.2 The landscape of professional research literature relating to the concept of workplace support for PGNS to translate learning in practice	44
3.3.3 Conceptualising workplace support for PGNS to translate learning in practice.....	45
3.3.4 Factors influencing workplace support for PGNS to translate learning in practice	48
3.3.5 Understanding the part one findings to inform research development.....	51
3.4 Part two literature search and review approach	53
3.4.1 Overarching approach	53
3.4.2 Part two literature search strategy and findings.....	54
3.5 Part two literature review findings	59
3.5.1 Furthering understanding of the research landscape	59
3.5.2 Perceptions associated with the impact of PGNE	61
3.5.3 Further factors and challenges to PGNE	62
3.6 Bringing together the parts one and two literature reviews.....	64
Chapter 4 – Methodological Context.....	67
4.1 Introduction.....	67
4.2 Methodological framework	67
4.3 Framework for rigour	73
4.4 Ethical approval.....	74
4.4.1 Ethical approval process.....	74
4.4.2 Ethical framework	75
4.5 My hermeneutic phenomenological approach.....	75
4.5.1 Methodology	75
4.5.2 My approach to reflexivity	78
4.5.3 Sampling and recruitment strategy.....	79
4.5.4 Data collection	81
4.5.5 Data interpretation	85
4.5.6 Approach to presenting the research outcomes	90
4.5.7 Dissemination plan.....	91

4.6 Ethical approaches	92
4.6.1 Autonomy, veracity and informed consent	92
4.6.2 Privacy and confidentiality.....	93
4.6.3 Justice and inclusiveness.....	94
4.6.4 Benefits and harms	95
Chapter 5 - Invitation to Offerings	97
5.1 Introduction.....	97
5.2 Approaches to the part three literature search and review	100
Chapter 6 - Offering 1: Contextualising Being.....	104
6.1 Introduction.....	104
6.2 Being and becoming a PGNS	105
6.3 Temporality of self-experiences of Being	108
6.4 The significance of contextualising being.....	112
Chapter 7 - Offering 2: Furthering understanding of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP	114
7.1 Introduction.....	114
7.2 Fore-havings of workplace support	115
7.3 Workplace supporting	118
7.3.1 Workplace supporters and workplace supporting	119
7.3.2 Workplace supporting being there or not being there	121
7.3.3 The giving, taking and allowing of workplace support.....	124
7.3.4 Curiosity of asking and knowing.....	127
7.4 Furthering understanding of PGNS ALiP	131
7.4.1 Furthering understanding and the 'doing' of ALiP	131
7.4.2 Bringing and contributing ALiP	135
7.5 Bringing together the parts: Workplace support to ALiP	136
7.5.1 Moods of workplace support to ALiP	137
7.5.2 Being with resistance	140
7.5.3 The being there of workplace support cultures and the could be possibilities.....	144
7.6 Temporal and situational being	146

7.6.1 Temporal and situational everydayness	147
7.6.2 Inbetween experiences of workplace support to ALiP	148
7.7 Reflexive thoughts in furthering understanding of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP	149
Chapter 8 - Offering 3: Self-being	151
8.1 Introduction.....	151
8.2 Self-being and changing of being a PGNS.....	152
8.3 Affirming being a PGNS.....	155
8.4 Towards future possibilities.....	157
Chapter 9 - Offering 4: Inviting Curiosity	159
9.1 Introduction.....	159
9.2 PGNS presencing	160
9.3 PGNS in workplace supporting	162
9.4 Challenging presuppositions of ALiP	164
9.5 Professional being	165
Chapter 10 – Bringing together the parts and whole: Discussion and synthesis of research	168
10.1 Reflexive considerations	168
10.2 Discussion and synthesis of research offerings	168
10.2.1 Beyond becoming and being a PGNS.....	169
10.2.2 Workplace support and supporting.....	172
10.2.3 Professional being	173
10.2.4 The thread of practical wisdom	176
10.3 Strengths and limitations.....	188
10.4 Reflexive synthesis	190
Chapter 11 - Calls to further thinking and enquiry.....	193
11.1 Introduction.....	193
11.2 Reconnecting with PGNE landscapes.....	193
11.3 Calls to further thinking and enquiry.....	194
11.3.1 Being a PGNS	194

11.3.2 Furthering workplace support for PGNS to ALiP	196
11.3.3 A call to wider professional considerations.....	198
11.3.4 Continuing to explore the thread of phronesis within PGNE, nursing practice and nurse education	200
11.4 Concluding statement	201
References.....	203
Appendices	229
Appendix 1: HEI Masters Degree Aims.....	230
Appendix 2: Generic themes relating to UK strategic postgraduate level descriptors.....	231
Appendix 3: Key attributes and characteristics associated with ALNP	232
Appendix 4: Synthesis of background contexts.....	233
Appendix 5: Supporting literature search strategy implementation.....	234
Appendix 6: Theme development supporting literature review	249
Appendix 7: Evidence of ethical approval	251
Appendix 8: Gatekeeper permission request	252
Appendix 9: Evidence of gatekeeper permissions.....	253
Appendix 10: Recruitment email	255
Appendix 11: Participant information sheet.....	256
Appendix 12: Potential response emails	261
Appendix 13: Informed consent form	263
Appendix 14: Supporting outline interview guide.....	266
Appendix 15: Being with the hermeneutic spiral.....	268
Appendix 16: Being present and applying the data interpretation framework	271
Appendix 17: Communities of practice framework	279

List of Figures

Figure 1: Reflective Framework – pedagogical considerations when setting the context of workplace support for PGNS to ALiP	26
Figure 2: A part and whole perspective of the literature reviews.....	35
Figure 3: Summary of part one literature search and findings	40
Figure 4: Overarching and key themes identified from the part one literature review.....	43
Figure 5: Bringing together identified components relating to the concept of support for PGNS..	47
Figure 6: Summary of part two literature search and findings.....	57
Figure 7: Overarching and key themes identified from the part two literature review	59
Figure 8: Framework for evaluating rigour.....	74
Figure 9: Outline Ethical Framework	75
Figure 10: Criteria for my research study	80
Figure 11: My Data Interpretation Framework.....	88
Figure 12: Overview of the Offerings Chapters	99
Figure 13: Offering 1 parts of the whole - Contextualising being in coming to understanding PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP	104
Figure 14: Offering 2 parts of the whole - Furthering understanding of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP	114
Figure 15: Adapted Reflective Framework – pedagogical considerations when setting the context of workplace support for PGNS to ALiP post-data interpretation	118
Figure 16: Iterative Reflective Framework – reflexive pedagogical considerations when setting the context of workplace support for PGNS to ALiP	123
Figure 17: Offering 3 parts of the whole – Self-being	151
Figure 18: Offering 4 parts and whole – Inviting curiosity	159
Figure 19: Bringing together the parts and the whole	169
Figure 20: Strategic contexts towards PGNE	233
Figure 21: Example critical analysis tool template.....	245
Figure 22: Example data transcription template	268
Figure 23: Phase 1-2 data interpretation template	270
Figure 24: Example of working with the Phase 1-2 data interpretation template.....	272
Figure 25: Example of working with the Phase 3a data interpretation template	273
Figure 26: Example of working with the Phase 3b data interpretation template.....	274
Figure 27: Working with the emerging shared meanings and expressions of shared connections	275
Figure 28: Example of returning to the Phase 3a data interpretation template	276

Figure 29: Prompt questions used to support supervisory team critical conversations and challenge through data interpretation	277
Figure 30: Guide developed to support Phase 4 and 5 data interpretation	278
Figure 31: Identifying the foundational components of my community of practice	279
Figure 32: Community of practice framework	280

List of Tables

Table 1: Overview of the part literature reviews within my professional doctorate enquiry.....	33
Table 2: Application of the PEO model to identify key search terms for the part one literature review search strategy	38
Table 3: Application of the PEO model to identify key search terms for the part two literature review search strategy	55
Table 4: Summary of the approaches that guided the part three literature search and review...	102
Table 5: Generic themes relating to UK strategic postgraduate level descriptors	231
Table 6: Key attributes and characteristics associated with ALNP	232
Table 7: Application of the PEO model to identify key search terms for parts one and two literature search strategies.....	234
Table 8: The inclusion and exclusion criteria applied to parts one and two literature search strategies	235
Table 9: Data sources used for parts one and two literature search strategies.....	236
Table 10: Key abbreviations used within the example literature search implementation templates	238
Table 11: Example of literature search implementation template	239
Table 12: Example of stage one literature search implementation template	240
Table 13: Key abbreviations used within the example literature search implementation template	241
Table 14: Example of stage two literature search implementation template	242
Table 15: Summary of part one literature search findings	243
Table 16: Summary of part two literature search findings.....	244
Table 17: Example of theme development from thematic and reflexive thematic analysis of the part one literature review findings	249
Table 18: Extraction of theme data to support literature review	250

List of Abbreviations

The list below includes full terms for abbreviations used within this thesis.

Abbreviation	Full Term
A	Appendix (number)
ACP	Advanced Clinical Practitioner
AEI	Approved Education Institution
ALiP	Application of learning in practice / Apply learning in practice
ALNP	Advanced level nursing practice
ANP	Advanced nursing practice
APN	Advanced Practice Nurse
C	Chapter
CNO	Chief Nursing Officer
CNOD	Chief Nursing Officer Department
CNOW	Chief Nursing Officer Wales
COVID-19	Coronavirus disease-2019
CPD	Continued / Continuing Professional Development
DoH	Department of Health
ECCF	Early Clinical Career Fellows
EHEA	European Higher Education Area
EoR	Expressions of Rigour
EPCEU	European Parliament and the Council of the European Union
F	Figure (number)
FHEQ	The Framework for Higher Education Qualifications of Degree-Awarding Bodies in England, Wales and Northern Ireland
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HE	Higher education
HEE	Health Education England
HEI	Higher Education Institution(s)
ICN	International Council of Nurses
ICN NP/APNN	International Council of Nurses Nurse Practitioner / Advanced Practice Nursing Network
MSTI	Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation
NA	Nurse Advanced
NAGSPE	The National Advisory Group on the Safety of Patients in England

Abbreviation	Full Term
NES	NHS Education for Scotland
NHS	National Health Service
NIPEC	Northern Ireland Practice and Education Council for Nursing and Midwifery
NLIAH	National Leadership and Innovation Agency for Healthcare
NMC	Nursing and Midwifery Council
PEO	Population, Exposure and Outcome model
PG	Postgraduate
PGCPSNC	Postgraduate certification for a perioperative speciality nursing course
PGE	Postgraduate education
PGN	Postgraduate nurse
PGNE	Postgraduate nurse education
PGNS	Postgraduate nursing student(s)
PLP	Practice learning partners
PRNE	Pre-registration nurse education
QAA	Quality Assurance Agency
QAAHE	Quality Assurance Agency for Higher Education
QAAS	Quality Assurance Agency Scotland
QF – EHEA	Qualifications Framework for the European Higher Education Area
RCN	Royal College of Nursing
SCPHN	Specialist Community Public Health Nurse
SCQF	Scottish Credit and Qualifications Framework
SCV	Social critical vocationalism
s.l	No place of publication
SLAiP	Standards to support learning and assessment in practice
T	Table (number)
UEC	University Ethics Committee
UK	United Kingdom
WHO	World Health Organisation

Chapter 1 - Introduction

1.1 Initial rationale and context of enquiry

Prior to commencing my professional doctorate, my professional awareness of strategic healthcare drivers, nursing visions and anecdotal experiences of practice evoked professional curiosity and motivation to explore postgraduate nursing students' (PGNS) experiences of workplace support to apply learning in practice (ALiP). Within the context of global healthcare delivery, there was a need for the nursing workforce to respond to increasing health inequalities, complexities of disease, technological healthcare advances and economic constraints (World Health Organisation (WHO), 2016a; Chief Nursing Officer Department (CNOD), 2017a; Scottish Government, 2017). While also providing safe, effective, evidence-based, person-centred care (Scottish Government, 2017; Health Education England (HEE), no date).

Globally, nursing roles with a masters level of postgraduate nurse education (PGNE) were associated as critical and essential to the capacity and capability of the nursing workforce to meet such future healthcare needs (Finlay, 2012; Willis, 2015; WHO, 2016a; CNOD, 2017a; Scottish Government, 2017; CNOD, 2018; HEE, no date). Postgraduate (PG) models of nurse education were also acknowledged as essential to transforming nursing roles beyond the initial point of registration (CNOD, 2017a; Scottish Government, 2017; CNOD, 2018). Consequently, there was increasing global demand for masters level PGNE to develop part of the nursing workforce to advanced levels of practice (Willis, 2015; WHO, 2016a; CNOD, 2017b; Scottish Government, 2017; CNOD, 2018; HEE, no date).

Within United Kingdom (UK) nursing practice, the Nursing and Midwifery Council (NMC) professional regulatory body for registered nurses stated that nurses have an individual professional responsibility to undertake learning and share knowledge and skills with colleagues to benefit those receiving care (NMC, 2018e). There was also a clear strategic need for national and local infrastructures to ensure that nurses have the right targeted education and support to enable them to confidently and competently translate their learning to maximise the potential of their nursing roles (Willis, 2015; WHO, 2016a; Scottish Government, 2017; CNOD, 2018).

From a UK higher education (HE) perspective some HE institution (HEI) pedagogical approaches also focused on educational experiences making a difference to communities served (Quality Assurance Agency for Higher Education (QAAHE), 2011; Quality Assurance Agency Scotland (QAAS), no date). As well as transitional approaches to support students to transfer their learning during their programme of study (QAAHE, 2011; QAAS, no date).

These strategic healthcare drivers along with my anecdotal experiences of practice, professional curiosity and motivation influenced my decision to undertake a professional doctorate to explore PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP. The nature of my professional doctorate included ongoing assessment at key stages throughout the taught and research components of the programme. This included continuous engagement with reviewing the literature to support formative and summative module assessments, research proposal development, research study approval and implementation. Subsequently, the structure of this thesis demonstrates the iterative use of literature at different stages of my professional doctorate. Particularly to emphasise how this furthered my understanding of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP and informed the developing philosophical and methodological approaches that underpinned my study.

My initial curiosity about PGNS experiences of applying learning to practice led to two iterative literature reviews being undertaken to support justification for my area of research beyond my motivations and professional insights. The literature reviews identified clear ongoing global strategic visions, drivers, and desired outcomes for advancing and transforming nursing roles with a level of PGNE to meet future nursing workforce, healthcare, and person-centred care needs. The findings also revealed that PGNS may experience variation in the provision of PGNE, workplace support infrastructures and the attitudes of others. These aspects influenced contrasting perspectives of PGNS feeling enabled or motivated to implement changes in practice. The seminal Willis (2015) review of the future education and training of registered nurses also identified deficits in registered nurses being supported to undertake PGNE. From a methodological perspective, the literature reviews significantly identified an absence of qualitative research relating to my chosen subject area. Particularly, limited use of lived experience methodologies specifically exploring PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP. Therefore, the literature review findings strengthened the rationale and direction of my proposed research area towards understanding PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP.

Subsequently, this thesis presents and provides justification for a hermeneutic phenomenological study to explore PGNS lived experiences of workplace support to ALiP. My research was underpinned by constructionist and interpretivist views which assume multiple realities, truths and subjectivity of lived experiences as opposed to a positivist view focused on providing an objective, definitive, singular truth (Fleming, Gaidys and Robb, 2003; Denscombe, 2010; Kalfe, 2011). The ontological, epistemological and methodological approaches that underpinned my hermeneutic phenomenological research were influenced by the philosophical work of Martin Heidegger (Heidegger, 1962/1927; 1996/1927). In addition to drawing upon philosophical hermeneutic aspects of Hans-Georg Gadamer (Gadamer, 2004/1960). The underpinning philosophical assumptions of Heidegger and Gadamer also aligned with my chosen

world view that assumes our lived experiences are subjective and influenced by our temporal being in a socio-historic world (Heidegger, 1962/1927; Gadamer, 2004/1960).

I was drawn to Heidegger's (1993a/1927) fundamental ontology that relates to questioning the meaning of being. I assumed this approach would bring meaning to understanding the lived experience of being a PGNS set within the context of workplace support to ALiP. However, I was aware that Heidegger's (1962/1927; 1996/1927) work is grounded in philosophy and philosophical ways of coming to thinking rather than an intention to provide a prescriptive, structured research methodology or method. Subsequently, Heidegger's (1962/1927; 1996/1927) work provided the philosophical underpinnings of my research guiding my approach to understanding the meaning of the lived experiences of being a PGNS. Key philosophical underpinnings related to Heidegger's (1962/1927; 1996/1927) position of the concept of phenomenology that seeks to reveal the concealed or taken for granted phenomenon within our human lived experiences. Heidegger's (1996/1927) Introduction to the exposition of the question of the meaning of being, brings together the preliminary concept of phenomenology:

This self-showing is nothing arbitrary, nor is it something like an appearing. The being of beings can least of all be something "behind which" something else stand as, something that "does not appear". (Heidegger, 1996/1927, p. 31)

Heidegger (1996/1927) positioned the distinction that phenomenon is something that does not initially show itself based on the assumption that it may be concealed or covered up. Heidegger's (1996/1927) concept of phenomenology brought to my attention the possibility that phenomena may be concealed and brought to light. Within this thesis, Heidegger's (1962/1927) further work relating to the hermeneutic circle of understanding and philosophical notions also underpinned my way of bringing phenomenon to light through my research.

'In the circle is hidden a positive possibility of the most primordial kind of knowing' (Heidegger, 1962/1927, p.195).

The hermeneutic circle guided my approach to furthering understanding and surfacing meaning from the PGNS lived experiences of workplace support to ALiP. Heidegger (1962/1927) also positioned the importance of coming into the circle in the right way by bringing our own fore-structures of understanding and historicity to interpretation. The methodological chapter of the thesis positions how my approaches to data interpretation were influenced by the hermeneutic circle of understanding. Furthermore, the offerings (findings) chapters reflexively and openly demonstrate how I brought my fore-structures of understanding to the ways of interpreting the participants' lived experiences (data).

As part of Heidegger's (1962/1927) positioning of the concept of phenomenology, Heidegger (1962/1927) drew upon the Greek term 'logos' with the term 'phenomenon'. The term 'logos' highlighted a hermeneutic focus and acknowledgement of the interpretation of speech and language (Heidegger,

1962/1927). Within Heidegger's (1993c/1959) later work, Heidegger positions this as a way of letting things show as being unconcealed.

In contemporary research, hermeneutic phenomenological methodologies are also associated with seeking meaning of phenomenon with the purpose of understanding the lived human experience (Crist and Tanner, 2003). Crowther and Thomson (2023) position that bringing together phenomenological and hermeneutic aspects of Heidegger and Gadamer's philosophical work is invaluable to seeking a greater human understanding. Furthermore, contemporary hermeneutic phenomenological research aims to bringing together two key questions; the phenomenological question concerned with what is the lived experience like; and the hermeneutic question of how the lived experience is meaningful (Crowther and Thomson, 2023). Collectively, the concerns of these two questions aim to support a deeper understanding and meaning of the phenomenon revealed through hermeneutic phenomenological research (Lavery, 2003; Crowther and Thomson, 2023). Subsequently, both philosophical and contemporary methodological approaches to hermeneutic phenomenology guided my research study and methodology. These approaches aimed to further understanding and illuminate meaning from the PGNS lived experiences of workplace support to ALiP throughout the research component of my professional doctorate. Furthermore, these approaches acknowledge the socio-historic, cultural contexts and contemporary time of my research.

To set further context around my ontological approach to enquiry as a professional doctorate student undertaking a hermeneutic phenomenological research study. My role and engagement throughout my study was purposefully immersive and reflexive. These approaches aimed to support methodological and philosophical congruence with Heidegger's (1962/1927) hermeneutic circle. Particularly by openly bringing my fore-structures of understanding to interpretation of the participants' lived experiences. My engagement with my research was also influenced by Gadamer's (2004/1960) notions of prejudice and historicity. Gadamer (2004/1960, p. 274) associated the term prejudice with the 'courage to make use of your own understandings' as part of interpretation. As opposed to the contemporary use of the term prejudice which may be associated with negative connotations. Gadamer's (2004/1960) notions of prejudice and historicity emphasised my immersive role within my research and the importance of reflexively attuning to my understandings as a way of ensuring rigour and the quality of my research. These notions also brought awareness to situating, challenging and furthering my professional knowledge and understanding within the context of my research, aligning to the nature of professional doctorate studies (QAA, 2020a).

Based on the philosophical and methodological underpinnings of my study, the research offerings (findings) aim to further understanding and illuminate meaning about PGNS experiences of workplace support. The research offerings also aim to extend beyond the context of this thesis. Particularly, as my hermeneutic phenomenological approaches seek to invite relevant professional peers to lean in and

think further about PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP across professional, academic, research, and practice contexts. Potentially bridging and connecting the application of learning across academic and workplace contexts to enhance nursing roles, the delivery of person-centred care and the experience of the learning professional.

In setting out on the research phase of professional doctorate, I was drawn to Smythe's (2011) position of lived experience research.

...always it is to remember what matters; to strive to enhance the experiences of those we go on to walk with through similar experiences. Yes, phenomenon has been articulated, but always it comes back to people, like you and me. Life is only ever lived as 'my experience'. (Smythe, 2011, p. 51)

This reflexively called to thinking the importance of revealing phenomenon through my research in harmony with participants' lived experiences being at the centre and soul of my approaches and role as a professional doctorate student.

1.2 Context of thesis

The development of this thesis was informed by a preliminary body of work and enquiry into PGNS experiences of application of learning acquired through the taught stages of my professional doctorate. This thesis presents the subsequent research stage to specifically explore PGNS lived experiences of workplace support to ALiP.

The narrative style of this thesis is partially written in the first person to align with my immersive and participatory role as a research student undertaking a hermeneutic phenomenological study. The use of tense also aims to engage and convey to readers a transitional narrative through the stages of my research journey. Collectively, the writing styles aim to emphasise my journey of enquiry, reflexivity and learning through my professional doctorate. To demonstrate the iterative nature of my research and connections between chapters, relevant sections are cross referenced throughout this thesis for example, appendices (A), chapters (C), figures (F) and tables (T) e.g. Figure 10 (F10).

Chapters 1-3 set context and background for the area of research. Chapter 1 provides insight into the personal and professional rationale for the area of research and foregrounds the philosophical and methodological underpinnings of my hermeneutic phenomenological study. Chapter 2 purposefully focuses on presenting the fundamental, underpinning contexts associated with PGNE, workplace support and ALiP. Chapter 3 outlines the iterative approach used to review relevant literature through my professional doctorate. The initial literature reviews aimed to constructively challenge and strengthen the

rationale for my study prior to seeking ethical approval to implement my research. The literature reviews also contributed to deepening my critical insight and understanding of my chosen subject area which I could reflexively draw upon to enhance interpretation of the research data. Based on the chosen hermeneutic phenomenological philosophical and methodological underpinnings, the initial chapters do not aim to predict anticipated issues or findings that may emerge from my research study. As it is assumed that issues should be uncovered from seeking to understand the unpredicted, subjective lived experiences of PGNS.

Chapter 4 presents the philosophical underpinnings and methodological frameworks applied to my hermeneutic phenomenological research study. This chapter also addresses key ethical principles and considerations that led to ethical approval and research implementation.

Chapter 5 sets the philosophical context of the research study findings termed as 'offerings' from my interpretation of the participants' PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP. Subsequently, Chapters 6-9 present the research offerings from my hermeneutic phenomenological interpretation of the participants' PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP. Each chapter aims to convey to the reader the phenomena revealed, and the meaning surfaced to further understanding of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP. The chapters are supported by integrated analytical discussion and reviewed literature to deepen and reflexively challenge insights into the phenomena revealed and broaden horizons of understanding (Gadamer, 2004/1960). Collectively, these chapters invite relevant professional peers to lean in and think further about understanding PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP within the context of their professional practice.

Chapters 10 and 11 bring together the parts and whole of my professional doctorate research. Chapter 10 provides a discussion and synthesis of the research offerings. This chapter also acknowledges the temporal context of the offerings, methodological strengths and limitations, and reflexive considerations. Chapter 11 aims to extend thinking beyond the research offerings, presenting potential areas for further research. Furthermore, inviting relevant professional peers to creatively consider opportunities to extend understanding, research, and practice to further PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP.

Chapter 2 - Background Contexts

2.1 Introduction

Reflexively, I used my professional strategic awareness, experiences and subject knowledge acquired through the initial stages of my professional doctorate to identify key contexts to support further exploration of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP. This led to three key contexts being identified and explored from theoretical, pedagogical and professional perspectives within this chapter: PGNE, application of learning in nursing practice and the workplace. It was assumed that exploration into these key contexts was essential to deepen and illuminate preliminary understanding of PGNS experience of workplace support to ALiP across HE, nursing, and research domains. As well as providing an initial lens to understand how post-registration nurses may become situated in PGNE.

In developing this chapter, I was provided with reflexive opportunities to consider my theoretical, pedagogical, and professional assumptions prior to implementation of my research study and data interpretation.

2.2 The context of postgraduate nurse education

2.2.1 Defining PGNE

UK HEI are associated with the approval, design, delivery, and accreditation of PG education (PGE). Therefore, this section sets out how PGE is defined from UK HE perspectives to support understanding PGNE throughout this thesis and to contextualise interpretation of the research outcomes.

Historically, the 1999 Bologna Declaration led to the development of the Qualifications Framework for the European Higher Education Area (QF-EHEA) (Ministry of Science, Technology, and Innovation (MSTI), 2005). At the time of enquiry, the QF-EHEA underpinned UK HEI qualification frameworks (MSTI, 2005). The significance of the QF- EHEA (MSTI, 2005) to my area of research, is that it provides a cyclical lifelong learning framework to inform the development of prescriptive, national HE frameworks including masters level education. Further detailing qualifications, level descriptors, academic credits, learning outcomes, indicators, and notional workloads for masters level degrees (MSTI, 2005).

In the UK, masters degree descriptors align to a level 7 qualification within the Framework for HE Qualifications of Degree-Awarding Bodies in England, Wales and Northern Ireland (FHEQ) and level 11 of the Scottish Credit and Qualifications Framework (SCQF) (Quality Assurance Agency (QAA), 2014; 2020b). The masters degree descriptor also includes collective reference to; full masters degrees, PG

certificates, or diplomas for the purpose of research, specialised / advanced study, or professional practice (QAA, 2020b).

Focusing on the context of PGNE, the QAAHE (2019) withdrew outdated 2001 nursing programme subject benchmarks. At the time of enquiry, the 2009 nursing benchmark statements for qualifying awards for professions in Scotland were stated as under review (QAAHE, 2019).

In seeking to further understand the specific context of masters level HE. The QAA recommended that HEI masters degrees should offer students at least one of the QAA (2020b) stated aims (A1). As responsibility had been devolved to UK HEIs to provide at least one of the masters aims, there may be potential diversity of aims offered or associated with different HEI masters degrees (QAA, 2018a; 2018d; 2020b). However, across the QAA (2020b) masters degree aims there was a focus on students bringing prior subject or professional knowledge and experiences to masters level education (A1). In the context of masters degree education for nursing students, this may influence assumptions or requirements that nurses come into PGNE with previous professional and academic experiences.

The QAA also devolved responsibility to individual HEIs for setting associated masters award titles, credit values, qualification descriptors, specific requirements and delivery methods (QAA, 2014; 2018a; 2020b). Subsequently, there may be varied approaches to masters degree programme aims, requirements, delivery methods and outcomes across HEIs. However, standardisation of some components may exist for PGNE programmes influenced by professional regulatory body requirements. For example, the NMC as the independent regulator for nurses and midwives in the UK, and healthcare associates in England require HEI to achieve NMC approval for the delivery of some specific pre- and post-registration nursing and midwifery programmes with set NMC educational standards and requirements (NMC, 2022b; 2022d). In alignment with the NMC, HEI delivering such programmes will be referred to through this thesis as Approved Education Institutions (AEIs),

... the status awarded to an institution, or part of an institution, or combination of institutions that works in partnership with practice placement and work placed learning providers. AEIs will have provided us with assurance that they are accountable and capable of delivering NMC approved education programmes. (NMC, 2018c, p. 13)

To seek further insight into defining PGE, a scoping activity of UK HEI quality organisational descriptors for PGE was undertaken (A2). The activity identified several key themes associated with a PGE including:

- Critical knowledge and understanding
- Ability to deal with unpredictable and complex issues

- Critical awareness / insight
- Originality
- Creativity
- Critical approaches to knowledge, understanding, reflection and research
- Autonomous approach to professional learning
- Being at the forefront of practice and change
- Professionalism (SCQF Partnership, 2012; QAAHE, 2013; QAA, 2014; 2020b; QAAS, no date).

These key themes provided insight into the potential characteristics, facets and outcomes that may be associated with nurses undertaking PGNE.

However, in the context of PGNE programmes masters degrees characteristics, facets and outcomes may vary due to decisions and responsibilities about these aspects being devolved to individual HEIs. Subsequently, within this thesis the term 'postgraduate education' (PGE) will be used as an overarching term inclusive of masters SCQF level 11 or FHEQ level 7 PG modules, certificates, diplomas, programmes or full masters degrees. Inclusion of the term 'education' was purposeful to mitigate a focus on the overall educational award or outcome and alternatively emphasise a focus on educational experiences throughout PGE.

Based on the research topic the term 'postgraduate nurse education' (PGNE) will be used to overarchingly refer to PGE within the context of nursing. Use of this term also aligns to terms used within associated nurse education policy literature (National Health Service (NHS), 2017; CNOD, 2018; National Leadership and Innovation Agency for Healthcare (NLIAH), no date).

2.2.2 Contemporary factors influencing PGNE

This section provides specific insight into factors potentially influencing the contemporary context of PGNE within the UK. There is a broader, historical narrative relating to the emergence of masters level education within the context of pre-registration nurse education (PRNE). However, exploration into this area was deemed beyond the scope of my research topic and study.

Definition of the contemporary context was largely influenced by the most recently published relevant, strategic policy literature influencing HE, nursing and healthcare practice prior to research approval and implementation. Therefore, strategic literature publication dates mainly ranged across 2004 – 2020.

Changes to PRNE requirements

From historic and global perspectives, the delivery of initial nurse education has ranged from school level education, apprenticeship models, training programmes and diplomas to university degrees and masters level pre-registration nursing programmes (WHO, 2009). The WHO (2009) Global Standards for the Initial Education of Professional Nurses and Midwives identified that global variation existed across initial nurse education from secondary school to university level education, qualification and registration requirements.

To reduce educational disparity and strengthen global nursing services, the WHO (2009) set out that future nurse education standards lie 'in good preparation at the professional, first-degree level' (WHO, 2009, p. 10). Initial professional nurse registration would therefore require a HEI or university nurse education programme to be completed at degree level with regulatory authority validation (WHO, 2009). This change led to a period of WHO transitional requirements towards degree level nurse education (WHO, 2009).

In the UK context, changing healthcare needs relating to advances in technology, financial costs, better care for long-term conditions and increasing community care, highlighted the need for the future nursing workforce to be a key contributor to quality healthcare and successful healthcare reform (Scottish Executive, 2006; DoH, 2006; 2009). Subsequently, UK strategic reports including Modernising Nursing Careers (Scottish Executive, 2006) and the High Quality Workforce Review (DoH, 2009) recognised the need to review the direction of UK PRNE.

The High Quality Workforce Review (DoH, 2009) acknowledged the need to shift towards a graduate level registered nursing workforce to support the achievement of high quality care objectives. At the time, the DoH (2009) review pended outcomes of a NMC consultation and review of PRNE. This being the initial pre-registration nursing programme that must be completed by a student nurse to meet the NMC criteria and competencies for UK NMC registration to practice as a nurse (NMC, 2010).

The NMC consultation and review of PRNE acknowledged changing healthcare needs and environments, and quality of care as factors influencing future nurse education (NMC, 2010). Further highlighting the impact of changing healthcare needs on the future professional attitudes, competencies, knowledge, skills and standards that would be required at the point of initial nurse registration (NMC, 2010). Similar to the WHO (2009) developments, the NMC (2010) review resulted in a transitional period towards new pre-registration standards for nurse education. The new NMC standards set a minimum outcome of a degree award (UK FHEQ level 6 or SCQF level 9 or 10) for PRNE delivered by NMC AEI (NMC, 2010).

Of further significance is that the WHO (2009) acknowledged that the educational shift towards a minimum pre-registration degree requirement may provide a foundation for the development of

advanced nurse education beyond the initial point of registration. The DoH (2009) also set a national agenda for modernising post-registration nurse education and career pathways to support high quality healthcare. Further highlighting post-registration education and advanced level practice for extended, advanced and autonomous nursing roles. However, at the time the DoH (2009) and WHO (2009) agendas did not set out specific definitions, generic education standards or levels for advanced, post-registration practice.

With the shift to an all-graduate nursing profession at the point of initial registration and the recognised need for post-registration nurse educational agendas. These factors may have influenced transitional opportunities to shift the concept of post-registration nurse education and advanced level practice towards PGNE. With the potential to support academic and professional career development opportunities for nurses beyond initial degree level to PG levels of nurse education.

NMC post-registration standards influencing PGNE

The NMC set and monitor professional registration standards for nurses practicing in the UK, relating to education, training, conduct and performance including some NMC AEI post-registration specialist programmes (NMC, 2019b). In 2004 the NMC set specific standards of proficiencies for NMC Specialist Community Public Health Nurse (SCPHN) registration influenced by the NMC role to protect the public and the distinct public protection characteristics of SCPHN roles (NMC, 2004; no date). Subsequently, to achieve NMC SCPHN registration, nurses were required to achieve NMC SCPHN standards of proficiency as part of completing a minimum degree level AEI SCPHN programme (NMC, 2004; no date). At the time of enquiry, to achieve NMC registration as a nurse prescriber, nurses were also required to achieve specific NMC standards of proficiency as part of completing a minimum level equivalent to a bachelor's degree AEI post-registration prescribing programme (NMC, 2018c).

Of significance to exploring contemporary factors influencing PGNE, is that the NMC standards for SCPHN and prescribing programmes provided AEIs with the flexibility to set programmes above the minimum degree level to higher PGE academic levels e.g. SCQF level 10-11 (NMC, 2004; 2018c). As part of my contextual enquiry, scoping exercises of UK AEI generic SCPHN programmes in 2020 identified that 10 of 18 programmes were delivered at PG level and of seven available Scottish AEI independent and supplementary prescribing programmes, five programmes were delivered at a PG level (SCQF level 10 or 11) (NMC, 2018f; 2019c; no date).

The findings from these scoping exercises suggested that some AEIs used the flexible approach to set NMC AEI specialist programmes above minimum degree to PG levels. It was beyond the remit of this thesis to explore the rationale for AEIs decisions regarding the academic level for associated NMC programmes. However, delivery of these specific NMC programmes at PG level may reflect transitions towards PGNE to support higher, advanced level knowledge, skills and complex decision-making

required for such post-registration roles (NMC, 2004; 2018c). A further consideration is whether the NMC change to a minimum degree level of PRNE may have influenced the provision of some post-registration NMC AEI programmes at higher PG levels.

Advanced level practice and transforming nursing roles

The need for advanced level nursing practice (ALNP) was identified within global healthcare policies as a strategy contributing to meeting complex healthcare needs and reform (WHO, 2016a; 2016b; Scottish Government, 2017; NHS, 2019a; 2019b; HEE, no date). Understanding ALNP educational requirements within this thesis aimed to identify whether ALNP may be a significant factor influencing transitions towards UK PGNE.

A scoping enquiry of strategic advanced nursing practice (ANP) literature to further insight into ALNP and ANP education requirements identified no generic definition or consistently used term relating to ANP (Northern Ireland Practice and Education Council for Nursing and Midwifery (NIPEC), 2016a; WHO, 2009; 2016a; 2016b; CNOD, 2017b; NHS, 2017; CNOD, 2017b; 2018; Royal College of Nursing (RCN), 2018a; International Council of Nurses (ICN), 2020; HEE, no date; NLIAH, no date). This finding may have reflected the need for flexible ANP definitions to support relevance to diverse areas of practice and international healthcare needs. As well as potentially being influenced by historic variations in the level of nurse education at the point of initial nurse registration. Therefore, within the context of this thesis ALNP and ANP will be used as overarching terms to reflect the range and interchangeable use of ANP terms and roles.

From an international perspective, the ICN (2020) Guidelines for Advance Practice Nursing definition for the Advanced Practice Nurse (APN) role states:

a generalist or specialist nurse who has acquired, through additional graduate education (minimum of a master's degree), the expert knowledge base, complex decision-making skills and clinical competencies for Advanced Nursing Practice, the characteristics which they are credentialed to practice (adapted from ICN, 2008)... (ICN, 2020, p. 6)

Of significance to the context of PGNE is that the ICNs specific requirement of a minimum masters degree for APN may influence international transitions towards PGNE for APN and ANP (ICN, 2020).

From a UK regulatory perspective, a scoping activity of NMC literature in 2020 identified that the NMC did not set out a generic ANP definition, regulatory standards or educational requirements. This finding appeared to relate to the NMC upholding the UK Central Council for Nursing and Midwifery and Health Visiting 1997 decision not to set standards or a part registration for ANP following consultation (NMC, no date). Alternatively, the NMC set the broad context of ANP within the sphere of the NMC (2018e) Code of standards and behaviours for all registered nurses. Potentially this finding may limit the influence of

NMC regulatory drivers towards PGNE for ANP. However, the future NMC development of new post-registration standards and review of ANP may provide opportunities for ANP role requirements, education, regulation and standards to be considered (NMC, 2020; no date). Particularly given the identified emphasis on ANP within strategic UK healthcare policies.

To further understand ANP within the context of PGNE a scoping activity of ALNP strategic nursing frameworks and policies was undertaken (A3). Similar to the ICN APN definition, key UK strategic nursing frameworks and workforce policies aligned ANP to PG or masters level education (NIPEC, 2016a; 2016b; CNOD, 2017b; NHS, 2017; RCN, 2018d; NLIAH, no date). There was consensus that ANP terms related to a level of advanced practice across the four pillars of nursing practice (clinical practice, leadership and management, education or facilitation of learning, and research or evidence) as opposed to a defined or prescribed role (NIPEC, 2016a; CNOD, 2017b; NHS, 2017; NLIAH, no date). The identified key attributes and characteristics at an advanced PG level also emphasised practicing with; a critical approach and awareness across professional and academic nursing practice; and an autonomous approach in applying advanced nursing knowledge and skills to address complex decision-making and unpredictable healthcare issues (A3).

Significantly, consensus was identified across global and UK strategic policies that investment in post-registration advanced nursing roles with a level of PGNE was critical and essential to the capacity and capability of the ANP, and wider nursing workforce to contribute to future healthcare needs (Finlay, 2012; Willis, 2015; WHO, 2016a; Scottish Government, 2017; CNOD, 2018; HEE, no date; ICN, no date). Subsequently, the right targeted models of PGNE were considered essential to transforming nursing roles beyond the initial point of registration (Willis, 2015; NHS England, 2016; NICEP, 2016a; WHO, 2016a; CNOD, 2017a; NMC, 2017b; Scottish Government, 2017; CNOD, 2018; HEE, no date; ICN, no date).

In seeking to understand strategic perspectives of the right, targeted models of PGNE beyond initial nurse registration, UK strategic policies referred to the need for nationally commissioned models of PGNE. Broadly setting out that PGNE would need to be flexible, responsive and fit for purpose to meet advanced to consultant level nursing role requirements (Willis, 2015; NICEP, 2016b; White, 2016; Scottish Government, 2017; CNOD, 2018; HEE, no date).

However, while associated global and UK policies highlighted some strategic drivers towards ANP and PGNE, understanding the context of what might specifically constitute the right, targeted models of commissioned PGNE may be a complex landscape. Assumed to be potentially influenced by evolving nursing roles requiring a level of PGNE responsive to diverse current and future global, national and local nursing workforce infrastructures and wider healthcare needs.

2.2.3 Understanding how registered nurses may become situated in PGNE

This section aims to further insight into the contemporary factors that may influence registered nurses pathways into PGNE beyond NMC AEI post-registration SCPHN and nurse prescribing programmes.

Consideration of commissioned and non-commissioned PGNE

In UK practice, the provision of some PGNE by HEI may be commissioned nationally or locally by associated employer organisations e.g. government or local NHS organisations (NICEP, 2016b; CNOD, 2018). For example, Scottish Government funding and support for an additional 500 advanced nurse practitioners to complete HEI delivered, PG diplomas in advance practice (CNOD, 2017b; NES, 2019). Furthermore, the commissioning of PGNE may also be influenced by NMC regulatory and educational standards, NHS role requirements or projected nursing workforce plans (NICEP, 2016b; CNOD, 2018; NMC, 2022c).

At the time of exploration, the absence of specific NMC requirements or educational standards for ANP may have influenced the development of UK NHS strategic Advanced Clinical Practitioner (ACP) frameworks in partnership with HEI stakeholders (Scottish Government, 2010; NICEP, 2016a; NHS, 2017; NLIAH, no date). These frameworks set out that nurses aspiring to NHS ACP or ANP clinical roles would be required to undertake a HEI PGNE programme inclusive of achieving set clinical competencies relevant to the area of practice. Subsequently, identifying a further role associated route that may determine how a nurse may become situated within the context of PGNE.

Scoping activities of associated UK strategic literature revealed limited literature relating to commissioned PGNE for broader post-registration nursing roles beyond ACP roles. This finding may have been influenced by educational commissioning being devolved to individual NHS organisations to support local workforce planning and healthcare needs. Therefore, it was assumed that a wider range of commissioned and non-commissioned PGNE might exist to support nurses aspiring to ALNP roles focused on educational, leadership and research aspects of the pillars of practice.

The influence of nursing job role requirements

A further factor influencing how nurses may become situated in PGNE related to whether a PGNE qualification is a prerequisite for a specific nursing role. Beyond UK SCPHN, prescribing and ACP roles, I undertook a scoping activity of NHS national nursing profiles in 2020 to explore whether other nursing job roles may require specific levels of PGNE (NHS Employers, 2020a). NHS national profiles provide common features relating to job descriptions and person specifications to support individual NHS organisations to match job profiles (NHS Employers, 2020b). Based on an advanced level of practice associated with PGNE, the NHS national profile for a Nurse Advanced (NA) was reviewed. Similar to

definitions of advanced level practice the NA profile description focused on a specialist or higher approach to practice with highly specialist knowledge, skills, leadership, research and the provision of education for others (NHS Employers, 2020a). However, no specific educational requirements were described or matched within the NA national profile (NHS Employers, 2020a). This finding may have been influenced by individual NHS organisations having responsibility to further develop the national NHS profile to match the specific job description, banding, responsibilities, personal skills and qualification requirements (NHS Employers, 2020b).

It was beyond the remit of this chapter to further explore individual NHS NA role job descriptions. However, of significance is that NA role and qualification requirements determined by individual NHS organisations might influence how a nurse aspiring to a NA role may become situated in PGNE.

Guiding post-registration nursing career development and educational frameworks

Across the UK, national post-registration career and educational development frameworks exist for nurses (Welsh Assembly Government, 2009; NES, no dateb). These frameworks commonly outline generic knowledge, skills and behaviours expected at each level across the four pillars of nursing practice. Of significance to the context of PGNE is that the qualifications expected at an advanced, high or experienced level 7 of practice are aligned to PGE at certificate, diploma or masters degree levels (NICEP, 2016a; NES, no dateb; NLIAH, no date) (A3). As these frameworks may be used by nurses and associated managers to identify and plan towards future career roles, education and professional development opportunities (NES, no dateb). Potentially, level 7 career development and educational frameworks may influence nurses towards PGNE to support ALNP roles.

Consideration of continuing professional development requirements

The WHO (2009) associated continual professional development (CPD) as a graduate attribute in which post-registration nurses continue to maintain or expand knowledge or skills for a specific career trajectory. Globally, nurse registrants also have a responsibility to undertake CPD to maintain professional registration, competence, accountability and responsibility for practice (ICN, 2012; NMC, 2019d).

From a NMC regulatory perspective, registered nurses are required to revalidate every three years to maintain registration (NMC, 2019d). This process includes undertaking and recording evidence of 35 hours of CPD relevant to the registrant's scope of practice (NMC, 2019d). The NMC do not prescribe the type of CPD as responsibility lies with the registered nurse to undertake and evidence CPD activities relevant to their scope of practice (NMC, 2019d). From a theoretical perspective, this may be associated

with the concept of authentic professional learning with approaches influenced by individual intentionality and achievements (Webster-Wright, 2010).

The associated NMC CPD guidance, however, refers to accredited university-level education as an example of CPD activities (NMC, no datec). The NMC (2018a) Standards of proficiency for registered nurses also refers to nurses having the ability to think critically, although this does not require a PG level of nurse education. Reference to critical approaches may support a nurse to link associated PGNE attributes with their approach to maintaining CPD requirements (A3). Therefore, a nurse's approach to undertaking NMC revalidation CPD activities may influence registered nurses becoming situated in PGNE, if relevant to their scope of practice.

2.3 Setting the context of postgraduate learning and application of learning in nursing practice

This section outlines the preliminary theoretical positions in which learning and the application of PG learning are understood from pedagogical, HE and professional nursing perspectives. It was beyond the scope of this section to critique the breadth of pedagogical theories and iterations associated with learning and the application of learning. However, this section aims to provide a lens as to how these perspectives may influence learning and application of PG learning prior to data interpretation.

2.3.1 Pedagogical perspectives influencing the context of learning and application of PG learning in practice

The pedagogical context of learning

Preliminary theoretical understanding was underpinned by humanistic and holistic pedagogical perspectives of learning. In addition to the Kantian position that experience is part of knowledge, and the contemporary assumption that knowledge is part of learning (Curran, 2007; QAA, 2018b). Influential humanistic and holistic learning theories related to; John Dewey's theory of experiential learning, Carl Rodger's humanistic concept of self within learning, Malcolm Knowles' Theory of Andragogy, Kolb's (1983) Learning Cycle, and Jack Mezirow's views of self-actualisation and transformational learning (Curren, 2007; Jarvis, 2010).

These theories informed a position that learning may be an individual, subjective experience through a transformative spiral of continuous, lifelong learning. Humanistic perspectives may also assume that individuals have motivations, needs, capacity and responsibilities for continued learning (Knowles,

Holton and Swanston, 2005). Therefore, an individual's movement through spirals of continuous, lifelong learning may also be influenced by continually changing self, socio-historic and cultural experiences and contexts (Knowles, Holton and Swanston, 2005; Jarvis, 2010; Cranston, 2016). In contrast to purist behavioural, mechanical and elemental pedagogical theories and perspectives that resonated with objective, positivist approaches.

Based on the preliminary pedagogical assumptions presented, Jarvis' (2010) definition of learning resonated with the collective pedagogical perspectives of learning posed.

The combination of processes throughout a lifetime whereby the whole person – body (genetic, physical and biological) and mind (knowledge, skills, attitudes, values, emotions, meaning, beliefs and senses) – experiences social situations, the content of which is then transformed cognitively, emotively or practically (or through any combination) and integrated into the individual person's biography resulting in a continually changing (or more experienced) person. (Jarvis, 2010, p. 39)

Jarvis' (2010) definition underpinned the concept of learning within this thesis prior to data interpretation. With the additional assumption that continual changes resulting from learning may be orientated beyond individual self to a wider socio-cultural impact of applying learning to practice (Dyke, 2017). Section 2.2 also considered the potential influence of PGNE socio-cultural contexts including organisational, employer and professional regulatory standards or requirements. In view of these perspectives, it is assumed that PG learners may exist within a complex sphere and interplay of autonomous self and professional responsibilities and intentionality (Webster-Wright, 2010). Subsequently, preliminary understanding of PG learning assumes that learning may be influenced by self and wider professional and educational contexts.

Application of learning

Through iterative professional doctorate enquiry, concepts ranging from translation of knowledge to the later ALiP were explored. The decision to refer to the overarching term 'application of learning' prior to data interpretation was based on the understanding that the concept of knowledge is part of the learning process (QAA, 2018b). Application theories relating to experiential, situational and transformative learning also resonated with the chosen underpinning definition of learning. As well as contemporary frameworks such as Detect-Elect-Connect and High and Low Transfer models (Perkins and Salomon, 2012).

Given the initial assumptions relating to individual learners being part of the learning process and authentic professional learning involving an interplay of autonomous self and professional responsibilities (Webster-Wright, 2010; Aspin *et al.*, 2012). It was further assumed that self and socio-cultural factors

may influence an individual's experience of applying learning (Jarvis, 2010; Webster-Wright, 2010; Dyke, 2017).

The further dimension of lifelong learning may also influence the learner participating in multiple, interconnected forms of learning e.g. formal, non-formal and informal learning (Jarvis, 2010). Subsequently, the intentions of applying informal to formal learning could resonate with outcomes ranging from abstract attributes, subjective experiences, to measurable, objective products (Aspin *et al.*, 2012). A potential example of the application of formal learning in the context of PGNE may relate to ACP learners being required to undertake formal prescribed learning activities with the aim of demonstrating application of learning and clinical competence through assessed clinical exams to support ACP role requirements.

If it is assumed that lifelong learning is an inherent, intrinsic part of an individual learner's being. Consideration of inherent and informal aspects of learning may impact on an individual's level of consciousness to identify whether learning has been applied (Jarvis, 2010). Furthermore, an individual's ability to reflect on the ALiP may be influenced by semi-conscious socialisation processes. In which experiences are further influenced by workplaces cultures and conscious learning from or with others (Eraut, 2004; Jarvis, 2010).

Understanding that wider interrelated socio-cultural contexts may influence application of learning facilitated enquiry into further pedagogical perspectives (Dyke, 2017). Including consideration of socially critical vocationalism (SCV) approaches and debates surrounding potential paradigm shifts from traditional academic, economic education toward liberal, vocational education (Peach, 2010).

Application of learning from social constructionism and SCV perspectives assumes that individuals have critical awareness and responsibility for challenging and transforming practice and cultures influenced by subjective self and social contexts (Peach, 2010; Webster-Wright, 2010). These aspects appeared reflective of identified advanced PG level nurse attributes and characteristics particularly, the application of learning to support innovation or change in practice (A3). However, employer role requirements, workplace drivers and professional regulatory standards may also influence traditional academic and economic approaches within PGNE delivery and ALiP.

Subsequently, an individual learner and their learning may be influenced by a complex interplay of self, professional, traditional and SCV concepts, and levels of conscious application of learning. A hypothetical illustration of this may relate to a PGNS undertaking a specific, commissioned PGNE programme with the expectation that professional learning is applied to achieve clinical competence to undertake a specific clinical role and contribute to local organisational healthcare needs. Alternatively, for a PGNS pursuing non-commissioned PGNE for self or career development the application of learning may be more dependent on self-awareness of responsibilities and accountability as to whether more

abstract concepts of professional learning could be appropriately applied within their relevant sphere of practice (A3).

In both cases at an advanced PG level of practice associated attributes assume learner self-motivation and critical awareness of the professional responsibilities of applying learning, challenging and transforming practice and cultures (Peach, 2010) (A3). Which may further contribute to an individual learner's sense of self-actualisation and wider outcomes of PGNE learning.

The complex assumptions, critiques and debates existing between pedagogical approaches across educational, professional, organisational, self and societal contexts, provided insight into how these complex pedagogical perspectives may influence PGNS experience of ALiP. Furthermore, consideration of the diversity of learning outcomes from the objective to subjective and consciousness levels of applying learning, raised awareness of how these aspects may influence an individual PGNS ability to share experiences of ALiP.

While there appeared to be an acknowledged need for further research into these complex areas (Coffield and Edward, 2009; Peach, 2010; Webster-Wright, 2010). These complexities provided insight as to why a limited body of research may exist in relation to pedagogical approaches to application of learning within the context of PGNE.

Based on the identified complexities, this thesis does not conform to a singular pedagogical theory or framework relating to ALiP. However, preliminary assumptions relate to the application of learning being part of an individual learner's / PGNS being. Potentially, influenced by complex interrelated self, professional, traditional and SCV contexts, motivations and outcomes, and consciousness levels of applying learning. Reflexively, awareness of these pedagogical perspectives supported movement from a theoretical liminal space into an unknown transformative landscape. In which, exploration into PGNS experiences of ALiP may deepen pedagogical understanding.

2.3.2 HEI perspectives influencing the context of learning and application of PG learning in practice

From a UK, HEI perspective, learning is defined by the QAA (2018b, p. 1) as 'the process through which students acquire new, build on, or reformulate existing, knowledge, skills and practice'. Reference to learning as a process potentially reflected underpinning pedagogical perspectives of the learner being a participant in the learning process. However, reference to the collective acquisition of new and existing knowledge, skills and practice emphasised further multiple concepts considered integral to the HE perspective of the learning process.

No specific definition of PG learning was found from a scoping of QAA strategic literature. However, given that PGE is aligned to a masters degree, the QAAHE (2013) Framework for Considering Mastersness was explored to further enquiry. The framework was designed from a collaborative project with students and staff from UK and international HEI to examine the concepts of mastersness. Aiming to present dimensions, facets and aspects that underpin the concept of mastersness within HE.

The QAAHE (2013) Framework for Considering Mastersness includes seven facets: abstraction, autonomy, complexity, depth, professionalism, research and unpredictability. It was beyond the remit of this chapter to critique each facet in depth. However, following a review of facet definitions, the facet of autonomy was defined within a degree of learner autonomy and responsibility in that the learner takes responsibility for their own learning in the context of self-organisation, motivation, location and acquisition of knowledge (QAAHE, 2013). In contrast to the facet of professionalism relating to the learner also being within academic or professional communities and cultures. These facets resonated with the pedagogical assumptions that an individual learner and their learning may be influenced by self and wider professional, educational socio-cultural contexts. Furthermore, the facets of complexity and abstraction were concerned with applying what has been learned to practice. Resonating with pedagogical SCV perspectives, levels of consciousness and professional responsibilities associated with the application of learning, challenging and transforming practice and cultures (Peach, 2010).

Across the facet definitions, learning appeared to be associated with complex application, depth and capacity for self and co-constructed learning. The focus on complexity across the facets highlighted the potential pragmatic challenges in seeking a unified definition of PG learning or HE approaches to applying PG learning to professional practice. The concept of lifelong learning did, however, appear to translate from pedagogical perspectives into Scottish HEI graduate attributes. With the concept of lifelong learning contextualised to support graduates working lives in employability, career development and changing workplace contexts (QAAHE, 2011).

Student transitions had previously been a focus of the QAA enhancement themes with reference to the chronological masters journey including 'moving on from there' and a focus on transitional 'real-world application of knowledge' (QAAHE, 2013, p. 9). At the time of scoping QAA enhancement theme literature there appeared to be a greater focus on transitions into HE studies than transitions during HE or moving on from HE. Consequently limiting further enquiry into HE perspectives of application of learning during PGE and transition out of PGE.

Exploration into HEI perspectives of learning and application of learning illuminated the complex, multi-layered dimensions of learning and application of learning. There appeared to be some comparative pedagogical and HE perspectives emerging relating to the learner and their learning being influenced by self and wider professional and educational socio-cultural contexts. Furthermore with assumed learner autonomy and responsibility for the application of learning within professional practice contexts.

2.3.3 Strategic nursing perspectives influencing the context of learning and ALiP

In view of global professional regulatory nursing requirements, learning is assumed as part of a continual process of undertaking professional development activities to demonstrate and maintain professional responsibility, accountability and competence (WHO, 2009; ICN, 2012; NMC, 2019d). Subsequently reflecting key emerging pedagogical and HE perspectives of learning discussed in Sections 2.2.

A scoping of key NMC regulations and UK nursing strategy literature identified no specific definition of either PG learning or learning (Chief Nursing Officer Wales (CNOW), 2016; NICEP, 2016a; Scottish Government, 2017; CNOD, 2018; NMC, 2018a; 2018b; 2018e; NHS Employers, 2020a; NHS, no date; NES, no dateb). However, broader references to learning were embedded within NMC standards and UK strategic nursing literature.

Within NMC standards learning was associated with maintaining professionalism and a conduit to effective nursing practice, performance and improvement (NMC, 2018a; 2018e; 2019d). The NMC reference to application of learning related to NMC registered nurses supporting the learning of others, learning from experiences to support development and applying knowledge (NMC, 2018a; 2018e). Furthermore, to meet NMC revalidation requirements to maintain registration, nurses are required to evidence how learning has been applied to change or improve practice (NMC, 2019d). As nurses are not required to formally provide measurable evidence of the impact of applying learning to practice, such learning activities are not subject to direct NMC quality assurance for each registrant (NMC, 2019d). Consequently, these factors limited further enquiry into evidence of PGNE being undertaken as part of NMC CPD activities and how learning from PGNE may have been applied to practice.

Professional strategic literature also referred to learning as a conduit to continuous development with references to; facilitation of learning, learning infrastructures and application of knowledge (CNOW, 2016; NICEP, 2016a; 2016b; Scottish Government, 2017; NHS, 2019a; 2019b; NHS Employers, 2020a; NHS, no date; NES, no dateb).

There appeared to be clear associations with the context of learning and application of learning with professionalism, accountability and continuous practice development (CNOW, 2016; NICEP, 2016a; Scottish Government, 2017; NMC, 2018e; NHS, 2019b; NMC, 2019d; NHS Employers, 2020a; NHS, no date; NES, no dateb). However, there were limited definitions of learning and the application of learning within strategic, professional literature which may have been influenced by complex pedagogical perspectives of learning and the application of learning. A consideration is whether pedagogical assumptions that lifelong learning is an intrinsic part of a learner's being within a sphere of autonomous self and professional responsibilities may influence a professional assumption that learning is inherently understood and embedded within the context of professional nursing practice and part of individual nursing practice (Webster-Wright, 2010).

2.4 The context of workplace support to apply learning to practice

The final context of workplace support was explored as being an assumed conduit influencing PGNS applying learning to and in practice. Enquiry led to initial exploration of defining the context of workplace learning to further understanding of workplace support for PGNS.

2.4.1 Defining the context of workplace learning

Enquiry identified varied terms associated with the context of workplace learning including work-based learning and work-related learning (NMC, 2018b; 2018c; QAA, 2018c). The QAA (2018c) referred to work-based learning within HE courses as bringing together HE providers and work organisations to create authentic, structured learning opportunities within the workplace. Subsequently, the design of HE work-based learning may be influenced by professional regulatory requirements, employer or workforce organisational needs and commissioned education (QAA, 2018c).

Work-based learning was described as learning through work, for work or at work in the context of developing knowledge, skills and professional behaviours (QAA, 2018c). The nearest aligned definition by the WHO (2009) related to clinical learning within the context of the practice setting rather than the workplace with clinical learning being part of an educational process that takes place in any practice setting. The identified perspectives of work-based learning resonated with some NMC AEI post-registration programme requirements. For example, the NMC (2004) SCPHN programme standards required a fifty percent curriculum weighting between theory and practice learning, with a period of consolidating learning in practice. Such standards may therefore influence work-based curriculum design, placements, role requirements and competency assessment to support the achievement of practice learning outcomes and competencies to meet NMC (2004) SCPHN registration requirements.

However, the QAA set out distinctions between work-based and work-related learning for HE courses. In contrast, work-related learning was not deemed dependent on formulation, commissioning, or employer partnerships to address workforce needs (QAA, 2018c). Therefore, the concept of work-related learning may be applicable to PGNE programmes that do not have specific work-based professional or employer role related standards, requirements, or competencies.

Differing work-based or work-related learning components within HE may determine or influence the context of the workplace and role requirements that PGNS are situated within while undertaking PGNE. However, underpinning pedagogical and HE assumptions may provide a consistent thread across work-based, work-related or workplace PGNE contexts. For example, assumed self, professional and educational socio-cultural factors influencing learner autonomy and responsibility for the application of learning within professional, work or practice contexts.

At this early stage of enquiry, the potential diversity of workplace contexts highlighted a further dimension in seeking to understand an evolving, complex sphere of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP. It was also assumed that workplace diversity would permeate further into the context workplace support for PGNS.

2.4.2 Understanding context of workplace support for PGNS

Acknowledging the potentially diverse workplace contexts for PGNS. It was assumed that what constitutes the context of workplace support will be varied, subjective and dependent on the individual PGNS workplace. Therefore, this section does not focus on a singular, defined context of workplace support, alternatively exploring the potential contextual landscapes of workplace support for PGNS.

Pedagogical perspectives relating to the context of workplace support

It was beyond the scope of this chapter to provide an in-depth presentation and critique of the vast historic and contemporary pedagogical theories that could be associated with workplace support to ALiP. However, further enquiry focused on the previous pedagogical perspectives and assumptions associated with the context of workplace support. This approach aimed to support the iterative nature of this thesis and for further pedagogical exploration to be potentially led by future interpretation of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP.

Based on the pedagogical assumptions that the learner and their learning may be influenced by self, wider professional and educational socio-cultural contexts. It is further assumed that the context of workplace support would be influenced by self, professional, education and workplace socio-cultural contexts. The context of workplace support may also be influenced by complex continuums relating to conscious application or learning, and the application of informal to formal learning in practice.

From the humanistic, holistic, and social critical pedagogical perspectives set out in relation to the context of learning and application of learning. It was also assumed that the context of workplace support may be underpinned by shared visions, values and cultures. As well as commitments to pedagogical concepts of learning societies, lifelong learning, and organisational learning (Jarvis, 2010). Furthermore, the context of workplace support may be influenced by other individuals that exist and learn within the immediate workplace of the PGNS and the wider organisational context (Eraut, 2004).

Enquiry identified a proposed taxonomy relating to new employee development learning tasks which potentially reflected initial pedagogical perspectives relating to workplace support (Knowles, Holton and Swanson, 2005). The taxonomy associated with Fisher's (1986) domains of new employee learning aimed to extend the macro-structures and guide learning for new employee development (Knowles,

Holton and Swanson, 2005). In creating Figure 1 the four Taxonomy domains; Individual, People, and Organisational and Workforce tasks were considered and applied to further understanding of the potential context of workplace support for PGNS (Knowles, Holton and Swanson, 2005, p. 310, F19-1).

Figure 1: Reflective Framework – pedagogical considerations when setting the context of workplace support for PGNS to ALiP

The framework guided initial exploration into the context of workplace support from self, immediate workplace, workplace organisation and wider organisation perspectives. It was assumed that the four pedagogical considerations would be interrelated and inter-contributory to the context of workplace support reflecting Knowles, Holton and Swanson (2005) taxonomy and underpinning philosophical assumptions.

Individual – Self perspectives relating to the context of workplace support

Within the context of UK nursing practice individual NMC registered nurses must meet the NMC (2018e) Code of standards, practice and behaviours, Standards of Proficiency (NMC, 2018a) and Revalidation requirements (NMC, 2019d) to maintain NMC registration. Across these NMC standards broad references were made to individual nurses supporting the learning of students, teams and colleagues, and ALiP. These activities were also associated with the development of professional practice. However,

no strategies were prescribed by the NMC relating to specific workplace infrastructures, mechanisms, or evidence-based measures to support nurses to ALiP.

In the context of PGNS, this finding resonated with the pedagogical and professional assumptions relating to individual self-motivations and critical self-awareness of the professional responsibilities of applying learning, challenging and transforming practice and cultures within the workplace (Peach, 2010).

Immediate workplace perspectives relating to the context of workplace support

Senior nurse leadership within the workplace:

Within the ICN (2012) Code of Ethics part of the Nurse Manager role is associated with establishing systems for the continuing education for others. Similar educational role associations were also reflected in the NES (2011) Education and Development Framework for Senior Nurses, Midwives and Team Leaders in All Areas of Practice. The Senior Nurse role across all associated staff and students included support for learning, development and creating learning opportunities (NES, 2011). As well as creating an effective learning environment which may be inclusive of mentorship, coaching and clinical supervision infrastructures (NES, 2011).

In the context of PGNS working as registered nurses in practice, it may be assumed that Senior Nurses have a role in supporting PGNS learners within their area of practice (NES, 2011; ICN, 2012). Furthermore, this role may vary from creating learning opportunities, environments and infrastructures to support PGNS and their learning within the workplace.

Mentorship infrastructures:

Historically, the NMC (2008) Standards to support learning and assessment in practice (SLAiP) set out the required preparation, roles and responsibilities for nurse mentors, sign-off mentors, practice teachers and teachers in supporting learning and assessment in the practice learning environment. The SLAiP set out the knowledge and skills that nurses would be required to achieve to support and assess nursing students in practice. However, these standards were only applicable to supporting students undertaking NMC AEI programmes e.g. PRNE or SCPHN programmes. Therefore, the SLAiP did not set out broader workplace roles or infrastructures to support PGNS on non-NMC AEI specialist programmes.

In 2018 the NMC (2008) SLAiP were replaced with the NMC (2018d) Standards for Student Supervision and Assessment, as part of a new range of NMC standards and frameworks for nursing and midwifery education for AEI pre-registration and specialist NMC post-registration programmes. Focusing on the context of workplace support for PGNS and assuming that some NMC AEI specialist post-registration programmes are delivered at masters level; the NMC (2018d) standards set out that students must be

assigned to a practice and academic assessor in accordance with the associated programme standards. For AEI SCPHN programmes, those undertaking such assessor roles must be registered as NMC SCPHN with appropriate experience to the student's field of practice (NMC, 2018d). The practice assessor also has responsibility to support evidence-based assessment, learning opportunities, feedback, and reflection within the practice environment for the post-registration student (NMC, 2018d).

Of significance is that the NMC (2018d) standards provide insight into the context of workplace support that might be available to PGNS on NMC AEI post-registration specialist programmes. At the time of exploration similar NMC standards did not exist for non-NMC AEI PGNE programmes. Therefore, for PGNS undertaking non-NMC AEI programmes the context of immediate workplace support may alternatively be influenced by those with broader roles in supporting learning in the workplace e.g. individual nurses and senior nurses (NES, 2011; NMC, 2018e).

Workplace organisational perspectives relating to the context of workplace support

Within UK practice, following the Mid-Staffordshire public enquiry and subsequent recommendations from the Francis Report (Francis, 2013). The subsequent National Advisory Group on the Safety of Patients in England (NAGSPE) (NAGSPE, 2013) A Promise to Learn – A Commitment to Act, Improving the Safety of Patients in England report recommended that the NHS should become a learning organisation. Further supported by leadership that commits, creates and supports lifelong learning and learning capability (NAGSPE, 2013).

At the time of exploration, the NHS Long Term Plan (NHS, 2019b) and supporting Interim NHS People Plan (NHS, 2019a) reflected an ongoing focus on supporting lifelong learning for those employed within the NHS. Setting out a vision that nurses must be supported to develop in their careers with better employer support and time to support staff development (NHS, 2019a; 2019b). Furthermore, highlighting that at an advanced level of practice, staff would need to be equipped with skills to support the delivery of advanced practice (NHS, 2019b).

Associated UK strategic healthcare education organisations acknowledged work being undertaken to develop or review PG level career frameworks (HEE, 2017; CNOD, 2018). With such frameworks aiming to set out developmental and educational pathways for nursing practice from clinical, educational, leadership and research perspectives (HEE, 2017; CNOD, 2018). The CNOD (2018) briefing paper outlined that future approaches to transforming education and career development pathways may be inclusive of national approaches to the strategic commissioning of PGNE. Further recognising the need to enhance the capacity and capability of those supporting learning.

Based on the proposed strategic visions and outlines for future nurse education, it was assumed that the potential future development of detailed PG frameworks may provide further insight into workplace

support infrastructures within NHS practice. However, it is acknowledged that not all NMC registered nurses will be employed by NHS organisations with associated PGE frameworks or commissioned PGNE. Potentially, creating further diversity which may influence workplace support for PGNS to ALiP.

Wider organisational perspectives relating to the context of workplace support

Consideration of NMC and employer organisational requirements and partnerships:

The NMC (2018e) set out that all employer organisations of NMC registered nurses should support nurses in upholding the NMC (2018e) Code standards. From a NMC perspective this may broadly suggest that all employer organisations have a role in supporting learning and application of learning for NMC registered nurses within the workplace. Particularly, given that NMC (2018e) Code standards relate to registered nurses supporting the learning of students, teams and colleagues. With context set in relation to ALiP and maintaining CPD revalidation activities (NMC, 2018e; 2019d).

However, the NMC (2018e) Code does not provide further guidance as to how employer organisations should undertake a supportive role in upholding specific standards regarding NMC registrant learning. Subsequently, limiting further understanding relating to employer regulations, supporting infrastructures and assurance of workplace support for NMC registrants by employers, which may include nurses undertaking PGNE.

Consideration of tripartite organisational requirements and partnerships - NMC, AEIs and practice learning partners:

The NMC (2004; 2018c) Standards associated with AEI post-registration specialist programmes require students to undertake practice experiences provided by practice learning partners (PLP). Of significance is that PLP organisations must provide practice learning necessary to support post-registration students to meet proficiencies and AEI programme outcomes, with AEI and PLP organisations being accountable to the NMC for the associated standards being met (NMC, 2018b). Furthermore, AEI and PLP are required to meet standards associated with an effective learning culture and environment, empowering and supporting lifelong learners, enabling learning, and providing learning opportunities and support (NMC, 2018b). The learning environment being the physical location where learning takes place within a system of shared values, beliefs and behaviours (NMC, 2018b).

The NMC (2018b) standards support AEI and PLP to provide flexible, innovative approaches to meeting these requirements which may influence diverse approaches to workplace support for PGNS to apply learning across AEI programmes and within PLP learning environments. However, the NMC (2018b) also set standards for AEI and PLP regarding the practice assessor role to support students undertaking such specialist AEI programmes in practice. Subsequently, specific requirements to support the

preparation, ongoing support, development and training for practice assessors might influence clearly defined aspects of workplace support roles and infrastructures for PGNS undertaking NMC AEI post-registration specialist practice programmes.

Consideration of HEI and practice organisational requirements and partnerships:

Reflecting on UK government and NHS commissioning of HEI PGNE for ACP roles within the nursing workforce. Across associated ACP educational frameworks there was recognition of the high levels of partnership required between ACP HEI providers and the commissioning NHS organisation, and consistent acknowledgement of the need for supervision and support in the workplace for ACP PGNS (NIPEC, 2016a; CNOD, 2017b; NHS, 2017; RCN, 2018b; NLIAH, no date). This may be influenced by some frameworks requiring ACP PGNE programme design to include fifty percent practice delivery and 500 hours of supervised clinical practice to support the achievement of ACP clinical competencies (NIPEC, 2016a; RCN, 2018b). Furthermore, supporting workplace infrastructures were frequently associated with relevant and prepared ACP supervisors, mentors, preceptors or facilitators (NIPEC, 2016a; CNOD, 2017b; NHS, 2017; RCN, 2018b; NLIAH, no date). Such frameworks did not provide specific detail or prescribed workplace support infrastructures, which may have been influenced by the strategic level of the frameworks and acknowledgement of partnership working and agreements required at individual NHS and HEI provider levels. Therefore, diversity may exist across ACP workplace support infrastructures.

2.5 Chapter synthesis

In seeking to understand how contexts of PGNE, application of learning and the workplace may influence nurses becoming situated in PGNE. A diverse range of complex and situational factors emerged (A4). UK strategies relating to NMC regulatory requirements, NMC education standards, and ANP roles were identified as influencing pathways into PGNE for specific nursing roles. The NMC standards providing AEIs with flexibility to deliver NMC post-registration specialist programmes beyond minimum degree level may also influence how nurses aspiring to NMC specialist roles may become situated in PGNE at masters level.

UK nursing frameworks identified the broader concept of ALNP with alignment to PGNE developmental opportunities. As the concept of ALNP was associated with a level of practice rather than prescribed roles, routes into PGNE to support an ALNP may be influenced by a diverse range of; individual employer organisation role or qualification requirements, nationally or locally commissioned or non-commissioned PGNE, and individual nurse or collaborative employer CPD plans or career aspirations.

Furthermore, routes into PGNE may also be influenced by PGNE entry requirements, organisational support and recruitment processes.

Professional attributes aligned to advanced, PG levels of nursing practice emphasised a pragmatic approach to associated application, use and capabilities in practice (A3). Potentially, highlighting an assumption that learning from PGNE is applied or used in practice. However, theoretical enquiry from pedagogical, HE and professional perspectives illuminated complexities associated with defining the context of learning and application of learning. Particularly given assumptions relating to learning as part of individual's being influenced by continually changing self, educational, professional and socio-cultural contexts.

Enquiry furthered insight that application of learning may be viewed within a multi-dimensional, interrelated sphere in which autonomous, self and professional responsibilities for learning, mastersness facets and formal to informal learning continuums may exist. Understanding such perspectives including conscious levels of learning raised further awareness of the complex pedagogical and research considerations that may be required when seeking to explore individual PGNS experiences of ALiP.

The context of workplace support also related to diverse environments rather than a defined context of workplace or components associated with application of learning. Workplace support was alternatively assumed to be underpinned by broader concepts relating to effective learning environments, cultures, lifelong learning and a continuum of formal to informal infrastructures. Potentially influenced by PGNE programme requirements, the professional roles or remits of others in supporting learning, and wider strategic HEI, professional or employer organisation standards and visions. Workplace support for learning and learners was also broadly associated with upholding professional standards enabling the capacity and capability of individual nurses and the nursing workforce to address future healthcare needs.

Enquiry within this chapter illuminated some of the pragmatic and theoretical complexities associated with researching experiences of PGNE, workplace support and application of learning. Highlighting that understanding such contexts may need be viewed from a multi-directional lens that focuses on individual PGNS choice of PGNE programme and their workplace. In addition to any potential role, organisational, professional or HEI standards, requirements or infrastructures relating to PGNE.

To further enquiry beyond strategic, theoretical and pedagogical perspectives, the next chapter explores research perspectives to bring these contextual insights together with existing research knowledge. Potentially, providing an opportunity to reflexively challenge or deepen initial assumptions relating to PGNE, workplace support and application of learning prior to the design and implementation of my research study.

Chapter 3 – Iterative Literature Review

3.1 Contextualising the literature review

This thesis presents three iterative literature reviews completed over the course of my professional doctorate. Each of these are referred to as 'part literature reviews' to distinguish between the specific aim and purpose of each review at different stages of my professional doctorate enquiry. This aimed to demonstrate the iterative approach to searching and reviewing literature through taught professional doctorate stages which led to further exploration of the literature during the research stage of my studies. Collectively, the three literature reviews were underpinned by critical analysis, evaluation and synthesis of relevant literature to contribute to a deepening understanding of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP (Hart, 2018). Table 1 provides an overview of the positioning and purpose of the part literature reviews throughout my professional doctorate. Further justification for each of the literature search and review strategies is contextualised throughout this thesis.

Table 1: Overview of the part literature reviews within my professional doctorate enquiry

(* Truncation applied to word endings)

Part literature review	Stage of professional doctorate studies	Overarching type of review	Overarching aim of review:	Date conducted	Databases used	Overview of key search terms used
Part One	Research proposal development to support ethics approval application	Blended literature review and systematic search and review (Grant and Booth, 2009).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Critically explore the state of knowledge relating to workplace support for PGNS to translate or ALiP. - Inform justification and refinement of the proposed area of research. 	2017-2018	British Library e-thesis online service (EThOS), Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL), Education Source Database, One Search (eBooks/books only), Relevant organisational websites, Web of Science.	PG nurs* students, experience*, support*, in practice, trans* learning.
Part Two	Post-ethics approval, pre-data collection	Blended literature review and systematic search and review (Grant and Booth, 2009).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Deepen specific understanding of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP. - Support up to date knowledge of contemporary research literature to ensure ongoing justification for an original area of research. 	2020-2021	American Doctoral Dissertations, CINAHL, DART-Europe e-thesis portal, EThOS, Education Resources Information Centre (ERIC), Education Source Database, One Search (eBooks/books only), Relevant organisational websites, Web of Science	PG (or masters) nursing students, experiences, workplace support, appl* learning (and / or in practice).
Part Three	Post-data collection, interwoven with interpreting the data and writing the offerings (findings) chapters	Hermeneutic / hermeneutic phenomenological literature review (Smythe and Spence, 2012). Philosophical underpinnings (Heidegger, 1962/1927; Gadamer, 2004/1960).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Further interpretation and understanding of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP. - Follow threads of phenomenon revealed and broader horizons of understanding. 	2022	CINAHL, One Search (eBooks/books only), hand searching however, flexible databases used to support the phenomenon revealed or call to thinking being followed.	Threads followed: Humanistic and transformative learning; motivation and encouragement associated with learning; experiences of learning during the pandemic; mastersness; PGNS presence; CPD; praxis; phronesis /practical wisdom; Heideggerian notions.

During the early stages of my professional doctorate, a blended literature review and systematic literature search and review approach was considered essential to demonstrate rigour and researchability of my proposed area of research (Grant and Booth, 2009). Furthermore, these approaches aimed to support progressive refinement of my research area and question prior to research implementation (Hart, 2018).

The part one literature review initially explored the state of academic, professional, and research knowledge relating to workplace support for PGNS to translate or apply learning in practice. This review indicated a gap in qualitative research literature relating to PGNS lived experiences of workplace support to translate or apply learning in practice. Subsequently, this finding was presented as part of a professional doctorate module summative assessment, leading to progression and submission of an ethics approved research proposal. Based on the timeframes between research proposal development, ethics approval and detailed methodological design, a later part two literature review was conducted to ensure ongoing justification for an original area of research prior to research implementation. This review also deepened my understanding of recently published research literature specifically relating PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP.

Through the ongoing development of my methodological approach prior to research implementation, I developed a deeper understanding of hermeneutic phenomenological research. This deeper philosophical and methodological understanding influenced a strengthening movement towards engaging with the literature in hermeneutic and hermeneutic phenomenological ways. Therefore, the third literature review undertaken post-data collection was guided by these approaches. This review became interwoven with interpretation of the participants' lived experience within the offerings and discussion chapters (C5-10). Heidegger (1962/1927) suggested that interpretation is never presuppositionless. This led me to consider Gadamer's (2004/1960) hermeneutic discussion about the position of the literature. Particularly that 'literature is not unrelated to the reader' (Gadamer, 2004/1960, p. 154). I was also drawn to the unknown opportunities that part three literature review may bring through Gadamer's position that:

Understanding consciousness acquires – through its immediate access to literary tradition – a genuine opportunity to change and widen its horizon, and thus enrich its world by a whole new and deeper dimension. (Gadamer, 2004/1960, p. 391)

Reflexively, these hermeneutic phenomenological assumptions emphasised that the researcher brings their socio-historic, pre-understandings of being in the world to interpretation rather than objectively, removing or bracketing these out (Heidegger, 1962/1927; Gadamer, 2004/1960). Subsequently, reflexive approaches were transparently integrated through the literature reviews to situate and bring my professional knowledge to the reviews, which also resonated the nature of professional doctorate studies (QAA, 2020a). This approach provided an opportunity to challenge my pre-understandings of the subject

area. This also supported a way of ensuring an openness to exploring and reviewing associated literature that may broaden insights or deepen understanding of PGNS experience of workplace support to ALiP.

Subsequently, the literature reviews integrated into my professional doctorate research do not conform to a purist, singular literature review typology. Furthermore, the literature reviews do not aim to seek an objective truth or answer about the existing literature associated with my research topic. Dwelling with Gadamer's (2004/1960) notion that understanding constantly moves from the whole and the part, back to the whole. The iterative approach to the literature review within my thesis alternatively aims to demonstrate a continuous movement between the parts and whole of the literature reviewed over several years of exploring workplace support for PGNS to ALiP (F2; T1).

Figure 2: A part and whole perspective of the literature reviews

Collectively, the three iterative literature reviews aim to contribute to further understanding of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP before and after the data collection activities. Furthermore, the

literature reviews aim to demonstrate rigour, transparency and philosophical congruence at different stages of my professional doctorate.

This chapter presents the part one and two literature reviews conducted prior to research implementation, data collection and analysis. Further justification for the part three literature review is presented in Chapter 5. The subsequent research offerings and discussion chapters also demonstrate the integration of the part three literature review and a fusion of literature from the earlier part one and two reviews in coming to interpret PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP.

3.2. Part one literature search and review approaches

3.2.1 Overarching approach

The part one literature review was conducted between 2017-2018 and aimed to critically explore the existing state of knowledge relating to workplace support for PGNS to translate or apply their learning in practice. The review focused on contemporary academic, theoretical and professional literature relating to the proposed research area. This literature review was considered to be essential at the early stages of my professional doctorate studies and enquiry to:

- provide insight into the type and volume of literature associated with my proposed research area.
- identify any associated theoretical or conceptual frameworks.
- further my understanding of contemporary issues and methodological contexts relating to the proposed research / subject areas.
- identify any research or knowledge gaps relating to the proposed research area.
- ensure that my research would make an original contribution to knowledge and understanding relating to the subject area.

The literature review findings also aimed to contribute to informing future methodological choices for my research. Subsequently informing the development of my research question and proposal prior to submission for ethical approval.

At this stage of my professional doctorate, my approach to part one literature review was underpinned by aspects of literature review and systematic search and review typologies (Grant and Booth, 2009). A blended approach was chosen to; support alignment with the aims of the part one literature review, demonstrate rigour, and provide flexibility to address some of the perceived limitations associated with these typologies. Grant and Booth's (2009) literature review typology specifically relates to the use of recent or current published literature. Blending the characteristics of a systematic search and review

typology supported the inclusion of a more diverse range of literature sources (A5). This was considered essential at the early stages of my enquiry to ensure that my literature review provided insight into policy and research literature associated with my proposed research area. Subsequently, typologies associated with meta-synthesis and mixed methods review were not chosen as the part one literature review aimed to be inclusive of grey literature such as professional policies and strategies.

Both literature review and systematic search and review typologies are associated with providing flexibility to include comprehensive search strategies and appraisal of methodological quality to support transparency and rigour with literature reviews (Grant and Booth, 2009). Approaches to critically analysing literature include the use of thematic analysis and a focus on what was known about the research topic and recommendations for future practice or research (Grant and Booth, 2009). A thematic analysis approach aligned with the aims of my review to identify any research or knowledge gaps, to support justification for an original area of research. Other literature review typologies were not selected due to the lack of alignment with the part one literature review aims. Typologies associated with meta-analysis and qualitative evidence synthesis alternatively focused on methods of aggregating, combining and/or comparing quantitative or qualitative research study results (Grant and Booth, 2009). Furthermore, a critical review typology was not chosen based on review outcomes being associated with a specific hypothesis or theoretical model development (Grant and Booth, 2009).

Grant and Booth's (2009) typologies outline key attributes associated with literature search, appraisal, synthesis and analysis stages. The attributes associated with literature review and systematic search and review typologies were used to underpin and guide my approaches to searching, appraising, synthesising and analysing the literature within the part one review. However, Grant and Booth's (2009) typologies and attributes do not provide detailed or prescribed ways of conducting literature search strategies and reviews. Therefore, further authors within the field of approaches to literature search strategies and reviews were drawn upon to guide the pragmatic design and implementation of the search, appraisal, synthesis and analysis stages of the part one review.

3.2.2 Part one literature search strategy and findings

Literature search strategy

The principles of Bettany-Saltikov and McSherry (2016) steps for conducting a comprehensive and systematic search strategy were applied to support my literature review search strategy. Particularly, as the principles aligned with the comprehensive, systematic characteristics of my chosen literature review typologies and support an effective search strategy to yield relevant literature (Grant and Booth, 2009; Bettany-Saltikov and McSherry, 2016). The key steps undertaken focused on: identifying component parts and key search words associated with the literature review aim, identifying any synonyms,

truncations and abbreviations associated with key search words, developing a list of key words to be used when implementing the search, implementing the search using relevant databases, and recording implemented searches and the results (Bettany-Saltikov and McSherry, 2016).

I applied the Population, Exposure and Outcome (PEO) model to identify relevant, component parts and key search terms based on the aim of the part one literature review (Bettany-Saltikov and McSherry, 2016) (T2; A5). The PEO model was purposefully chosen to align with the exploratory nature of the literature review aim and the subject area being assumed to relate to multiple realities. In contrast to applying a model focused on answering a specific measurable literature review question or interventional outcomes reflective of a positivist, objective or measurable approach to enquiry e.g. the Population, Intervention, Comparison Intervention, Outcomes model (Beecroft, Booth and Rees, 2015). Table 2 demonstrates the identified component parts and key search words associated with the aim of my literature review and illustrates some of the initial truncations used.

Table 2: Application of the PEO model to identify key search terms for the part one literature review search strategy

(* Truncation applied to word endings)

Aim: To critically explore the state of knowledge relating to workplace support for PGNS to translate or apply their learning in practice.					
Key search terms	1.PG nurs* students (Population)	2.Experience* (Exposure)	3.Support* (Exposure)	4.In practice (Exposure)	5.Trans* learning (Outcome)
Key associated words	Masters nursing students Masters programme(s)/ module(s) Post-registration nursing students PG programme(s) /module(s) PG nursing learner	Lived experience(s) Encounters Perception(s) Attitudes Understanding Opinions	Opportunities Preparation Enablement Staff Support Facilitation	Work Workplace Work-based environment Employment Job Occupation Clinical practice	Transferring, Transfer, Transitional, Transition, Translate, Translation of learning Use of learning Utilisation of learning Appl* learning Implementation of learning

As part of search strategy implementation, the key words and associated words in Table 2 were combined with Boolean operator terms (A5). The use of Boolean operator terms aimed to mitigate the

literature searches being restricted by singular search terms (Bettany-Saltikov and McSherry, 2016) (A5). Databases used to implement the search strategy included CINAHL, EThOS, Education Source Database, One Search, relevant organisational websites and Web of Science. Overall justification for database selection related to database alignment with subject areas associated with the aim of my literature review including: education, nursing, research and policy areas. The One Search database associated with my HEI was used to search specifically for eBook and book sources. Appendix 5 provides a detailed rationale for each of the databases used and the inclusion and exclusion criteria applied to the part one search strategy.

When implementing the search strategy, initial searches were conducted and recorded using singular key search terms to provide insight into the landscape and volume of associated literature (Bettany-Saltikov and McSherry, 2016) (A5). A range of comprehensive searches were then conducted by applying combinations of key and associated search words using the range of chosen databases and websites to yield research, theoretical and grey literature sources (A5). Throughout implementation of the literature searches, findings were transferred into electronic referencing management systems and record tables to support transparency (A5). Expert librarian support also facilitated additional application of the term 'research' to some searches to generate further research source findings. Some electronic databases and websites were limited in search functionality. This restricted full application of the search components e.g. Boolean operator terms, limiters. Where possible, I applied the search criteria manually to support a consistent search strategy.

Process of refinement and appraisal

A process of refinement was undertaken to select relevant literature from the searches to be included within the literature review. This process aimed to identify the most relevant sources for in-depth critical appraisal and support a transparent, comprehensive systematic search strategy within associated professional doctorate timeframes (Cronin, Ryan and Coughlan, 2008; Grant and Booth, 2009; Bettany-Saltikov and McSherry, 2016). Figure 3 provides a summary of the part one literature search and process of refinement.

Figure 3: Summary of part one literature search and findings

Initial implementation of the search strategy resulted in 711 identified sources. As part of the process of refinement, each of the 711 source titles and abstracts were reviewed for relevance and alignment with the literature review aim and search strategy inclusion and exclusion criteria (A5). This resulted in 103 sources being deemed relevant for further review. The full text of each of the 103 sources were reviewed against a checklist criterion based on more detailed aspects of the search criteria and the literature review aim (Bettany-Saltikov and McSherry, 2016) (A5). This approach aimed to provide a consistent and transparent way of identifying the most relevant sources (A5). The review of book sources was focused on full text review of relevant sections that aligned with the checklist criteria. Following this

further process of refinement, 29 relevant sources were identified for detailed critical appraisal and review.

Each of the 29 full text sources were reviewed using combined data extraction and critical appraisal templates. A range of tables were developed and used to support in-depth critical appraisal that aligned to the source type (Grant and Booth, 2009; Rees, Beecroft and Booth, 2016). To ensure rigour I explored a range of recognised critical appraisal templates, frameworks and questions from theoretical and practice contexts. This exploration led to me applying a range of adapted critical appraisal templates including templates for: qualitative research sources (Letts *et al.*, 2007a; 2007b; Caldwell, Henshaw and Taylor, 2011); quantitative research sources (Law *et al.*, 1998a; 1998b; Caldwell, Henshaw and Taylor, 2011); grey sources e.g. policy literature (Weber, 2010; Greenhalgh, 2014); and a flexible template for other sources outwith these categories e.g. discussion or opinion sources (Hek and Langton, 2000) (A5). Across the templates, key areas of data extraction and critical appraisal related to methodological components, ethical considerations, rigour, theoretical connections, findings, conclusions and any implications or considerations for practice.

All the templates included a section to capture my reflexive thoughts relating to my research area (A5). I considered this to be essential to bringing awareness of any assumptions, my pre-understandings or ideas that may deepen analysis or contextualise the literature reviewed. Furthermore, this approach aimed to demonstrate transparency of my reflexive thoughts. I realised these early reflexive approaches resonated with a developing hermeneutic thread through my work. This illuminated unconscious hermeneutic ways in which I was evolving to use the literature as a dialogical partner (Smythe and Spence, 2012). Particularly to deepen my understanding of the research area and provoke thinking to further the development of my research.

Synthesis and analysis

In alignment with the analysis attributes of the literature review typology, principles of thematic analysis were applied to support synthesis and analysis across the completed critical appraisal templates (Grant and Booth, 2009). I applied principles of thematic analysis as opposed to using thematic analysis in the context of a research study methodology, method and purist approaches involving coding reliability (Braun and Clarke, 2021a). The rationale for applying principles of thematic analysis at this stage of my professional doctorate enquiry aimed to support a consistent approach to analysis and identify common threads of meaning (Braun and Clarke, 2006; 2021b; Willig, 2013). This approach also supported generating key themes to convey what was known or not know about my chosen area of research with the literature review (Grant and Booth, 2009).

Aspects of Braun and Clarke's (2006; no date) thematic and reflexive thematic analysis were used to guide my approach to thematic analysis based on alignment with a constructivist ontology and the role of the researcher. Braun and Clarke (2021a, p. 39) position that 'themes cannot exist separately from the researcher – they are generated by the researcher ...'. Therefore the process is subjective and interpretive requiring the researcher to reflect on their assumptions and reflexively engage in analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2021b). These aspects resonated with my approach to situating and bringing my pre-understandings and professional knowledge to the analysis of the literature reviewed. Reflexively, this called to thinking further unconscious hermeneutic and hermeneutic phenomenological ways in which I was engaging with the literature, prior to confirming that these philosophical and methodological approaches would underpin my later professional doctorate work and research study.

Application of the principles of thematic and reflexive thematic analysis included; familiarisation, reading and re-reading the completed critical appraisal templates including reflexive notes; systematically capturing aspects that were significant and relevant to the literature review aim; colour coding text to search for and generate initial themes; developing and reviewing the themes against the coded data and completed templates; refining, defining and naming themes; and writing up to contextualise analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006; no date) (A5). Subsequently applying the principles of thematic and reflexive thematic analysis across the 29 completed critical appraisal templates resulted in identifying two overarching themes with four key themes and a number of sub themes (A5-6). Use of the terms overarching, key and sub themes aimed to reflect the interpretation of patterns of meaning rather than distinct topic summaries associated with other approaches to thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, no date). Figure 4 illustrates the overarching and key themes identified from the part one literature review focused on exploring existing knowledge relating to workplace support for PGNS to translate or apply learning in practice.

Figure 4: Overarching and key themes identified from the part one literature review

The themes were used to structure the following part one literature review and contextualise analysis of workplace support for PGNS to translate their learning in practice. To support transparency and rigour through the part one literature review the overarching themes are to mapped to each section.

3.3 Part one literature review findings

3.3.1 The landscape of professional policy literature relating to the concept of workplace support for PGNS to translate learning in practice

(Overarching theme: Policy context)

The review of 16 sources of global policy literature identified consensus that agendas for PGNE aimed to contribute to meeting increasing future healthcare, workforce and patient care needs (Willis, 2015; WHO, 2016a; Scottish Government, 2017; HEE, no date). This finding correlated with the contemporary, strategic factors identified as influencing PGNE in Chapter 2. The review of policy literature also further confirmed a global focus on the strategic development and implementation of advancing nursing roles

with a masters level of PGNE, as part of the future nursing workforce (Willis, 2015; WHO, 2016a; 2016b; Scottish Government, 2017; HEE, no date).

Variation was noted across the policies relating to PGNE infrastructures, education, commissioning, and associated nursing roles and requirements, resonating with some of the Chapter 2 findings (Willis, 2015; HEE, no date; NES, no date). Potentially influencing diversity relating to how nurses may become situated in PGNE, the availability and delivery of PGNE, and associated workplace support for PGNS.

At the time of the part one review, Scottish policy reflected a greater focus towards the need for agreed national acute and community ANP roles, education and supporting infrastructures (CNOD, 2017b). In contrast to a focus on ALNP roles across other aspects or pillars of practice e.g. other clinical roles or educational, leadership and research pillars of practice. It was assumed that this focus may have been influenced by the need for nationally consistent, sustainable and progressive nursing workforce infrastructures required to meet the current and future needs of health and care systems within NHSScotland including acute and community care needs (CNOD, 2017b).

Across the policies, there were common strategic themes relating to the need for supporting commissioned models of PGNE and developmental pathways associated with advancing nursing roles (Willis, 2015; WHO, 2016a; Scottish Government, 2017; CNOD, 2017a; 2017b; 2017c; HEE, no date; NES, no date). However, there were no specific references to the concept of workplace support for PGNS or how PGNS would be supported in the workplace to ALiP. There was also a lack of clarity as to how strategic PGNE initiatives would be monitored or evaluated at national or local levels.

At the time of the part one review these findings may have been influenced by the identified lack of UK professional regulations or PGNE requirements for ANP. Subsequently, reviewing the landscape of professional, strategic policy literature highlighted limitations in understanding the pragmatic implementation and evaluation of PGNE policy. Particularly, how professional, strategic policies may influence workplace support for PGNS to translate or ALiP.

3.3.2 The landscape of professional research literature relating to the concept of workplace support for PGNS to translate learning in practice

(Overarching theme: Professional research context)

Of the 11 sources of research literature reviewed, none specifically focused on the concept of workplace support for PGNS to translate learning in practice. Research studies commonly referred to increasing global requirements for masters level PGNE to support nursing roles to meet future healthcare needs (Drennan, 2008; Drennan and Hyde, 2009; Black and Bonner, 2011; Shearer and Adams, 2012; Millberg

et al., 2014; Ng, Eley and Tuckett, 2016). This finding potentially highlighted the increasing global requirements for PGNE to support nursing roles and future healthcare needs, becoming a thematic thread throughout strategic, policy and research literature.

The study with the greatest alignment to my subject area was an exploratory descriptive study of distance PGNS needs for employer-based support (Black and Bonner, 2011). Most of the remaining research studies focused on; nurses' academic experiences of PGNE (Black and Bonner, 2011; Shearer and Adams, 2012; Illingworth *et al.*, 2013; Millberg *et al.*, 2014), PG nursing preparation, selection and destinations (Drennan, 2008; Drennan and Hyde, 2008; Illingworth *et al.*, 2013) and values and motivations pertaining to the pursuit of PGNE (Drennan and Hyde, 2009; Rooney, 2015; Ng, Eley and Tuckett, 2016). The academic, HEI focus of the research studies may have been influenced by most being conducted by nurse academics situated within HEI (Drennan, 2008; Drennan and Hyde, 2009; Black and Bonner, 2011; Millberg *et al.*, 2014). As well as previously identified strategic agendas relating to the need for purposeful and targeted models of PGNE and commissioned PGNE aligned to ALNP workforce needs. Potentially, influencing a greater research focus on the need to build knowledge relating to academic experiences of PGNE and purposeful PGNE programmes beyond initial nurse registration. In contrast to research focused on exploring practice-based PGNS experiences or workplace support.

The part one review of the landscape of professional research literature significantly identified limited qualitative lived experience research specifically focused on workplace support for PGNS to translate or apply learning in practice. At an early stage of professional doctorate enquiry, this identified limitation indicated a specific gap in knowledge and research and supported a strengthening rationale and need for original, contemporary lived experience research into PGNS experiences of workplace support to translate or apply learning in practice.

3.3.3 Conceptualising workplace support for PGNS to translate learning in practice

(Overarching theme: Professional research context)

In reviewing the literature to critically explore existing knowledge relating to workplace support for PGNS to translate or apply their learning in practice. I was curious whether the literature review would reveal any existing theoretical or conceptual frameworks associated with workplace support for PGNS to translate their learning in practice. At this early stage of professional doctorate enquiry, I assumed that identification of any existing conceptual or theoretical models would further my understanding about the subject area providing insight into any contexts of knowledge that may influence views and literature about workplace support for PGNS to translate or apply learning in practice. I also considered that such

insights may potentially inform and influence the future development of my research question, and ontological and methodological approaches within my research proposal.

Findings from the part one review identified no specific, conceptual models of workplace support for PGNS to translate or apply learning in practice. Similarly, no models were identified relating to the wider context of formal or informal support, or workplace support for PGNE. However, my review identified a focus within the literature on factors and categories associated with the concept of support for PGNS. Commonly including those related to 'systems', 'emotional' and 'facilitative' categories.

Black and Bonner's (2011) exploratory descriptive study, using a questionnaire tool categorised 15 types of workplace support into five categories: cost, system, academic, social/emotional and other. The literature reviewed suggested that the concept of support could be situated within academic and workplace/practice contexts, or by the PGNS providing self-support (Black and Bonner, 2011; Illingworth *et al.*, 2013; Millberg *et al.*, 2014).

Richardson's (2013) case study evaluation of early clinical career fellows (ECCF) including nurses undertaking masters programmes found that clinical coaching and line manager support attributed to positive ECCF support. Whereas Millberg *et al.* (2014) grounded theory study exploring the major concerns of specialist nurses pertaining to academic learning found a lack of employer support which resulted in some participants feeling abandoned and the use of their learning inhibited in practice. Potentially, these findings indicated that some factors could be perceived as both catalysts and barriers to PGNS support.

Rooney's (2015) descriptive phenomenological study of post-registration nurses' experiences of HE in Ireland found that a positive association with funding was counteracted by lacking support factors. These factors included lack of managerial support and time which negatively impacted on the participants' overall experience of support. However, Rooney's (2015) study was focused on funded post-registration degree education which may have influenced participants' expectations of support.

Potentially, these findings suggest that some support factors could be interrelated or interdependent. With further examples within literature relating to the concept of encouragement potentially being dependent on mentorship (Black and Bonner, 2011; Richardson, 2013). Further suggesting that factors associated with the concept of support may have the capacity to positively or negatively influence PGNS experiences of support (Illingworth *et al.*, 2013; Millberg *et al.*, 2014; Rooney, 2015; Ng, Eley and Tuckett, 2016).

As part of my literature review, I developed Figure 5 as a way of visualising my understanding of the diverse factors or components associated with the concept of PGNS support that were identified from the literature reviewed (A6). This illustration does not intend to represent a developing conceptual model associated with the outcomes of other literature review typologies (Grant and Booth, 2009).

Figure 5: Bringing together identified components relating to the concept of support for PGNS

The literature reviewed highlighted the potential complexity of conceptualising workplace support for PGNS to translate learning in practice. Due to the influence of a diverse range of interrelated and interdependent factors and varying contexts of support. These complexities may have influenced the lack of a conceptual model of workplace support for PGNS to translate learning in practice being identified within the scope of my part one literature review. Reflexively, in developing Figure 5 I also became curious about how these categorised factors and components of support may be experienced by PGNS in translating or applying their learning to practice. Furthermore, I was curious about how these factors and components may influence different individual and subjective experiences of support for PGNS across academic, self and workplace contexts.

3.3.4 Factors influencing workplace support for PGNS to translate learning in practice

(Overarching theme: Professional research context)

The influence of workplace colleagues' attitudes towards PGNE on workplace support for PGNS

My literature review identified evidence of positive and negative attitudes held by workplace colleagues and senior colleagues towards PGNS and PGNE which, in some cases influenced workplace support for PGNS (Drennan and Hyde, 2008; 2009; Illingworth *et al.*, 2013; Richardson, 2013; Millberg *et al.*, 2014).

Richardson (2013) undertook a case study evaluation of four ECCF that had been selected in association with their future leadership attributes to take part in a national early clinical careers initiative including fully funded masters level programmes, coaching and study leave. The study identified that the ECCF participants encountered a range of workplace attitudes and experiences from no resentment and positive excitement from workplace colleagues to animosity and challenge towards their PGNE (Richardson, 2013).

Illingworth *et al.* (2013) small qualitative study to explore the programme experiences of six community masters and nine undergraduate students highlighted that students were aware that their engagement in HE influenced the nature of roles, power relationships and positioning with workplace colleagues. However, the context of the students professional, organisational environment was unknown which may have been a further factor that influenced the findings.

My review of the literature also identified that the attitudes of nurse managers and senior colleagues towards PGNS and PGNE may be influenced by programme choice and purpose. Nurse managers and senior colleagues commonly held positive attitudes towards PGNS and PGNE when purposeful programmes were undertaken (Drennan and Hyde, 2008; 2009; Illingworth *et al.*, 2013; Richardson, 2013; Millberg *et al.*, 2014). For example, programmes cognisant of occupational progression or, employer or service needs and roles.

In contrast Drennan and Hyde's (2008) interview study of five Irish nurse managers' perspectives of registered nurses selection for masters programmes found that when PGNE was not aligned to a clear clinical career pathway, some nurse managers held sceptical views of PGNS and PGNE. These sceptical views influenced the level of workplace support that nurse managers were prepared to provide for PGNS. A specific finding reflected that one nurse manager would only provide workplace support for PGNS undertaking clinical studies. A potential factor influencing workplace support, may relate to the further finding that some nurse managers held a common assumption that PGNS would not remain in their employed area or clinical practice on completion of PGNE. This assumption negatively influenced the level of workplace support that nurse managers were prepared to provide for nurses from the point of application to completion of their PGNE (Drennan and Hyde, 2008).

However, Drennan's (2008) cross sectional survey of 220 masters nursing graduates destinations (68% response rate) from six Irish universities over a five-year period. Contrastingly, identified a historical shift from previously predominant graduate destinations into academia to remaining in clinical practice. Over 50% of participants remained in clinical nursing roles and a further 16% in nurse management roles. It was not stated whether any of the participants' PGNE had been supported by their employer or linked to an employed role on completion, which may have influenced the findings. The historical shift posed by Drennan (2008) potentially challenges assumptions and provisions of workplace support for PGNS. However, Drennan and Hyde's (2008) study did not identify how the nurse managers own experiences of nurse education, their roles and service needs may have influenced the findings.

Collectively, the studies of Drennan and Hyde (2008), Richardson (2013) and Illingworth *et al.* (2013) illustrated the significant influence that workplace colleague, nurse manager and senior colleague assumptions and attitudes may have on diverse PGNS experiences of workplace support.

The influence of expected PGNE outcomes on workplace support for PGNS to translate learning in practice

My literature review identified both similarities and differences between the perceived outcomes of PGNE among nurse academics, managers and PGNS. Nursing academics, managers and PGNS commonly associated PGNE outcomes with the concept of the 'knowledgeable doer' and assumed benefits to patient care (Drennan and Hyde, 2009; Shearer and Adams, 2012; Illingworth *et al.*, 2013; Millberg *et al.*, 2014; Ng, Eley and Tuckett, 2016). With the concept of the 'knowledgeable doer' associated with '... a high level of theoretical knowledge with practical know how' (Drennan and Hyde, 2009, p. 173).

Drennan and Hyde's (2009) qualitative interview analysis of eight nurse academics and seven senior nurse managers' perceptions of masters programmes. Identified nurse academics, perceived 'knowledgeable doer' outcomes related to PGNS use of nomothetic knowledge to inform practice. Conversely, nurse managers viewed outcomes as the tangible use of acquired clinical and managerial skills, and visible role capability (Drennan and Hyde, 2009).

Illingworth *et al.* (2013) similarly found that some PGNS focused on desired clinical skill outcomes. While other PGNS recognised a shift from outcomes focused on 'doing' to 'being' due to their development of complex thinking (Drennan and Hyde, 2009). PGNS also associated PGNE outcomes with changes towards higher levels of professional status, identity, credibility, knowledge and skills, and contribution to practice and patient care (Shearer and Adams, 2012; Illingworth *et al.*, 2013; Millberg *et al.*, 2014; Rooney, 2015; Ng, Eley and Tuckett, 2016).

Despite the perceived outcomes of PGNE by nurse managers, Illingworth *et al.* (2013) and Millberg *et al.* (2014) identified that some nursing students experienced inconsistent workplace support and limited opportunities to use outcomes of acquired knowledge and skills in practice. Subsequently, Illingworth *et al.* (2013) presented the notion that those in advancing nursing roles may be deauthorised by others to use their outcomes in practice. Further resonating with a participant's experience as part of Millberg *et al.* (2014, p. 717) study stating, 'Yes, it feels so difficult, so we've given up'.

Richardson (2013) and Millberg *et al.* (2014) also identified that some PGNS sought to create their own opportunities to use their PGNE outcomes in practice, despite workplace barriers or lack of support. Examples included PGNS facilitating change within their own sphere of practice to enhance patient experiences and establishing professional support networks with other PGNS or PG nurses (Shearer and Adams, 2012; Richardson, 2013; Millberg *et al.*, 2014).

Within the literature reviewed there were no specific research studies that explored why PGNS may be unsupported in the workplace to use their PGNE outcomes or translate learning in practice. However, the literature provided insight that workplace support for PGNS to translate learning or use outcomes in practice may be influenced by varied stakeholder attitudes and expected outcomes of PGNE (Drennan and Hyde, 2008; Illingworth *et al.*, 2013; Millberg *et al.*, 2014).

The influence of infrastructures on workplace support for PGNS to translate learning in practice

No specific infrastructures were identified that referred to how PGNS would be supported to translate learning in practice. Alternatively, my review identified varied infrastructures associated with broader support for PGNS in the workplace.

Some examples of PGNE associated with national initiatives or advanced, specialist nurse practitioner roles were found to have more defined and consistent infrastructures for PGNS workplace support. This may have been influenced by associated strategic agreements between the PGNE provider and employer organisation (Drennan and Hyde, 2008; Richardson, 2013). For example, the ECCF initiative and some advanced and specialist nurse practitioner PGNE programmes had service level agreements for financial programme funding, study leave and release from practice (Drennan and Hyde, 2008; Richardson, 2013).

Contrastingly, there appeared to be significant variation and a lack of defined workplace support infrastructures associated with advanced leadership, educational or research nursing roles compared to specific advanced clinical roles. Variation commonly related to organisational employer funding for PGNE, study leave, and peer or line manager support mechanisms. Black and Bonner (2011), Illingworth *et al.* (2013) and Rooney (2015) also found that some nursing students experienced negative self and role perceptions due to disparity of organisational support.

Discourse was identified between PGNS ideal supporting workplace infrastructures and the reality of their experiences (Black and Bonner, 2011; Richardson, 2013; Millberg *et al.*, 2014). This finding was highlighted by Black and Bonner's (2011) descriptive questionnaire study to identify registered nurses' experiences of workplace support. A convenience sample of 270 registered nurses who were undertaking or had recently undertaken distance PGNE (34% response rate) was used from one major Acute Australian Hospital. Although the findings were limited to one organisation and frequencies of occurrence, Black and Bonner (2011) found that 28% of participants reported having received no type of academic, cost, systems, social, emotional or other form of workplace support. 71% of participants also reported that no forms of support had been offered despite 59.5% seeking support. Furthermore, 94.6% of participants would like or have liked at least 3 types of support, with study leave and roster requests being commonly preferred. 73% viewed that support should be a compulsory requirement by their employer (Black and Bonner, 2011).

Cumulatively the studies reviewed, significantly identified an emerging need for defined and available workplace support infrastructures for all types of PGNS (Drennan and Hyde, 2008; Black and Bonner, 2011; Illingworth *et al.*, 2013; Richardson, 2013; Millberg *et al.*, 2014; Rooney, 2015).

3.3.5 Understanding the part one findings to inform research development

At the time of the part one review there were clear global policy visions, drivers and desired outcomes for advancing nursing roles with a masters level of PGNE. Particularly, advanced level nursing roles associated with meeting future nursing workforce, healthcare and patient care needs. However, the part one search revealed limited literature surrounding the concept of workplace support for PGNS to translate learning in practice across contemporary professional, academic and research contexts. This finding restricted pragmatic insight into the implications of PGNE policies to practice. Subsequently, furthering my curiosity about the concept of workplace support for PGNS and PGNS experiences of workplace support.

Reasons for the lack of professional, academic and research literature may relate to several key issues identified in my review. For example, the identified absence of conceptual models of workplace support and for PGNS to translate learning in practice. Potentially, further influenced by the lack of specific, detailed strategies to support the implementation of PGNE support from policy to practice and to PGNS. Some studies also illustrated the potential influence that colleague, nurse manager and senior colleague attitudes and assumptions towards PGNE and outcomes may have on PGNS experiences of workplace support (Drennan and Hyde, 2008; 2009; Illingworth *et al.*, 2013; Richardson, 2013; Millberg *et al.*, 2014).

My review also identified global policy agendas for consistent national infrastructures of PGNE (Drennan and Hyde, 2008; Black and Bonner, 2011; Illingworth *et al.*, 2013; Richardson, 2013; Millberg *et al.*, 2014; Rooney, 2015). However, there appeared to be variation in existing workplace support infrastructures at local and national levels with no specific reference to workplace support infrastructures for PGNS to translate learning in practice.

Based on these emerging issues there appeared to be a gap between PGNE policy visions and outcomes with the pragmatic implementation of PGNE in practice and the experiences of PGNS. The lack of literature relating to the design or implementation of strategic and workplace support infrastructures may potentially influence a risk of disabling or underutilising PGNS (Drennan, 2008; Drennan and Hyde, 2009; Illingworth *et al.*, 2013). Particularly given that PGNS may experience variation in the provision of workplace support from application, participation, completion and translation of PGNE learning in practice. Which may further be influenced by workplace infrastructures and attitudes surrounding PGNS and PGNE.

Potentially, these factors may impact on the short and long-term achievement of policy ambitions and desired PGNE outcomes (Drennan, 2008). Which may impact on PG nurses and PGNS self-identity and professional motivations to translate learning in practice and contribute to future patient care and healthcare delivery needs.

The part one literature review focused on the overall context of workplace support as opposed to a specific focus on academic or individual self-support which are assumed to also influence the wider concept of support for PGNS. The findings of this initial literature review indicated several areas for further research including advancing understanding of nurse manager perceptions of PGNE and their roles in support. From a conceptual or theoretical viewpoint, recommended areas for further enquiry related to exploring strategic and practice workplace support infrastructures and models from employer, academic, nursing and PGNS perspectives. Given the identified limited literature focused on the design and implementation of strategic and workplace support infrastructures; a significant area for further research related to exploring the potential gaps, spaces and transitions between PGNE policy visions, implementation and experiences in practice. The importance of extending research in these areas was illuminated by the findings that PGNS may experience variation in workplace support provisions, infrastructures and attitudes across PGNE application, participation, completion and translation of learning. The review also highlighted the associated risks of disabling or deauthorising PGNS to use PGNE outcomes in practice, and underutilising PGNS (Drennan, 2008; Drennan and Hyde, 2009; Illingworth *et al.*, 2013). Potentially, these factors may also impact on the short and long-term achievement of policy ambitions and desired PGNE outcomes (Drennan, 2008). However, these factors and issues may also pose a significant impact on PGN and PGNS experiences of self-identity and

professional motivations to translate learning in practice and contribute to future patient care and healthcare delivery needs.

The collective findings of the part one review brought to attention to the importance of research in these areas. It was also assumed that future enquiry would be essential in furthering insight to support PGNS and PGN to contribute to enhanced patient care and healthcare ambitions. The finding of limited qualitative lived experience research specifically focused on PGNS experiences of workplace support to translate or apply learning in practice significantly influenced refinement of my research topic. This finding also brought consideration to lived experience methodological approaches as part of my developing research proposal. Therefore at a later stage of my professional doctorate studies, it appeared timely and necessary to deepen my specific understanding of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP through a subsequent part two literature review.

3.4 Part two literature search and review approach

3.4.1 Overarching approach

This later part two literature review was conducted between 2020-2021 following ethical approval for my research study. The rationale for this further literature review related to the part one review indicating limited qualitative research literature relating to PGNS lived experiences of workplace support to translate or apply learning in practice. This led to refinement of my research topic, development of the research question and an ethics approved research study. These aspects also led to the decision to transition to use of the term application of learning in practice rather than translation (C2).

Based on the timeframes between the development of my research proposal, ethics approval and detailed methodological design activities as a part-time professional doctorate student. I decided to undertake a further review of the literature with the aim of deepening specific understanding of PGNS experience of workplace support to ALiP. This iterative literature review was considered essential prior to research implementation to:

- Enhance and inform further development of my research question and detailed aspects of methodological and method design e.g. data collection and interpretation approaches.
- Support up to date contemporary knowledge of recently published or new literature relating to PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP since the part one literature review.
- Ensure ongoing justification for an original area of research throughout the research process and my professional doctorate studies.

Similarly to the part one literature review, the overall approach to the part two literature review was also underpinned by a blended literature review, and systematic search and review typology (Grant and Booth, 2009). This approach was based on blended characteristics and attributes of these typologies aligning with aspects of the part two literature review aim. In contrast to the part one literature review which drew upon the attribute of the systematic search and review typology supporting the inclusion of a more diverse range of literature sources. The part two review was guided by the literature review typology attribute of a comprehensive search focused on recent or current research literature (Grant and Booth, 2009). Furthermore this attribute aimed to ensure rigour and transparency through search and review processes (Grant and Booth, 2009). This approach supported the focus of the part two search and review on recently published literature between the time of the part one review, specifically relating to PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP. However, combining attributes of the systematic search and review typology supported a systematic and comprehensive search strategy (Grant and Booth, 2009). Given that the part two review focus on research literature, a mixed method research synthesis typology was considered (Grant and Booth, 2009). However, this typology was not chosen due to a focus on aggregating and configuring study findings towards a theoretical framework of model which did not align with the part two review aim (Grove, 2021).

The blended literature review, and systematic search and review typology also supported a thematic analysis approach to critical appraisal of the literature (Grant and Booth, 2009). This approach aligned with the aims of my review to identify any research or knowledge gaps to support ongoing justification for an original area of research. The attributes associated with literature review and systematic search and review typologies were again used to underpin and guide my approaches to searching, appraising, synthesising and analysing the literature within the part two review. However, I also drew upon authors within the field of approaches to literature search strategies and reviews to guide the design and implementation of the part two review.

3.4.2 Part two literature search strategy and findings

Literature search strategy

The principles of Bettany-Saltikov and McSherry (2016) steps for conducting a comprehensive and systematic search strategy outlined in the part one search strategy were applied. This approach aimed to support a consistent, transparent and effective search strategy to yield relevant literature (Bettany-Saltikov and McSherry, 2016).

I also applied the PEO model within the part two search strategy to identify relevant key search terms based on the literature review aim (Bettany-Saltikov and McSherry, 2016). The PEO model was chosen

based on the part two review aiming to deepen understanding of PGNS experiences which reflected the qualitative and multiple realities nature of the PEO model. Table 3 demonstrates the identified key search terms and the use of truncations associated with the aim of the part two literature. In contrast to the part one search strategy, the part two search strategy focused on identifying and using key search terms only (A5). Justification for this decision related to the refined, focused aim of part two literature search and area of research following the part one review.

Table 3: Application of the PEO model to identify key search terms for the part two literature review search strategy

(* Truncation applied to word endings)

<p>Aims:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Deepen specific understanding of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP. - Support up to date knowledge of contemporary research literature to ensure ongoing justification for an original area of research.
<p>Key search terms</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PG (or masters) nursing students (Population) • Experiences (Exposure) • Workplace support (Exposure) • Appl* learning (and / or) in practice (Outcome)

The key search terms in Table 3 were combined with Boolean operator terms to mitigate the literature searches being restricted by singular search terms (Bettany-Saltikov and McSherry, 2016) (A5).

Databases used to implement the search strategy included; American Doctoral Dissertations, CINAHL, DART-Europe e-thesis portal, EThOS, Education Resources Information Centre (ERIC), Education Source Database, One Search, relevant organisational websites and Web of Science. Overall justification for database selection related to database alignment with my refined research topic and a focus on the search yielding research-based literature only. Appendix 5 provides a further rationale for the databases used and the inclusion and exclusion criteria applied to the part two search strategy.

The searches implemented were conducted by applying combinations of key search terms and Boolean operators across the chosen databases and websites (A5). The literature search findings were transferred into electronic referencing management systems and record tables to support transparency (A5). Similar to my experiences of implementing the part one search strategy, some electronic

databases and websites were limited in search functionality. To mitigate the impact of limited database search functionality on the search results where possible, I applied the search criteria manually to support a consistent and comprehensive search strategy.

Process of refinement and appraisal

A process of refinement was undertaken to identify the most relevant sources that aligned with the specific focus on PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP and the search criteria. This process also aimed to support a realistic and manageable approach to critically appraising relevant sources in-depth, balanced with the stage and timeframes of my professional doctorate enquiry. Figure 6 provides a summary of the part two literature search findings and the process of refinement.

Figure 6: Summary of part two literature search and findings

Initial implementation of the search strategy resulted in 589 identified sources. As part of the process of refinement, each of the 589 sources titles and abstracts were reviewed for relevance and alignment with the part two literature review aim and search strategy inclusion and exclusion criteria (A5). This resulted in 17 sources being deemed relevant for further review. The full text of each of the 17 sources were reviewed against a checklist criterion based on more detailed aspects of the search criteria and literature

review aim. This approach aimed to support consistency, rigour and transparency throughout the process of review and refinement (Cronin, Ryan and Coughlan, 2008; Bettany-Saltikov and McSherry, 2016). Following this process seven sources were deemed relevant for detailed critical appraisal and review.

Each of the seven full text sources were reviewed using the combined data extraction and critical appraisal templates previously developed (A5). The template used to critically appraise each article was dependent on alignment with the sources research methodology. This led to application of critical appraisal templates for qualitative research sources (Letts *et al.*, 2007a; 2007b; Caldwell, Henshaw and Taylor, 2011) and quantitative research sources (Law *et al.*, 1998a; 1998b; Caldwell, Henshaw and Taylor, 2011). These templates consistently supported data extraction and critical appraisal of the sources methodological components, ethical considerations, rigour, theoretical connections, findings, conclusions and any implications or considerations for practice. The templates also included a section to capture my reflexive thoughts relating to the critique, my pre-understandings, assumptions and any thoughts that evoked thinking about PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP. This was considered essential at this further stage of my professional doctorate enquiry to provide a record and dialogue of my reflexive thoughts and ideas to inform the written literature review. However, I was also developing awareness that I may return to these reflexive notes as a dialogical partner post data collection to provoke thinking as part of interpretation approaches (Smythe and Spence, 2012).

Synthesis and analysis

The approaches to synthesising and analysing the completed critical appraisal templates used in the part one literature review also guided approaches used within the part two literature review. Therefore, principles of thematic and reflexive thematic analysis aligned to my blended literature review typology were applied to support synthesis and analysis across the completed critical appraisal templates (Grant and Booth, 2009; Braun and Clarke, 2021a). Justification for this approach aimed to support a consistent approach to; analysis, identifying common threads of meaning and generating key themes associated with deepening an understanding of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP (Grant and Booth, 2009; Willig, 2013; Braun and Clarke, 2006; 2021b). Aspects of reflexive thematic analysis also supported a focus on bringing my pre-understandings, reflexive thoughts and ideas and professional knowledge to the analysis of the literature reviewed (Braun and Clarke, 2021b).

Subsequently, I worked with the completed templates applying principles of thematic and reflexive analysis to: read and re-read the completed critical appraisal templates including my reflexive notes; systematically capture aspects that were significant and relevant to the part two literature review aim; apply colour coding to the text to search for and generate initial themes; develop and review the themes against the colour coded data and completed templates; towards refining, defining and naming themes;

to support contextualised analysis within the written literature review (Braun and Clarke, 2006; no date) (A5). Following application of this process across the six completed critical appraisal templates, three overarching themes and four key themes were identified from the part two literature review focused on PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP (F7).

Figure 7: Overarching and key themes identified from the part two literature review

Focus of part two literature review to deepen specific understanding of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP.			
Overarching themes			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Furthering understanding of the research landscape 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perceptions associated with the impact of PGNE 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Further factors and challenges to PGNE 	
Key themes			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Factors influencing the need for PGNE 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perceived impact of PGNE 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Barriers and challenges to PGNE 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recommendations for PGNE

These themes were then used to structure the subsequent part two literature review focused on deepening understanding of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP. To support transparency and rigour the identified overarching themes were used as headings within the written part two literature review.

3.5 Part two literature review findings

3.5.1 Furthering understanding of the research landscape

Similar to the part one literature review, none of the part two sources reviewed specifically focused on the concept of workplace support for PGNS to ALiP (n=6). Many of the sources reviewed provided limited details within conceptual, methodological, literature review or findings sections. In contrast to the depth of writing and detail required as part of doctoral research and thesis development. Potentially, this finding may have been influenced by some sources relating to pilot projects, preliminary stages of research and publication requirements e.g. word count. However, due to the limited body of literature some of these sources were included within the review to further insight into existing and emerging research.

Across the research-based literature reviewed, research study justification related to the need for PGNE in response to evolving patient care delivery and needs (Rawlings and Devery, 2018; Ślusarz, 2019; Wilson, Johnson and Asbury, 2019), professional development requirements (Ślusarz, 2019; Brodie, Butler and McLeod, 2020) and nursing workforce needs (Penman, Robinson and Cross, 2019; Brodie, Butler and McLeod, 2020). Correlating with the research studies rationales identified within the part one review.

Further justification for the research studies related to informing future strategic PGE planning, provision and capacity (Onwe, 2018; Rawlings and Devery, 2018; Penman, Robinson and Cross, 2019). These aims may have been influenced by most authors being associated with academic roles and HEI contexts. The research literature sources were also commonly associated with PG nursing programmes provided by the authors related HEI. Potentially influencing the finding that most of the sources reviewed focused on impact or impact evaluation of PG nursing programmes. With impact considered from the perspectives of graduate outcomes, participant destinations, change or improvement (Rawlings and Devery, 2018; Penman, Robinson and Cross, 2019; Wilson, Johnson and Asbury, 2019; Brodie, Butler and McLeod, 2020). Subsequently, research designs across the studies related to quantitative and qualitative surveys and questionnaires, frequently underpinned by descriptive approaches. Onwe (2018) qualitative inquiry focused on experiences however, the experiences related to those of lecturers, masters and PhD students regarding programme completion and withdrawal situated within an academic context. Reflecting on the findings of the part one review, this finding significantly highlighted the ongoing absence of qualitative research underpinned by lived experience methodologies specifically focused on PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP.

A geographical trend was also noted as four sources related to emerging research across Australia and New Zealand. These sources were purposefully included within my review to broaden understanding of global perspectives relating to the research area. Particularly based on Australian and New Zealand national nursing authorities and councils that have a similar regulatory role and requirements to the UK nursing regulatory body which may influence relevant insights relating to regulatory and CPD contexts of PGNE. Particularly, given the CPD requirements and educational standards for some specific PG and masters nursing programmes (Australian Nursing and Midwifery Board, 2019; NMC, 2019d; Australian Nursing and Midwifery Accreditation Council, no date; Nursing Council of New Zealand, no date).

The findings from this theme, illuminated that an absence of qualitative research underpinned by lived experience methodologies into PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP practice remained. This finding significantly supported ongoing justification for my study contributing to an original area of research and furthering understanding of PGNS experiences of workplace to ALiP.

The broader contexts of the research sources reviewed influenced the two remaining themes reflecting wider concepts associated with PGNE including the impact of PGNE and factors and challenges to PGNE.

3.5.2 Perceptions associated with the impact of PGNE

Wilson, Johnson and Asbury (2019) undertook a longitudinal, ten-year impact evaluation survey of a PG certification for a perioperative speciality nursing course (PGCPSNC). The study aimed to explore participant, service and organisational perspectives of course impact on clinical practice and nursing care, using Likert scale and descriptive statistics. A total of 100 participants were purposefully recruited from six associated private and public hospitals. Of which 27% were previous course graduates, the remaining participants included those with course specific student support roles (40%) and advisory board members (31%). The impact variables measured appeared to vary depending on the role of the participant. From previous course participant perspectives, positive PGCPSNC impact was associated with; confidence and self-efficacy (91%), knowledge and skills acquisition (87%), questioning and challenging practice (86%), decision-making (79%) and problem solving (75%) (Wilson, Johnson and Asbury, 2019). Positive impact from unit or service perspectives were at least 84% positively associated with; evidence-based practice, collegial support, team communication and quality of nursing (Wilson, Johnson and Asbury, 2019). Organisationally, the greatest impact was perceived to be associated with workforce development, skill mix and staff retention. While the findings of this study provided insight into the positive impact of PGE across student, service and organisational perspectives, the findings were limited to a specific PG course.

In seeking to further my understanding of the impact of PGNE, Rawlings and Devery's (2018) online retrospective survey explored PG palliative care education on the ability to change practice. The findings were limited to 76 respondents, influenced by a poor response rate from 426 associated alumni students. The majority of participants had undertaken either a graduate certificate, diploma, masters (respondents=29) or PhD programme within the previous five years. Participants were able to select multiple options relating to changes to practice. Of the participants 86.8% (respondents=66) agreed that the course studied had a long-term impact on practice and their ability to affect change. Commonly, associated agreed or somewhat agreed changes included confidence to disseminate knowledge (92%, n=68); development, influence or participation in decision-making with the team (93%, n=71) or within their workplace or organisation (80%, n=61) (Rawlings and Devery, 2018). Further identifying that knowledge and decision-making were also associated with impact. However, the study findings related to participants undertaking a broader range of PGNE including PhD programmes in contrast to PGNE focused on masters level education, within the context of my research.

Across the two studies, outcomes relating to the acquisition and dissemination of knowledge, confidence and decision-making were associated with positive impact following PG studies (Rawlings and Devery, 2018; Wilson, Johnson and Asbury, 2019). Potentially, these findings may reflect an emerging correlation between students and stakeholders' expectations and associated PGNE attributes. Outcomes associated with knowledge acquisition and dissemination, confidence and decision-making also resonated with fundamental competencies and standards required to practice at the point of registration as a registered nurse within the UK (NMC, 2018a). Due to the descriptive nature of the studies, it was not possible to explore how this aspect may have influenced the findings or gain further insight into possible distinctions between registered nurses having or not having a level of PGE on impact and change.

It is assumed that perceptions associated with the impact of PGNE would be a complex area to research given the multiple factors and contexts that influence PGNE and PGNS (F5). However, future in-depth research into assumed PGNE impact, change and influencing factors may contribute to a greater body of research evidence and understanding associated with PGNE outcomes. Such research may also provide opportunities to explore how interrelated factors may influence perceived PGNE outcomes, impact and changes to practice. For example, factors relating to previous learning experiences, professional regulatory standards, PG level descriptors and professional practice.

3.5.3 Further factors and challenges to PGNE

The literature reviewed identified further potential factors and challenges that may influence nurses undertaking PGNE. Within the context of Australian practice, Penman, Robinson and Cross' (2019) online survey aimed to identify factors that might attract previous nursing degree students to pursue PGNE. A limited total of 23 participants that completed a nursing degree in the past five years at one academic institution were recruited from an alumni of 694 associated graduates (Penman, Robinson and Cross, 2019). Of which six of the respondents had undertaken further graduate or PG education, although 14 participants planned to undertake PG studies within the next five years. The findings identified that 18 participants interest was dependent on government supported places. However, Penman, Robinson and Cross (2019) acknowledged limited government fee support for PGNE within the context of their research. Consequently, government or organisational funding, or support could potentially be viewed as enabler or barrier to PGNE (Penman, Robinson and Cross, 2019; Ślusarz, 2019).

Penman, Robinson and Cross (2019) also identified alternative factors and strategies to attract students to PGNE including previous good academic experience, online and flexible learning, course availability,

subject content and a range of courses. Potentially HEI may therefore need to further consider how multiple factors might be utilised to attract PGNS and mitigate barriers to PGNE.

Rawlings and Devery (2018) discussed organisational culture as a complex factor potentially influencing students ability to change practice. Based on their online survey focused on whether alumni with experiences of PG palliative care studies thought that their studies had a long-term impact on their practice and ability to affect change. The survey identified that 42% (n=23) of respondents felt that the organisational culture was not receptive to change. Although, the specific context of change and organisational culture was unknown, which may have been influenced by the design of the survey. Subsequently, 91% (n=50) of respondents did not feel enabled to implement change as a result of their further studies. Furthermore, it was identified that 16% (n=9) of respondents felt that they were not in a position to propose change following the PG course, with 33% (n=18) not feeling that they had a voice in the organisation (Rawlings and Devery, 2018). Similar to the part one literature review findings, some participants referred to positive course attributes to address organisational and workplace challenges (Richardson, 2013; Millberg *et al.*, 2014). Particularly with confidence in critical thinking and communication associated with not giving up or persevering to influence change in practice (Rawlings and Devery, 2018). Highlighting that organisational culture may be an enabler or barrier to PGNS and PGN application of PGNE attributes to practice, and ability to contribute to organisational and workplace change.

Rawlings and Devery (2018) also found that respondents motivation to implement practice changes declined from the time of PG studies. During studies 92.1% (n=70) of respondents agreed or strongly agreed that they felt motivated to implement practice changes. This response declined to 89.4% (n=68) immediately following studies, to 64% (n=48) much later after studies. Although, no specific contributory factors were attributed to this finding. Rawlings and Devery (2018) highlighted several potentially complex, interrelated barriers and enablers influencing PGNS and PGN ability and motivation to impact or change practice. These influencing factors resonated with those identified in the part one review including; personal, cultural, organisational, social, financial and structural aspects (Rawlings and Devery, 2018) (F5). Rawlings and Devery (2018) also suggested the need for further enquiry into change theory factors and that a different skillset may be required to support ability to appropriately change practice.

A further potential factor influencing PGNE related to mentorship. In the context of Wilson, Johnson and Asbury's (2019) ten-year longitudinal evaluation survey relating to the impact of a PGCPNSC it was briefly suggested from the results that mentoring experiences were less than ideal for some students. Further referring to earlier surveys reporting that mentorship was poor or insufficient (Wilson, Johnson and Asbury, 2019). Based on these earlier findings, training and mentor support had been developed further to enhance student-mentor experiences. It was acknowledged that in the context of the specific

PGCPSNC mentorship was a requirement. This may also have been influenced by acknowledged expectations of the Nursing Council of New Zealand relating to student support to consolidate learning and translate theory to practice (Wilson, Johnson and Asbury, 2019).

Within the remit of the part two review, no further literature was specifically identified relating to PGNE mentorship being an influencing factor. This finding may have been influenced by the part two review focusing on PGNS experiences of workplace support to apply learning in or to practice. However, in the context of UK practice, this may also have been influenced by the previously identified variety of PGNE programmes. Particularly, given specific educational standards for NMC AEI PG programmes or ACP programmes influenced by national or locally agreed practice partner agreements influencing workplace support infrastructures including mentorship. In contrast, to non-ACP or non-NMC related PGNE programmes. However, these considerations further suggested that mentorship may also be a contributory factor within the complex, multi-dimensional construct of workplace support for PGNS (F5).

Given the findings presented within this section, the ability for associated stakeholders to understand the influence of factors and challenges to PGNS is suggested as a key area for future research. Further research is considered key to support the assumed positive strategic, policy outcomes of PGNE by evidencing application of learning, impact and change to practice.

Given that Penman, Robinson and Cross' (2019) survey found that motivational reasons for undertaking PGE related to professional growth (39%, frequency number=9), community / patient care (13%, n=3) and benefiting colleagues, workplaces and patient care (as per qualitative comments). It is also essential that future research considers how students motivations prior to PGNE (e.g. applying learning and influencing future practice) can be maintained and supported throughout PGNE and beyond. Based on the assumption that PGNS can use learning, attributes and outcomes to positively impact and change practice.

3.6 Bringing together the parts one and two literature reviews

The majority of research justification and some findings supported the continued association with PGNE and positive outcomes relating to PG and advanced level attributes, benefits to patient care, strategic workforce and organisational objectives (Rawlings and Devery, 2018; Penman, Robinson and Cross, 2019; Ślusarz, 2019; Wilson, Johnson and Asbury, 2019; Brodie, Butler and McLeod, 2020). Assumed positive outcomes, however, appear to be situated within a complex sphere of interrelated personal, organisational and system contexts in which multiple enablers and barriers to PGNE may exist or evolve (Rawlings and Devery, 2018; Penman, Robinson and Cross, 2019; Ślusarz, 2019). Such enablers and barriers may be influenced by experiences prior to, during and following PGNE. With further sub-

dimensions relating to motivation, knowledge translation, confidence, criticality and decision-making influencing PGNS and PGN abilities and opportunities to impact and change practice (Rawlings and Devery; 2018; Penman, Robinson and Cross, 2019).

The part two review identified a continued emphasis on the need for education and for service providers to work in partnership with a commitment to support PGNE programme development and service needs (Rawlings and Devery, 2018; Wilson, Johnson and Asbury, 2019). Particularly, to inform educational preparation, professional development opportunities and evidence the quality, investment and value of PGNE from student, service and organisational perspectives (Rawlings and Devery, 2018; Wilson, Johnson and Asbury, 2019).

From the second literature review there appeared to be shift towards the need for future research into more complex theoretical and practical PGNE constructs to further support impact and change in practice (Rawlings and Devery, 2018). Particularly, in relation to PGNE knowledge translation, motivation, implementation of learning and change (Rawlings and Devery, 2018). In the context of my research, exploring PGNS experience of ALiP during PGNE rather than after completion was considered to be essential. Based on the assumption that understanding experiences from PGNS perspectives may provide insight to support and mitigate factors that may influence application of learning and motivation to impact and change practice during PGNE and beyond.

Collectively the part one and two literature reviews identified a specific gap in research literature, knowledge and understanding relating to PGNS lived experiences of workplace support to ALiP. The review findings also highlighted that PGNS may experience variation in the provision of PGNE workplace support, infrastructures and attitudes towards PGNE. However, motivations for undertaking PGNE related to professional growth and perceived benefits of PGNE to colleagues, workplaces and patient care. The part two findings also furthered understanding beyond the risks of disabling or deauthorising PGNS to use PGNE outcomes in practice, or underutilising PGNS (Drennan, 2008; Drennan and Hyde, 2009; Illingworth *et al.*, 2013). To reveal contrasting perspectives of PGNS feeling enabled or motivated to implement change in practice from the time of PG studies (Rawling and Devery, 2018). Reflexively, this furthered insight into the complex organisational, cultural, self and practice contexts that may impact on associated PGNE policy ambitions and desired PGNE outcomes. Significantly the collective findings of the reviews bring attention to the experience of the PGNS and importance of research that seeks to understand PGNS lived experiences of workplace support to ALiP. Based on the assumption that a greater field of research and understanding in this area may support PGNS and PGN to ALiP and contribute to enhanced patient care and healthcare ambitions.

Therefore, the research study taken forward within this thesis aims to explore PGNS lived experiences of workplace support to ALiP, with the purpose of making an original contribution to the limited body of

knowledge and lived experience research surrounding the concept of workplace support for PGNS to ALiP.

Chapter 4 – Methodological Context

4.1 Introduction

The parts one and two literature reviews identified a significant gap in research, knowledge and understanding relating to PGNS lived experiences of workplace support to ALiP. Therefore, this chapter outlines the research framework and methodology applied to my study to explore PGNS lived experiences of workplace support to ALiP. This chapter also brings together underpinning pedagogical learning perspectives with the chosen research ontology and approach to research design.

4.2 Methodological framework

The development of my methodological framework was initially led by considering the nature of social phenomena (ontology) and the beliefs and values that I held as a researcher about the nature of social reality (Denscombe, 2010). I also considered how these aspects influenced the research framework for my study. Reflexively, I became aware that my professional values and motivations relating to my area of research were influenced by a belief that it is essential to understand PGNS lived experiences of workplace support to ALiP. Furthermore, my beliefs, values and motivations were underpinned by a need to support PGNS as individuals in their roles and to ALiP as a way of contributing to person-centred healthcare practice. Subsequently, I chose to underpin my research study with a constructionist (subjective) ontology which assumes that the social world is viewed and constructed by multiple realities (Denscombe, 2010). This view aligned with the aim of my research to explore individual PGNS subjective lived experiences of workplace support to ALiP. Furthermore, aligning with the assumption that PGNS lived experiences would be diverse and individual to each person within the context of their workplace. Therefore, my chosen ontological and epistemological framework rejected a positivist framework that alternatively assumes an objective approach to knowledge, outcomes and universal truth (Fleming, Gaidys and Robb, 2003; Denscombe, 2010; Kalfe, 2011).

Correlating with constructionism, an interpretivist epistemology (existential ontology) further underpinned my methodological framework. My interpretivist approach assumed the creation of knowledge in the form of understanding multiple realities of PGNS lived experiences. This approach aimed to support my research making an original contribution to understanding PGNS subjective, lived experiences of workplace support to ALiP. Particularly, given that my literature reviews identified limited lived experience research and knowledge relating to PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP.

I was aware that the aim of my research study and literature review findings were guiding my decisions towards use of a qualitative lived experience methodology. However, to ensure rigour regarding my methodological framework choices and decisions, I reviewed approaches such as ethnography, grounded theory, action research and qualitative phenomenology e.g. descriptive phenomenology, interpretive phenomenological analysis and hermeneutic phenomenology. Following my review, I chose to underpin the methodological framework of my study with a qualitative, hermeneutic phenomenological approach. This decision was influenced by the key underpinning philosophical and methodological assumptions associated with hermeneutic phenomenology and hermeneutics. Particularly, the key philosophical underpinnings and work of Martin Heidegger (1962/1927; 1996/1927) and Hans-Georg Gadamer (2004/1960) which assume that our lived experiences are subjective and influenced by our temporal being in a socio-historic world.

Within contemporary qualitative research, hermeneutic phenomenological methodologies are also associated with seeking meaning of a phenomenon with the purpose of understanding the human experience (Crist and Tanner, 2003). Subsequently, the philosophical and methodological underpinnings of hermeneutic phenomenology provided an appropriate methodology to further understanding and illuminate meaning relating to PGNS subjective lived experiences of workplace support to ALiP. The chosen constructionist and philosophical underpinnings of my methodological framework also resonated with humanistic and lifelong learning pedagogical perspectives relating to my area of research (C2). Particularly, my beliefs and assumptions that learning is part of our individual being influenced by our individual, multiple subjective self, socio-historic, cultural experiences and contexts (Basset, 2004; Knowles, Holton and Swanston, 2005; Jarvis, 2010; Cranton, 2016). As opposed to contrasting behavioural, mechanical and elemental pedagogical theories which resonated with other ontological and epistemological frameworks (Knowles, Holton and Swanson, 2005; Curren, 2007).

In coming to this methodological decision, my enquiry led me to consider the broader philosophical development of phenomenology. Edmund Husserl is often considered the key philosopher of phenomenology in which he aimed to bring a focus to lived, taken for granted experiences through consciousness and intentionality of understanding phenomena (Koch, 1995; Lavery, 2003; Van Manen, 2014). Further influencing the development of other philosophers work and approaches to descriptive phenomenology. Husserl's (2012/1931) work was underpinned by an objective approach to concepts of bracketing, epoché and phenomenological reduction (Koch, 1995; Moran, 2012; Van Manen, 2014). To bring these concepts into the pragmatic context of research, such approaches involve the researcher bracketing, suspending and removing their own presuppositions about the phenomena to support an objective approach to interpreting the lived experiences (Koch, 1995). I chose not to underpin my methodological framework using such Husserlian approaches or a purely descriptive phenomenological

methodology. This decision was influenced by my choice of pursuing a professional doctorate rooted in the value of professionals bringing their own experiences and knowledge to their research and ways of furthering understanding. This led to my decision to reject the notion of the researcher objectively removing and suspending their own presuppositions from data interpretation and understanding phenomena. This decision was also influenced by my assumptions that as individuals, professionals and learners our experiences are influenced by multiple subjective self, socio-historic, cultural experiences and contexts of being with others. Subsequently, the decision to reject a purist Husserlian approach, drew me further towards a framework underpinned by Heideggerian and Gadamerian philosophical assumptions that acknowledge that our pre-understanding of being in a socio-historic world cannot be objectively separated (Heidegger, 1962/1927; Gadamer, 2004/1960). However, Heidegger acknowledged that his investigation of the preliminary concepts of phenomenology were influenced by the foundations laid by Husserl (Heidegger, 1993a/1927).

Heidegger's (1962/1927) fundamental ontology relates to our human '*Being*' ('*Dasein*') and what it means to be human in a socio-historical world, which is influenced by our pre-understandings, fore-structures and co-constitutions. In contrast to Husserl (2012/1931), Heidegger (1962/1927) positioned that we cannot objectively separate our fore-structures of understanding of being in the world from our interpretation. Therefore, Heidegger (1962/1927) assumed that interpretation is never presuppositionless. Furthermore, our fore-structures of understanding are brought to interpretation and grounded in something we have in advance that already exists in the world (our fore-having), something we see in advance (our fore-sight) and something we grasp in advance (our fore-conception) (Heidegger, 1962/1927). Underpinning the fore-structures of understanding within the context of my research aimed to recognise that as a professional doctorate student, I would bring my professional experiences, assumptions and ideas to interpretation. This would involve drawing upon an interplay of my past, current and future contexts, and acknowledging that the participants may bring these aspects to their lived experiences of being a PGNS. I also assumed the reflexive consideration of my fore-structures of understanding and that of the participants would contribute to a richer, in-depth, humanistic understanding of PGNS lived experiences of workplace support to ALiP.

Within Gadamer's (2004/1960) seminal text '*Truth and Method*', Gadamer positions that interpretation may not be purely reliant on our fore-meanings. This being influenced by a person coming to interpretation with consciousness of being prepared and open for it to tell us something (Gadamer, 2004/1960). Subsequently, I reflected upon assumed conscious to unconscious levels of awareness particularly relating to my role in interpreting the data. This highlighted the importance of reflexive and transparent approaches through interpretation and the use of critical conversations with my supervisors to bring conscious awareness to my thinking and fore-structures of understanding. This also led me to explore and consider Gadamer's (2004/1960) notions of prejudice and historicity. Within Gadamer's work the term prejudice is associated with having the 'courage to make use of your own understandings' as

part of interpretation (Gadamer, 2004/1960, p. 274). The use of this term contrasting to contemporary English language usage which may be associated with negative connotations. Of significance is that Gadamer's (2004/1960) notions of prejudice and historicity further emphasised my immersive role through my research and the importance of reflexively attuning to my understandings as a way of ensuring rigour and quality within my research. Reflexively, the philosophical assumptions of the fore-structures of understanding and remaining open to possibilities through interpretation of the text telling us something, drew me further towards a hermeneutic phenomenological approach (Heidegger, 1962/1927; Gadamer, 2004/1960). This approach also aimed to support my research illuminating and seeking meaning from PGNS lived experiences of workplace support to ALiP rather than a descriptive phenomenological approach.

Heidegger (1962/1927) also positioned the concept of phenomenology relating to the Greek terms 'logos' and 'phenomenon'. Heidegger (1993a/1927) discussed the meaning of 'logos' as speech, language and relatedness in coming to understand phenomenological meaning of the world and a way of letting things show as being unconcealed. Heidegger's (1962/1927) approach to unconcealing phenomenon is rooted in an ontological perspective relating to the deeper structures of our human existence rather than an ontic factual structure of human existence (Frede, 2006). Reflexively, this brought consideration back to the importance of Heidegger's (1962/1927) fundamental ontology about what it means to be human in a socio-historical world, which is influenced by our pre-understandings, fore-structures and co-constitutions. Furthermore, Heidegger (1993b/1967) positioned truth (alētheia) relating to unconcealment of phenomenon, drawing upon a continual interplay of forgottenness, hiddenness or covering up. In considering the preliminary concept of phenomenology and phenomenological concept of phenomenon Heidegger (1996/1927) positioned that:

This self-showing is nothing arbitrary, nor is it something like an appearing. The being of beings can least of all be something "behind which" something else stand as, something that "does not appear". (Heidegger, 1996/1927, p. 31)

Furthermore, Heidegger (1996/1927) drew upon the unconcealment or revealing of phenomenon through semblance, announcement and appearance. This furthered my understanding that phenomenon associated with the lived experience of PGNS may be concealed, covered up and brought to light through interpretation. However, in considering how I would and could reveal phenomenon through my hermeneutic phenomenological research. I was aware that Heidegger's work (1962/1927; 1993d/1954) is grounded in philosophy and a philosophical way of coming to thinking as opposed to providing a prescriptive, structured research methodology or method. However, Heidegger (1962/1927) positions the importance of coming into the circle of understanding in the right way, by bringing our own fore-structures of understanding and historicity to our interpretation.

'In the circle is hidden a positive possibility of the most primordial kind of knowing' (Heidegger, 1962/1927, p.195).

Subsequently, within my research, Heidegger's (1962/1927) philosophical work relating to the hermeneutic circle of understanding and philosophical notions underpinned a way of bringing phenomenon to light and let things show to furthering understanding and surfacing meaning about PGNS lived experiences of workplace support to ALiP. I was also drawn to Gadamer's position that:

The horizon is the range of vision that includes everything that can be seen from a particular vantage point. Applying this to the thinking mind, we speak of narrowness of horizons, of the possibility of expansion of horizon, of the opening up to new horizons and so forth. (Gadamer, 2004/1960, p. 301)

Gadamer's (2004/1960) work extends beyond Heidegger's (1962/1927) concept of horizons and possibilities towards the notion of a fusion of horizons. This highlighted the importance of being self-aware in maintaining an openness to revealing phenomenon. Furthermore, how underpinning my methodological framework with Gadamer's (2004/1960) notion of a fusion of horizons could broaden possibilities when interpreting and surfacing meaning from the lived experience of the PGNS.

I also chose to draw upon contemporary hermeneutic phenomenological approaches and methodological literature to guide my methodological framework and pragmatic aspects of undertaking my research study. This approach aimed to support a balance, rigour and congruence between the socio-historic philosophical work of Heidegger and Gadamer and the remit of my study being set within professional doctorate and practice contexts. This decision was also influenced by awareness of Heidegger's further work relating to literature surrounding potential political associations. Therefore within the context of my study, Heideggerian approaches to enquiry were guided and set within the context of contemporary hermeneutic phenomenological healthcare research and researchers including the work of Elizabeth Smythe, Gill Thomson, Lesley Dibley and Susan Crowther.

In contemporary research, hermeneutic phenomenological methodologies are also associated with seeking meaning of phenomenon to understand lived human experiences (Crist and Tanner, 2003). Crowther and Thomson (2023) position that bringing together phenomenological and hermeneutic aspects of Heidegger and Gadamer's philosophical work is invaluable to seeking a greater human understanding. Furthermore, highlighting the aim of contemporary hermeneutic research to support a deeper understanding and meaning from the phenomenon revealed (Crowther and Thomson, 2023). Particularly in bringing together the phenomenological question concerned with what is lived experience like, with the hermeneutic question of how the lived experience is meaningful (Crowther and Thomson, 2023).

Subsequently, both the philosophical and contemporary methodological underpinnings of hermeneutic phenomenology guided my methodological framework. These approaches aimed to support a sustained orientation to understanding what is the lived experience of PGNS of workplace support to ALiP and how is their lived experience meaningful to understanding the phenomenon revealed. These approaches also aimed to support my research revealing phenomenon to furthering understanding and illuminating meaning from the PGNS lived experiences of workplace support to ALiP.

Based on my chosen methodological framework, my study did not aim to provide outcomes associated with a positivist paradigm or seek an objective knowledge or a universal truth relating to PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP. For example through generalisable findings, developing a theoretical or conceptual framework, or testing a hypothesis relating to PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP. Alternatively, my research findings termed as 'offerings' alternatively aimed to reflect multiple, subjective realities and '*temporality*' of being a PGNS and '*being-in-the-world*' (Heidegger, 1993a/1927). However, I was aware that some of my professional beliefs and values influenced a desire for the research findings to make an original contribution to furthering understanding and meaning about PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALIP. In seeking to understand my presuppositions, I considered Gadamer's (2004/1960) position that,

'To acquire horizon means that one learns to look beyond what is close at hand – not to look away from it but to see it better, within a larger whole and truer proportion' (Gadamer, 2004/1960, p. 304).

In dwelling with Gadamer's (2004/1960) position to look beyond what was close at hand, I came to a deeper understanding that my professional hopes for my study were influenced by a deeper assumption. This assumption related to the professional motivations and hopes that furthering understanding and meaning of PGNS experiences may positively contribute to enhancing; workplace support for PGNS to ALiP; and the delivery of patient care or aspects of nursing roles. Crowther and Thomson (2023) also suggest that the philosophical underpinnings of hermeneutic thinking call the researcher to be open to new horizons of understanding. Reflexively considering these greater perspectives, provided a way of reaching a personal harmony. This harmony relating to the professional expectations that I placed on myself about the uncertain, unknown and unpredictable outcomes of my research and the value of maintaining an openness to bringing new possibilities (or horizons) of understanding and meaning about PGNS lived experiences of workplace support to ALIP through my research.

4.3 Framework for rigour

At the time of enquiry, no universal, standardised criteria or framework for assessing rigour (trustworthiness) within qualitative and hermeneutic phenomenological research was identified (Lavery, 2003; Rolfe, 2006). This finding may be influenced by the diversity of qualitative methodologies and debate associated with an appropriate criterion due to the influence of the paradigm debates (De Witt and Ploeg, 2006; Rolfe, 2006). Furthermore, hermeneutic phenomenology is underpinned by philosophical approaches rather than prescribed methodologies and methods.

I considered that rigour within my research was essential to support the quality and credibility of my research and research outcomes, my legitimacy as a researcher and to address ethical requirements and considerations (De Witt and Ploeg, 2006; NMC, 2018e). Subsequently, I used De Witt and Ploeg's (2006) Framework for Evaluating Rigour to address rigour and trustworthiness developed from a critical review of interpretative phenomenology quality frameworks aligning with the phenomenological aspect of my study.

The Framework for Evaluating Rigour focused on transparent consideration of 'expressions of rigour' from the philosophical underpinnings of the research through the research process, to the research outcomes (De Witt and Ploeg, 2006). Using a framework with expressions of rigour as opposed to traditional criterion of rigour may potentially limit understanding or risk transparency of how rigour had been addressed. To mitigate against this potential risk, Figure 8 demonstrates my alignment of De Witt and Ploeg's (2006) expressions of rigour to more commonly associated qualitative criteria. This approach supported me to demonstrate how rigour would be addressed as part of the ethical approval application for my study. Expressions of rigour have been stated as 'EoR' throughout the subsequent chapters to demonstrate consideration of rigour throughout the research process.

Figure 8: Framework for evaluating rigour

Expression of rigour (EoR)	Key elements	Alignment to traditional qualitative criteria of rigour
Actualisation	Interpretation goes beyond my study, with an emphasis on future realisation of the finding e.g. dissemination of the research findings / offerings.	Transferability
Balanced Integration	Alignment between philosophical approach, methodological framework and subject e.g. application of Heideggerian approaches throughout my research process balanced with participants sharing their experiences.	-
Concreteness	Written findings are articulated pragmatically with relevance and meaning to the lived experience, subject / research question, historical and cultural contexts.	Rhetoric
Openness	Sustained orientation to my subject and the participants sharing of their experiences e.g. interview guide, data analysis / interpretation. Transparent and accountable decision-making throughout my research process to support scrutiny.	Confirmability, Credibility, Dependability, Transferability
Resonance	The richness of my research processes influence readers' experiences and understanding of the subject and study.	Credibility, Transferability

Adapted from: De Witt and Ploeg (2006).

4.4 Ethical approval

4.4.1 Ethical approval process

Ethical approval for my study was sought and received from the associated University Ethics Committee (UEC) (A7). At the time of research, the Ethical Principles Guiding Research with Human Participants (UEC, 2016) and the UEC (2016) frameworks and guidelines were applied to support ethical approval and my practice as a research student. The aim being to support meeting the fundamental ethical principle of respecting human dignity.

Permission to access and recruit PGNS for my study was received from relevant professionals with a gatekeeper role for the associated PGNE programmes (A8-9). NHS Integrated Research Application System ethical approval was not required based on the aim and purpose of my study and the inclusion criteria focused on PGNS.

In view of undertaking research during the Coronavirus disease-2019 (COVID-19) pandemic I sought further approval processes in view of Health and Safety, and Risk Assessment with the support of my supervisory team. Subsequently, I received confirmation from the associated HEI that a Privacy Impact Assessment was not required for my research study.

4.4.2 Ethical framework

As a research student and registered nurse adherence to the UEC (2016) ethical framework and professional standards (NMC, 2018e) aimed to support:

- compliance to required ethical, legal, professional and research codes (UEC, 2016; NMC, 2018e)
- a participant-centred approach
- research integrity, rigour and worthiness (Punch, 2016).

Figure 9 provides an outline of the ethical frameworks applied to my study.

Figure 9: Outline Ethical Framework

Ethical principles guiding research with human participants (UEC, 2016)	Aligned to good practice principle (UEC, 2016)
Autonomy, veracity and informed consent	Honesty
Privacy and confidentiality	Openness (transparency)
Justice and inclusiveness	Respect
Benefits and harms	Care

To align with De Witt and Ploeg's (2006) framework for rigour the ethical principle of transparency was referred to as 'openness' rather than transparency. Section 4.6 further demonstrates how key ethical principles and considerations were addressed throughout my research.

4.5 My hermeneutic phenomenological approach

4.5.1 Methodology

Heidegger's intention was not to provide a prescriptive method for applying hermeneutic phenomenology. Alternatively, Heideggerian approaches provide an underpinning philosophical ontology

to interpret, uncover and reveal phenomena to further understanding about the meaning of our human '*being-in-the-world*', described by Heidegger (1993a/1927) using the term '*Dasein*'. This underpinning philosophy aligned with the aim of my study to explore PGNS lived experiences of being-in-the-world related to workplace support to ALiP.

Heidegger's (1962/1927) ontological approach to the way in which we come to understanding our '*being-in-the-world*', '*Dasein*' is through the hermeneutic spiral (used interchangeably with the hermeneutic circle) and our fore-structures of understanding. Heidegger (1962/1927) positioned that:

... we genuinely take hold of this possibility only when, in our interpretation, we have understood that our first, last and constant task is never to allow our fore-having, fore-sight, and fore-conceptions to be presented to us by fancies and popular conceptions, but rather to make the scientific theme secure by working out these fore-structures in terms of the things themselves. (Heidegger, 1962/1927, p. 195)

Gadamer (2004/1960) positions that Heidegger's reference to making the scientific theme secure, relates to bringing consciousness to our fore-structures of understanding. From a contemporary perspective of hermeneutic phenomenological research, this involves bringing our being-in-the-world with an interplay of our past, present and future experiences. Furthermore, such philosophical underpinning should be interwoven as a golden thread in the doing of hermeneutic phenomenological research (Dibley *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, a researcher's reflexive engagement with the hermeneutic spiral aims to support a focus on what it means to be in the world and surface meaning from lived experiences (Crowther and Thomson, 2020). Based on this understanding, I chose to refer to the term hermeneutic spiral rather than cycle within my research. This decision aimed to emphasise the continual, dynamic approach that I would be immersed in to interpret and move between the parts and the whole of the participants lived experiences. Furthermore, use of the term spiral aimed to highlight the philosophical assumption that sharing my interpretations and research findings with others would bring new interpretations, horizons of understanding and further thinking about my research topic (Heidegger, 1962/1927; Crowther and Thomson, 2023).

Drawing upon Heidegger's (1962/1927; 1996/1927) seminal first and second divisions of 'Being and Time'. Heidegger (1962/1927) viewed that the philosophical principles, notions and existential structures of our '*Dasein*' provide a way of uncovering and revealing phenomena to understand our meaning of '*being-in-the-world*'. Heidegger's (1962/1927) work also sought to create a new language and meaning of our '*Dasein*' through these philosophical notions, existential structures and concepts. Subsequently, using traditional words in a different context, introducing new words and in some cases using nouns as verbs (Dibley *et al.*, 2020). This aspect of Heidegger's work may lead to criticism in applying contemporary hermeneutic phenomenological research due to the complexities of accurately translating Heidegger's use of language and the meaning of words from our traditional understanding (Dibley *et al.*,

2020). Particularly, as Heidegger's seminal text 'Being and Time' was written in German with slight variations existing between several English translations and guides (Heidegger, 1962/1927; 1993a/1927; 1996/1927; Mulhall, 2013). In considering rigour within my research, I was aware of the need to ensure that the contemporary, English language understanding of words were not blurred with Heideggerian meaning.

A challenge within my research was to clearly demonstrate the appropriate use and application of Heidegger's principles, notions and concepts. In view of these challenges, I interchangeably compared and contrasted several translations of Heidegger's (1962/1927; 1993a/1927; 1996/1927) 'Being and Time', supported with the use of a wider range of texts relating to understanding Heidegger's philosophy and notions. I also completed hermeneutic phenomenology courses influenced by expert researchers including Crowther, Dibley, Smythe and Thomson with experiences of Heideggerian approaches to hermeneutic phenomenology within the context of contemporary healthcare research. Such learning activities supported me to use the philosophical language and notions as a way of being called to further thinking through my interpretation of the research data and therefore, come to new or further contemporary thinking about phenomenon associated with PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP (Dibley *et al.*, 2020).

In the absence of a prescriptive method for implementing hermeneutic phenomenological research. My methodological framework primarily drew upon Heideggerian philosophy, principles and assumptions as well as some Gadamerian aspects to guide my hermeneutic phenomenological research (Heidegger, 1962/1927; Gadamer, 2004/1960). This approach aimed to support interpretation, furthering understanding and surfacing meaning from the PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP. Therefore, throughout the research process:

- I maintained a clear commitment to the concern of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP, orientation to the research aim and exploration of the lived experience through application of the hermeneutic spiral (Kalfe, 2011). This included ensuring a focus on both the phenomenological question what is the lived experience and the hermeneutic question of how is the lived experience meaningful (Crowther and Thomson, 2023).
- My role as a research student was reflexive, immersive and participatory. My fore-structures of understanding relating to my being-in-the-world also contributed to the richness and depth of interpretation (Heidegger, 1962/1927; Koch, 1995; Moran, 2000; Lavery, 2003). Therefore, my pre-understandings were not bracketed out through data interpretation, rejecting a reductionist bracketed method and Husserlian approach (Husserl, 2012/1931; Moran, 2012).
- A holistic understanding of the phenomena aimed to arise through data interpretation and 'indissoluble unity' (Koch, 1995, p. 831) between myself and the participants' lived experiences

and being-in-the-world (co-constitution) within cultural, historical and social contexts (Lavery, 2003).

- It was assumed that participants would react to being studied which was accounted for within my interpretation of the data, ethical considerations and my reflexive role as a researcher (Denscombe, 2010). In the context of qualitative interviews, social and relational factors between the participant and the role of the interviewer may influence participant responses or disclosure of a perceived acceptable response by the participant (Streubert, 2011). Based on the philosophical underpinnings of my study, it is assumed that our *being-in-the-world* is one always already there that we share with others (Heidegger, 1996/1927). Therefore, rejecting a notion that our individual self being is detached from others, or that the influence of others can be objectively measured or separated (Heidegger, 1996/1927). I also considered the philosophical assumptions that our subjective lived experiences are grounded by our temporal being in a socio-historic world with others, and our fore-structures of understanding (Heidegger, 1962/1927; Gadamer, 2004/1960). Subsequently, I assumed that participants' pre-understandings in coming to the interview and sharing their experiences may potentially be influenced by their perceptions of my historic professional backgrounds as a nurse, nurse educator and professional doctorate student. In acknowledging these assumptions, a range of approaches aimed to support developing a trusting relationship with participants and ways participants could come to openly sharing their lived experiences of being a PGNS. Examples of such approaches included; the provision of participant information, setting the interview context with the participant prior to the interview commencing and ways of anonymising and presenting the research data.

Collectively, these approaches aimed to demonstrate rigour throughout my research study including balanced integration, concreteness, openness and resonance.

4.5.2 My approach to reflexivity

In the context of my research reflexivity was understood as an essential, active process threaded through my professional doctorate studies (Dibley *et al.*, 2020; QAA, 2020a). Reflexive approaches supported maintaining self-awareness to explore critical questions and bring my pre-understandings to the research process as a research student, person and nurse educator. These approaches also supported methodological and philosophical congruence with Heidegger's (1962/1927) hermeneutic circle such as bringing my fore-structures of understanding to interpretation of the participants' lived experiences (Heidegger, 1962/1927; Gadamer, 2004/1960). The integration of reflexive approaches aimed to support ethical approaches and rigour from the identified area of research through the research process to dissemination of the research outcomes.

Based on the view that it was essential to weave reflexive approaches into and through the research process. This section does not explicitly describe a list of prescriptive reflexive activities undertaken. Alternatively, iterative, reflexive ways are demonstrated by bringing a sense of self within the writing style of my thesis. Furthermore, reflexive approaches are interwoven through the research process e.g. from the initial rationale for my area of research to reflections on the literature reviewed and the integration of critical reflexive questioning as part of data interpretation (A16).

4.5.3 Sampling and recruitment strategy

Following ethical approval and gatekeeper permissions a purposeful sampling strategy was used to recruit voluntary participants enrolled on PGNE programmes (SCQF level 11) across one HEI (A6). The purposeful recruitment strategy and proposed sample size of 6-10 participants aimed to:

- support convenient access to relevant PGNS associated with my study.
- yield a manageable volume of rich, in-depth subjective data that I could realistically immerse myself in through data interpretation (Smythe, 2011) (EoR: Openness).
- align to my philosophical and methodological approach, rejecting the purpose of providing generalisable results from a wide population to reach data saturation or theory generation associated with other methodologies (Lavery, 2003; Bond and Gerrish, 2006; Dibley *et al.*, 2020).
- be appropriate to professional doctorate requirements e.g. thesis and completion requirements (Smythe, 2011).

The inclusion and exclusion criteria within Figure 10 was used to ensure that participants would be able to share their subjective PGNS lived experiences of workplace support to ALiP (Lavery, 2003) (EoR: Balanced integration).

Figure 10: Criteria for my research study

Inclusion criteria Participants must be:	Exclusion criteria Students that:
➤ a continuing PGNS enrolled on a PGN programme (SCQF level 11) at the associated HEI.	➤ had only completed one term of a PGN programme (SCQF level 11) at the associated HEI.
➤ practising as a professionally registered nurse.	➤ were not enrolled on a PGN programme (SCQF level 11) at the associated HEI.
➤ willing to share their subjective lived experience as a PGNS.	➤ were not practising as a professionally registered nurse.

My recruitment strategy included dissemination of an email invitation to PGNS to participate in my study across the chosen PGNE programmes, all of which received gatekeeper permissions. The email invite was sent by associated programme administration teams ensuring anonymity and confidentiality when recruiting participants from the overall sample population. This approach aligned to my approved ethics application, to ensure appropriate access to personal student data based on my research student role.

To support an open and informed recruitment processes, the recruitment invitation included a participant information sheet and standard privacy notice. These sources were approved by the associated ethics committee and provided information regarding voluntary participation, an outline of the research purpose and participant involvement (A10-11). PGNS interested in participating in my study were requested to respond via my university email address for further information.

Any respondents expressing interest were sent a standard email including the electronic participant information sheet, privacy notice and informed consent form (A11-13). In view of ethical considerations, respondents were advised of a two week period to confirm participation and return a completed informed consent form (UEC, 2016). Participants were requested to complete the electronic informed consent form using a simple or advanced electronic signature and return this directly to my university email address (NHS Health Research Authority (HRA), no date). If additional responses had been received beyond the required sample size, students would have been emailed, thanked for their interest and notified of potential further contact e.g. in the case of a withdrawal (A12).

Two phases of recruitment occurred over several months to support recruitment across a range of PGNE programmes at one HEI. Invites were sent on no more than two occasions in view of ethical principles and supporting response rates. A total of four voluntary PGNS participants were recruited, a smaller sample size than the proposed 6-10 participants. This was still deemed appropriate to align with my

methodology and yield rich, in-depth subjective data to explore PGNS experience of workplace support to ALiP (Smythe, 2011). Based on the smaller sample size agreement was sought and given from my Supervisory Team and the Chair of the Ethics Committee to proceed with my research. I was aware that the smaller sample size may influence criticism of my research and the significance and credibility of my research outcomes. Therefore, Chapter 10 discusses the perceived strengths and limitations associated with the sample size and the actions I took to mitigate concerns and ensure rigour and credibility within my research.

4.5.4 Data collection

Within hermeneutic phenomenological research data collection and interpretation occur simultaneously guided by the hermeneutic spiral, through a continual way of listening, reading, writing, dwelling and thinking (Gadamer, 2004/1960; Buxton, 2011). The hermeneutic spiral also involved bringing my fore-structures of understanding to come to understanding the phenomena in the right way and reflexively surface meaning about the lived experience (Heidegger, 1962/1927; Gadamer, 2004/1960; Crowther and Thomson, 2020) (EoR: Openness, concreteness, resonance). Subsequently, my experiences of working with the data and the hermeneutic spiral from the point of data collection involved a continual process of moving from the whole to parts and back to the whole to further understanding and meaning from the data (Gadamer, 2004/1960).

Prior to data collection, I completed a pilot of the interview schedule and pre-grounding discussion with a professional doctorate supervisor to reflexively identify and deepen understanding of my fore-structures of understanding associated with PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP (EoR: Openness). It was assumed that revealing and bringing self-awareness of my fore-structures of understanding prior to data collection and interpretation would contribute to a richer, in-depth understanding of the phenomenon revealed. Furthermore, this aimed to be congruent with Heidegger's (1962/1927) approach to coming into the hermeneutic circle rather than my pre-understandings and experiences as a person, student researcher and nurse educator being reductively bracketed out. Based on Heidegger's (1962/1927) notion of '*temporality*', I integrated further reflexive grounding and fore-structure activities throughout my research process including hermeneutic phenomenology CPD activities during the research stage of my professional doctorate and as part of coming to data interpretation (EoR: Openness).

Reflecting on the philosophical underpinnings of my study, Heidegger (1993c/1959) also brought a hermeneutic focus to the interpretation of speech and language as a way of letting things show as being unconcealed. Furthermore, within Gadamer's (2004/1960) seminal 'Truth and Methods' text, Gadamer (2004/1960) positions a focus on language that lives in speech, transcription and interpretation of the

text. Gadamer (2004/1960) emphasised the person interpreting the text being open and prepared for it to tell him something. Furthermore, it is assumed that through interpretation we remain open to meaning of the text and to a questioning of things that opens possibilities (Gadamer, 2004/1960). Subsequently, within contemporary hermeneutic phenomenological research, participant interviews are associated as a primary data collection method to obtain an accurate description or account of the participants verbal telling of their lived experiences (Buxton, 2011). Within the context of my research, digital audio-recorded interviews with volunteer PGNS participants were chosen as the way of collecting data about PGNS lived experiences of workplace support to ALiP. The audio-recorded interviews were then transcribed and interpreted to reveal phenomenon to further understanding and surface meaning about PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP.

My rationale for the use of telephone interviews as opposed to video or in person interviews at a specific location was based on my chosen sample population and supporting experiential and empirical evidence relating to the use of telephone interviews in qualitative and hermeneutic phenomenological research. The inclusion criteria for my study required participants to be practicing as registered nurses and be a continuing PGNS enrolled on a PGN programme which may have influenced participants studying across varied geographical locations and distances from the HEI location. Subsequently, the use of telephone interviews rather than in person interviews at a geographical location aimed to support an inclusive, participant-centred, flexible, cost effective and time efficient method of data collection (Musselwhite *et al.*, 2007; Holt, 2010; Trier-Bieniek, 2012; Mealer and Jones, 2014; Ward, Gott and Hoare, 2015; Drabble *et al.*, 2016).

Telephone interviews were also preferable to digital recorded video interviews based on ethical considerations relating to supporting participant privacy, participant accessibility to video technology and internet access and video data storage and processing system issues at the time that I sought ethical approval (pre-pandemic context) and data collection. The use of audio-recorded telephone interviews also aimed to minimise intrusion within the participant's home, HEI or work environment in contrast to online digital recorded video or in person interviews at a set location e.g. the participant's home, work or study environment. Subsequently, the physical distance created by telephone use aimed to enhance the participants' experiences of; confidentiality, anonymity, privacy, and a relaxed interview environment (Musselwhite *et al.*, 2007; Holt, 2010; Trier-Bieniek, 2012; Ward, Gott and Hoare, 2015; Drabble *et al.*, 2016).

The use of telephone interviews may be challenged in contrast to video approaches due to the associated loss of two forms of non-verbal data. However, the absence of kinesics and proxemics data was considered advantageous to maintain a focus on collecting an accurate description or account of the participants verbal telling of their PGNS experiences and support emotional distance, removing any potential judgements or power between the participant and researcher (Holt, 2010; Trier-Bieniek, 2012;

Ward, Gott and Hoare, 2015) (EoR: Openness, concreteness, resonance). To mitigate against potential challenges regarding the loss of non-verbal data and cues, the interview guide was underpinned by an open prompt question framework to support active listening, clarity and in-depth understanding of the participants experiences (Benner, Tanner and Chelsea, 1996; Ironside, 2014; Mealer and Jones, 2014) (A14). Active listening is a positive attribute associated with telephone interviews supporting participant orientation to their experience, reciprocation, a natural conversational style and rapport between the participant and researcher (Ward, Gott and Hoare, 2015; Drabble *et al.*, 2016) (EoR: Openness). Active listening requires intense concentration and presence of the researcher, therefore interviews were planned over a period of time, with self-reflection and anonymous supervisory team discussion used to support reflexive, interview practice (Trier-Bieniek, 2012; Irvine, Drew and Sainsbury, 2013).

The individual interviews were undertaken from a private room within the associated HEI. Based on participant information, participants were advised to ensure a private environment of their choice (A11). The participant information aimed to ensure the participant was situated within a safe, comfortable and private interview environment in consideration of good ethical and professional practice and data protection considerations (A11). Such environmental considerations aimed to promote a trusting space and relationship with the participants to support exploration and immersion in the sharing of their lived experiences (Rapport, 2005; Smythe *et al.*, 2008).

Interviews were anticipated to last around 60 minutes depending on the PGNS availability and the time required to share their lived experience. Within several qualitative studies, an average of 60 minute telephone interviews with the use of open questioning were deemed to yield rich, in-depth data which aligned to the anticipated duration of my interviews (Holt, 2010; Irvine, 2011; Drabble *et al.*, 2016). Two digital dictaphones and electronic researcher notes were used to accurately record verbal and non-verbal data (chronemic and paralinguistic) during the interviews.

I used a discovery interview approach based on asking each participant a consistent, broad, open hermeneutic phenomenological questions that sought the telling and sharing of their lived experience (Ryan, Coughlan and Cronin, 2009; Healy, 2011, Crowther and Thomson, 2023). For example: 'Can you please tell me about...' (Healy, 2011, p. 224) your experiences of workplace support to apply your learning in practice? (A14). The use of this type of question supported a focus on the participant's being-in-the-world by creating openness to explore the participant's unknown subjective lived experience, as opposed to the participant answering closed, pre-planned structured questions (Lavery, 2003; Smythe *et al.*, 2008) (EoR: Balanced integration, concreteness). Open prompt questions were used to facilitate deeper exploration into the participant's lived experience or to clarify understanding e.g. 'Can you tell me more about? What happened next?' (Healy, 2011; Crowther and Thomson, 2020) (EoR: Openness).

Benner, Tanner and Chesla's (1996) guide to interview questioning was used to develop a prompt question framework (A14). As part of my professional doctorate, development activities were undertaken

to support knowledge and skills associated with effective interview techniques and practice. These activities aimed to enhance effective communication and a trusting relationship with the participants to yield rich, in-depth, relevant data and support rigour during the interview process (Ryan, Coughlan and Cronin, 2009) (EoR: Openness). Such activities also demonstrated my consideration and ongoing development towards aspects of the Vitae (2010) Research Development Framework e.g. Domain A Knowledge and Intellectual Abilities and Domain C Research Governance and Organisation.

A pilot interview conducted with a professional doctorate supervisor supported my knowledge and skills development, and constructive feedback to support any modifications to my interview schedule or equipment (Chenail, 2011). Feedback positively commented on the use of a check in style with the participant prior to the interview. Following discussion this type of question was considered transferable to interviews and was subsequently integrated into the interview schedule. The addition of this question aimed to support a participant-centred focus, openly asking if there was anything important to the participant about their PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP that they may wish to share prior to bringing the interview to a close (A14).

Participants were offered a debriefing conversation with me via telephone immediately after the recorded interview. This information was provided as part of the participant information sheet and initial introductory information during the telephone conversation prior to data collection commencing (A11; A14). Debriefing provided me with an opportunity to check-in with the participant to identify any potential concerns or issues that may have arisen during the interview process.

In view of approved ethical and data protection processes, post-interview digital recordings were immediately uploaded from the dictaphone to an approved encrypted electronic drive. The recordings were then deleted from both dictaphones. I then listened to each digital recording using headphones within a private environment to anonymously transcribe each interview. Data transcripts were saved on the approved encrypted electronic drive. During this process, any electronic interview notes were integrated into the transcriptions as non-verbal data to contribute to the richness and depth of understanding the participant's lived experience (Ryan, Coughlan and Cronin, 2009) (EoR: Openness, richness) (A15).

Following transcription, I listened to the digital recording again while reading the transcript to ensure accurate transcription and make any required amendments (A15). Member checking of transcripts or interpreted data was not used to assess rigour. From an ontological perspective, member checks create an opportunity for new perspectives to emerge. Therefore, it was assumed that member checking of the transcript in a different space and time might compromise the original data and methodological rigour (McConnell-Henry, Francis and Chapman, 2011; Dibley *et al.*, 2020) (EoR: Openness, balanced integration). Subsequently, participant involvement in my research study ended at telephone interview completion prior to participants being offered a debrief conversation.

Data transcription, analysis and written thesis development took place between the associated HEI and my study environment in adherence to ethical approval (UEC, 2016), governmental and HEI COVID-19 guidelines and General Data Protection Regulations (GDPR) (European Parliament and the Council of the European Union (EPCEU), 2016) at the time of my research.

4.5.5 Data interpretation

Within the context of my hermeneutic phenomenological study, it was assumed that no singular, correct or finite interpretation (analysis) of the data exists based on the philosophical and methodological assumptions of multiple realities, truths and the notion of '*temporality*' relating to our constantly changing '*being-in-the-world*' ('*Dasein*') (Heidegger, 1962/1927). Alternatively, the aim of hermeneutic phenomenological data interpretation is to reveal the phenomena by unconcealing the data until interpretation is plausible and surface meaning from the lived experience (Heidegger, 1962/1927; Crowther and Thomson, 2023). Reflecting, on the positioning of the hermeneutic spiral within my research, this involved bringing my fore-structures of understanding to interpretation (Heidegger, 1962/1927). Furthermore, I was immersed in a way of interpretation that involved continually moving from the whole to the parts and back to the whole of the data to come to understanding the phenomena in the right way and illuminate meaning about the PGNS lived experiences (Heidegger, 1962/1927; Gadamer, 2004/1960) (EoR: Openness, concreteness, resonance).

As part of being on the way to reveal phenomenon and surface meaning about PGNS lived experiences of workplace support to ALiP. I manually transcribed each of the digital audio-recorded tapes from the individual participant interviews while simultaneously commencing the process of data interpretation. The anonymised digital text transcripts also included my initial reflexive, interpretive notes which were then transferred into my developed data interpretation table (A15).

Gadamer (2004/1960) discussed the interpreter bringing their own thoughts to re-awaken the meaning of the text and their own horizon into play with the text and towards a fusion of horizons. However, as previously acknowledged, there is no singular, prescribed method associated with hermeneutic phenomenological research including interpretation and presentation of the transcribed data. Following reading around contemporary hermeneutic phenomenological research, this led me to Crowther *et al.* (2016) work around crafting stories. Crowther *et al.* (2016) positions crafted stories being philosophically congruent as an approach to revealing our ways of being, supporting researchers to be attuned to what lies in, between and beyond the transcribed words relating to the phenomenon. Furthermore, this approach aims to support the researcher to surface meaning and share participants' lived experiences in ways that resonate with the reader or listener (Crowther *et al.*, 2016).

Subsequently, I used aspects of Crowther *et al.*' (2016) crafted stories approaches as part of data interpretation. These aspects aimed to guide and support anonymous text excerpts being taken from the verbatim transcripts and crafted to convey the phenomenon revealed and illuminate meaning from the participants' lived experiences of workplace support to ALiP. My reflexive and immersive engagement with the crafting of stories also supported me to move from initial descriptive analysis towards deeper interpretation of the participants' lived experiences (Crowther and Thomson, 2020). Further approaches to crafting the stories could have been extended for example towards poetic ways of crafting stories and presenting the research findings (Crowther *et al.*, 2016). However, I chose to use an approach that grounded the crafted extracts into analytic discussion of the research offerings (C5-9). This approach aimed to support the crafted stories meaningfully conveying the phenomenon revealed and my interpretative leaps that surfaced meaning from the PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP. As a professional doctorate student, this decision was also based on finding a balance between the extent of creative approaches to crafting stories and aspects of research integrity, rigour and timeframes.

Crowther *et al.* (2016) also raised some of the debates associated with crafted stories based on perceptions of the researcher altering verbatim transcripts and their potential role and power influencing the crafting of stories. Subsequently, I used a range of templates to capture my approaches to data interpretation and crafting stories to demonstrate philosophical and methodological congruence, transparency and openness regarding my role crafting stories (A15-16). Furthermore, my approach to crafting stories was guided my data interpretation framework underpinned by the hermeneutic spiral (F11). My data interpretation framework aimed to maintain ways of moving from the transcripts to crafted stories and from the whole and parts to come to understanding and illuminate meaning from the PGNS lived experiences of workplace support to ALiP in the right way (Heidegger, 1962/1927; Gadamer, 2004/1960; Crowther *et al.*, 2016).

I initially reduced the anonymised verbatim transcripts to openly remove irrelevant details as part of the process of showing the phenomenon being presented (Crowther *et al.*, 2016) (A15). The reduction and removal of the transcribed text was considered an iterative process throughout the crafting of stories. Initially, removal of irrelevant or extraneous details did not result in significant reduction of the transcripts. Justification for this initial approach aimed to mitigate initially assumed irrelevant details or sections being significantly reduced prior to further interpretation. As this approach could have limited future interpretation of parts and the whole of the transcribed text and the revealing of concealed phenomenon. To support openness, I balanced this process with sustaining orientation to the research question, maintaining records of unreduced and reduced transcripts. Furthermore, to ensure that the crafted stories were clear, flowed and conveyed the phenomenon being revealed, some incomplete sentences were removed to link one section to another. Where relevant, any aspects of grammar were polished to support clarity for the reader while maintaining the authenticity of the participants' lived experiences (Crowther *et al.*, 2016) (A15). The process of reducing the transcripts did not aim to reflect

phenomenological reduction associated with Husserl's concepts of bracketing by suspending or removing my pre-understandings when interpreting the participants lived experiences (Heidegger, 1962/1927; Husserl, 2012/1931). Alternatively, this process aimed to clearly demonstrate my attunement to what lied in, between and beyond the participants transcribed words as a way of transparently and plausibly revealing phenomenon and surfacing meaning about the PGNS lived experiences that would resonate with readers (Gadamer, 2004/1960; Crowther *et al.*, 2016).

My approach to data interpretation was underpinned by philosophical and methodological principles of the researcher being with and working with the data, rather than using electronic data interpretation software. I used the hermeneutic spiral to bring my fore-structures of understanding to interpretation, to guide me to come to understanding phenomena in the right way through an iterative, continuous process of moving between the parts and whole of the verbatim transcripts and crafted stories through naïve and interpretive reading and interpretation (Heidegger, 1962/1927; Diekelmann and Ironside, 1998; Laverty, 2003; Gadamer, 2004/1960; Crowther *et al.*, 2016) (EoR: Openness, concreteness, resonance). The hermeneutic spiral also resonated with the pedagogical assumptions of a continuous, lifelong, transformative spiral of learning (C2).

Figure 11 shows the data interpretation framework that I developed to provide a pragmatic, reflexive data interpretation guide to support me to bring together the research question with key philosophical and methodological aspects including:

- The hermeneutic circle (Heidegger, 1962/1927; Gadamer, 2004/1960)
- Crist and Tanner's (2003) Interpretive Process
- De Witt and Ploeg's (2006) Expressions of Rigour
- Interpretation being founded upon the fore-structures of understanding (fore-having, fore-sight and fore-conceptions with past, present and future temporal contexts) (Heidegger, 1962/1927).
- Application of the fore-structures of understanding aimed to mitigate interpretation reflecting what is already known to support uncovering and revealing phenomenon (Crowther and Thomson, 2020).
- Maddison's (1988 cited in Benner, 1994) Principles of Evaluation
- Prompt questions to support dwelling with hermeneutic phenomenological notions (Crowther and Thomson, 2023)
- Reflexive questions to consider my reflexive role in data interpretation.

Use of my data interpretation framework aimed to support openness and balanced integration throughout the data interpretation process. Particularly, sustained orientation to the research question, the participants experiences and methodological alignment (De Witt and Ploeg, 2006).

Figure 11: My Data Interpretation Framework

Heidegger's (1962/1927) notion of *'attunement'* as part of the existential structures brought awareness to my role in being reflexively attuned to interpretation of the data. Furthermore, Gadamer (2004/1960) suggested that understanding the text means to understand the question, positioning that such understanding lies behind what is said. Therefore, as part of data interpretation activities, I initially reviewed my guiding data interpretation framework and spent time dwelling, reading, thinking and reconnecting with the data (F11).

My data interpretation framework also included a range of prompt questions underpinned by Heideggerian approaches, key modes and notions relating to *'Dasein'*, *'being-in-the-world'* (Heidegger, 1962/1927) (F11). This provided me with a reflexive aid to deepen interpretation towards revealing phenomena to further understanding and surface meaning about the participants' PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP. Furthermore, Crowther and Thomson (2020) position that continued dialogue with the data and engagement with Heidegger's philosophical notions supports a movement towards an interpretive leap, to further thinking and surfacing meaning beyond initial descriptions and interpretations. However, my data interpretation framework did not aim to present all of Heidegger's (1962/1927) modes and notions that could potentially be relevant to deepen data interpretation. This was a purposeful decision in the development of my framework based on the understanding that the purpose of hermeneutic phenomenology is not to fit the interpretation of data into Heideggerian notions. Furthermore, such an approach would challenge rigour, authenticity and plausibly surfacing meaning from the participants' lived experiences within my research. Alternatively, the prompt questions were used to further my philosophical insights, supporting me to be present in dwelling with the data and to confront any potential concerns relating to the PGNS *'being-in-the-world'* (*'Dasein'*) to reveal authentic phenomenon (Heidegger, 1962/1927; Cerbone, 2008).

As a research student, integrating Madison's (1988) principles of evaluation aimed to mitigate misinterpretation of the data (EoR: Balanced integration, openness). The principles of evaluation included coherence, comprehensiveness, penetration, thoroughness, appropriateness, contextuality, agreement, suggestiveness and potential (Madison, 1988) (EoR: Balanced integration, openness). The integration of *'Ask self'* questions posed by Dibley *et al.* (2020) also supported me to continue to reflexively consider my fore-structures of understanding through data interpretation (F11). Particularly, as the data interpretation processes reflected a lone approach, as a research student.

However, my framework also prompted me to continually connect with my supervisory team as critical conversation partners throughout data interpretation. Critical conversations with my supervisory team supported application of Crist and Tanner's (2003) phases, ensured rigour and maintained an openness to possibilities through the data interpretation process (Gadamer, 2004/1960) (F11; A16). Smythe *et al.* (2008, p. 1395) describes conversation partners as *'offering keys to unlocking doors previously closed'*. This particularly resonated with my supervisory team undertaking critical conversation partner roles to

support critical discussion of emerging central concerns and my thinking in coming to shared meanings and connections through interpretation of the data. Throughout the research process, supervisory team ways of working further included being challenged in relation to my presuppositions, data interpretation and fore-structures of understanding (F11; A16).

I chose not to use data analysis software to support data management through the interpretation process. Alternatively, I developed data interpretation tables underpinned by the principles of Heideggerian approaches, my data interpretation framework and hermeneutic phenomenological approaches (A16). Based on the assumption that use of the frameworks and tables would support me to become immersed in data interpretation, demonstrate rigour through interpretation and apply key aspects of the hermeneutic spiral through the design of the tables (A16). The data interpretation tables also provided me with a visual and pragmatic way of moving between the parts and whole of the individual participant and collective transcripts, and the five phases of the Crist and Tanner (2003) interpretive process. Appendix 16 provides a further outline of the interpretative process and examples of table application to demonstrate openness throughout the research process.

Hermeneutic phenomenological approaches to data interpretation are often considered to have no completion or end point which may pose potential challenges to research students with completion timeframes. However, Crist and Tanner's (2003) fifth phase offered realistic principles to guide coming to a final stage of my interpretation within the context and timeframes of my research (EoR: Balanced integration). I also sought the support of my supervisory team as critical conversation partners to critically challenge my justification for reaching a final stage of my data interpretation. Particularly, to critically challenge that my final account at the time of writing provided plausible, contextual and credible offerings that reflected the research question and illuminated meaning from the participants' experiences. However, dissemination of my research offerings aimed to invite relevant professional peers to further thinking and understanding of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP (EoR: Actualisation).

4.5.6 Approach to presenting the research outcomes

Similar to there being no prescribed method(s) for hermeneutic phenomenology, there were no specific rules or prescribed methods of presenting the research findings (Dibley *et al.*, 2020). Approaches to presenting the research findings within contemporary hermeneutic phenomenological research may range from presentation of the participants' lived experiences as transcript extracts to crafted poems and stories through the process of data interpretation (Crowther *et al.*, 2016). To support rigour, my approach to presenting the research findings, as offerings were underpinned and guided by my chosen philosophical, methodological and data interpretation frameworks. The offerings presented include

integration of anonymised crafted story extracts from the participants' lived experiences supported by analytic discussion and transparent use of philosophical notions (Heidegger, 1962/1927; Gadamer, 2004/1960). Collectively, presenting the offerings in this way aimed to convey the phenomenon revealed and reflexively demonstrate my interpretative leaps that furthered understanding and surfaced meaning from the PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP (EoR: Balanced integration, concreteness, resonance). These approaches also aimed to mitigate potential criticism that may be associated with the use of transcript extracts alone not fully revealing participants' lived experiences or surfacing meaning from the lived experiences (Crowther *et al.*, 2016). Reflexively, my chosen approaches supported a balance between hermeneutic phenomenological principles, my role and integrity as a professional doctorate student, methodological rigour and revealing the phenomenon of interest to surface meaning about PGNS lived experiences in a way that may be relevant to others and call others to thinking.

The part three literature review was also integrated into the presentation of the research offerings to further understanding and contextualise the research offerings across the domains of PGNE, nursing practice, HE and research. Chapter 5 further sets the context and justification for the part three literature review and presentation of the research outcomes as offerings.

Presenting the research outcomes in this way, ultimately aimed to meaningfully engage relevant professional peers with the outcomes of my research. Van Manen (2014) positions the potential for meaningfulness happening within phenomenological writing. This relating to when meaning becomes experienced, speaking to our existence in a way that touches the reader. The approaches to my writing and presentation of the research offerings aimed to create opportunities for PGNS lived experiences to meaningfully resonate with professional peers, potentially provoking a phenomenological nod and inviting further thinking about PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP (Van Manen, 2014) (EoR: Resonance, actualisation). However, a key aspect of presenting the research outcomes was to emphasise the subjective, temporal nature of the PGNS lived experiences and my interpretation of data at the time of my research.

4.5.7 Dissemination plan

Due to the unknown nature of research outcomes, my plan for disseminating the research outcomes is iterative, flexible and responsive to emerging dissemination opportunities (Fulton *et al.*, 2013). My current and future communities, and landscapes of practice will be used as opportunities to support a range of purposeful and targeted dissemination strategies (A17). The overall aim of disseminating my research outcomes being to effectively present the phenomena revealed and invite professional peers to think openly about the outcomes presented and further possibilities relating to PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP (Gadamer, 2004/1960; Dibley *et al.*, 2020).

It is anticipated that key dissemination strategies will involve:

- Writing for publication focused on the associated literature review and research outcomes e.g. relevant journal publications and organisational briefing papers.
- Participating in conference activities to share research outcomes, emerging curious questions for PGNE, HE and nursing practice and further areas for research.
- Engaging with professional network forums to share, discuss and constructively debate research outcomes, subject understanding and learning from my research.
- Seeking opportunities to contribute to further research in the subject area or professional practice developments across nursing, healthcare, HE and research contexts.
- Using my advanced research knowledge, skills and learning to contribute to facilitation of learning activities e.g. sharing methodological learning, providing peer support for those that may be involved with professional doctorate studies or research within the context of their professional practice.

4.6 Ethical approaches

This section demonstrates how key ethical principles and considerations were addressed through my research. Based on the fundamental ethical principle of respecting human dignity, my underpinning ethical framework and the approved ethical application for my study (UEC, 2016) (A7).

4.6.1 Autonomy, veracity and informed consent

To respect participants' right to autonomy and veracity, the principles of informed consent were applied throughout my research (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). Informed consent processes demonstrated the principles of competence, voluntarism, and comprehension of participant information to support openness and mitigate against deception through the research process (UEC, 2016).

To adhere to good ethical practice and guidance participants were provided with an electronic participant information sheet, privacy notice and informed consent form (UEC, 2016; NHS HRA, no datea) (A11; A13). Collectively, these documents provided participants with accurate details of the:

- research aim, purpose and methods
- potential use and presentation of findings
- anticipated outcomes, benefits and harms

- participant involvement and requirements
- ethical considerations e.g. confidentiality, anonymity, data protection
- researcher and supervisory team roles e.g. my role as a professional doctorate student
- participants freedom and self-determination to withdraw from the interview at any time (Buxton, 2011; Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018)

To respect participants autonomy to take part in my research within a realistic timeframe following initial expressions of interest, potential participants were given a two week decision-making period to complete and return the informed consent form (UEC, 2016) (A11-13).

4.6.2 Privacy and confidentiality

Confirmation was received from the associated HEI Legal Services Team that a Privacy Impact Assessment was not required for my research study. However, through the informed consent process participants were informed of the ethical good practices to support privacy, anonymity and confidentiality throughout the study (A11; A13). Such open communication aimed to support the development of a trusting relationship, care and respect between myself and the participants and mitigate against participant withdrawal due to any privacy or confidentiality concerns (Rinaldi Carpenter, 2011).

To promote privacy, telephone interviews were conducted from a private room within the associated HEI. Participants were informed that they should participate in the telephone interview from an individual, private location free from disruption to support confidentiality, anonymity and a safe, and comfortable interview environment (A11). I used headphones within a private environment to transcribe the taped interview recordings and check each interview transcript. Data transcription, analysis and thesis development activities were undertaken between my associated HEI and personal base in adherence with associated ethical, data management and COVID-19 guidelines (EPCEU, 2016; UEC, 2016).

The use of probing interview questions to gain an in-depth understanding of the participants' subjective PGNS lived experiences may potentially intrude on the participants' privacy. To mitigate against the risk to privacy, I used a reflexive approach to my practice to promote respect and care during interviews including a check-in and check-out activities, and the opportunity for participants to have a post-recording debrief conversation. Participants were informed of their right not to answer any interview questions and freedom to withdraw from the interview at any time.

Through informed consent, participants were made aware that their identity would be known to myself due to my participatory role in the research process. Participants were informed that coding and pseudonymisation processes would be used throughout data collection, transcription, interpretation and presentation of the findings to support anonymity (UWS, no datec). Therefore, within this thesis crafted

story extracts are presented using pseudonyms. Due to the nature of professional doctorate research, participants were informed that anonymised research data may be reviewed and discussed with my supervisory team to support data interpretation, analysis and a reflexive approach to my fore-structures of understanding (Heidegger, 1962/1927).

Participants were informed that any records of personal or research data required as part of the research study would adhere to associated guidelines and regulations (UWS, 2015; EPCEU, 2016; UEC, 2016; NMC, 2018e; UWS, 2019a). Therefore, personal data would be held and accessible only to me, unless in the case of a professional or care concern arising (UEC, 2016; NMC, 2018e).

Personal and research data was stored using a password protected email account and encrypted electronic drive accessible only to myself as approved by the associated HEI. Personal and research data would be held for the required time prior to destruction using confidential waste shredding processes or electronic deletion processes (EPCEU, 2016; UEC, 2016; 2019).

4.6.3 Justice and inclusiveness

Fully inclusive and equitable participation was not possible due to purposeful sampling. Justification for my sampling strategy aimed to ensure that participants had a subjective lived experience of being a PGNS at the time of being a professionally registered nurse.

The use of telephone interviews aimed to support an inclusive participant-centred, flexible, cost effective, and time efficient methods of data collection cognisant of:

- Potentially varied PGNE programme delivery methods. Therefore, there may have been significant geographical differences across the sample population from the participants base location to the HEI influencing possibilities for on campus interviews (Holt, 2010; Trier-Bieniek, 2012; Mealer and Jones, 2014; Musselwhite *et al.*, 2017).
- Minimising intrusion within the participant's home, HEI or work environment which may be associated with video interviews or in person interviews at a set location e.g. the participant's home, work or study environment. The physical distance created by telephone use aimed to enhance the participants' experiences of; confidentiality, anonymity, privacy, and a relaxed interview environment (Musselwhite *et al.*, 2007; Holt, 2010; Trier-Bieniek, 2012; Ward, Gott and Hoare, 2015; Drabble *et al.*, 2016).
- Participants working in practice, studying and potential personal commitments. Telephone interviews aimed to support a flexible, safe method of interviewing which could be conducted out with normal working hours and support rescheduling depending on the participants needs (Musselwhite *et al.*, 2007; Trier-Bieniek, 2012; Drabble *et al.*, 2016).

If a participant disclosed any additional support needs, where possible any reasonable adjustments would be made. The participant information sheet also informed participants of my role as a professional doctorate student, providing this information aimed to facilitate a trusting researcher-participant relationship and mitigate any participant concerns relating to; coercion, power relationships, autonomous voluntary participation or non-participation, interview withdrawal or impact on academic studies (Gray, 2021) (A11).

4.6.4 Benefits and harms

Ethical approval aimed to ensure respect for non-maleficence to the participants and mitigate against PGNS becoming an over researched group, which could pose a risk to my recruitment strategy (UEC, 2016).

Assessment of harm due to the context and nature of my research study was considered low risk. However, participant interviews may unintentionally evoke emotional vulnerability due to the potentially sensitive issues that may arise through the participants sharing their experiences (Rinaldi Carpenter, 2011; Smythe, 2011). Participants were informed of how anonymous quotes would be sensitively used to present the findings, aiming to mitigate against misrepresentation or reputation concerns (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). My professional interpersonal skills would also be used to create an empathetic, supportive and trusting relationship with participants to minimise any potential emotional distress (Smythe, 2011) (A14).

All participants were offered a debriefing conversation with me via telephone immediately after the interview had been completed. Debriefing aimed to provide an opportunity for a check in between myself and the participant to identify any concerns or issues that may have arisen during the interview process. I also informed participants of my role as a professional doctorate student to prevent any potential expectations of the debriefing process facilitating a therapeutic relationship due to my role as a registered nurse (Rinaldi Carpenter, 2011; Gray, 2021). If required, participants would be signposted to further sources of support e.g. associated HEI support and wellbeing services, practice-based support, programme/module leaders, health services e.g. General Practitioner, or professional bodies e.g. NMC. Participants were informed that to ensure non-maleficence to themselves and others, if a professional or care concern was raised or disclosed during the interview or debriefing process this may be discussed with my supervisory team and appropriately reported based on my professional duty of care (UEC, 2016; NMC, 2018e).

Should a participant have any concerns regarding my principle investigatory practice, the participant would be advised to escalate their concerns to my supervisory team or the stated independent

representative identified through the process of informed consent (UWC, 2016; 2019). If appropriate or required, any issues or concerns would also be discussed with my supervisory team. Where possible interview dates were planned out with the general HEI assessment times to mitigate any potential additional pressures on participants.

Due to the methodological framework of my research, it was not possible to predict the research outcomes or benefits. Participants were informed of their potential to contribute to furthering understanding of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP through use and dissemination of the research outcomes (A11).

Chapter 5 - Invitation to Offerings

5.1 Introduction

Hermeneutic phenomenological approaches fundamentally focus on data interpretation reflecting the research findings, outcomes or results (Dibley *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, Chapters 6-10 present the research findings as 'offerings' from my interpretation of the participants' PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP. Each chapter aims to show the reader the phenomena revealed to further understanding and surface meaning about PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP.

Crafted story extracts developed from the anonymised verbatim transcripts (raw data) are integrated into each of the offerings chapters. This approach aimed to demonstrate my interpretation of the participants' experiences, show the phenomenon revealed and illuminate the significant things that mattered from the PGNS lived experiences (Smythe *et al.*, 2008; Crowther *et al.*, 2016). The crafted stories are presented using pseudonyms to support participant anonymity. However, the use of pseudonyms aimed to emphasise the philosophical assumptions underpinning my research relating to our individual, subjective experiences of being in the world (Heidegger, 1962/1927). In developing the crafted stories from the original verbatim transcripts, participants' conversational pauses or intonations were denoted as '(...)' and '...' used to denote removed aspects e.g. incomplete or repeated words or sentences. Where relevant any aspects of grammar were polished to support clarity for the reader while maintaining the authenticity of the participants' lived experiences (Crowther *et al.*, 2016) (A15). These approaches aimed to support a clear focus on conveying the participants' lived experiences and ensure aspects of anonymity. Some of the PGNS experiences are repeatedly shown within several offerings. This approach aims to show the significant things that mattered within the subjective, temporal and situational contexts of the PGNS experiences. As opposed to representing common themes or frequencies within the offerings, aligned to other methodological approaches.

As discussed in Chapter 4, the underpinning philosophical assumptions and notions of Heidegger (1962/1927) and Gadamer's (2004/1960) work including the hermeneutic circle aimed to guide interpretation and challenge my thinking towards new and deeper horizons of understanding PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP. This approach also aimed to ensure philosophical and methodological congruence throughout my research. Subsequently, my writing style including the use of Heideggerian and Gadamerian terms throughout the chapters further demonstrates my immersion in hermeneutic phenomenological ways of coming to interpretation of the participants' lived experiences.

Chapter 4 acknowledged some of the complexities associated with the use of Heideggerian language, terms and approaches within contemporary research. Particularly, dichotomy between the use of Heideggerian notions to illuminate and convey meaning that resonates with the reader (Dibley *et al.*,

2020). Subsequently, the writing style aims to differentiate between the use of Heideggerian notions to demonstrate interpretation within my research and the linguistic use of traditional, everyday words (Dibley *et al.*, 2020). To support clarity and distinction between terms within the chapters, terms associated with the context of Heideggerian approaches or notions have been stated in italic text enclosed by quotation marks e.g. '*Being*'. To guide the reader, concise explanations of key Heideggerian terms have been integrated where relevant, prior to setting context relating to my interpretation of the participants' experiences. Gerund words have also been purposefully integrated within the chapters. For example, some words purposefully ending with '*...ing*'. This approach aims to emphasise an ontological focus and hermeneutic phenomenological approach to bringing the PGNS, subjective, lived experiences to life within the chapters, and reflect the participants' experiences at the time of my research (Dibley *et al.*, 2020). This approach also aimed to convey ways in which I came to unconcealing phenomenon and made interpretative leaps to surface meaning about the PGNS lived experiences of workplace support to ALiP.

Heidegger's (1962/1927) fundamental concept of '*Being*' is concerned ontologically with the question and understanding of what it means to be. In some areas of relevant writing, the term 'being' is purposefully presented in italics with a capital letter, '*Being*'. Use of the term '*Being*' in this way aims to align with ontological, Heideggerian and hermeneutic phenomenological approaches to interpreting and understanding the participants' experiences of being there, in their lived experience and '*being-in-the-world*'. Presenting the term '*Being*' in this way, also aimed to distinguish between the Heideggerian approach to '*being*' without a capital letter, which is alternatively associated with the ontic meaning of an object or description (Heidegger, 1962/1927).

Each offering chapter is interwoven with crafted stories and analytical discussion to demonstrate movement from the participants' experiences towards a deeper interpretation to reveal phenomena and demonstrate my interpretive leaps to surface meaning from the participants lived experiences (Crowther *et al.*, 2016; Crowther and Thomson, 2020). This approach was also underpinned by integrating reflexivity e.g. my fore-structures of understanding, philosophical approaches and relevant literature (F11; A16). Subsequently, analytical discussion through the offerings chapters aims to bring meaningful interpretation to the professional contexts of the contemporary PGNE, nursing practice and HE.

The approach to integrating literature into the offerings chapters was underpinned by the part three literature review. This literature review was guided by the phenomenon revealed from the participants' lived experiences with the aim of identifying and integrating any new or relevant literature that may further insight into the phenomenon revealed (Smythe, 2011) (T1). In some areas, relevant literature from part one and two literature reviews and context chapter was integrated and considered within the new context of the research offerings. This approach provided an opportunity to reflexively challenge my previous understanding of the literature and consider whether emerging horizons of understanding

created new possibilities for the previous literature to offer further insights based on the phenomena revealed from the participants' experiences (Gadamer, 2004/1960).

In developing the offerings chapters, I engaged with my supervisory team as critical conversation partners (A16). This aimed to support critical challenge of my presuppositions and interpretations; to ensure the offerings chapters demonstrated an in-depth philosophical understanding of Heideggerian approaches, transparency of interpretation, and clearly conveyed meaning that resonated with the reader, the research question and relevant contemporary contexts.

Chapters 6-9 present four offerings including part offerings reflective of the things that mattered from my interpretation of the participants' experiences and the identified expressions of shared meanings and connections (A16). Collectively the chapters aim to further understanding through the phenomenon revealed and the ontological meaning surfaced about being a PGNS and participants' lived experiences of workplace support for PGNS to ALiP. Therefore, readers are encouraged to consider the parts and the whole and move back and forth between the offerings chapters.

Figure 12: Overview of the Offerings Chapters

The offerings chapters also aim to provide the reader with a meaningful and plausible understanding of the participants' experiences of workplace support to ALiP, relevant to the contemporary contexts of PGNE at the time of my research. The reader is invited to meaningfully engage and lean in to the offerings and my interpretation of the PGNS experiences. This approach aims to create opportunities for the research offerings to meaningfully resonate with professional peers, potentially provoking a phenomenological nod and inviting further curiosity and thinking about PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP (Van Manen, 2014).

To listen is to continually give up all expectation and to give our attention, completely and freshly, to what is before us, not really knowing what we will hear or what it will mean. In the practice of our days, to listen is to lean in, softly, with a willingness to be changed by what we hear. (Nepo, 2005)

5.2 Approaches to the part three literature search and review

Smythe and Spence (2012) position that the purpose of exploring literature within hermeneutic research is to provide context and provoke thinking about the phenomenon of interest in a way that is interpretive and aligned with Gadamer's (2004/1960) philosophy. Therefore, integrating a hermeneutic / hermeneutic phenomenological approach to the part three literature review was considered essential to support the philosophical and methodological alignment at the data interpretation stage of my research (T4). Subsequently, the third literature review conducted during 2022 aimed to explore literature relating to the phenomena revealed to further and broaden horizons of understanding relating to PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP (T1).

Hermeneutic approaches to exploring literature are not associated with prescriptive literature search strategies or review processes (Smythe and Spence, 2012). Furthermore, such approaches are considered to have few rules to searching and reviewing the literature (Smythe and Spence, 2012). Hermeneutic approaches alternatively focus on the use of literature being led by the researcher's way of being attuned to the data and bringing their own pre-understandings to interpretation of the literature (Heidegger, 1962/1927; Gadamer, 2004/1960; Smythe and Spence, 2012). Therefore the third literature review was guided by hermeneutic and hermeneutic phenomenological approaches to searching and reviewing relevant literature, as opposed to an approach specifically aligned or underpinned by a literature review typology (Grant and Booth, 2009). However, Smythe and Spence (2012) highlight that such approaches may present challenges for doctoral students embarking on hermeneutic approaches to reviewing literature. Challenges may be associated with students exploring diverse types and sources of literature

relating to the phenomenon revealed (Smythe and Spence, 2012). Particularly, as researchers may be led towards the use of poetic, historical or story sources of literature as opposed to following traditional scholarly literature review methods and requirements that focus on recently published literature, critical appraisal formats and search processes (Smythe and Spence, 2012).

To mitigate against these challenges, my approach to searching and reviewing the literature within the part three review was guided by Smythe and Spence's (2012) hallmarks towards a hermeneutic approach to literature. This approach was selected as it is also associated with the context of hermeneutic phenomenological research (T4). To further ensure congruence with hermeneutic phenomenology, my approach to the part three literature review was also underpinned by the hermeneutic circle (Heidegger, 1962/1927). Furthermore, Heidegger's (1962/1927) philosophical assumptions of '*Dasein*' and our way of '*being-in-the-world*' ensured a focus on furthering understanding about being a PGNS and PGNS experience of workplace support to ALiP (Heidegger, 1962/1927). Reflexively, I also drew upon the previous philosophical assumptions of the reader being related to the literature and interpretation never being presuppositionless (Heidegger, 1962/1927; Gadamer, 2004/1960). This influenced my role in searching and review the literature being immersive including bringing my fore-structures of understanding to interpretation of the literature through the offerings chapters.

Table 4: Summary of the approaches that guided the part three literature search and review

Underpinning type of literature review:	Guiding approaches and assumptions
Hermeneutic phenomenological literature review	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Philosophical underpinnings (Heidegger, 1962/1927) and Gadamer (2004/1960). • The hermeneutic spiral (e.g. reading, re-reading, thinking, writing, dwelling) (Heidegger, 1962/1927) (F11). • A constructivist approach to assuming multiple realities. • The part three literature provided a dialogical partner to further thinking, meaning or insight (Smythe and Spence, 2012). • Quotes were used from the reviewed literature to convey meaning, notions or provoke further thinking where relevant (Smythe and Spence, 2012). • My reflexive thoughts and fore-structures of understandings were brought to interpretation of the literature, integrated into analytic discussion to support furthering understanding and broader horizons relating to the phenomenon revealed (Heidegger, 1962/1927; Gadamer, 2004/1960; Smythe and Spence, 2012). • Sources were deemed relevant based on contributing deeper understanding or new insights to the phenomena revealed. Where relevant the literature was critically appraised depending on the source of literature.

The presentation of the part three literature review is interwoven into the analytic discussion throughout the offerings chapters. To support transparency and rigour throughout these chapters, discussion has been integrated to highlight to the reader where a phenomenon or meaning led me to follow a thread to search for and review further literature to provoke thinking (Smythe and Spence, 2012). This included using a broader range of literature led by the phenomenon including philosophical literature. Therefore some of the search approaches were not pre-defined by inclusion publication date timeframes or subject or discipline areas. However, the literature chosen and deemed relevant to be integrated into analytic discussion aimed to relate to the context of my research and the phenomenon revealed (Smythe and Spence, 2012). Some of the phenomenon revealed also led me to re-engage and re-read literature from the earlier part one and two reviews with new perspective and curiosity based on the phenomenon

revealed. Collectively, these approaches and my role within the part three literature review resonated with Gadamer's (2004/1960) position of literature:

... understanding consciousness acquires – through its immediate access to literary tradition – a genuine opportunity to change and widen its horizon, and thus enrich its world by a whole new and deeper dimension. (Gadamer, 2004/1960, p. 391)

The assumptions of widening horizons and new and deeper dimensions resonated with the aim of my research to make an original contribution to furthering understanding and surfacing meaning of PGNS experience of workplace support to ALiP. Furthermore, integrating calls to thinking from the part three literature review aimed to meaningfully resonate with relevant professional peers and evoke further calls to thinking about PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP across context of nursing practice and education.

Within Chapter 2, I set out that the iterative approach to the literature review within my thesis aimed to demonstrate a continuous movement between the parts and whole of the literature reviewed over several years to explore workplace support for PGNS to ALiP. This led me to dwell further with the assumption of the hermeneutic spiral;

' ... the movement of understanding is constantly from the whole to the part and back to the whole. Our task is to expand the unity of the understood meaning centrifugally' (Gadamer, 2004/1960, p. 291).

Reflexively, this emphasised the use of literature throughout the offerings chapters being temporal, influencing a constant movement of understanding. Smythe and Spence (2012) highlight that the context of the literature review within hermeneutic research is not definitive, complete or all encompassing. These aspects evoked pragmatic curiosity as to how I would follow the threads of literature relating to the phenomenon revealed in balance with realistic professional doctorate timeframes and bringing the offerings chapters together. I drew upon aspects of Crist and Tanner's (2003) final phases of the interpretive process to find a harmony of integrating the part three literature review within the offerings chapters, bringing the reader's attention to new horizons of understanding and meaning, offering further threads of research and professional enquiry within subsequent Chapters 10 and 11.

Chapter 6 - Offering 1: Contextualising Being

6.1 Introduction

This chapter reveals some of the participants' experiences relating to the wider context of their being and knowing self. These offerings were underpinned by the expressions of shared meanings and connections from my interpretation of the participants' experiences relating to self-being, being a PGNS, and temporality of self-experiences as illustrated in Figure 13 (A16). Presenting these offerings was significant to broaden horizons of understanding about PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP.

Figure 13: Offering 1 parts of the whole - Contextualising being in coming to understanding PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP

6.2 Being and becoming a PGNS

Interpretation of the participants' experiences surfaced meaning about the broader holistic and socio-historic contexts of being a person, rather than exclusively being a PGNS:

'I'm already quite a motivated and determined person anyway.' (Pat)

Pat's sharing of already being a motivated and determined person revealed an already-ness of knowing self as a person before becoming a PGNS. This critically challenged me to consider and clarify use of the term PGNS throughout the offerings chapters. The term PGNS within my research aimed to reflect a holistic understanding of being a PGNS, person and personhood (McCormack *et al.*, 2021). As opposed to a potential view of self, limited to being a PGNS. Furthermore, Pat's experience led me to reflexively return to my understanding of '*Being*' within the early philosophical and methodological parts of my research. Heidegger (1962/1927) positioned:

'If Being-in-the-world is a kind of Being which is essentially befitting to Dasein, then to understand Being-in-the-world belongs to the essential content of understanding of Being' (Heidegger, 1962/1927, p. 118).

Therefore, Heidegger's (1962/1927) fundamental concept of '*Being*' is concerned ontologically with the question and understanding of what it means to be. Subsequently, bringing the concept of '*Dasein*' to my interpretation of the participants' lived experiences brought a focus on reflexively questioning, interpreting and surfacing meaning about the ways in which we meaningfully exist as humans and our experiences of '*being-in-the-world*'. In the context of Pat's experience, bringing the philosophical notions of '*Being*', '*Dasein*' and '*being-in-the-world*' to interpretation furthered my understanding of Pat's experiences of '*being-in-the-world*', as PGNS and person. In dwelling with Pat's experience, I realised that by remaining open to possibilities when inviting the participants to share their lived experiences revealed a broader, holistic context of PGNS being and '*being-in-the-world*'. This understanding furthered my thinking towards the concept of an indissoluble unity within hermeneutic phenomenological research between myself, the participants' lived experiences and their world (co-constitutions) within cultural, historical and social contexts (Koch, 1995; Lavery, 2003; Gadamer, 2004/1960).

Returning to Pat's experience of already being motivated and determined as a person, brought to interpretation the philosophical assumption that '*being-in-the-world*' is influenced by our '*fore-structures*' of understanding; our '*fore-having, fore-sight*' and '*fore-conception*' (Heidegger, 1962/1927). This attuned me to the '*fore-havings*' of the participants' experiences, background knowledge and contexts before becoming a PGNS. Pat's shared experiences of being in a time and place before deciding to enter into PGNE, further called to thinking Gadamer's (2004/1960) hermeneutic position that understanding is fundamentally a historically effected event, influenced by the reality of history and historical understanding:

'Before I entered into doing it, I'd done a lot of research before I went into doing the postgraduate. Because, I wanted to make sure that I was in a place that I was ready to do it.' (Pat)

In being attuned to the participants' *'fore-havings'* prior to becoming a PGNS revealed the concept of motivation being a self-attribute or way of being that may influence PGNS experiences of being, and coming to PGNE:

'... what's really important to me is I've always, I'm motivated by helping other people and I've always kind of (...) used that motivation to kind of influence other people, and to lead other people as well. And I think it's just that's something that's really important to me, that even though I'm learning for my own personal reasons for learning and for my own career development. It's important for me to be able to pass that knowledge on to other people.' (Pat)

'It's actually purely my private kind a motivation to go for further education to kind of expand my knowledge.' (Taylor)

Pat and Taylors' experiences of self or private motivation, called to thinking Heidegger's (1962/1927; 1996/1927) philosophical notion of *'readiness-to-hand'* and equipment or useful things being at our disposal and put to use. Heidegger (1962/1927) positions these aspects in relation to the use of a hammer and the context of hammering:

... the more we seize hold of it and use it, the more primordial does our relation to it become, and the more unveiledly it is encountered as that which it is – as equipment. The hammering itself uncovers the specific 'manipulability' ["Handlichkeit"] of the hammer. The kind of Being which equipment possess – in which it manifests itself in its own right – we call "*readiness-to-hand*". (Heidegger, 1962/1927, p. 98)

Dwelling with Heidegger's (1962/1927) example beyond the context of a hammer, Pat and Taylor's experiences illuminated a conscious awareness of motivation being at their disposal, being readily available to themselves in order to expand self-knowledge or pass knowledge on to others. Reflexively, consideration of this notion illuminated motivation as an inherent self-attribute or characteristic as part of the participants' *'Being'* and readiness in coming into PGNE.

The participants' experiences of motivation also reflexively orientated my thinking to the humanistic learning pedagogies discussed within Chapter 2. Particularly, the humanistic, pedagogical assumptions that individuals have motivations and needs for continued learning that are influenced by changing self, socio-historic, cultural experiences and contexts (Knowles, Holton and Swanston, 2005; Jarvis, 2010; Cranton, 2016). Attunement to wider social and cultural experiences led me to dwell with Pat's experience of motivation to help, lead and influence other people. I was drawn towards Heidegger's

(1996/1927) philosophical notion of *'Being-with'* and use of the term *'Others'* which assumes that the world is always already one that an individual shares with others, as opposed to being separated from others. Heidegger (1962/1927) positions that *'being-with'* is also an essential part of *'being-in-the-world'*. Reflectively moving to Pat's experience, I became attuned that PGNS motivations for being and becoming a PGNS may not be isolated from others but influenced by pre-existing socio, historic and cultural background experiences of being with others.

This understanding revealed that my presuppositions of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP may have assumed a focus on PGNS being with others specific to the context of the workplace. Pat's experiences and Heidegger's (1996/1927) assumptions of *'being-with Others'* as part of *'being-in-the-world'* illuminated an inseparable way of being a PGNS, being inter-related or interwoven in being with others. Reflexively, this called to thinking whether asking PGNS about their individual experiences of workplace support had assumed lived experiences being separated or detached from others. Subsequently, Pat's experience and Heidegger's (1996/1927) notion of *'being-with'* broadened horizons to being a PGNS being grounded with socio-historic experiences of already being with others and the context of others not being limited to the workplace.

The participants' experiences further showed personal motivations and reasons for coming into PGNE, including career development and passing on knowledge to other people:

'... I'm obviously doing this course to try an improve my skill set, to gain more knowledge ...' (Ronnie)

'Have some back up from educational perspective and kind of better knowledge and understanding how you can put that education and knowledge into the practice.' (Taylor)

'And I think it's just that's something that's really important to me, that even though I'm learning for my own personal reasons for learning and for my own career development. It's important for me to be able to pass that knowledge on to other people.' (Pat)

Pat, Ronnie and Taylor's experiences reflected the findings of Penman, Robinson and Cross' (2019) pilot study which explored factors that might attract nursing students to PG study. Particularly, that nurses' motivations for undertaking further education may relate to personal and professional growth, the provision of best care and career advancement (Penman, Robinson and Cross, 2019).

Across the participants' experiences the concept of knowledge also revealed, from intentions to gain more knowledge, better knowledge, pass on knowledge and put knowledge into practice. This may have been influenced by the inclusion criteria for my study, requiring participants to be NMC registered nurses. Particularly, as NMC registered nurses are required to maintain and share up to date knowledge and skills, for safe and effective practice as part of NMC registration requirements (NMC, 2018e). The WHO (2009) concept of CPD for post-registration nurses also focuses on nurses maintaining and

expanding knowledge or skills for specific career trajectories. Therefore, the appearance of knowledge and skills as motivational aspects towards PGNE surfaced a concealed professional construct about continued development and use of knowledge in practice.

Assuming that knowledge is part of learning, the showing of knowledge as part of the participants' experiences of coming into PGNE resonated with the QAA definition of learning which '... students acquire new, built on, or reformulate existing, knowledge ...' (QAA, 2018b, p. 1). Taylor and Pat's experiences relating to passing on and putting knowledge into practice, reflexively drew my thinking to Drennan and Hyde's (2009, p. 173) concept of the PGNS being a 'knowledgeable doer' with a high level of theoretical knowledge and practical know how. As well as social constructionism and SCV pedagogical assumptions that individuals have critical awareness and responsibility for challenging and transforming practice and cultures; influenced by subjective, self and social contexts (Peach, 2010; Webster-Wright, 2010). These pedagogical and philosophical assumptions with the participants' experiences attuned me to whether the participants' *'fore-havings'* to gain, pass on, better, and put knowledge into practice revealed an ontological *'mood'*. Heidegger (1962/1927) assumed an ontological *'mood'* in coming to interpretation and attunement to how one is, how one is faring, bringing Being to its *'there'*, rather than a psychological mood:

'A mood assails us. It comes neither from *'outside'* nor from *'inside'*, but arises out of Being-in-the-world, as a way of such Being' (Heidegger, 1962/1927, p. 176).

Heidegger (1962/1927) also positioned that Dasein always already has some *'mood'*. Therefore, we are always attuned to, never free of, or without *'mood'* (Heidegger, 1962/1927; 1996/1927). In hermeneutic phenomenological research, the *'mood'* that we are attuned to interpreting lived experiences and revealing phenomenon aims to deepen our understanding and meaning of *'Being'* (Mulhall, 2013). Reflexively, this brought to my awareness the need to consider the meaning behind the *'mood'* and that I was not excluded from being without *'mood'* (Smythe and Spence, 2023). Subsequently, the participants' experiences of motivations coming into PGNE and *'fore-havings'* to gain, pass on, better, and put knowledge into practice, attuned me to a *'mood'* about how the participants' may be *'faring'* in relation to self-being, being a PGNS and being-with others. Particularly, whether these aspects may influence their future situational experiences (*'fore-sights'*) and expectations of workplace support to ALiP, and use of knowledge.

6.3 Temporality of self-experiences of Being

The participants' experiences also offered insight into their broader, situational and temporal experiences of *'being-in-the-world'* (*'fore-sight'*). Reflecting Heidegger's (1962/1927) assumption that our human

'Being' (*'Dasein'*) in the socio-historical world is influenced by our *'fore-structures'* of understanding. As I moved through the parts and whole of the participants' experiences, I became aware that parts of their lived experiences were situated in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic. Potentially shaping experiences of being a PGNS and workplace support to ALiP at the time of my research:

'As you know we are now in the pandemic. So, all the courses They've been all postponed now and cancelled till further notice.' (Taylor)

'... just all the learnings ... support for practice over the last year and a half was all postponed. So, there is kind of nothing to be honest.' (Taylor)

The showing of 'we are' resonated with Heidegger's (1996/1927) positioning of *'being-with'* and Taylor's experience of being in the pandemic with others. Taylor's experience also showed being in the past, the present and the future from the acknowledgment of courses being postponed and cancelled until further notice. In dwelling with Taylor's experience, I was also drawn to Heidegger's (1996/1927) complex notion of temporality as a character of *'Dasein'* which assumes:

Having-been arises from the future in such a way that the future that has-been (or better, is in the process of having-been) releases the present from itself. We call the unified phenomenon of the future that makes present in the process of having-been *temporality*. (Heidegger, 1996/1927, p. 300)

Heidegger's (1996/1927) notion of *'temporality'* called to thinking that our experiences are interwoven by our past, present and future being in the world (Mulhall, 2013). Returning to dwell with Taylor's experience revealed a temporal unfolding of postponed learning and support for practice. This raised curiosity whether PGNS experiences of postponed learning may influence expectations, experiences and opportunities of workplace support to ALiP in temporal contexts within and beyond the pandemic. Furthermore, Taylor's experience of postponed learning challenged my pedagogical presuppositions of learning being a continuous, life-long, inherent part of our everyday being in the world as individuals, and professionals in practice. Subsequently, calling to question the notion of learning postponing or ceasing from pedagogical and learner perspectives.

Taylor's experience revealing a temporal unfolding of postponed learning and support for practice, led me towards undertaking a focused scope of the literature to deepen and further understanding of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP during the pandemic. My scoping activities identified limited research-based literature relating to this area, despite broadening the scope of literature to PGNS experiences of learning or CPD during the pandemic. I assumed that this may have been reflective of other research priorities at the time. In addition to the feasibility of research being conducted and published during the pandemic and lockdown restrictions influencing research.

However, Ramelet *et al.* (2022) undertook a qualitative descriptive study relating to PGNS experiences of providing care during the COVID-19 pandemic using focus groups. The study included nine PG masters nursing students and four doctoral students from one Swiss university. Most students studied full-time, which may have influenced the majority of participants being called back into work in clinical practice (Ramelet *et al.*, 2022). In contrast to my study, where participants were required to be PGNS practicing as NMC registered nurses. Of significance is that some of the themes identified through Ramelet *et al.* (2022) thematic analysis related to participant concerns about the postponement or suspension of their studies. The study found that participants faced drastic changes to their clinical environment including increased working hours, working in new or different care environments and demand for registered nurses. Further sub-themes related to participants being concerned or uncertain about; not having enough time to complete their studies, the potential increase to their future study workload and the financial cost that may occur with the postponement of their studies. Subsequently, Ramelet *et al.* (2022) called for educators to acknowledge the impact of COVID-19 on PGNS, referring to PGNS being in a tension between PGNS academic career aspirations and their duty of care.

In dwelling with Ramelet *et al.* (2022) findings and Taylor's experiences, I became further attuned to the situational and temporal contexts influencing being a PGNS. This led me towards Heidegger's (1962/1927) complex notion of *'thrownness'* positioned in different contexts throughout his seminal text *'Being and Time'*:

And as thrown, Dasein is thrown into the kind of Being which we call "projecting". Projecting has nothing to do with comporting oneself towards a plan that has been thought out, and in accordance with which Dasein arranges its Being. (Heidegger, 1962/1927, p. 185)

The notion of *'thrownness'* extends beyond being thrown into something to consider the context from which we are thrown (Withy, 2014). Therefore, the situatedness to which we are thrown goes beyond time and place to the diverse, socio-cultural, historic contexts of our lives (Withy, 2014). The notion of *'thrownness'* also assumes that our *'Being'* in the present co-exists with the past and being thrown into possibilities of *'being-in-the-world'* (Heidegger, 1962/1927). Subsequently, in the context of my research, *'thrownness'* was assumed as part of *'Being'* and that we are always already thrown into life situations that influence and shape our existence of *'being-in-the-world'* (Heidegger, 1996/1927). Reflexively, I returned to dwell with Taylor's experiences and Heidegger's (1996/1927) notion of *'thrownness'*:

'... just all the learnings ... support for practice over the last year and a half was all postponed. So, there is kind of nothing to be honest.' (Taylor)

Initially, Taylor's experience showed learning being postponed and revealed a wider nothingness of learning and support in practice during the pandemic. However, dwelling with Heidegger's (1996/1927) notion of *'thrownness'* surfaced the complex socio-historic and cultural ways of being a PGNS, particularly being present in practice and the pandemic. This illuminated that part of being a PGNS exists

with continual projection into diverse situations and possibilities that shape being a PGNS and experiencing workplace support to ALiP. Returning to consider Ramelet *et al.* (2022) position of a tension between PGNS academic career aspirations and a duty of care during the pandemic called to thinking the positioning of tensions. Heidegger's (1962/1927) notion of *'thrownness'* surfaced meaning that PGNS may always experience such tensions based on the assumption that being a PGNS always exists with continual projection into diverse, complex socio-historic, cultural situations. Furthermore, such complex and diverse projections may influence possibilities for being a PGNS and opportunities for workplace support to ALiP. However, in PGNS coming to conscious awareness of such tensions and projections, PGNS may open and create their own ways of being a PGNS in practice.

Pat's experiences of the pandemic also furthered insight and understanding of a situational *'thrownness'* of being a PGNS:

'And the focus obviously throughout Covid, as well with remote working. It's been really difficult for the team to actually kind of get together as well. To make any kind of chat about anything that's up and coming, and to discuss really any kind of new ideas or any new thoughts that people came across. So, that whole kind of essence of supervision and learning from each other has kind of dissipated I suppose over the last, it's kind of had a bigger impact.' (Pat)

Pat's experience of the pandemic resulting in remote working, appeared to have projected Pat's way of being into a different and difficult socio-cultural way of *'being-with'* others and learning as part of individual, team and professional ways of being. Heidegger's (1996/1927) notion of *'ready-to-hand'*, deepened interpretation of Pat's experience to reveal *'ready-to-hand'* taken for granted, assumed or inherent team ways of being a learner and *'being-with'* others in learning becoming *'unready-to-hand'*. Particularly, as part of Pat's previous ways of being a learner and workplace support involved chatting and discussing ideas to ALiP becoming noticeably unavailable through the dissipation of learning, supervision and ways of being with others.

To further insight into the potential impact of the pandemic on workplace support to ALiP, an online survey open to all UK nursing staff during pandemic reported that of 2,026 participants, 77% experienced disruption to education and training due to the pandemic (Dean, 2020). Due to the focus on the pandemic and lockdown periods many participants were affected by cancellations to study days, face-to-face training and conferences. However, the findings were limited to an editorial analysis and conducted over a short period (8th-19th of June 2020) limiting the context of the findings to the first three months of the pandemic (Dean, 2020). The NMC (no datee) also acknowledged that the pandemic may affect registrants meeting participatory learning (learning with others) requirements due to limited face to face learning activities and cancelled courses. Furthermore, the NMC (no datee) announced temporary changes to support registrants meeting participatory learning requirements as part of NMC revalidation.

However, the overall requirement to complete 35 hours of CPD over a three-year period remained unchanged during the pandemic (NMC, no date). Subsequently, there appeared to be an acknowledgement of the pandemic disrupting formal learning activities for the broader nursing workforce which might be assumed to limit opportunities to ALiP.

6.4 The significance of contextualising being

The offerings within this chapter may evoke curiosity as to why I chose to present some briefer extracts that may be considered to diverge from the participants' experiences of being a PGNS and workplace support to ALiP. However, the offerings were deemed significant in revealing a broader, richer, holistic interpretation of the participants' experiences of being a person coming into PGNE and becoming a PGNS (EoR: Resonance).

In coming to these offerings, reflexively I learned that application of the hermeneutic spiral extended beyond a focus on my pre- and fore-structures of understandings. Subsequently, I was led by the data to lean into the participants' experiences, which provided an opportunity to bring to interpretation the participants' pre-understandings and '*fore-havings*'. This furthered my understanding of how data interpretation may show '*fore-structures*' of understanding to reveal phenomenon and surface meaning about the everyday aspects of the participants' '*being-in-the-world*'. In this case, my interpretation of the participants' experiences revealed a broader, deeper understanding of the participants' experiences of knowing self, being a person and being a PGNS.

The participants' motivations and reasons for coming into PGNE also resonated with previous research findings about motivations for coming into PGNE, humanistic and social constructionism pedagogical approaches and professional contexts of NMC registration requirements (Peach, 2010; Webster-Wright, 2010; NMC, 2018e; Penman, Robinson and Cross, 2019). However, the participants' experiences of knowing self and motivations for coming into PGNE, called to thinking Heidegger's (1962/1927; 1996/1927) notion of '*readiness-to-hand*'. Subsequently, revealing motivation as an inherent, assumed self-attribute and attitude influencing the experience of being and becoming a PGNS. I also became attuned to an ontological '*mood*' hidden behind the participants' '*fore-havings*' of coming into PGNE. Heidegger's (1996/1927) notion of '*temporality*' assumes interwoven past, present and future ways of '*being-in-the-world*' within socio-historic and cultural contexts. This surfaced meaning about an interplay of PGNS past and present expectations to gain, pass on, better and put knowledge into practice influencing future situational experiences ('*fore-sights*') of being a PGNS and workplace support to ALiP. The participants' experiences of the pandemic, also called to thinking taken for granted or inherent ways of being PGNS and being-with colleagues, particularly as part of learning becoming noticeably unavailable or postponed. This surfaced meaning that the participants' situational and temporal

experiences, such as being in the pandemic created a *'thrownness'* into further temporal and socio-cultural possibilities influencing and shaping experiences of workplace support to ALiP, being a PGNS, and being with workplace colleagues.

As part of my professional doctorate occurred during the pandemic, I felt concerned about how I would or could acknowledge and write about the pandemic within my thesis. However, the context of the pandemic showed itself through interpretation of the participants' temporal and situational experiences of being a PGNS and the wider context of *'being-in-the-world'*. Reflexively, this illuminated the significance of *'temporality'* in interpreting the participants' experiences that: 'Time must be brought to light – and genuinely conceived – as the horizon for all understandings of Being ...' (Heidegger, 1962/1927, p. 39). This called to thinking the temporal nature of understanding and surfacing meaning from human lived experiences of being when undertaking hermeneutic phenomenological research. Dibley *et al.* (2020) positions that hermeneutic phenomenological data interpretation is reflective of a moment in time. However, Heidegger's (1962/1927; 1996/1927) assumptions of *'being-in-the-world'* and *'temporality'* attuned me to a non-traditional concept of everyday time towards a complex interplay of past, present and future socio-historic and cultural contexts influencing the offerings presented to further understanding and meaning of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP.

Chapter 7 - Offering 2: Furthering understanding of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP

7.1 Introduction

Offering 1 demonstrated that by remaining open to possibilities through data interpretation, broader insights were gained into the participants' experiences of being a person coming into PGNE from fore-structural, situational and temporal perspectives. However, use of my data interpretation framework also supported sustained orientation to the research question and a focus on the things that mattered to surface meaning about being a PGNS from the participants' experiences of workplace support to ALiP (EoR: Openness). This second offering aims to deepen and further understanding of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP underpinned by five part-offerings reflective of the expressions of shared meanings and connections revealed from my interpretation of the participants' experiences demonstrated within Figure 14 (A16) (EoR: Resonance).

Figure 14: Offering 2 parts of the whole - Furthering understanding of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP

7.2 Fore-havings of workplace support

Being attuned to Heidegger's (1962/1927; 1996/1927) notion of *'temporality'* and the participants' background experiences (*'fore-havings'*) caused me to dwell with Vic's initial experiences of workplace support:

'... I think that from the very beginning it was always kind of not expected but sort of encouraged that I would take part in further education, ...' (Vic)

Vic's experience called to thinking a sense of 'beginningness' being situated with others in a wider professional context before becoming a PGNS. Philosophically, this led me towards Gadamer's (2004/1960) translated notion of 'effective historic consciousness' or 'historically effective consciousness', that we are always already affected by history and that our consciousness is not independent of history. The notion of effective historic consciousness assumes that we are all part of history and larger historical contexts that we cannot objectively step outside of to consider the past and in coming to our interpretation and understanding (Dostal, 2002; Figal, 2002; Fleming, Gaidys and Robb, 2003). Therefore, there is an interplay between tradition within historical consciousness, horizons and prejudices in interpretation of the text, past and present contexts and the interpreter (Gadamer, 2004/1960).

Dwelling with Vic's experience of beginningness alongside Gadamer's (2004/1960) notion of effective historic consciousness, surfaced meaning that PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP may be influenced by a wider interplay of already existing historic contexts of learning and further education within the workplace and the nursing profession. Vic's experiences of expectations and encouragement from others to take part in further education before becoming (past) and in becoming (present) a PGNS, illuminated a larger, socio-historic context of workplace support being experienced by nurses prior to being a PGNS. This called to thinking the unconscious or conscious influence of historic, cultural contexts of being a nurse, practicing within professional nursing standards and codes of practice including upholding CPD requirements (NMC, 2018e; 2019d). Subsequently, Vic's experience surfaced a larger, inseparable socio-historic professional nursing and regulatory context, influencing PGNS experiences of expectations and encouragement to take part in further learning and education within the workplace.

Vic's experience also revealed encouragement from others as part of workplace support, illuminating a distinction between the experience of encouragement and expectations to take part in further education. Reflexively, returning to consider my part one literature review called to thinking the finding that nurse manager and senior colleague attitudes varied towards workplace support for PGNS and PGNE (Drennan and Hyde, 2008; Illingworth *et al.*, 2013; Richardson, 2013). Furthermore, manager and senior colleague attitudes were influenced by programme choice and purpose, and employer, role and service needs (Drennan and Hyde, 2008; Illingworth *et al.*, 2013; Richardson, 2013). Subsequently, Vic's

experience surfaced further meaning about the experience of becoming situated in PGNE, also being influenced by encouragement from workplace colleagues to take part in PGNE.

Reflexively, Vic's experience also furthered my understanding of the importance of hermeneutic phenomenological researchers bringing their fore-structures of understanding, effective historic consciousness and prejudice to interpretation (Heidegger, 1962/1927; Gadamer, 2004/1960). Drawing upon Gadamer's (2004/1960) notion of prejudice led me towards greater reflexive awareness and attunement to the historic influences of my own professional knowledge and experiences. This surfaced my professional socio-historic experiences of being a nurse and presuppositions about nurses inherently supporting the learning of students and colleagues in practice, based on upholding the NMC (2018e) professional standards. Such reflexive awareness supported me to surface encouragement from workplace colleagues as part of Vic's experiences of workplace support and being a PGNS. Without such reflexive awareness PGNS experiences of encouragement may have been passed over due to my presuppositions that encouragement for learning is an inherent part of workplace support and professional ways of being with each other as nurses. Although, as part of NMC (2019d) revalidation, nurses also have an individual responsibility to demonstrate, maintain and evidence CPD and learning. Vic's experiences illuminated the experience of encouragement from colleagues mattering as part of being a PGNS and being with other professionals in the workplace.

Vic's further experiences broaden understanding as to how the experience of other colleagues may influence PGNS situational and relational contexts of workplace support:

'... so luckily some of my colleagues have already done some postgrad courses already. So, I think that the kind of procedure for supporting sort of nurses doing that was already in place which was good.' (Vic)

Vic's experience revealed workplace support procedures already existing prior to experiences of becoming a PGNS in the workplace. This resonated with Gadamer's (2004 /1960) assumption that we are always already affected by historical and situational contexts. However, Vic's experience also revealed relational contexts of workplace support from colleagues being influenced by nurses that had already undertaken PG course:

'... it's kind of started when my colleague was doing her own course So, I had read her previous essays before and had given her some information and help. So, it was always something ..., that kind of relationship that we already had. And I was kind of (...) unsure about whether I had time to fit in doing a masters course and things. So, I spent a lot of time with her initially before I applied working out, ... how could I balance my time, how could I work this out, is it worth doing the course kind of thing. So, she initially encouraged me to do it and then she's always been a kind of support.' (Vic)

Vic's experience of already having a supportive relationship and always having a colleague's support, further called to thinking the philosophical notion of *'ready-to-hand'*. Offering one, revealed the potential for knowing self and motivations to be inherent or assumed individual attributes that may influence PGNS readiness in coming into PGNE. Vic's experience of already having peer support, furthered understanding that PGNS readiness in coming into PGNE may also be influenced by pre-existing, relational aspects of workplace support and being with others.

Significantly, Vic's experience of workplace support from self and colleagues before commencing PGNE brought further meaning to the research question. The research question may have assumed PGNS experiences of workplace support being exclusively set in the time, workplace and context of being a PGNS. However, Vic's experiences of pre-existing workplace support, further illuminated the socio-historic context of PGNS experiences of workplace support, being experienced before or as part of coming into PGNE. Although, my hermeneutic phenomenological study and interpretation did not philosophically align with the aim of producing a conceptual model of workplace support to ALiP as an outcome of my findings. Reflecting on the previously identified absence of a conceptual model of workplace support to ALiP, called to thinking the possibility of socio-historic dimensions further influencing the complexity of a construct of workplace support for PGNS to ALiP (C2).

Vic's experience also showed a reciprocity in being supported by workplace colleagues and previously being a workplace supporter to colleagues:

'... it's kind of started when my colleague was doing her own course So, I had read her previous essays before and had given her some information and help. So, it was always something ..., that kind of relationship that we already had. So, she initially encouraged me to do it and then she's always been a kind of support.' (Vic)

Vic's experience drew me to reflexively consider the proposed reflective framework of pedagogical considerations within Chapter 2 underpinned by Knowles, Holton and Swanson's (2005) four taxonomy domains (F1). Dwelling with the potential for reciprocity of support between PGNS and workplace colleagues called to thinking a further underpinning dimension and way of being with others, reflective of a two-way reciprocal relational construct of workplace support between PGNS and workplace colleagues, illustrated in Figure 15.

Figure 15: Adapted Reflective Framework – pedagogical considerations when setting the context of workplace support for PGNS to ALiP post-data interpretation

Bringing the philosophical notions and assumptions of *'temporality'*, *'fore-structures'* of understanding, *'being-with'* others and *'effective historic consciousness'* to interpretation of the participants' experiences highlighted the temporal, socio-historic contexts influencing PGNS of workplace support to ALiP (Heidegger, 1962/1927; Gadamer, 2004/1960). Significantly, surfacing meaning that PGNS previous experiences of being a workplace supporter for colleagues might influence PGNS own presuppositions, reciprocal expectations and future experiences of workplace support from some colleagues during PGNE.

7.3 Workplace supporting

When I asked participants about their PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP, aspects also revealed relating to others being workplace supporters and the how or doing of workplace supporting.

7.3.1 Workplace supporters and workplace supporting

The concept of the workplace supporter revealed through the participants' experiences of directly or indirectly being with workplace colleagues. The showing of PGNS being with workplace colleagues, registered nurses and managers, may have been reflective of the previously identified NMC and organisational workforce policies influencing role requirements and remits of nurses, managers, leaders and employers to support the learning of others within the workplace (NES, 2011; ICN, 2012; NMC, 2018e; NHS, 2019a; 2019b).

Of significance was that the participants' experiences continued to surface meaning about workplace supporters having experience of PGNE or associated experience in practice:

'And a colleague had done a sort of very similar course to that I'm doing just now. So, ... it was even practical support like how to access books and particularly during this time because a lot of libraries have been closed, so it's been things like that. Sort of sharing of experiences of how to look for articles ...' (Vic)

'I did have a, ... that was kind of helping me kind of move that stuff on, which was good. It was good for them because they had, they were a more experienced member of the team. So, they kind of knew some of the hurdles that maybe I would come across. So, they kind of gave me good pointers.' (Pat)

Vic and Pat's experiences furthered insight into the diverse ways that workplace supporters with experience of PGNE or associated experience in practice may provide support. From the pragmatic doing of workplace support e.g. how to access literature resources or potential funding. To abstract ways of workplace supporting through personal knowing and understanding of PGNE e.g. the need for time or hurdles that may be experienced as a PGNS:

'Yeah, I think generally I've found that people are very supportive of me doing the course(s) and what that might mean in practice. (...) But I feel that the people that have had the most understanding is people that have maybe done postgraduate things before. Because they understand how much time is required. Not that other people haven't been supportive, but they just don't understand the same. (...) I suppose (...) it's good for people to be supportive throughout doing these things and aware that you either need time or you do need head space or additional support just for somebody to help you to do things, if you are applying in practice.' (Vic)

Vic's experience showed that workplace supporters with or without experiences of PGNE, may be supportive of PGNS doing PGNE. However, Vic's experience furthered meaning about the contrasting ways in which PGNS may experience being with workplace supporters. Pat and Vic's experiences

illuminated workplace supporters with previous PGNE or associated experiences offering different ways of workplace support through shared knowing and understanding of previous PGNE learning experiences. Dwelling with Gadamer's (2004/1960) notion of effective historic consciousness surfaced meaning that PGNS experiences of workplace support may not be limited or restrictively bound with the context of their own socio-historic experiences. Alternatively, PGNS experiences of workplace support may be influenced and intertwined with the historic, learning experiences that workplace supporters bring to the context of workplace support for PGNS.

However, there appeared to be something unsurfaced between the notion of workplace supporters having historic, learning experiences of PGNE and the ontic practical ways of supporting PGNS or sharing personal knowing and understanding of PGNE. This led me to question whether there was a hidden, ontological meaning about what it means to be a PGNS supported by workplace colleagues that have and bringing experience of PGNE.

Ronnie's experience further illuminated a differentiation and significance about workplace supporters having previous or current experience of PGNE mattering to the experience of workplace support:

'... you do get a good (...) chat or a good debrief with another nurse, but she's not doing the course. She's, doing her own things but she's happy to listen and say that's great, how are you getting on and I'm like yeah, I passed that last module. And she's going well-done you, that's great. But it's not support from your line manager, it's peer support.'
(Ronnie)

Ronnie's experience also significantly illuminated a distinction between peer support not being line manager support. Subsequently, I became attuned to a potential ontological 'mood' announcing between PGNS expectations and experiences of peer support and line manager support. This evoked curiosity about how PGNS may be 'faring' in the context of being with workplace support from peers to colleagues in managerial roles. I also wondered whether further meaning would surface through experiences of a presence, distinction or absence of line manager support to ALiP. Reflexively, my attunement to this 'mood'; was influenced by my presuppositions that those in senior nursing or associated workforce leadership or management positions have a role in actively supporting the learning of nurses including nurses that may be undertaking PGNE within their area of practice or organisation (NES, 2011; ICN, 2012; NMC, 2018e; NHS, 2019a; 2019b). However, my attunement to this 'mood' was also influenced by the part one literature review identifying varied line manager or employer support from positively contributing to support to support lacking or being inconsistent, inhibiting learning (Drennan and Hyde, 2008; Illingworth *et al.*, 2013; Richardson, 2013; Millberg *et al.*, 2014).

The shared connections and meanings across the participants' experiences of workplace support revealed pragmatic and abstract ways of workplace supporting. This furthered insight into the ways in which workplace supporters may be there as colleagues with or without PGNE experience or within

managerial roles. Considering the philosophical assumption of *'Being'*, illuminated PGNS experiences being co-constructed within a socio-historic context of being a PGNS and being with workplace colleagues. The revealing of workplace supporters having or not having experiences of PGNE, deepened understanding that workplace support may be influenced beyond PGNS *'fore-havings'*, to PGNS being aware or cognisant of the background experiences (*'fore-havings'*) of workplace supporters. Furthermore, Gadamer's (2004/1960) notion of 'effective historic consciousness' surfaced workplace supporters having past experiences of PGNE mattering and influencing possibilities for PGNS to experience different ways of being supported.

Of significance is that interpretation of the participants' experiences of workplace support brought awareness to the ways of workplace supporters being there influencing contrasting PGNS experiences of being with workplace supporters. Subsequently, revealing a complex phenomenon about a wider socio-historic, relational context of support and supporting influencing ways of being with workplace support prior to ALiP. This phenomenon was considered significant to understanding being a PGNS particularly based on the assumption of workplace support being a conduit to effectively support PGNS to ALiP.

7.3.2 Workplace supporting being there or not being there

Although my research focused on PGNS experiences in the context of the workplace environment (EoR: Actualisation). Vic's experiences of workplace support broadened insight beyond the workplace environment:

'I suppose it's even just been an emotional support because big courses aren't easy trying to balance doing all that with work as well. And it was even just having that person there So, you're not really getting to meet (...) people in a classroom and creating a kind of environment where you have peer support. You don't really have a consistent following of people So, I've not had the same people follow me through. So, I've not really built-up relationships with any peers in my class properly. So, she's kind of been that person for me that I can bounce ideas off of or Just have the support of, I'm struggling, this is too much work or Or even just, right I did that well, is that okay'
(Vic)

Dwelling with Vic's experience initially revealed an ontic rather than ontological perspective of *'thrownness'* influenced by the characteristics and attributes of classroom peers providing emotional support within an academic environment. This insight called to thinking a potential area for wider research relating to PGNS experiences of support across workplace and HEI environments. However,

this ontic perspective, reflexively supported me to move towards an ontological perspective of *'thrownness'*, surfacing the socio-cultural and historic contexts influencing a projection towards ways of being with workplace colleagues as workplace supporters. Heidegger (1996/1927) assumed that *'Dasein'* is always already thrown and projecting as part of our *'Being'* and that our *'being-in-the-world'* is not separated from *'being-with'* others. I was also drawn to Guignon's (2006, p. 8) interpretation of the structure of *'Dasein'* positioning 'things already count in determining ways in relating to the community's practices'. Guignon's (2008) reference to community practices called to thinking Heidegger's (1996/1927) notion of *'being-with'* others and the different academic and workplace contexts within Vic's experience of being with others. Vic's experience illuminated an interplay of PGNS past, socio-historic experiences of academic peer support influencing or becoming intertwined with projected socio-historic experiences of being-with workplace support relationships and ways of being supported in practice. This surfaced meaning that the socio-historic and cultural contexts in which PGNS experience support may not only influence their own projected thrownness towards being with workplace support but also that of their workplace supporters, particularly in determining PGNS expectations of support from workplace supporters.

This offering called to thinking further reflection on the proposed reflective framework of pedagogical considerations underpinned by four taxonomy domains (Knowles, Holton and Swanson, 2005) (C2; F1). Particularly, as the framework initially focused on the singular context of workplace support as opposed to acknowledging a potentially inter-related sphere of PGNS peer support within the HEI environment (F16).

Figure 16: Iterative Reflective Framework – reflexive pedagogical considerations when setting the context of workplace support for PGNS to ALiP

Returning to the workplace context, Pat’s experience also furthered understanding of PGNS being there with colleagues in the workplace:

‘So, there’s a colleague ... quite close with the team. And having spent quite a bit of time kind of talking with them as well, about, where I’m kind of going and what I’m kind of thinking. They’ve been quite instrumental at offering that extra bit of support. In terms of being able to set up some meetings, set up some networking within the wider organisation to allow me to kind of take that forward. Which has kind of helped, within my own team because they’ve kind of then recognising that actually other more senior managers are kind of taking this ..., a bit more seriously I suppose. So that’s certainly helped and it’s made things a bit easier,’ (Pat)

Pat’s experience revealed that workplace supporters may provide direct and indirect ways of supporting e.g. PGNS directly talking with workplace supporters to workplace supporters facilitating wider support opportunities. This revealed the potential for workplace supporters to provide direct support within the immediate workplace and illuminated workplace supporters being a conduit to facilitating a continuum of

workplace support for PGNS beyond their immediate workplace. Potentially, creating further opportunities for PGNS to be with wider organisational support or networks to ALiP.

A deeper understanding of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP was also revealed from Vic's experience of workplace support being there:

'I think the support has been there but actually applying it in practice has not really worked out in a lot of circumstances. (...) we were trying to allocate days to do a bit. So, for example the module that I'm carrying out just now the lectures have been but we're trying to plan ahead so that I don't miss the next one kind of thing. So, I think the support idea is there but sometimes actually applying that in practice is not possible.' (Vic)

The showing of a contradiction between workplace support being there for Vic and the actual application of workplace support in practice, significantly illuminated whether 'application of workplace support to practice' had previously been concealed when developing the research question. Particularly given the immediate transition of terms from 'workplace support to ALiP'. Subsequently, this surfaced meaning about the application of workplace support being experienced by PGNS as a prerequisite prior to workplace support to ALiP.

7.3.3 The giving, taking and allowing of workplace support

The participants' experiences continued to deepen insights into the pragmatic and abstract ways of PGNS being supported by workplace colleagues. Particularly, through emerging meanings from the participants' experiences of the giving, taking and allowing of workplace support:

'... she's helped me just to kind of balance my time and then, it's in addition to that it's even things like she gave me a lot of articles that she'd used before ...' (Vic)

Vic's experience revealed further ways of workplace supporting from the provision or availability of abstract and pragmatic ways of supporting PGNS in the workplace e.g. of balancing time and giving resources. The showing of workplace support being 'given' also challenged my presuppositions that available aspects of workplace support from workplace supporters would be taken or received by PGNS:

'I probably would have got her to proofread things and help that way but I was probably a bit too embarrassed, so I didn't But she has offered to do things like that if need be, if I felt I needed that help kind of thing. And even just someone to bounce ideas off of (...).'
(Vic)

Subsequently, Vic's experience evoked curiosity whether workplace supporters may offer PGNS aspects of support however, PGNS may influence or choose whether the offered workplace support becomes

available to them or used. Subsequently this illuminated whether individual PGNS responses to available workplace support may influence future situations, possibilities and experiences of workplace support from colleagues and ALiP. Reflecting on the philosophical assumptions of *'being-in-the-world'*, always *'being-with'* others, Vic's experience, illuminated an area for further research enquiry relating to the experiences of colleagues in providing workplace support for PGNS. This proposed area of research may provide an alternative lens to understanding the offering, giving and taking of workplace support for PGNS to ALiP.

Shared connections and meanings through interpreting the participants' experience also revealed the significance of time as an aspect of workplace support. Resonating with the findings of Black and Bonner (2011) and Rooney's (2015) studies that highlighted time and study leave as key factors associated with workplace support:

'I think (...) one of the main things has been trying to give me time It takes time to actually attend lectures if they're during the day or even just have the time to (...) do some course work or essays or things like that.' (Vic)

'The team has been supportive in allowing me to take the time that I need., they've allowed me, they've supported me to have, the hours that I need to go and do my kind of ... my tutorials and stuff, and that's been fine.' (Pat)

'(...) some of my colleagues ... allowed me to have time to sort of debrief and speak about even just workload or things like that generally rather than just actually applying it to practice.' (Vic)

Reflexively, considering the philosophical fore-structure of *'fore-having'*, called to question whether the inclusion criteria for my study, requiring PGNS to be practicing as registered nurses, may have influenced the appearance of time as a significant aspect of workplace support. This presupposition was based on an assumption that participants would be balancing time in being a PGNS while also practicing as a registered nurse.

Of further significance is that there appeared to be potentially concealed *'mood'* relating to the *'giving'*, *'supporting'* and *'allowing'* of time for PGNS, by or from workplace colleagues. This *'mood'* illuminated a potential phenomenon relating to the *'allowing'* or *'permissioning'* of workplace support for PGNS from colleagues. Subsequently, the participants' experiences evoked further curiosity whether the giving or not giving, allowance or permission of time as workplace support, may influence opportunities for PGNS to ALiP. Revealing a potential further relational dimension and area of enquiry in understanding PGNS experiences of workplace support and being with workplace colleagues.

Participants' experiences of time further showed through their situational and temporal experiences of *'being-in-the-world'*, as PGNS in the context of the pandemic and workplace:

'As I mentioned before, it's on my private time spent for that. There is no time from, no time kind of from the workplace.' (Taylor)

'(...) I think time is probably the most significant thing and (...) it's okay saying, is someone being supportive and say yeah you can take the time. But that's quite difficult when they have staff, that kind of ... lots of changes happening ..., new members of staff needing support and training plus it's holiday time. So, it's difficult to take out that time without either me feeling too guilty for taking it or well I just have to cancel it because (...) there's more of a clinical need and I have to go in. So, that's probably the most challenging thing.' (Vic)

The participants' PGNS experiences of time being with workplace colleagues in the context of everyday workplace practice and the pandemic led my thinking towards Heidegger's (1996/1927) notion of 'Everydayness'. Based on the philosophical notion of 'everydayness' bringing meaning to the way in which we live our lives rather than a context reflecting a sum of days or calendar sense:

Everydayness means the How in accordance with which Da-sein "lives its day," whether in all of its modes of behaviour or only in certain ways prefigured by being-with-one-another. (Heidegger, 1996/1927, p. 339)

Subsequently, my interpretation of the participants' experiences illuminated a potential tension in the 'everydayness'. Particularly, between time, being a PGNS and being with colleagues in the workplace, PGNE, and the wider pandemic, shown through experiences of guilt, difficulty and cancellation. Dwelling with Vic's experience of time led me to Heidegger's (1996/1927, p. 64) position that the 'Being' of equipment (or useful things) always belongs to a totality of equipment, therefore equipment relates to 'something in-order-to ... contains a reference of something to something'. Heidegger (1962/1927) set out that the focus should not be on the conception of material objects but must consider circumspection, the activities in which they are put to use which we may not be conscious of. Furthermore, we must also consider the wider referential totality of social and cultural encounters within-the-world (Heidegger, 1962/1927). Reflexively, Vic's experience revealed the experience of taking time being interrelated with the offering of time from workplace colleagues. However, Vic's experience also surfaced meaning about PGNS having time in-order to be a PGNS with workplace colleagues and wider PGNE environments. This further illuminated the potential of PGNS 'everydayness' influencing a wider context in which workplace support and being a PGNS is experienced.

Vic's experience of difficulty to take time, initially showed the lived experience of 'everydayness' influencing a temporal 'breakdown' of time being a previously taken for granted aspect of workplace support becoming noticeably unavailable or 'unready-to-hand'. Reflexively, I was aware that this interpretation brought an ontic perspective to time being a characteristic of workplace support. Mulhall (2013) offered that Heidegger's notion of 'un-readiness-to-hand' of an object brings us to conscious

consideration of the 'with what' and 'for what' they were '*ready-to-hand*' which underpins the objects handiness. Furthermore, '*un-readiness-to-hand*' may be brought to the fore from something being unusable, missing, or getting or standing in the way of our concern (Heidegger, 1962/1927; 1996/1927). Within Macquarrie and Robinson's translation of Being and Time (Heidegger, 1996/1927, p. 104) the translated term '*obstinacy*' relates to an obstacle standing in the way of the achievement of some purpose. Therefore, it is assumed that we need to attend to or dispose of such obstacles before we can finish what we want to do and achieve some purpose (Heidegger, 1962/1927). This called to thinking Vic's experience of time not simply becoming unavailable or absent, to something getting in the way. Subsequently, I considered, the 'for what' of the '*ready-to-handness*' of time and the totality which may underpin the handiness of time. Reflexively, this illuminated that PGNS 'everydayness' may disturb time or workplace support and move away time to be a PGNS and ALiP. This called to thinking PGNS moving beyond conscious self-awareness of their '*everydayness*' towards actively discussing their experiences of the everydayness with workplace colleagues to open possibilities to be a PGNS and ALiP. This further insight brought to the fore the complex, dynamic and temporal '*everydayness*' which PGNS may experience and potential influence workplace support to ALiP.

7.3.4 Curiosity of asking and knowing

Interpretation of the participants' experiences unconcealed a phenomenon relating to the asking and knowing of workplace support by PGNS and workplace colleagues. This initially revealed from Taylor's experience of not asking for workplace support:

'... I never actually ask for any support from work or financial or educational. It's actually purely my private kind a motivation to go for further education to kind of expand my knowledge.' (Taylor)

Taylor's experience of private motivation towards PGNE resonated with the Chapter 6 offering of participants' experiences of knowing self and motivations for coming into PGNE. However, dwelling further with Taylor's experience, surfaced that PGNS experiences of motivations in coming into PGNE may influence PGNS ways of asking workplace colleagues for support. This illuminated the potential significance of PGNS ways of being with colleagues in the asking or not asking of support potentially closing or opening opportunities for workplace support to ALiP. The showing of a sense of 'privateness' and 'never asking' for workplace support called to thinking PGNS being present and visible to colleagues in the workplace. My curiosity was drawn to wondering if in PGNS asking for workplace support to ALiP whether being a PGNS also becomes present, visible or known to colleagues. This aspect invited further curiosity about PGNS being present within the workplace further explored in Chapter 9.

Dwelling with Vic's experiences continued to broaden horizons about being a PGNS and asking for workplace support:

'And as much as ... are supportive, one ... in particular is not necessarily ... they wouldn't have necessarily encouraged me to do this course. So, I don't really ask for time off there, unless there's something really specific that I need, that's out with my control. But my more clinical side are very, they were ... like they encouraged me to do the course, kind of thing. So, I feel like it's a little bit easier to ask for time off for that. And they actively ask, how is the course going, do you need more time, put things in the calendar just take it off kind of thing.' (Vic)

Initially, I was drawn to Vic's experience showing encouragement to undertake PGNE by workplace colleagues being there or not being there. However, Vic's experience of encouragement from colleagues revealed being with active, passive and absent ways of asking for workplace support. Reflexively, Taylor and Vic's experiences called to thinking Heidegger's (1996/1927) assumptions of *'being-with'* others which surfaced PGNS being with complex socio-historic and cultural contexts as part of being with workplace colleagues and in asking colleagues for support. Furthermore, Heidegger (1996/1927) assumed that our human existence is thrown into the world in a way that we do not choose, our existence being determined, delivered or given over to something. *'Dasein'* also exists as thrown, projecting itself upon the possibilities in which it is thrown (Heidegger, 1962/1927). Withy (2014) positions that that *'thrownness'* extends beyond a concept of being thrown, to the context from and in which we are thrown from socio-historic, cultural contexts. Returning to Vic's experiences further revealed workplace colleagues actively asking about workplace support needs or volunteering workplace support. This illuminated possibilities of PGNS already being with workplace support influencing PGNS ways of not asking for support from colleagues. Taylor and Vic's experiences subsequently revealed complex relational aspects, background experiences (*'fore-havings'*) and attitudes towards PGNE influencing ways of asking for workplace support by PGNS, workplace colleagues, and opportunities for PGNS to ALiP. This surfaced meaning about the socio-historical and cultural professional and workplace contexts from and in which being a PGNS may determine and project upon ways of being with colleagues. Furthermore, influencing PGNS ways of asking for workplace support and possibilities for PGNS being with workplace support to ALiP.

Reflexively, coming to this further understanding led me to dwell with Vic's further experiences of being with encouragement:

'So, we've tried to put things in the calendar to give me sort of time out. But it's good because I haven't had to ask for that, they've encouraged me to talk about it and make sure I've put in the time. So, then it is my responsibility to make that time but they're actively showing me that, that's what they want me to do, which was nice.' (Vic)

Vic's experiences showed already being with encouragement from colleagues influencing being actively asked or shown workplace support from colleagues. However, Vic's experience revealed a sense of responsibility to take time offered from workplace colleagues. This called to thinking PGNS being with encouragement from colleagues opening possibilities towards a co-responsibility of workplace support between PGNS and colleagues. This surfaced meaning about PGNS being and becoming responsible in the taking and co-creation of workplace support with colleagues. Furthermore, this evoked curiosity whether PGNS ways of being with colleagues and asking for support may influence PGNS being empowered, responsible and autonomous as part of the experience of workplace support to ALiP.

Pat and Ronnie's experiences also revealed not being asked within the broader context of being a PGNS and workplace managerial support:

'... certainly kind of like senior management level, have yet to ask me how I got on You know whether I passed stuff, whether I was struggling with anything, if there was anything they could do to help me. So, I've not had any of that kind of additional support if you like. So, that kind of, ... meeting my kind of emotional needs, making sure that obviously I wasn't getting overwhelmed with both my university work and my daily clinical work as well. If I've needed extra support I've had to source that out and actually say.' (Pat)

'My ... manager, isn't what would I say, isn't interested. I don't mean that in a bad way (...). But, hasn't really mentioned the fact that I'm doing the course, hasn't really said much about it to be honest with you. When I've been asking for things, it's actually been colleagues that I work with that have been more helpful' (Ronnie)

Dwelling with Pat and Ronnie's experiences initially called to thinking Heidegger's (1962/1927) notions of *'being-with'* and *'solicitude'*. The notion of *'solicitude'* relates to existential concerns as a character of *'Being'*, concern for others and our existence of *'being-in-the-world'*, rather than objects of concern (Heidegger, 1962/1927). Furthermore, the notion of *'solicitude'* is assumed to have two positive modes of possibilities, one that can take care away from the other (*'leap-in'*) or give care back to another (*'leap-ahead'*) (Heidegger, 1962/1927). Of significance is that the positive modes of solicitude are considered as being active or involving action in *'being-with'* others (Heidegger, 1962/1927; Crowther and Thomson, 2020). This called to thinking, Pat and Ronnie's experiences revealing contrasting inactive ways of not being asked about being a PGNS or workplace support by those in managerial roles. Subsequently, I was drawn to the philosophical positioning of Dasein alternatively maintaining itself mostly in the negative mode of indifference (Heidegger, 1962/1927; Crowther and Thomson, 2020).

'... yet ontically there is an essential distinction between the "indifferent" being together of arbitrary things and the not-mattering-to-one-another of beings who are with one another' (Heidegger, 1996/1927, p. 114).

This temporal mode of *'Being'* assumes possible ways of concern as a passing by or not really being interested in being with another. This significantly surfaced meaning about PGNS experiences of a not asking or mentioning of workplace support by managerial colleagues, illuminating passive ways in which workplace support may be experienced and inhibit or close off possibilities for PGNS to ALiP. However, dwelling further with Pat and Ronnie's' experiences, attuned me to PGNS alternatively sourcing their own support by asking other colleagues. Significantly, revealing that experiences of managerial colleagues not asking or mentioning workplace support, may influence PGNS creating alternative situations to actively seek and open up their own possibilities for support from wider workplace colleagues. Subsequently, illuminating how PGNS may become their own active facilitator of workplace support in different situational contexts of being with workplace colleagues.

Being attuned to the concept of asking for workplace support also called to thinking a question that arose from Ronnie's experience of workplace support:

'So, they have been very helpful. I'm not entirely sure they know why they're helping me look for this stuff, cause we don't really have the chance to then sit down and say well actually, I was looking for the ... because I was focusing on But I don't think there's an understanding there behind why I'm looking for them.' (Ronnie)

Ronnie's self-questioning about colleagues knowing and understanding of why they were helping illuminated a significant question whether workplace colleagues know and understand why PGNS may ask for their support, in the context of being a PGNS and PGNE. This evoked further questions as to whether workplace colleagues knowing and understanding of the context of PGNS workplace support may influence; conversations about the asking of workplace support, the availability of workplace support from colleagues, and the opening or closing of opportunities for PGNS to ALiP.

I continued to dwell with Ronnie's experiences and Heidegger's (1996/1927) assumptions of the *'indifferent'* mode, as an existential mode of concern:

But because concern, initially and for the most part, dwells in the deficient or at least indifferent modes-in the indifference of passing-one-another-by-a nearest and essential knowing oneself is in need of a getting-to-know-oneself. And when even knowing oneself loses itself in aloofness, concealing oneself and misrepresenting oneself, being-with-one-another requires special ways in order to come near to the others ... (Heidegger, 1996/1927, p. 117)

The *'indifferent'* mode called to thinking the concept of PGNS knowing self and how colleagues get to know PGNS in the workplace to understand their workplace support needs. Furthermore, whether these aspects may influence the potential continuum of asking approaches between PGNS and workplace colleagues. Understanding the *'indifferent'* mode, from the perspectives of essentially knowing and

representing oneself also furthered curiosity about the appearance and presence of being a PGNS in the workplace and PGNS being known to workplace colleagues.

It was beyond the scope of hermeneutic phenomenological interpretation to seek to answer why PGNS and colleagues may or may not ask about workplace support for PGNS to ALiP. However, to further understanding about the phenomenon of the asking of workplace support by PGNS and workplace colleagues I undertook a scope of literature within the past 10 years relating to asking for support across PGNS, nursing, workplace and professional contexts using the CINAHL database. However, the literature scope revealed limited, relevant research literature to further analytical discussion.

The participants' experiences and philosophical notions revealed a phenomenon relating to the asking and knowing of workplace support by PGNS and workplace colleagues influencing possibilities of workplace support for PGNS to ALiP. Furthermore surfacing meaning about the complex relational, temporal, situational experiences of PGNS self-being and being with workplace colleagues (*'being-with-others'*). The revealing of this phenomenon alongside limited, relevant contemporary literature, illuminated the asking and knowing of workplace support by PGNS and workplace colleagues as a further area of enquiry to broaden horizons of understanding PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP.

7.4 Furthering understanding of PGNS ALiP

Through interpretation of the participants' experiences of workplace support to ALiP, expressions of shared connections and meanings revealed insights into the participants' pre-understandings, background experiences (*'fore-havings'*) and ways of applying PGNE learning in practice, furthering understanding of workplace support for ALiP.

7.4.1 Furthering understanding and the 'doing' of ALiP

ALiP showed through the participants' experiences of PGNE and implementing learning in practice:

'... a lot of the things that I'd covered were about tools and strategies that you could implement in your workplace.' (Ronnie)

'... because, when you start read and kind of discover new things in the theoretical, you maybe try to implement that in your practice.' (Taylor)

Vic's experience also showed reflection as part of the doing of PGNE as opposed to an immediate assumption of ALiP:

'... it's just probably more me reflecting while I'm doing my course work rather than actually applying that to practice but like I said it's just making me think about that in a different way.' (Vic)

In dwelling with Vic's experience, I considered the showing of 'reflecting' while 'doing' PG learning as opposed to immediate, direct or actual ALiP. This called to thinking, whether the context of workplace support to ALiP within the research question, may have been assumed with a direct 'doing' of ALiP. As opposed to collective humanistic, experiential, social constructionism and transformative pedagogical approaches and assumptions underpinning presuppositions relating to the ALiP. Illuminating that these presuppositions may not have been explicit to the participants within the context of the research question. Reflexively, this attuned me to this potential assumption when interpreting the data.

Returning to the participants' experiences of reflecting and implementing learning in practice, resonated with the abstraction and complexity facets of mastersness (QAAS, no date). In which masters level students, construct new knowledge and meanings integrating application into practice as part of the learning process (QAAS, no date). Subsequently, the participants' experiences evoked curiosity about PGNS assumptions and expectations of PGNE, and how this may present or appear through ALiP:

'... it is difficult because I've not had kind of specific (...) practical things that I have had to take in to necessarily apply.' (Vic)

Through interpretation, I was drawn to a potential tension between the taking of specific practical things to ALiP and the contrasting abstract facets of mastersness and characteristics of PGNE influencing the context of ALiP (A2-3). This orientated thinking to whether PGNS choice of PGNE programme and the facets of mastersness underpinning specific PGNE programmes may influence PGNS experiences and expectations of taking pragmatic or tangible things to apply in practice. Particularly, when considering the diverse range of PGNE programmes available, with varied purposes and learning outcomes. For example, consideration of PGNE programmes specifically designed and aligned to role requirements with clinical practice competencies (NMC, 2004; 2018b), in contrast to, PGNE programmes with varied purposes and learning outcomes, reflective of broader professional aspects and abstract learning outcomes.

Reflecting on the abstract nature of the facets of mastersness and the generic themes identified from scoping UK PG level descriptors (QAAS, no date) (A2). Particularly, PG student characteristics associated with self-autonomy, creativity, critical reflection and awareness, and understanding abstract, complex professional issues. Called to question the reality of PGNS pragmatically and feasibly taking specific practical or tangible things from PGNE to apply in practice.

This deeper understanding led to further questions being raised about whether the application of practical things to abstract PGNE attributes and characteristics may influence how PGNS demonstrate

ALiP to workplace colleagues. The participants' experiences revealed potential complexities surrounding the application of PGNE learning in practice. Further illuminating, whether these complex aspects may influence the pragmatic ways in which PGNS and workplace colleagues ask and know about the context of workplace support for PGNS to ALiP.

However, participants' experiences of applying PG learning also showed through applying research and evidence in practice. Contrastingly revealing, how PGNS may experience the application of PGNE and ALNP attributes associated with critical analysis and critical research skills to practice, and demonstrate these aspects within the workplace to colleagues (A2-3):

'As I said before the pandemic the time when I spent that was enjoyable, I enjoyed that research, enjoyed gather all the resources, analysing all that and thinking how I can apply to my post. ..., how maybe that can improve my workplace, my daily work ...' (Taylor)

'But sometimes these types of meetings because you're sitting with sort of leaders and managers and also medical staff it's quite difficult to (...) have your voice heard, I guess. But being able to have that evidence to display you can't really argue with that. So, that was quite a positive experience from that perspective.' (Vic)

Vic and Taylor's experiences of 'having evidence' called to thinking, the potential for PGNE attributes becoming available as part of being a PGNS in practice, influencing approaches and possibilities to ALiP (A2-3):

'And, actually, the evidence that I brought was being backed up by external sources. So, it kind of added that extra level of research and that extra level of understanding I suppose about why this needed to change. So, it was quite good to see that for all that I had recognised that there'd been a change at the lower level. At higher up levels in, within the organisation, it was actually been recognised that it had to be a change that happened as well. So, that made me feel quite kind of positive and quite kind of valued in that, well if I hadn't of proposed that change then maybe you know rather than being proactive the team would have ended up being reactive.' (Pat)

The participants' experiences revealed bringing and using research evidence to create opportunities for a heard voice by workplace colleagues. This further attuned me to a 'mood' about PGNS using PGNE attributes and capabilities to influence different possibilities ('projection') of being with workplace colleagues. Particularly, the potential for PGNS to influence possibilities for professional recognition as a PGNS, changes to practice and positive self experiences of being a PGNS. This deeper understanding, resonated with the previous pedagogical assumption that an individual's experiences of applying learning are influenced by self and socio-cultural factors (Jarvis, 2010; Webster-Wright, 2010; Dyke, 2017). This significantly illuminated the potential transformational possibilities for PGNS associated with

applying PGNE attributes and learning to practice as part of being a PGNS and professional within the workplace context.

ALiP further revealed through the concept of self, which showed from the participants' experiences of self-thinking and self-reflection:

'... I think with all the additional learning you're doing it's making me think about other things. Such as the policies that's driving different settings and the workplace culture,'
(Ronnie)

'Yeah, it's probably more as I'm reading the things while I'm doing the course work of the module that I suppose I'm trying to think And I'm just sort of reflecting on how I am in practice at the moment in that sort of situation. So, when I'm reading the sort of different things, I'm like well have I done this, have I done that, how would that maybe fit in to the future.' (Vic)

'... the previous kind of experience which maybe wasn't kind of great but thanks to the reflection I'm enlightened ... what went wrong, what could be improved. So, basically after this previous experience I kind of have always planned in my head kind of steps what I need to do and how I need to apply them. And from that point of view if there's any problems, quickly I can analyse them and how I can support my teams to make sure the service is delivered.' (Taylor)

The showing of self-thinking, reflecting and analysing further resonated with the facets of mastersness relating to critical reflection, awareness and insight (A2). Further, philosophical and pedagogical assumptions were also brought to light through the participants' experiences of thinking and reflecting on previous, present and future contexts. Particularly, assumptions relating to *'temporality'* and learning being part of an individual's being influenced by continually changing self, educational and professional socio-cultural contexts (Jarvis, 2010; Peach, 2010; Webster-Wright, 2010; Dyke, 2017; NMC, no dateb).

The participants' experiences also called to thinking the Heideggerian notion of *'breakdown'*. In the context of English language, use of this term may be negatively associated with synonyms such as failure or collapse (Collins, 2022). However, Heidegger's (1962/1927) notion of *'disturbance or breakdown'* relates to an ontological movement from the taken for granted, absorbed ways of being, towards a different or significant way of existing and *'being-in-the-world'*. This illuminated the participants' experiences of reflecting, thinking, analysing and questioning potentially revealing a movement towards different temporal ways of being a PGNS and being with workplace colleagues in the context of ALiP and further possibilities for ALiP:

'... continue, to make these kind of proposed changes and continue to influence people to kind of carry on with these, like further research and questioning things when You

know rather than just going with the kind of norm and kind of changing that culture. So, yeah definitely motivated me going forward.’ (Pat)

The participants’ experiences of doing and having practical things such as evidence and research to support the need for change. Further called to thinking ontic perspectives of PGNS having defined, pragmatic or material things in order to influence changes in the workplace or practice. This challenged my presuppositions about ALiP being underpinned by humanistic, abstract mastersness facets, transformative pedagogical approaches and ontological ways of being and becoming as a PGNS. Subsequently, revealing an ontic sense of doing as a PGNS, calling to further question the understanding of ALiP.

7.4.2 Bringing and contributing ALiP

The participants’ experiences brought insight to understanding ALiP, in the context of bringing and contributing ALiP. Vic’s challenging experiences of workplace support to ALiP, evoked further curiosity about PGNS assumptions and workplace expectations of bringing or contributing ALiP:

‘So, I suppose that’s the only challenge. So, I haven’t had lots of maybe sort of practical things that I’ve had to take back or like too many tangible things that I’ve had to take back.’ (Vic)

The showing of taking practical or tangible things back to the workplace continued to significantly raise questions about how ALiP may appear or be experienced by PGNS and workplace colleagues.

Pat and Vic’s experiences further showed pragmatic ways of ‘doing’ ALiP in the context of research and evidence however, also revealed bringing and contributing self with the context of ALiP:

‘... that’s remained a big focus throughout the communication of ideas and the communication of new evidence and research that’s kind of coming out. So, that’s something that is really important, passing that information on. ... and doing something with it rather than just, me taking complete ownership of it and saying right okay well I’ve learned this, this has been great, an I know all about this. You know now, it’s still important for me to make sure that actually I kind of influence other people kind of taking that forward.’ (Pat)

‘But one of the things that we’re looking at, is publications out there, and some of the evidence that I had created from one of the modules that I was doing, some of the articles and standards and things that I’d found was able to contribute to (...) that service redesign and what kind of evidence we needed to do that. So, that was something that

was quite significant because (...) I had, (...) I knew that they existed and it's not like anything like you know that all these policies and guidelines and stuff exist but sometimes you don't actually take the time to delve into them in detail. So that was quite good, usually maybe previously my manager would have done that and lead on that. But it was quite nice to be able to contribute to that in a different way than maybe I would have done before.' (Vic)

The showing of time, communication and self, challenged thinking beyond key characteristics of PGNE and facets of mastersness influencing ALiP. Potentially, revealing the use of time and communication as PGNS ways of supporting ALiP.

However, Pat and Vic's experiences of influencing and contributing to practice furthered understanding towards a potential continuum of ALiP beyond self-contexts to being with workplace colleagues. Reflexively, furthering thinking beyond previously revealed participants' self motivations and reasons for coming into PGNE, towards earlier pedagogical assumptions that as part of a learner's being there may be self-motivations to apply learning, as well as critical self-awareness of the professional responsibilities of applying learning (Peach, 2010). Subsequently, revealing complex pedagogical, motivational and relational aspects of ALiP between self, being a PGNS and being with workplace colleagues.

The insights into ALiP from the pragmatic to abstract 'doing' of PGNE, and the bringing and contributing of ALiP in being with workplace colleagues further illuminated the complex, abstract ways of ALiP in the context of being a PGNS. This deeper understanding brought curiosity about the visibility of ALiP to workplace colleagues. Evoking further questions relating to the potential challenges to PGNS and workplace colleagues feasibly providing and demonstrating workplace support to ALiP, given the abstract construct and ways of ALiP.

7.5 Bringing together the parts: Workplace support to ALiP

In seeking to understand PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP, this offering presents shared meanings and connections revealed from the participants' experiences that showed a bringing together of workplace support and ALiP.

7.5.1 Moods of workplace support to ALiP

From the participants' experiences of workplace support to ALiP, I became attuned to an ontological 'mood' about how PGNS may be 'faring' in 'being-with' colleagues in the context of workplace support to ALiP:

'... just support me really or look at my essays or to talk about different topics that I'm doing so, that then I can talk about how I can use that in practice.' (Vic)

'... there's been nobody there with regards to discussing your learning with. There's been nobody there that you could even tell about it. So, even if I have learned something at various parts on various modules and I wanted to you know implement it or talk about it at work there's nobody there to do that with.' (Ronnie)

Initially I was drawn to Ronnie's experience of nobody being there, which called to thinking Heidegger's (1962/1927) position that:

... when something ready-to-hand is found missing, though its everyday presence has been so obvious that we have never taken any notice of it, this makes a break in those referential context which circumspection discovers. Our circumspection comes up against, emptiness, and now sees for the first time what the missing article was ready-to-hand with, and what is was ready-to-hand for. (Heidegger, 1962/1927, p.105)

Reflexively, dwelling with Ronnie's and Vic's experiences revealed being with workplace colleagues as part of ALiP. Ronnie's experience of nobody being there brought reflexive awareness to the socio-cultural workplace contexts which PGNS may be situated in being-with colleagues. This illuminated ALiP being influenced or dependent on PGNS being with workplace colleagues in order for conversations about their learning to occur prior to ALiP. Subsequently, surfacing the complex relational ways of PGNS being with colleagues to converse and open opportunities for ALiP.

The participants' experiences of talking and discussing with colleagues also revealed further insights about how PGNS may be 'faring' in the context of workplace support to ALiP:

'... oh, well done you and good luck with your study, nothing else other than that.' (Taylor)

'But as I say the kind of culture within my team isn't really a big emphasis on additional learning or additional academic work. So I think, it kind of felt at times it was a bit like, okay well that's just something that ... doing, and ... okay fair enough ... wants to do it and that's fine. But weren't really kind of interested if you like, wasn't really kind of interested in saying what have you been learning, what have you been doing.' (Pat)

'So, I definitely think, having the support of your line manager or at least the understanding of them as to why you're doing it or ... I mean she's just basically said to me I don't know why you're doing that (...). I'm like well, you know professional development, you know, learning new skills, enhancing your knowledge, you know, everything that you know, she's kind of just like (...) I don't know why you're doing that.'
(Ronnie)

Dwelling with Pat, Ronnie and Taylor's experiences, led me to consider Heidegger's (1996/1927) notion and assumptions of *'idle talk'* to deepen interpretation of the participants' experiences of talking with workplace colleagues. The notion of:

Idle talk does not have the kind of being of *consciously passing off* something as something else. The fact that one has said something groundlessly and then passes it along is in further retelling sufficient to turn disclosing around into a closing off. For that is said is initially always understood as "saying," that is, as discovering. Thus, by its very nature, idle talk is a closing off since it *omits* going back to the foundation of what is being talked about. (Heidegger, 1996/1927, p. 158)

Considering the notion of *'idle talk'* evoked curiosity whether there was a concealed *'mood'* relating to absent or omitted aspects or approaches by colleagues in discussing with PGNS being a PGNS and workplace support to ALiP. This illuminated the possibility of talking and discussing with colleagues as conduit to ways of workplace support being inactive, reflecting passive or absent approaches to discussion with colleagues that closes off possibilities for workplace support to ALiP. However, Pat and Ronnie's experiences also revealed that talking and discussing with workplace colleagues as conduit to workplace support may actively open possibilities for workplace support to ALiP:

'... bringing all the literature reviews and stuff together. So, as I've been doing that and I've been bringing that back to the team and to senior managers. Also having that discussion at a higher up level of senior management, as well, like nursing directors about how potentially this could have a bigger impact on not only on ... services within which I work but also like That's been received quite positively as well which I didn't expect, given the initial kind of resistance. So, that's been quite good, and I've been given quite a bit of encouragement to kind of carry on with the line of kind of thinking and the line of studying that I'm kind of going in.' (Pat)

'... I'd discussed the reflective piece with ..., one of my colleagues. So, that was quite good because I'd actually discussed it with her before then coming home to then go on to write about it because it was a reflective piece. So, I felt better about it, I don't know (...). It felt like it was like a genuine (...), a genuine action, I don't know how you would describe it. I felt that she kind of reinforced to me that what I was writing was correct. ...

we'd both obviously discussed it at work and then said in hindsight this, that or whatever. So, she kind of reinforced to me that yeah this is a good thing to do, and it would be a good thing to write about.' (Ronnie)

Pat and Ronnie's experiences of talking and discussing with the showing of encouragement and reinforcement from workplace colleagues called to thinking the concept of genuine discourse. Heidegger (1993a/1927) positions the notion of genuinely being-there in discourse or conversation in a way that what is said comes from what is being talked about. This surfaced meaning about ways of PGNS and workplace colleagues being there together in conversation, actively listening and being present to discuss opportunities for workplace support to ALiP. Furthermore, this brought curiosity how the ways of such conversations with colleagues may influence how PGNS feel they are faring or getting along in being supported by colleagues and being a PGNS.

The participants' experiences of continuing with thinking and reflection following discussion or encouragement being with workplace colleagues also illuminated a potential unintentional assumption of the research question. Reflexively, I considered whether workplace support to ALiP had unintentionally been assumed as being one directional from PGNE to practice. Subsequently, revealing a phenomenon of a potentially dynamic interwoven spiral of workplace support for PGNS to ALiP, continuing towards further workplace support to ALiP as well as ALiP returning to contribute to PGNE and learning.

Pat and Ronnie's further experiences of being with workplace colleagues, reflexively drew me to the previous concept of the asking and knowing of workplace support by PGNS and colleagues to deepen interpretation:

'So, with regards to implementing any learning that's not gonna go ahead because I'm not obviously gonna start implementing strategies on ... when the manager or the deputy manager don't know why I'm trying to do things (...).' (Ronnie)

'... just the resistance I suppose to change that I have kind of mentioned before, which was particularly challenging, especially initially because I think it was just always seen as this is something that I wanted to do. An, it was more personal to me and wouldn't really have a particular impact on the team. That it wasn't clear, the team weren't clear about how my learning could then influence both their practice, and the overall kind of ethos of the team, and the culture of the team.' (Pat)

Through the showing of workplace managers and colleagues not knowing or having clarity about the doing of PGNE to ALiP. I became attuned to a potential 'mood' about how PGNS may be 'faring' in being with workplace colleagues if there is an unknowing about PGNE or being a PGNS, and whether this may influence opportunities for workplace support to ALiP. This evoked curiosity about relational aspects and

roles between PGNS, workplace colleagues and managers in the knowing of PGNE potentially influencing the doing of ALiP.

Consideration of Heidegger's (1962/1927) notion of *'idle talk'* and *'indifferent'* mode previously illuminated that absent or passive approaches to asking, talking or discussion with workplace managers and colleagues may inhibit or close possibilities for PGNS to ALiP. However, Pat and Ronnie's experiences reflexively challenged my previous thinking to consider the further mode of *'authenticity'*. Heidegger (1993a/1927) positions *'authenticity'* and *'inauthenticity'* as modes of *'Being'*:

And because Dasein is in each case essentially its own possibility it can, in its very Being, 'choose' itself and win itself; it can also lose itself and never win itself; or only 'seem' to do so. But only in so far as it is essentially something which can be authentic – that is, something of its own – can it have lost itself and not yet won itself. (Heidegger, 1962/1927, p. 68)

Furthermore, *'authenticity'* may be unconscious with *'inauthenticity'* being influenced by busy, interesting or enjoyable experiences (Heidegger, 1962/1927). However, through *'breakdown'* of taken-for-granted aspects and calls to consciousness or thinking, an *'authentic'* self-mode of existence, of freedom and possibilities may also exist (Dibley *et al.*, 2020). Dwelling with Pat and Ronnie's experiences, called to thinking a breakdown of learning revealing from the relational experience of others not knowing about the context of ALiP. Particularly, with *'authenticity'* being assumed to exist within a complex interplay of situational, temporal and relational aspects of *'being-with-others'* (Heidegger, 1962/1927; Dibley *et al.*, 2020).

However, Heidegger (1962/1927) also positioned these modes with reference to 'mineness', that an individual can only give themselves their authentic self through choosing their own possibilities, rather than *'authenticity'* being something that can be given to others (Dibley *et al.*, 2020). Subsequently, Pat and Ronnie's experiences also surfaced meaning about PGNS conscious awareness of their own ways of being with workplace colleagues and their choices in talking about the context of applying PGNE to practice to create opportunities for workplace support to ALiP.

7.5.2 Being with resistance

Participants' experiences of workplace support to ALiP also showed being with resistance in the workplace. Pat's experience being set within the context of the challenges of workplace support to ALiP:

'Probably, more recently, when I was clear about what focus I wanted the remainder of the postgraduate to take towards Initially when I was asking my senior managers about who I should approach, who I should kind of discuss this with, they were quite resistant and quite reluctant to actually (...) lead me in the direction that I needed to go in.'

Because they kind of felt that One I wouldn't be listened to, and they also felt that er, the, people, the kind of people further up, the higher up people that I would need to go to wouldn't have the time to listen to me, wouldn't really have the interest, they've got other stuff going on and actually I would need to maybe rethink about whether or not I actually wanted to go down that route. Because it could change their perception of me, and I didn't ... they didn't want me to be perceived negatively at a more senior level as somebody who just came up with all these great ideas and didn't back it up kind of thing. So, that was really changing to actually put my point across and say well actually no I do have evidence to back up what I'm suggesting. So, that was really challenging to get them to kind of understand that and back me up on that. And when I did put the first email out to the senior managers saying this is what I'm kind of thinking could I meet up and chat. That was actually received quite favorably, which I think made the senior managers within my own team think differently. But ... initially, that was really, really difficult to actually just even get them on board, with that.' (Pat)

Pat's experience revealed a bringing together of the previously shown asking, discussing and understanding of workplace support with colleagues and ALiP, as evidence and bringing of ideas. Further illuminating curiosity previously raised about workplace colleagues understanding of PGNE and workplace support to ALiP.

However, I also became attuned to a tension of managers perceptions of higher workplace colleagues not having the time to listen or be interested. This attunement illuminated a way of manager's being active in response to the asking of workplace support however, this existing within a wider context of initial resistance and reluctance to lead Pat in future directions of workplace support. Pat's experience critically challenged interpretation beyond my previous call to Heidegger's (1996/1927) mode of '*indifference*', which illuminated managers being inactive in asking PGNS about their experiences or workplace support. Reflexively, Pat's experience challenged me to dwell further with the notion of '*solicitude*' and the alternative, positive, active mode of '*leap in*' assumed to:

... take the others' "care" away from him and put itself in his place in taking care, it can *leap in* for him. Concern takes over what is to be taken care of for the other This kind of concern which does the job and takes away "care" is, to a large extent, determinative for being with one another and pertains, for the most part, to our taking care of things at hand. (Heidegger, 1996/1927, p. 114)

To set context, Heidegger's (1996/1927) reference to '*care*' is from an ontological perspective and is assumed to relate to our whole '*temporality*' of '*Being*'. The structure of '*temporality*' assumed as '*thrownness*' (past), '*fallenness*' (present) and '*projection*' (future), and existential concerns (Heidegger, 1996/1927). The '*leap in*' mode is assumed to be a tacit one, that remains hidden or associated with an

'inauthentic' way of *'Being'* (Heidegger, 1996/1927). Dwelling with Pat's experience of initial resistance and reluctance by managers to lead future directions of workplace support within a tension of assumed higher workplace colleagues perceptions, illuminated the potential for workplace managers and colleagues to *'leap in'* and takeover *'care'* for PGNS. This surfaced meaning that in PGNS asking for workplace support, workplace colleagues may inhibit or close off opportunities (*'leap-in'*) for workplace support from a wider range of colleagues. Furthermore this may be influenced by assumptions about other colleagues situational contexts or perceptions of PGNS seeking workplace support to ALiP. This illuminated the complexities of PGNS asking for support in *'being-with'* others in the workplace. Further calling to thinking the significance of the ways of asking, discussing, and knowing about the context of workplace support to ALiP between PGNS and workplace colleagues.

In remaining open to possibilities in interpreting Pat's experiences, contrasting experiences of resistance revealed a *'temporality'* of PGNS being with resistance, in the context of workplace support to ALiP:

'Quite empowering I suppose, because I kind ..., at the beginning probably felt that I didn't have much of a voice, that I didn't really have much influence in about what was kind of going on. But I suppose now I feel a bit more (...) more relaxed about that. I feel a bit more like going forward, I don't feel as anxious about actually putting things across. Especially at that kind of higher level because I feel, because the initial feedback that I've got I suppose laterally has been a lot more positive than it was before. I now feel a bit better about actually proposing these changes going ahead, an about how better I've understood about how to actually formulate these changes. Rather than just saying oh I've got a great idea I'd love to put it forward. I've now got a better understanding and have been given loads of support as well about how to actually put, put these changes and ... into like a kind of format that actually senior managers will kind of listen to. So, yeah, so it's certainly, I feel more positive going forward, that with the changes that I'm proposing whilst they might not come to anything. You know depending on how the research goes at least it's been taken a bit more kind of seriously. So, it makes me feel better about going forward and knowing that I'm actually going in the right direction.' (Pat)

The showing of receiving feedback as part of workplace support significantly revealed a contrasting opening of possibilities for Pat in furthering learning, understanding, approaches and directions in going forward with ALiP. Reflexively, this orientated thinking towards the *'solicitude'* mode of *'leap in'* and the alternative mode of *'leap ahead'*, assumed with:

... there is the possibility of concern which does not so much leap in for the other as *leap ahead* of him, not in order to take "care" away from him, but to first give it back to him as such. (Heidegger, 1996/1927, p. 115)

Returning to Pat's experience evoked curiosity about a concept of the giving back (*'leap ahead'*) of workplace support by workplace colleagues. Pat's experience of feedback from colleagues illuminated a giving of empowerment, understanding and further workplace support to the PGNS to ALiP, through proposing and formulating potential changes to practice. This orientated thinking back to a dynamic interwoven spiral of workplace support for PGNS to ALiP continuing towards further opportunities for workplace support to ALiP.

Pat's experiences of being with resistance in the context of workplace support to ALiP, significantly illuminated the potential for colleague approaches to workplace support to open possibilities for PGNS to further learning, wider workplace support and ALiP. This understanding led to consideration of the connection between the Heideggerian modes of *'leap ahead'* and *'authenticity'* assumed as:

This concern which essentially pertains to authentic care; that is, the existence of the other, and not to a *what* which takes care of, helps the other to become transparent to himself *in his care and free for it.* (Heidegger, 1996/1927, p. 115)

Subsequently, these philosophical assumptions called to thinking previous curiosity about the authentic role of PGNS in the talking, discussing, knowing and understanding of being with workplace managers and colleagues in creating, choosing and opening opportunities for workplace support to ALiP. Revealing further insights into the situational aspects that may influence PGNS becoming part of the ways of workplace support to ALiP.

Pat's experience also revealed an acceptance that ALiP, as proposed changes to practice might not come to fruition, while acknowledging the context of such changes being taken seriously by workplace colleagues. This orientated thinking back to a potential *'temporality'* and situational aspects of PGNS being with resistance in the workplace, and workplace support to ALiP. Calling to thinking the philosophical assumption that:

'Everyday Being-with-one another maintains itself between the two extremes of positive solicitude – which leaps in and dominates, and that which leaps forth and liberates ...'
(Heidegger, 1962/1927, p. 159).

Subsequently, Pat's experience furthered thinking towards a potentially complex equilibrium and dynamic interplay in which ways of workplace support may range from *'leap in'* to *'leap ahead'*. Furthermore this may be influenced by relational aspects, approaches and ways of workplace support to ALiP between PGNS and colleagues. This illuminated a further area for pedagogical and research enquiry relating to potential co-creation of workplace support to ALiP between PGNS with workplace colleagues. Significantly illuminating the complex wider context of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP being influenced by changing, everyday temporal and situational experiences of being a PGNS, being with workplace colleagues and being in the workplace.

7.5.3 The being there of workplace support cultures and the could be possibilities

Shared meanings and connections relating to the being there or not being there of workplace support cultures showed through the participants' experiences of workplace support to ALiP. Particularly, through situational experiences of being a PGNS and being with colleagues in workplace contexts:

'There's staff that have been there for many years, an they've done things a certain way. So, why would they suddenly be listening to you and change that cause they've done this like this for ... odd years. So, it's not just procedures or whatever you're trying to change. It's, ... engrained (...) in some people that this is how we do it. So, you've got the whole workplace culture to deal with (...) ...' (Ronnie)

The showing of engrained workplace contexts and self-questioning about being listened to by workplace colleagues illuminated PGNS being situated within the socio-historic, 'everydayness' of 'Being' with colleagues in workplace cultures. Ronnie's experience called to thinking Heidegger's (1962/1927) notion of 'breakdown' and attunement to the ontological movement from absorbed to different ways of 'being-in-the-world'. Subsequently, evoking curiosity whether the experience of being a PGNS may attune or move PGNS from previously concealed or absorbed ways of 'Being' with workplace colleagues in practice, towards alternative ways of 'Being' with colleagues and seeking workplace support to ALiP. Subsequently, I was drawn to Pat's experience of workplace cultures and support to ALiP:

'So, as I say senior managers weren't really and still aren't really up on additional academic learning. Whilst they'll support people if they want to do additional training, they don't necessarily see it as something that's required in order to do the job effectively. And part of that I think is possibly because they are and have been nurses for such a long time. And they've been within the team for such a long time, and the senior management level hasn't changed significantly, probably in the last kind of like ... years. So, that whole culture that was there, is still there. So, I think it's really difficult to change that kind of mind set and that kind of culture of actually valuing the experiences of learning. And whilst they value students coming in terms of like undergraduate students and relish all of that aspect of it. They don't really kind of, have that same kind ... level of interest I suppose for postgraduate or future studies or any kind of like personal development in that respect (...).' (Pat)

Through Pat's experience of workplace culture, I became attuned to an ontological 'mood' relating to the experiences of being a PGNS, additional academic learning and further PGNE. This 'mood' orientated thinking to previous pedagogical assumptions relating to lifelong learning being an inherent, intrinsic part of an individual learner's being (C2). Reflexively, this called to thinking potentially concealed presuppositions about PGNE potentially being valued and part of continuing, professional lifelong

learning rather than additional learning. As well as revealing potential tensions associated with being a PGNS in workplace and learning cultures. Pat's experience of senior managers not being 'up-on' additional academic learning, further called to thinking the significance of the knowing and understanding of PGNE and workplace support for PGNS to ALiP between PGNS and workplace colleagues. Of further significance is that Pat's experience illuminated a significant area for further enquiry relating to professional perspectives and values within the workplace about the context of PGNE as part of professional, continuous or lifelong learning. Particularly, as these aspects may potentially influence workplace support for PGNS to ALiP.

Pat and Ronnie's experiences furthered curiosity about PGNS becoming attuned to workplace cultures and learning cultures, as part of the experience of being a PGNS, particularly through a questioning of workplace cultures. Such questioning revealed possibilities for PGNS experiencing a continuum from remaining situated within everyday, absorbed ways of being with colleagues and cultures, to moving towards alternative ways of being with colleagues and cultures. Furthermore, influencing opportunities for workplace support for PGNS to ALiP and potential pedagogical tensions between PG learners self-motivations and critical self-awareness of the professional responsibilities of applying learning, challenging and transforming practice and cultures (Peach, 2010).

Understanding PGNS being with workplace cultures, further revealed through Pat and Ronnie's experiences of the 'could be' possibilities of workplace support to ALiP, in being with colleagues:

'(...) Pretty disheartening to be honest with you, because I have lots of good ideas that have come from the courses that I've done. But it's pretty disheartening to think that you can change it and make things better on your shift but the minute you're not there is just gonna be ... go back to the ways it's always been.' (Ronnie)

'So, a bit deflating, a bit demotivating, an kind ... added to my anxiety I suppose about studying at a postgrad level. Thinking well how am I supposed to put this learning into practice if I'm gonna be met with resistance and actually what does that say about not just the team that I worked with but also the organisation as a whole, if it wasn't seen to be supporting staff who were obviously studying at that level, wanting to make these changes or propose these kind of changes. And if, if they were being kind of shut off at the very first hurdle then, what kind of How was that resistance going to be further on down the line as I kind of went through my postgrad studies. So, yeah, it kind, ... made me feel a bit uneasy I suppose. And also kind of made me kind of think about where I actually wanted to go in terms of my direction and where I felt I could better utilise my skills if you like' (Pat)

In seeking to deepen understanding of workplace support to ALiP in the context of being with workplace colleagues, resistance and cultures. I reflected on previous attunement to 'indifferent' and 'leap-in'

'solicitous' modes in 'being-with-others'. This led thinking to the philosophical notion of an 'authentic alliance' (Heidegger, 1996/1927, p. 115) or 'becoming *authentically* bound together' (Heidegger, 1962/1927, p. 159) as part of 'Being':

Concern proves to be constitutive of the being of Da-sein which, in accordance with its different possibilities, is bound up with its being toward the world taken care of and also with its authentic being toward itself. Being-with-one-another is based initially and often exclusively on what is taken care of together in such being. A being-with-one-another which arises from one's doing the same thing as someone else not only keeps for the most part within outer limits but enters the mode of distance and reserve. ... On the other hand, when they devote themselves to the same thing in common, their doing so is determined by their Da-sein, which has been stirred. This authentic alliance first makes possible the proper kind of objectivity which frees the other for himself in his freedom. (Heidegger, 1996/1927, p. 115)

Dwelling with this philosophical understanding and the participants' experiences illuminated a potential concept of a 'coming togetherness' or enhanced 'co-existence' of PGNS and colleagues within workplace cultures. Particularly, in the talking, listening, knowing and understanding of workplace support to ALiP between PGNS and colleagues within changing temporal, situational and relational contexts of the workplace and being a PGNS. The concept of a 'coming togetherness' also resonated with connections between the masters facet of autonomy; of PGNS having autonomy and responsibility for own learning and the facet of professionalism, PGNS being with professional communities and cultures (QAAHE, 2013).

However, the showing of workplace resistance and cultures in the context of workplace support for PGNS to ALiP brought attunement to PGNS potentially questioning self-being and being a PGNS with colleagues and workplace cultures. The participants' experiences of ALiP and awareness of the 'could be' possibilities for workplace support for PGNS to ALiP further illuminated complex situational, temporal, relational and socio-cultural aspects of being a PGNS influencing workplace support to ALiP. This offering called to thinking further research into these complex, interrelated areas to further understanding of supporting PGNS to ALiP to contribute to self-being, being with workplace colleagues and the development of workplace practices.

7.6 Temporal and situational being

Throughout the offerings the significance of temporal and situational contexts were revealed where relevant to the participants' experiences. Subsequently becoming a thread throughout the parts and

whole of the offerings which deepened contextual understanding of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP. This part offering further reveals the diverse, subjective temporal and situational contexts that may influence workplace support to ALiP.

7.6.1 Temporal and situational everydayness

Vic's experience showed a context of 'being put back into a place' of PGNE, which orientated my thinking to Heidegger's (1996/1927) complex concept of '*Dasein*' and the assumption of '*Dasein*', our way of '*Being*' is its future because of its past but also its past because of it is its future.

'But being sort of put back into that place of actually having to do that for a piece of course work, kind of just sort of brings back those skills that you've developed before, that you just haven't really used may be a bit more formally or properly for a while.' (Vic)

Reflexively, bringing these philosophical assumptions to interpretation of Vic's experience, revealed a potential interplay between the current situational context of being back in PGNE and bringing past academic skills to the current and future contexts of academic work, and ways of being a PGNS. This evoked thinking beyond an academic context, calling to question whether PGNS future skills and possibilities for ALiP may be influenced by past experiences and pre-existing skills relating to learning and ALiP within the everyday context of workplace practice. This furthered curiosity whether PGNS awareness of such previous experiences and skills relating to ALiP may potentially inform workplace support needs and future approaches to support to ALiP.

In returning to the workplace context and bringing together the part offerings. Previous offerings significantly called to thinking, the complex, dynamic and temporal '*everydayness*' which may influence PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP. Particularly, the potential for PGNS experiences of the '*everydayness*' of being with colleagues in the workplace influencing the availability of workplace support e.g. the giving, offering and allowance of time for PGNE and ALiP.

However, Ronnie's situational contexts of being in the workplace furthered insight into the '*everydayness*' of ALiP:

'... it's really a case of you can only do what you can do. ... So, with the best will in the world, you ..., you want to implement your learning, you want to do the best that you can do but a lot of the time due to things outwith your control. Lack of staff or someone taking not well or something that you have to then go and deal with. You don't always get the chance to maybe implement it as best you would like to.' (Ronnie)

In the showing of 'things being outwith' Ronnie's control, influencing opportunities for ALiP while being situated in the 'everydayness' of practice. I became attuned to a potential 'mood' between PGNS self-motivation towards ALiP and a potential acceptance of the everyday unpredictable or uncontrolled aspects of practice. This attunement also resonated with Taylor's experience of the 'everydayness' in the context of workplace and the pandemic:

'I think the senior management would be more approachable and kind of more support. We can also ask for more learning support and everything but it's because the demand for the service right now. So, probably they will not be able to provide anything for now so, ...' (Taylor)

Taylor's experience orientated my thinking to Heidegger's (1996/1927) assumption that 'temporality' is at the same time, 'thrownness' (past), 'fallenness' (present) and 'projection' (future). This understanding illuminated the past, present and future contexts within Taylor's experience, through a showing of being situated in practice in the now and a drawing on previous experiences. Of further significance is that Taylor's experience revealed a potential acceptance of the present 'everydayness' of workplace support, but also a projection towards changing future opportunities for workplace support from senior managerial colleagues.

Subsequently, interpretation of Ronnie and Taylor's experiences continued to illuminate shifting tensions and availability of workplace support to ALiP within the 'everydayness' of being a PGNS in the context of the workplace, and the wider pandemic. Further highlighting the complex, dynamic and temporal 'everydayness' which PGNS may experience in being with colleagues in the workplace which may potentially influence opportunities for workplace support for PGNS to ALiP.

7.6.2 Inbetween experiences of workplace support to ALiP

A further phenomenon that revealed from the participants' experiences of workplace support to ALiP, related to an 'inbetweenness', emerging from Pat and Ronnie's experiences of being situated between positive and not positive experiences of workplace support to ALiP:

'Just all in all, it's been ultimately a positive experience even though it's been challenging it has been a positive experience.' (Pat)

'So, I'm not gonna say it's not positive because obviously I'm trying to do the best I can when I'm there. But at the end of the day, it's not really negative either it's just kind of in the middle, it's just what you can do when you're there.' (Ronnie)

In seeking to further understand an 'inbetweenness' of Pat and Ronnie's experiences of workplace support to ALiP, further experiences revealed an academic or masters context of being a PGNS:

'Just having some people comment things like, well you know, you're only proposing this change because you're currently studying at ..., you know, do you really feel this or you're just putting your academic head on. So, yes, it wasn't all positive and it's still not all positive. There is still some people who are very resistant, which you're always going to find and that's absolutely fine I totally appreciate that.' (Pat)

'In fairness it's generally all been positive, that the other registered nurses that I work with have all been great. I've had all the comments of, oh you're a clever clogs and you're doing your masters (...). An, the various things (...) that you would get said to you. But they've all been very, very helpful for anything I've asked for. So, yeah that's been really positive, but I've had to take the oh yeah, ... doing ... masters comments (...).' (Ronnie)

The showing of workplace colleagues commenting and questioning academic and masters contexts of being a PGNS, further revealed participants' accepting or having to take comments and questioning about being a PGNS by workplace colleagues. In contrasting contexts of being with resistance and an inbetweenness of positive experiences of workplace support to ALiP.

Reflexively, I considered previous attunement to ontological 'moods' between PGNS self-motivation towards ALiP and a potential acceptance of the everyday unpredictable or uncontrolled aspects of workplace practice. Of significance is that Pat and Ronnie's experiences illuminated a further dynamic in the potential acceptance of being with colleagues in the 'everydayness' of workplace practice. This called to thinking professional perspectives and values within the workplace about the context of PGNE as part of professional, continuous or lifelong learning. Pat and Ronnie's experiences also raised significant questions about how PGNS may fare in the context of such acceptance, comments and questioning relating to PGNE. Furthermore, whether these aspects may influence being a PGNS in the workplace and opportunities for workplace support to ALiP. Ronnie's experiences also furthered curiosity about PGNS acceptance of the everydayness of practice and an emerging sense of PGNS experiencing an inbetweenness of willingness to ALiP and doing the best towards ALiP.

7.7 Reflexive thoughts in furthering understanding of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP

This offering furthered understanding and meaning about PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP. In coming to synthesising this offering, I felt challenged about bringing the offerings together within

this chapter. Dwelling with this I came to understand that this was influenced by not wanting to distract or diminish from the participants' experiences of the things that mattered to them. In bringing the offerings relating to workplace support to ALiP together, I was drawn to Gadamer's (2004/1960) discussion about the elements of theory of hermeneutic experience. Gadamer (2004/1960, p. 303) positions that we are not bound to one standpoint and that 'the horizon is, rather, something into which we move and that moves with us', changing for the person who is moving. This understanding surfaced a significant interwoven thread of the dynamic, temporal contexts of PGNS experiences of '*everydayness*' and complex socio-historic cultural ways of being continually moving through PGNS experiences of being a PGNS, being with workplace colleagues and ways of workplace support to ALiP. The offerings within this chapter also brought wider horizons of understanding and curiosity. I came to ease with the offerings being unbounded and supporting a movement towards further curiosity about the things that revealed, mattered and surfaced meaning about being a PGNS within the subsequent chapters. Furthermore, this supported my experience of a hermeneutic relationship with the text of the participants' experiences and analytical discussion always being in further conversation (Figal, 2002; Gadamer, 2004/1960).

Chapter 8 - Offering 3: Self-being

8.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the third offering relating to the revealing of self-being as part of the participants' PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP and expressions of shared connections identified through my interpretation of the participants' experiences (A16). Collectively, the part offerings of self-being, changing as a PGNS, affirming being a PGNS and temporality of being towards future possibilities illuminated a deeper understanding of the research question. Furthermore, the offerings surfaced meaning about a broader, holistic lived experience of being a PGNS beyond the experience of workplace support to ALiP.

Figure 17: Offering 3 parts of the whole – Self-being

8.2 Self-being and changing of being a PGNS

Vic's experience showed connections relating to ALiP in being with students (further discussed in C9.3) and being dually situated within university and workplace contexts:

'So, it's even me being able to use some of my additional knowledge from even basic things like being back at university ... Sometimes you step back a little bit once you've been a nurse for many years and as much as you want to support the students sometimes you're naturally out of touch with that just because you're not (...) continually learning or doing those sort of specific university courses. I've found that useful again, just being back at university doing that kind of thing, and being able to help them from a different perspective.' (Vic)

Vic's experience illuminated assumed temporal and situational aspects of self-being shown through changing self, professional, HEI and learning community contexts. Through Vic's experience I became attuned to a 'mood' of being 'out of touch' from stepping back from continual learning or HEI as a nurse over time. Furthermore, this surfacing through Vic's experience of returning to university as a PGNS. This called to thinking how PGNS may be 'faring' in the wider context of continual professional learning. Furthermore, this brought curiosity about PGNS sense of being in touch with learning and other learners through PGNE, and throughout the wider professional journey of being a nurse. Dwelling further with the 'mood' of being 'out of touch' and stepping back revealed a 'breakdown' relating to PGNS or nurses being disconnected or not doing continual learning within a HEI context. Subsequently, influencing a sense of being a PGNS and nurse in being current, useful and helpful in supporting student learning in the workplace. This called to thinking that although registered nurses must meet CPD requirements as part of NMC revalidation, the type and context of CPD may influence ways of nurses being in touch with others, particularly student nurses (NMC, 2019d). Reflexively, I was drawn to previous offering which surfaced meaning about workplace supporters with past or current experiences of being a PGNS bringing a different way of being a workplace supporter and supporting PGNS. Dwelling with Vic's experience furthered horizons of understanding about relational aspects of being a PGNS, particularly being with a diverse range of learners and nursing students situated within a HEI context, e.g. pre-registration nursing students. This surfaced that in being a PGNS, PGNS may also bring their past and continuing HEI experiences to bring a different way of being a supporter and a way of being 'in touch' with students situated within HEI and practice contexts as part of providing workplace support.

Pat and Taylor's experiences further resonated with Heidegger's (1962/1927) notion of 'temporality' shown through self-evaluation, questioning and realisations within past, present and projected contexts of being a PGNS:

'... I thought I was doing this automatically but I never kind of realised, my mind actually what I'm doing and not even thinking ... wasn't thinking about process. So, by going to

university, go to uni to do this module, ... enlightened me to steps and given me better understanding of the process and approach.’ (Taylor)

‘... in terms of like actual working practices, it’s made me (...) evaluate things better. So, whereas before I would have went with the norm, whether that was like the evidence base for particular therapeutic skills or whatever it may be. Before I wouldn’t have questioned them whereas now I am kind of maybe questioning more.’ (Pat)

Prior to undertaking my research, I considered complex pedagogical assumptions relating to a continuum of conscious to unconscious learning and inherent, intrinsic and informal ways of learning which I assumed might have influenced participants sharing experiences of workplace support to ALiP (Jarvis, 2010). However, Pat and Taylor’s experiences showing self-change from not questioning to questioning, previous automatic doing and not thinking to enlightenment, evaluation and understanding revealed possibilities of conscious ALiP and critical awareness of challenging and transforming self and workplace practices (Eraut, 2004; Jarvis, 2010; Peach, 2010; Webster-Wright, 2010) (A2-3). Pat’s experiences also called to question whether the workplace environment and PGNS being situated in the workplace could be considered as an aspect of workplace support. Particularly, in the context of the workplace being a potential conduit for critical self-awareness and opportunities to challenge and transform practice as a way of ALiP.

Pat and Taylor’s experiences also revealed a notion of bettering individual attributes and ways of being a PGNS through self-evaluation and understanding. In dwelling with Pat’s experiences of challenges and resistance to ALiP further attributes of self-adaptation and change revealed. Collectively, calling to thinking experiences of workplace support to ALiP creating possibilities for PGNS to come towards self-actualisation, change or aspects of transformative learning (Curren, 2007; Jarvis, 2010; Illeris, 2018):

‘I would have to kind of be a bit more creative about how I got these ideas across and had to kind of find allies that would work with me, an, help me kind of put that forward. I had to really kind of focus on my kind of leadership skills as well, and kind of adapt the way I worked I suppose and the way I spoke and communicated with people. So, that was quite a big challenge initially.’ (Pat)

The showing of Pat being creative and finding allies resonated with the PGNE and ALNP attributes of creatively addressing complex and unpredictable issues, having critical awareness and insight, and being autonomous (A2-3). This significantly illuminated the possibility of PGNS self-consciousness and critical awareness of workplace support to ALiP influencing PGNS being and becoming autonomous in creating their own opportunities to ALiP. Subsequently, Pat’s experiences surfaced the pedagogical assumption of application of learning being an individual, subjective experience through a transformative spiral of continuous lifelong learning influenced by complex and continually changing self, cultural and

socio-historic contexts of being with others (Knowles, Holton and Swanston, 2005; Jarvis, 2010; Webster and Wright, 2010; Cranton, 2016; Dyke, 2017):

'... I had to kind of re-evaluate (...) how I view things and how I place importance on things, but that same level of importance might not be the same for everybody. So, I had to kind of learn to change tactics and think right okay well how can I make this ... how can I put this across as something that's still important to me. But actually taking into and respecting the, the importance and the needs of the people that I'm trying to communicate this to.' (Pat)

In the showing of Pat self-evaluating and learning to change tactics, I became further attuned to a 'mood' of critical self-awareness which oriented thinking towards Heidegger's (1962/1927) modes of 'inauthenticity', 'authenticity', and the 'they':

The Self of everyday Dasein is the *they-self*, which we distinguish from the *authentic Self* - that is, from the Self which has been taken hold of in its own way ... As they-self, the particular Dasein has been *dispersed* into the 'they', and must first find itself. (Heidegger, 1962/1927, p. 167)

Heidegger's (1962/1927) modes illuminated the potential for transition from aspects of 'inauthenticity' assumed as passive acceptance of the collective norms and values of 'the they'; losing selfhood to an 'authentic' self-mode of 'Being'. Dwelling with Pat's experience revealed a conscious call to thinking about being a PGNS and being with others to influence self-change and opportunities for workplace support to ALiP. This deeper understanding surfaced meaning about PGNS consciously using self-evaluation, adaption and change as part of being a PGNS and being their own conduit to creating opportunities for change from contexts of self, being a PGNS and being in the workplace with colleagues.

In seeking further understanding I also returned to explore Jarvis' (2018) pedagogical perspectives of learning including Jarvis' theoretical development of transformation of sensations underpinned by learning from primary experiences and the transformation of the person through learning. This enquiry called to thinking Jarvis' (2018) pedagogical assumption that:

Fundamentally, it is the person who learns and it is the changed person who is the outcome of learning, although that changed person may cause several different social outcomes. (Jarvis, 2018, p. 18)

Jarvis (2018) focused on the transformation of the whole person through learning in social situations acknowledging a complex interplay of socially constructed experiences with emotions, thoughts, reflections and actions towards the changed person with more experience. The transformation of sensations process acknowledged a change from the person taking the life-world for granted towards a

movement to sensation and disjuncture; a conscious experience and sense of unknowing and questioning (Jarvis, 2018). Towards a process of potentially giving meaning to the sensation and a resolve of disjuncture which may then lead to practicing the resolution and taking the life-world for granted again (Jarvis, 2018). Subsequently this resonated with a potential movement from *'inauthenticity'* to *'authenticity'*. Returning to Pat's experiences with such philosophical and pedagogical understandings, illuminated PGNS coming to conscious questioning of previously taken for granted or absorbed ways of being and being in the workplace as part of self-change and transformation in being a PGNS.

Dwelling with Pat and Taylor's experiences and pedagogical literature also led me towards deeper philosophical consideration of Heidegger's (1962/1927) mode of *'authenticity'* within the context of self:

The Self of everyday Dasein is the *they-self*, which we distinguish from the *authentic Self* - that is, from the Self which has been taken hold of in its own way ... As they-self, the particular Dasein has been *dispersed* into the "they", and must first find itself If Dasein discovers the world in its own way ... and brings it close, if it discloses to itself its own authentic Being, then this discovery of the 'world' and this disclosure of Dasein are always accomplished as a clearing-away of concealments and obscurities, as a breaking up of the disguises with which Dasein bars its own way. (Heidegger, 1962/1927, p. 167)

This called to thinking PGNS experiences of critical self-awareness, evaluation or re-evaluation of self, being PGNS or professional creating possibilities for PGNS to come into a clearing. Subsequently, this surfaced meaning about being a PGNS and PGNS experiencing a clearing that provides space and time for thinking between and towards past, present and future possibilities of workplace support to ALiP and ALiP, as part of self, PGNS and professional being. Furthermore I was drawn to the concept of reflective practice being part of being a nurse and PGNS. This illuminated PGNS experiencing contemplative and transformative learning experiences as part of being a PGNS and being within PGNE (Barbezat and Bush, 2014; Jarvis, 2018; NMC, 2019a). Subsequently, bringing curiosity from a PGNE pedagogical perspective about the visibility and place of transformational learning experiences as part of PGNE curriculums and curriculum design. Furthermore, raising questions about how PGNS are supported within HEI and workplaces in experiencing transformational learning and self-evaluation.

8.3 Affirming being a PGNS

Following Ronnie sharing a specific experience of ALiP, a reinforcing of PG learning within the workplace context showed:

'So, I actually found it really positive, and I thought that just reinforces what we've been learning and what we've been looking at ...' (Ronnie)

Ronnie's experience revealed a coming towards a positive experience of learning and ALiP. However, I was drawn to Ronnie's positive experience reinforcing the experience of PG learning which called to thinking PGNS expectations of PGNE and ALiP. Reflexively, this led me to dwell with Pat's experiences of revalidation and knowing self through ALiP:

'... just in feeling really empowered, feeling motivated. Feeling quite kind of focused on what I'm doing, not just in terms of ..., my learning but like my future kind of career goals as well. So yeah, it's kind of revalidated everything that I knew within myself that I was capable of. So, it's kind of given me that bit of extra umph I suppose. Make me feel like right okay, I'm doing the right thing here and I'm definitely want to carry on with my studies.' (Pat)

Pat and Ronnie's experiences showed a sense of self-confirmation, validation and doing the right thing in relation to being a PGNS and PGNE learning. In considering the parts and whole of the PGNS experiences, my thinking was called to the previous offerings and participants' experiences that revealed a sense of self-questioning being a PGNS. This sense of self-questioning being revealed through PGNS being with resistance in the context of workplace support to ALiP, particularly Pat's experiences of being with resistance and learning to change tactics to ALiP (C7). I had previously become attuned to a 'mood' of PGNS being and becoming consciously and critically self-aware of adapting and changing as part of being a PGNS to create opportunities and ways to ALiP. Dwelling with Pat and Ronnie's further experiences, significantly called to thinking Heidegger's (1962/1927) assumptions that we are never free of or without 'mood' and that our 'being-in-the-world' with others is influenced by a constant interplay of our past, present and future. Reflexively, I became further attuned to a complex, shifting ontological 'mood' of PGNS being and becoming consciously and critically self-aware through self-questioning being with resistance, adapting and changing to coming to self-affirmation and validation of learning and being a PGNS. Furthermore, such movement towards self-affirmation and validation of being a PGNS may also create and open future possibilities for workplace support to ALiP from self and workplace colleagues.

In dwelling with Pat and Ronnie's experiences revealing a sense of self-validation being a PGNS, furthermore reinforcing PGNE learning and ALiP, I was also drawn to Mezirow's (2018) Transformational Learning Theory. In the later development of the theory, Mezirow (2018) acknowledged the need for learners to critically assess and validate assumptions supporting individual beliefs and expectations and that of others in the context of transformational learning. This pedagogical insight with Pat and Ronnie's experiences illuminated PGNS being with and coming to ways of critically assessing assumptions, beliefs and values relating to self, being a PGNS and being with workplace colleagues as part of transformational PGNE experiences. Furthermore, Pat and Ronnie's experiences of self-questioning,

confirmation or validation of being a PGNS and PGNE significantly surfaced curiosity about PGNS needs for affirmation and validation of PGNE from self, workplace colleagues and wider nursing communities.

8.4 Towards future possibilities

Throughout the part offerings participants' experiences brought insight into the opening, closing and future possibilities for workplace support to ALiP. However, my attunement to future possibilities revealed contexts beyond workplace support to ALiP towards broader self and professional learning and career contexts.

'... just in feeling really empowered, feeling motivated. Feeling quite kind of focused on what I'm doing, not just in terms of ..., my learning but like my future kind of career goals as well.' (Pat)

Pat's experiences of PG learning also revealed coming to a better self-understanding of roles and future possibilities for ALiP. Furthermore, illuminating a self-realisation of being a PGNS and a coming towards future possibilities within wider role, workplace and organisational contexts:

'... that's kind of given me better understanding of my role and of my kind of perspective and how can improve my service and my job.' (Taylor)

'(...) I think being postgraduate you realise more about the importance of improvement. And it's basically preparing you, I feel it's preparing you to then take a more managerial role, lead more people and bring about positive change and improvements to your workplace. (...), that's what I feel the MSc's preparing you for.' (Ronnie)

The showing of self-preparation through PGNE to lead people, bring about positive change and improvements resonated with previous participants' experience of coming into PGNE ('fore-havings') and illuminated potential expectations of being a PGNS, PGNE and ALiP. However, Ronnie and Taylor's experiences surfaced future opportunities for self, co-existing with professional and social responsibilities of applying PG attributes and learning to influence positive workplace change and improvements (Peach, 2010) (A3).

Pat's experiences also significantly revealed wider personal contexts of being a PGNS:

'... the level of motivation and self-determination, self-esteem that's kind of crossed over into my personal life as well. So, with that increase within my workplace it's kind of made me almost a bit more self-assured in my personal life as well. And has made me more kind of determined and more focused in my personal life actually through not be as anxious about certain situations, I suppose. To be a bit more kind of confident in own

abilities and my own thought processes as well. So, it's helped me kind of grow overall as a person not just within my professional level but within my own personal level as well.'

(Pat)

The showing of Pat's professional and personal self-growth resonated with previously assumed holistic, humanistic pedagogical perspectives and concepts of self (Curren, 2007; Jarvis, 2010). However, I was drawn to Jarvis' (2018) contemporary theoretical developments towards understanding the person – the learner and the concept of the unfinished person based on possibilities for more growth and experience remaining. Consideration of such possibilities further called to thinking Heidegger's (1962/1927) philosophical assumption that '*Dasein*' is always its possibility:

... any Dasein has, as Dasein, already projected itself: and as long as it is, it is projecting. As long as it is, Dasein always has understood itself and always will understand itself in terms of possibilities. (Heidegger, 1962/1927, p. 185)

Returning to Pat's experience and considering these pedagogical and philosophical assumptions, significantly illuminated the future possibilities that being a PGNS may bring to wider personal and professional growth. This surfaced meaning about holistically understanding PGNS experiences beyond being a PG learner to being a person experiencing wider personal and professional growth and transformation.

Chapter 9 - Offering 4: Inviting Curiosity

9.1 Introduction

This offering presents four part offerings underpinned by some of the questions and areas of curiosity that arose through my interpretation of the participants' experiences of workplace support to ALiP and expressions of shared connections across the data (A16).

Drawing upon Gadamer's (2004/1960) concept of horizons brought awareness to the offerings within this chapter expanding and opening up new horizons about what it means to be a PGNS. Subsequently, the questions raised from the participants' experiences of workplace support to ALiP brought a richness to understanding the research question. Reflexively, the offerings within this chapter also challenged and opened up my horizons of understanding beyond the specific focus of the research question to surface wider meaning about being a PGNS, professional and person within a co-constructed, socio-historic world with others.

Figure 18: Offering 4 parts and whole – Inviting curiosity

9.2 PGNS presencing

Interpretation of the participants' experiences of workplace support to ALiP evoked curiosity about the visibility and presence of PGNS to workplace colleagues. This curiosity revealed through my collective attunement to the participants' experiences of self-motivations in coming into PGNE, the concept of PGNE learning, and the asking and knowing of workplace support to ALiP by PGNS or colleagues across the offerings (C6-7).

Pat and Taylor's background experiences (*fore-havings*) of private motivations or personal reasons for coming into PGNE initially called to thinking whether such experiences may influence ways of being a PGNS being hidden or present to colleagues:

'It's actually purely my private kind a motivation to go for further education to kind of expand my knowledge.' (Taylor)

'And I think it's just that's something that's really important to me that even though I'm learning for my own personal reasons for learning and for my own career development. It's important for me to be able to pass that knowledge onto other people.' (Pat)

Considering ways of being known and present as a PGNS in the workplace orientated my thinking to the facets of mastersness and key characteristics of PGNE (A2-3). Subsequently, Pat and Taylor's experiences revealed a dynamic interplay of PGNS having autonomy and responsibility for their learning and professionalism, being with professional communities and cultures (QAAHE, 2013). This significantly illuminated PGNS presence coming from part of self and self-projected PGNS ways of being-with colleagues in workplace communities and cultures.

Curiosity about the presence of being a PGNS in the workplace also came from interpreting the participants' situational and temporal experiences of workplace support to ALiP during the COVID-19 pandemic. The participants' experiences revealed the postponement of learning, use of private time for learning and remote ways of working dissipating learning with workplace colleagues (C6-7).

Subsequently, this surfaced meaning that PGNS socio-historic, situational and temporal contexts of *'being-in-the-world'* may influence being present as PGNS within the workplace with colleagues, and opportunities for workplace support to demonstrate ALiP.

The participants' experiences of workplace support to ALiP further revealed a disturbance in being a PGNS in the *'everydayness'* of practice with workplace colleagues and cultures (Heidegger, 1962/1927). This illuminated PGNS coming to conscious awareness and acceptance of the unpredictable or uncontrollable socio-historic and cultural contexts of practice influencing being a PGNS, being with workplace support, colleagues and opportunities to ALiP. Such acceptance surfaced the absence of being a PGNS within the workplace, such absence potentially closing off possibilities to be present as a PGNS with workplace colleagues and support. Subsequently, illuminating that the absence of being a

PGNS in the workplace may then limit opportunities for PGNS to ALiP, if they are not being there as a PGNS. Previous offerings also illuminated the pragmatic to abstract ways in which PGNS may ALiP, bringing further complexity to the way in which PGNS may present or become visible in being a PGNS in the workplace and ALiP.

I was also reflexively drawn to Pat, Ronnie and Taylor's experiences of asking for workplace support and colleagues and managers knowing and understanding of PGNS and PGNE:

'My work, I never actually ask for any support from work or financial or educational. It's actually purely my private kind a motivation to go for further education to kind of expand my knowledge.' (Taylor)

'(...) Well, I genuinely think that anybody doing the course should have the backing of the manager. So's that you can then go back say to your line manager, this is what I've been learning, and this is how I feel we could use it in the workplace, or this is what we could do. And I obviously, am at a bit of a disadvantage because I don't have that (...).'
(Ronnie)

'... especially initially because I think it was just always seen as this is something that I wanted to do. An, it was more personal to me and wouldn't really have a particular impact on the team. That it wasn't clear, the team weren't clear about how my learning could then influence both their practice,' (Pat)

Pat, Ronnie and Taylor's experiences illuminated curiosity whether conversations between PGNS and colleagues about asking for workplace support or knowing the context of PGNE may influence PGNS being present as a PGNS with colleagues within the workplace. This called to question the absence of conversation to facilitate knowing and asking about being a PGNS, closing off opportunities and ways for PGNS to be there and be known to workplace colleagues as a PGNS and nurse. I also became curious how ontic and ontological perspectives may influence the complexity of this emerging question. Reflexively, this furthered curiosity whether PGNS and workplace supporters may be more aware and familiar with the asking and knowing of workplace support from ontic rather than ontological perspectives. Particularly, considering conversations focusing on objective, practical and material workplace support such as financial support, time for learning or providing resources or articles as opposed to a deeper individual, subjective conversations about what it means to be a PGNS. Subsequently, this curiosity led me to undertake a scope of associated contemporary literature to explore existing understanding about the concept of PGNS presence in the workplace and deepen insight into PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP. Using the CINAHL database and the key term PGNS I reviewed the 42 sources published between 2012-2022 to identify any specific literature relating to the concept of PGNS presence in the workplace. No specific literature was identified which may have been influenced by limited literature relating to the wider context of PGNS experiences, as

identified within the part one and two literature reviews. However, of significance is that the participants' lived experiences of workplace support to ALiP, opened a new horizon about what it means to be present as a PGNS with colleagues in the workplace. This called to thinking opportunities for future exploration and research into PGNS presence and professional identity in being, knowing and connecting with self and workplace colleagues, particularly from ontological perspectives of being (Diekelmann and Mendias, 2005).

9.3 PGNS in workplace supporting

In dwelling with Gadamer's (2004/1960) notion of a fusion of horizons throughout my interpretation of the participants' experiences, I continued to reflexively challenge my thinking by remaining open to new and expanding horizons of understanding about PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP. Subsequently, I became attuned to PGNS being and becoming workplace supporters to workplace colleagues and students. This was shown through Vic's experiences of ALiP in the context of student experiences and being back in the PGNE environment:

'So, it was quite nice to have that sort of fresh memory of doing things to be able to support them better, because I'm not sure if I could have given her as much as I would have wanted to if I wasn't doing the course.' (Vic)

Dwelling with Vic's experiences of supporting the learning of others called to thinking the NMC (2018e) Code of professional standards and behaviors which resurfaced the wider professional context that nurses must support the learning of students and colleagues. Subsequently, Vic's experience brought my awareness to a potentially narrow horizon of understanding influenced by my research question being specifically orientated to PGNS own experiences of workplace support. Vic's experience revealed an alternative interpretation or inversion of my research question from a focus on PGNS own experiences of workplace support to ALiP to PGNS experiences of learning to apply workplace support to or for others. Vic's experience illuminated a broader horizon of understanding that PGNS beliefs and values for learning may influence their experiences and expectations of workplace support to ALiP and extend to ways of workplace support for others. This surfaced meaning about being a PGNS and PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP being co-constructed and situated within a wider socio-cultural context of professional learning with others.

PGNS providing workplace support to others also showed through Pat's experiences of being with workplace colleagues:

'... the support from my colleagues Probably, the kind of discussions I've had with them was that they didn't feel that they would be supported or would be encouraged to go

forward to do additional study. And I suppose, that's kind of helped them move forward and actually ask that question. You know, well will I be supported, can I go ahead and do this, will you support me as a kind of team.' (Pat)

Pat's experience called to thinking a potential relational cycle of PGNS coming into PGNE, becoming a PGNS with experience of being a PGNS, to being a workplace supporter to other potential PGNS, learners or colleagues. Subsequently, this broadened insight into PGNS ways of being and becoming a workplace supporter for or to others, particularly in the context of supporting colleagues in asking about future possibilities of workplace support. Pat's experience illuminated colleagues being present with PGNS influencing the opening of conversations about the asking and knowing of workplace support for potential PGNS prior to becoming a PGNS. However, reflexively, this called to thinking PGNS experiences of the absence of conversation to facilitate knowing and asking of workplace support with others. I was drawn to the participants' experiences of active, passive and absent ways of asking about workplace support in being with workplace colleagues and managers within Chapter 7. Dwelling with Pat's experiences and Gadamer's (2004/1960) notion of effective historic consciousness surfaced meaning about PGNS past experiences of the asking and knowing of workplace support by colleagues becoming present through PGNS ways of being there with colleagues and supporting potential PGNS conversations about future workplace support. This further illuminated a larger, socio-historic context of PGNS being present with colleagues and workplace support being experienced by PGNS and workplace colleagues. Reflexively, in moving between the parts and the whole of the participants' lived experiences, I also became more attuned to Heidegger's (1962/1927) assumption that 'Dasein' is always already thrown and projecting as part of our 'Being' and that our 'being-in-the-world' is not separated from 'being-with' others. Furthermore, the participants past experience of the asking of workplace support by colleagues and managers, with PGNS experiences of supporting potential PGNS in their asking of workplace support, illuminated a complex interplay of the influence of past, present and future ways of 'Being' (Heidegger, 1962/1927).

However, Pat's further experiences revealed different insights of providing support for workplace colleagues:

'They've actually kind of come back and said to me that they had felt that it's made them re-evaluate their way of thinking and their way of working, and they on the back of that have also started relooking at stuff. So, it kind of gave me a bit of empowerment, thinking that well actually maybe at a lower level overall I'm meeting resistance to the changes that I want to propose, maybe in some ways, my staff seeing me doing this, they're then kind of rethinking the way that they work. And actually thinking, right okay well maybe if we did actually do a bit more kind of research into things, it would kind of influence practice going forward.' (Pat)

Pat's experience of workplace colleagues re-evaluating and rethinking ways of working called to thinking the experiences of colleagues in being with PGNS. Particularly, whether workplace colleagues' experiences of being with PGNS may influence coming to critical self-awareness or questioning about aspects of their professional self, workplace practices and opportunities to influence future workplace practices. This significantly illuminated the possibility of PGNS supporting the development of others to more widely influence future workplace practices. Pat's experience also revealed workplace colleagues noticing the 'doing' and ways of '*Being*' a PGNS in the workplace. This orientated thinking towards colleagues noticing PGNS 'doing' of PG learning in the workplace, potentially influencing ways of PGNS being presence and visible in the workplace.

The insights gained from this offering about PGNS being with workplace colleagues reflexively challenged my previous pedagogical understanding that, '... it is the person who learns and it is the changed person who is the outcome of learning' (Jarvis, 2018, p. 18). Pat's experiences surfaced that I had considered the person who learns and is the changed person as the outcome of learning to be narrowed to PGNS. However, Pat and Vic's experiences within this offering furthered my thinking beyond the person being a PGNS to workplace colleagues also being the persons who potentially learn and change as part of the experience and ways of being with PGNS in practice. This broader horizon of understanding illuminated a specific area for further enquiry into understanding workplace colleagues' experiences of being with PGNS particularly in the context of colleagues professional learning in practice and being part of workplace learning communities. Pat and Vic's experiences significantly illuminated PGNS being and becoming workplace supporters to others. This appeared to reveal through ontic outcomes and ways of doing, creating curiosity about a deeper ontological understanding of PGNS being a workplace support to other learners.

9.4 Challenging presuppositions of ALiP

Offerings presented in Chapter 7 relating to understanding PGNS ALiP called to thinking a potential continuum of ALiP and relational aspect of ALiP. However, Vic's experience invited further thinking about being with workplace colleagues in the application of learning across contexts of practice and PGNE:

'(...) some of my colleagues ... allowed me to have time to sort of debrief and speak about even just workload or things like that generally rather than just actually applying it to practice. But also some of the more set up sort of sessions to (...) kind of just support me really or look at my essays or to talk about different topics that I'm doing so, that then I can talk about how I can use that in practice.' (Vic)

Vic's experience evoked thinking towards a tidal-like movement between being with workplace support and application of learning. Particularly, possibilities for PGNS moving towards and into workplace support to bringing back self-learning and reflection in the context of PGNE prior to a further movement towards ALiP. This understanding challenged whether the research question could be interpreted by others to assume a singular, one directional context of workplace support to ALiP from PGNE rather than reflecting a potentially complex continuum and movement of application of learning between, within and across PGNE and practice.

Ronnie's experience also furthered thinking about the context of ALiP within the research question:

'I'm not there every shift, I'm not there to reinforce it, I'm not there, continually repeat why we would be doing something. So, a lot of the time you feel that it's wasted.' (Ronnie)

The showing of the PGNS being there or not being there in the doing of ALiP with colleagues, illuminated broader interpretation of the research question beyond self-ALiP. Of significance is that Ronnie's experience illuminated the context of ALiP extending beyond PGNS to workplace colleagues. Ronnie's experience also evoked curiosity about PGNS doing and being with workplace colleagues and the potential wasting of ALiP. This called to thinking future research opportunities to explore application of PGNS learning beyond self to workplace colleagues and PGNS experiences and expectations of workplace colleagues in the ALiP.

9.5 Professional being

While the research question focused on PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP, participants' experiences revealed a wider horizon of understanding relating to professional being. Vic's experience of application of learning revealed the potential for reflection as ALiP, also contributing to NMC (2019d) revalidation requirements:

'... sort of refreshing myself with reflection even for things like revalidation ...' (Vic)

In being attuned to experiences of wider professional being, I was drawn to Vic's experiences of time for PGNE being situated with self or workplace contexts:

'... it's hard to try and get the boundaries of (...), is this something that I should be doing in my own time or is this something I should be getting time out for.' (Vic)

Vic's experience revealed a self-questioning of time for being a PGNS, which evoked curiosity about the 'doing' of PGNE and time for being a PGNS becoming removed from the workplace. Subsequently this called to thinking a disturbance relating to being a PGNS in the context of practice:

‘So, it’s difficult to take out that time without either me feeling too guilty for taking it or well I just have to cancel it because (...) there’s more of a clinical need and I have to go in. So, that’s probably the most challenging thing.’ (Vic)

Initially my thinking was drawn back to the diverse routes that PGNS may take coming into PGNE. Particularly, the influence of some PGNE programmes that may have requirements for workplace support including practice learning and hours (NMC, 2004; 2018c). However, Vic’s experience of time being canceled due clinical need revealed wider temporal and situational experiences of PGNS being with colleagues and being in the workplace.

This surfaced potential tensions or disturbance that PGNS may experience between time and places to be a PGNS and nurse in clinical practice with workplace and professional roles and responsibilities. Vic’s experience also led me to dwell with previous offerings that surfaced PGNS coming to an acceptance of the ‘everydayness’ of being a PGNS in the workplace. Reflexively, this called to thinking an extended horizon of understanding relating to PGNS coming to an acceptance of ways of being a PGNS and nurse with professional roles and responsibilities within the uncertain, everydayness of practice. I became curious whether a separation or disconnect of being a PGNS and nurse was surfacing, potentially challenging my presuppositions about ongoing professional learning being inseparable and interwoven with being a nurse.

Furthermore, Pat’s experience showed a questioning by others that revealed academic or clinical ways of being a PGNS:

‘I’ve actually had some comments like well maybe you’ve taken on too much, maybe you need to kind of step back and ... decide what you want to do. Whether you want to do academic work or whether you want to do clinical work. ... It’s been quite a struggle to kind of go with that.’ (Pat)

Pat and Vic’s experiences also called to thinking a separation, ontic view and disconnect between academic and clinical types of work rather than ways of being a PGNS or nurse. This evoked further curiosity about being a PGNS within the wider socio-historic, cultural context of professional nursing practice and communities. This led me to consider Wenger-Traynor’s development from the concept of singular communities of practice towards landscapes of practice (Team BE, 2014). Subsequently, Pat’s experiences showing a doing of clinical or academic practice surfaced PGNS being within and across two separate communities of academic and clinical practice. Reflexively, I considered the four pillars of nursing practice; clinical practice, leadership and management, education or facilitation of learning, and research or evidence (NIPEC, 2016a; 2016b; CNOD, 2017b; NHS, 2017; NLIAH, no date). This brought to question my pre-understandings about a holistic construct of nursing practice founded upon all pillars. Furthermore, Heidegger’s (1962/1927) ontological focus on what it means to be,

challenged my thinking beyond the four pillars of practice as ontic characteristics or attributes of nursing practice to consider the complexities of what it means to be a nurse and PGNS. This surfaced my assumptions of academic and clinical ways of being a nurse, being interwoven as part of dynamic, evidence-based nursing practice, lifelong professional learning and development. Furthermore, Wenger-Traynor's development towards learning landscapes of practice reflected communities working across professional contexts towards social learning capability including the potential negotiation of identity between landscapes of practice (Team BE, 2014; McDonald and Cater-Steel, 2017). This further surfaced my assumptions about PGNS being within holistic, merging learning landscapes and communities unbound by academic or clinical contexts. Furthermore, such blended landscapes being assumed to be experienced as part of being a nurse, professional identity and broader horizons of practice, self and professional development. However, Pat and Vic's experiences called to thinking the previous questions raised about PGNS professional identity in the context of being, knowing and connecting with self and workplace colleagues. Pat and Vic's experience also surfaced further insight into professional being and identity in the context of workplace support to ALiP, and the wider landscape of the nursing profession.

Pat's experiences also revealed a wider cultural sense of professional being,

'I think it's really difficult to change that kind of mind set and that kind of culture of actually valuing the experiences of learning.' (Pat)

The showing of a culture of valuing learning experiences illuminated wider professional self-values and the values of others being experienced as part of being a PGNS and workplace support to ALiP. This led me to consider Mlambo, Silén and McGrath's (2021) meta-synthesis of 25 qualitative research articles focused on nurses' experiences of CPD and continuing education. The study identified five overarching and interwoven themes relating to; organisational culture, a supportive environment as a prerequisite, attitudes and motivations reflecting nurses' professional values, nurses' perceptions of barriers and impact on practice. Although, Mlambo, Silén and McGrath's (2021) study was set in the context of wider international CPD, values for professional development and shared understandings of CPD between nurses and managerial and organisational contexts were discussed as aspects potentially influencing experiences and conditions for CPD. These insights further illuminated experiences of being a PGNS being influenced by wider professional nursing learning cultures and values of workplace colleagues. Reflexively this called to thinking Heidegger's (1962/1927) assumptions of '*being-with*' which further illuminated that understanding what it means to be a PGNS is inseparable from understanding what it means to be a professional with others in the socio-historic cultural contexts and experiences of the workplace and nursing practice.

Chapter 10 – Bringing together the parts and whole: Discussion and synthesis of research

10.1 Reflexive considerations

This chapter reflexively considers my research question with a discussion and synthesis of the research offerings as parts and a whole to further understanding of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP at the time of writing. This approach aimed to support philosophical congruence with the hermeneutic spiral to demonstrate meaning and understanding that emerged from a constant interplay to and from the parts to the whole of the research offerings (Heidegger, 1962/1927; Gadamer, 2004/1960). To further demonstrate rigour and reflexivity within my research this chapter also presents methodological strengths and limitations, and a reflective synthesis of my experiences of being a professional doctorate student.

Based on my hermeneutic phenomenological research study, this chapter does not aim to provide a definitive answer to PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP or generalise the participants' experiences to all PGNS. Alternatively, this chapter aims to provide a relevant and credible synthesis of my interpretation of the participants' PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP whilst continuing to consider my *'fore-structures'* of understanding and hermeneutic phenomenological approach. This synthesis aims to be cognisant of the breadth, depth and significance of the things that mattered from the participants' experiences and interpretation of expressions of shared meanings and connections from their experiences to further illuminate meaning about being a PGNS.

This chapter continues to invite readers to consider the research offerings with their professional knowledge, to come to their own meaning of understanding PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP and consider transferability within the context of their relevant professional role (EoR: Actualisation). Collectively, Chapters 10 and 11 aim to demonstrate how the research offerings and my professional learning make a significant and original contribution to broadening horizons of understanding of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP and wider professional practice (UWS, 2019b).

10.2 Discussion and synthesis of research offerings

This section provides a discussion and synthesis of the research offerings presented in Chapters 6-9 to further understanding of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP at the time of writing. This section uses alternative headings to the four offerings presented in Figure 19 to demonstrate a reflexive

and methodologically aligned synthesis across the offerings in coming to understand PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP as a whole within the context of my study.

Figure 19: Bringing together the parts and the whole

10.2.1 Beyond becoming and being a PGNS

The participants' experiences surfaced meaning that understanding workplace support to ALiP extended beyond the context of being a PGNS to being a person. Particularly, relating to the participants' experiences of knowing self, coming into PGNE, transformation as a person and influencing workplace colleagues and practices. Gadamer's (2004/1960) notion of effective historic consciousness, surfaced meaning that PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP may be influenced by a wider interplay of already existing, inseparable socio-historic cultural contexts of learning and workplace support from self, colleagues, workplaces and wider professional nursing contexts before becoming, in becoming and being a PGNS. Background insight into the participants' experiences of coming into PGNE resonated with previously identified factors influencing nurses coming into PGNE (C3). Particularly, self-motivation

towards PGNE relating to personal and professional growth, the provision of best care and career advancement (Penman, Robinson and Cross, 2019). The participants' experiences also showed motivations and intentions to gain more knowledge, better knowledge and put knowledge into practice, which revealed an underpinning professional construct relating to professional knowledge as part of being a PGNS and registered nurse (NMC, 2018e) (C6).

In seeking to further understanding of PGNS experiences of ALiP within the context of my study, ALiP revealed through the participants' experiences of using research and evidence in practice. Particularly to provide opportunities to have a voice heard by workplace colleagues and potentially change, challenge or transform workplace practices and cultures. There also appeared to be a shared connection with some of the participants' motivations for coming into PGNE and ALiP. Of significance, is that these offerings illuminated possibilities for PGNS to actively live out personal, professional and PGNS motivations of influencing, challenging and changing workplace practices and cultures through ALiP. This offering resonated with PG characteristics associated with the application of critical research skills and attributes to creatively deal with complex issues to lead and contribute to developing and changing professional practice (A2-3). In addition to pedagogical assumptions that individual learners have critical awareness and responsibility for challenging and transforming practice and cultures influenced by subjective, self and social contexts (Peach, 2010; Webster-Wright, 2010; Penman, Robinson and Cross, 2019).

The offerings also revealed PGNS experiencing and being with diverse ways of workplace support and opportunities to ALiP. This resonated with Illingworth *et al.* (2013) and Millberg *et al.* (2014) studies which identified that some nursing students experienced inconsistent workplace support and limited opportunities to use acquired knowledge and skills in practice. However, in the context of my research, some participant experiences revealed the significance of being with genuine, authentic and encouraging ways of discussing and actioning workplace support with colleagues, as part of creating opportunities for PGNS to ALiP. Such as applying evidence and research skills to potentially influence changes in workplace practice. Furthermore, some participant experiences significantly revealed being with absent, passive or resistant ways of discussing or actioning workplace support with workplace colleagues, potentially closing or limiting opportunities to ALiP. Subsequently, this called to thinking the significance of engaging authentically in conversations to support open understanding and exploration of workplace support to ALiP between PGNS and workplace colleagues (McCormack *et al.*, 2021).

Heidegger's (1996/1927) notion of the 'everydayness' also illuminated the participants' experiences of being a PGNS within an everydayness of the workplace influencing opportunities of being with workplace support to ALiP. The everyday context of practice potentially influenced by being with workplace colleagues, needs and cultures, and wider situational and temporal aspects e.g. the pandemic and established ways of working. Therefore, the research offerings illuminated PGNS experiences of

workplace support to ALiP being with complex, relational, temporal and situational ways of being in everyday nursing practice. Further influencing possibilities and ways for PGNS to ALiP and contribute to changing, challenging or transforming aspects of practice.

Of further significance is that the participants' experiences of opportunities for workplace support to ALiP revealed PGNS being with disheartenment, demotivation, acceptance and empowerment relating to workplace support to ALiP (C7). Subsequently, some participant experiences revealed coming to self-awareness and questioning of previously concealed or absorbed ways of being a person, a PGNS and being with colleagues in workplace cultures and practice. This illuminated the possibility of PGNS experiencing dilemmas or disjuncture as part of assumed transformational aspects of learning influenced by experiences of workplace support to ALiP (Mezirow, 2000; Mezirow and Taylor, 2010; Jarvis, 2018). This also surfaced meaning about the transformational challenges and tensions that PGNS may experience between being and becoming autonomous and responsible to ALiP within their own sphere of influence and being with workplace colleagues, cultures and aspects of everyday practice that may create or inhibit opportunities for workplace support to ALiP (QAAHE, 2013).

Further interpretation of the participants' experiences, particularly experiences of being with resistance to ALiP revealed self-evaluation, adaptation and change as ways of being a PGNS and moving beyond such pedagogical or experiential disorientating dilemmas to self-create opportunities for workplace support and ALiP. Previously Richardson's (2013) and Millberg *et al.* (2014) studies identified PGNS seeking their own opportunities to use PGNE outcomes in practice in view of workplace barriers or lack of support. However, reflexively, Heidegger's (1962/1927) modes of '*inauthenticity*' and '*authenticity*' called to thinking PGNS moving from passive or unconscious acceptance of workplace cultures and approaches towards becoming and being consciously self-aware, applying critical ways of thinking and learning to challenge and transform ways of being with workplace practices.

This deeper understanding illuminated self-evaluation, adaptation and change as ways of being a PGNS, ALiP and part of PGNS experiencing transformative outcomes of PGNE. While this understanding presents a future opportunity to research broader outcomes of PGNE from theoretical transformative learning perspectives, such transformational outcomes may be assumed to be unconscious or hidden to the learner posing a potential challenge to further exploration. This deeper understanding also further revealed the complex situational, temporal and socio-cultural aspects of being a PGNS and being with workplace colleagues and cultures in the context of workplace support to ALiP. However, the offerings significantly highlighted PGNS becoming and being their own conduit in creating and opening possibilities for change and transformation across contexts of self-being, being a PGNS and within workplace practice.

10.2.2 Workplace support and supporting

In seeking to further understand PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP, Heidegger's (1962/1927) notion of '*readiness*' and '*ready-to-hand*' illuminated complex horizons of being a PGNS and being with workplace support. Heidegger (1962/1927) positioned something being '*ready-to-hand*' being missing or taken for granted to reveal or come to understanding of what it was '*ready-to-hand*' with. Initially, this led me to an ontic interpretation or focus on revealing defined things, human characteristics or attributes relating to workplace support such as workplace supporters providing articles or resources. The participants' experiences furthered insight into pragmatic and abstract ways in which workplace support may be available or experienced, including colleagues giving PGNS encouragement and time for PGNE. Furthermore, PGNS experiences of workplace support extended beyond workplace colleagues within the immediate workplace to wider practice contexts. This illuminated the possibility of workplace colleagues providing a supportive conduit for PGNS to engage with a wider range of senior managers, colleagues and networks to further opportunities for PGNS to share and apply learning and influence approaches to future practice.

Reflexively, Heidegger's (1996/1927) philosophical assumption that our '*Being*' in the world is always already one that is shared with others, furthered interpretation towards an ontological perspective of what it means to be a PGNS. Subsequently, interpretation of the participants' experiences revealed possibilities of PGNS being with pre-existing reciprocal relationships of workplace support before becoming a PGNS and in being a workplace colleague. Furthermore, dwelling with Gadamer's (2004/1960) effective historical consciousness revealed the '*fore-havings*' of colleagues influencing and being part of PGNS experiences of workplace support. While the participants' experiences showed that workplace colleagues with or without experiences of PGNE may be supportive of PGNS undertaking PGNE. Some of the participants' experiences revealed that workplace colleagues with experiences of PGNE, may offer different ways of PGNS being with workplace support through personal knowing and understanding of PGNE, being a PGNS and ALiP. The participants' experiences illuminated PGNS being with workplace support and supporting, being inseparable and interwoven with pre-existing and present socio-historic and cultural experiences of being with others. This surfaced meaning that experiences of being a PGNS with workplace support to ALiP may not be limited to or bounded by PGNS own socio-historic experiences or ways of being with workplace support.

Heidegger's (1996/1927) notions of '*everydayness*' and '*un-readiness-to-hand*' with the participants' experiences revealed everyday, temporal and situational experiences of being a PGNS mattering in the context of workplace to ALiP, being a PGNS and being with workplace colleagues. This illuminated PGNS being with workplace support constantly moving from being and becoming available or unavailable influenced by changing everyday workplace situations and needs, time to be a PGNS, be with colleagues and wider workplace support networks. Significantly, this further understanding called to

question PGNS being with the application of workplace support as a prerequisite prior to ALiP and application of workplace support being an essential part or conduit to opportunities for PGNS to ALiP.

This also called to thinking possibilities of PGNS being with diverse experiences of high support and high challenge within the workplace (Wilson and Devereux, 2014). Subsequently surfacing an area for further research into pedagogical perspectives associated with PGNS being with high challenge and high support across HEI and workplace contexts and the potential influence on PGNS experiences of ALiP.

10.2.3 Professional being

In exploring PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP wider offerings emerged relating to the asking and knowing of workplace support to ALiP and the presence of PGNS within the workplace.

The participants' experiences illuminated complex situational, relational and temporal aspects relating to the asking and knowing of workplace support by PGNS and colleagues. The participants' experiences called to question whether individual self-motivations and reasons for coming into PGNE may influence whether PGNS ask workplace colleagues for support. This surfaced how the background experiences (*'fore-havings'*) of PGNS coming into PGNE and approaches to asking workplace colleagues for support may create or close opportunities for workplace colleagues to provide support to PGNS to ALiP. The revealing of self-motivations for coming into PGNE, a privateness of being a PGNS and the absence of asking workplace colleagues for support significantly called to question, the visibility and presence of PGNS within the workplace. Particularly how being a PGNS is known to workplace colleagues and whether this aspect may influence PGNS and workplace colleagues' experiences, and opportunities for workplace support to ALiP.

It might be assumed that by PGNS and workplace colleagues not asking about workplace support opportunities for support to ALiP may become limited or inhibited. However, some participants' experiences revealed that through not asking or not being asked about workplace support by senior or managerial colleagues, alternative approaches may be created by PGNS seeking their own support opportunities from other colleagues within the immediate workplace or wider workplace communities.

The participants' experiences revealed insight that workplace colleagues ways of asking PGNS about workplace support may be influenced by previous attitudes or experiences of workplace support coming into PGNE. Particularly, as my interpretation illuminated that background experiences of being encouraged by workplace colleagues to undertake PGNE may influence experiences of colleagues actively offering or volunteering workplace support as opposed to PGNS needing to ask for workplace support. This subsequently called to thinking potential approaches to PGNS and workplace colleagues

co-initiating and co-creating opportunities to ask about workplace support as a conduit to supporting ALiP.

Subsequently the participants' experiences illuminated that background experiences (*'fore-havings'*) and relational aspects of *'being-with-others'* may influence approaches to asking about workplace support to ALiP by PGNS and workplace colleagues. Shared connections across the participants' experiences also illuminated the potential influence of wider contexts including approaches to discussing and actioning of workplace support to ALiP and complex situational, temporal, relational and socio-cultural aspects of being a PGNS in the workplace.

The revealing of participants questioning whether workplace colleagues know and understand why they are helping significantly raised curiosity about the understanding of PGNE and PGNS workplace support needs among colleagues. Particularly, if it is assumed that knowledge and understanding of these areas may support informed and effective approaches to workplace support to ALiP between PGNS and colleagues. Understanding the participants' experiences furthered insight as to whether this aspect may influence PGNS and colleague approaches to asking about workplace support and opportunities for authentic discussion between PGNS and colleagues about the provision of workplace support.

The participants' experiences also revealed potential challenges in taking practical or tangible things from PGNE to workplace practice. This called to thinking contrasting perspectives from taking practical or tangible things from PGNE resonating with ontic, material or functional perspectives to abstract PG student attributes and ontological attitudes associated with individual autonomy, creativity and critical approaches to complex professional issues (A2-3). Of significance, is whether such abstract PG attributes or ontological ways of being may influence how ALiP is understood or demonstrated by PGNS to workplace colleagues. Subsequently, bringing insight that the abstract nature of PG ALiP and being a PGNS may influence the complexity of conversations about workplace support and understanding how to provide workplace support feasibly and effectively for PGNS to ALiP. Potentially such abstract PG attributes or concealed ways of being may also influence PGNS presence or visibility in the everyday context of the workplace.

The participants' experiences of workplace support to ALiP also revealed a hidden notion underneath experiences of the allowance and giving of workplace support, particularly regarding time for learning. In the wider professional context, this evoked curiosity about a notion and sense of permissioning from PGNS and workplace colleagues in asking, allowing or giving workplace support. This called to thinking the potential influence of professional beliefs, values, background experiences and cultures associated with PGNE in the workplace. Some participants' experiences revealed self-questioning or tensions of taking time for PGNE within the everyday context of workplace practice; even though PGNS may be situated in encouraging and empowering contexts of workplace support. This illuminated a sense of some aspects of workplace support potentially being removed or separated from the workplace by

PGNS and colleagues, rather than being part of workplace practices or cultures. Furthermore, participants' experiences revealed the potential of being questioned by workplace colleagues about being a PGNS, and choices about being either clinical or academic. This evoked curiosity about the context of being a PGNS and PGNE within wider professional nursing practice and communities. Reflexively, these insights called to thinking the potential influence of recent NMC (2018b) standards requiring a minimum degree award for PRNE, alignment of ALNP with PG level of education and the complex situational and temporal aspects of everyday workplace practices (NIPEC, 2016a; CNOD, 2017b; NHS, 2017; NLIAH, no date).

Furthermore, the participants' experiences surfaced PGNS being situated between positive and not-positive experiences of workplace support to ALiP. Insights were gained into the complex relational, situational, temporal and cultural aspects that may uniquely and subjectively influence PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP. However, the possibility of PGNS experiencing an inbetweenness of workplace support to ALiP, brought awareness to whether such experiences may influence how PGNS may be doing or getting on in the wider context of PGNE and professional learning. Particularly as some participants' experiences illuminated PGNS coming to an acceptance of everyday aspects and workplace cultures. Furthermore, potentially limiting opportunities for workplace support to ALiP, to authentically questioning, challenging or seeking to change aspects of everyday workplace practices and cultures to create opportunities to ALiP.

The participants' experiences of self-questioning previously absorbed or taken for granted ways of being within the workplace and experiences of workplace support to ALiP. Subsequently illuminated PGNS being and becoming consciously and critically aware of applying PG learning to challenge or transform practice. Furthermore, revealing the potential for PGNS to apply abstract PGNS attributes such as self-evaluation to address complex and unpredictable issues to create opportunities for workplace support to ALiP (A2-3). The participants' experiences also revealed a conscious self-awareness of a better understanding of their role, opportunities for ALiP, and further possibilities within wider role and organisational contexts. Subsequently, PGNE and experiences of workplace support to ALiP may offer PGNS possibilities for transformational change, personal and professional development to influence workplace changes, future role development and the provision of workplace support for colleagues (Jarvis, 2018).

The participants' experiences also revealed the potential need for PGNS to seek validation and affirmation of being a PGNS and a sense of knowing that they are doing the right thing in undertaking PGNE beyond their own critical awareness of personal and professional transformation. Pedagogically, this may be influenced by the need to critically assess and validate assumptions to support PGNS beliefs and experiences as well as those of workplace colleagues (Mezirow, 2018).

In synthesising the offerings to further understanding of PGNS experience of workplace support to ALiP, a deeper understanding was gained into the complex relational, situational, temporal, socio-historic and cultural aspects that may uniquely and subjectively influence PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP within the everyday context of practice. Particularly bringing awareness to the wider influence of being a PGNS on self, professional contexts of being a PGNS and the everyday context of being with colleagues in the workplace to influence and create opportunities for ALiP.

10.2.4 The thread of practical wisdom

Discussion: Following the calling and thread

As a research student, I was aware of finding a balancing point between the final stage of interpretation and coming to an acceptance that interpretation in hermeneutic phenomenological research is never complete (Smythe and Spence, 2023). In seeking to find this point, I sensed something still concealed and mattering from the participants' experiences of workplace support to ALiP. The part offerings that kept calling me to further thinking related to PGNS experiences of:

- ALiP as having evidence and research in practice.
- The socio-cultural everydayness of the workplace and disorientating dilemmas influencing self-evaluation and growth.
- The significance of workplace supporters with socio-historic experiences of PGNE.

Furthermore, I was still curious about the presence of being a PGNS to self and colleagues within the workplace. Sensing something calling and mattering, I continued to follow the flow of the offerings and hermeneutic conversations, although uncertain where it would lead (Dunne, 1993). I also returned to a conference poster that I developed during the early stage of my professional doctorate. The poster positioned my initial research topic as potentially contributing to bridging and connecting learning from academic contexts to nursing practice. Subsequently, this called me to question whether there could be a concealed bridge, meaning or thread between these experiences. This evoked a feeling of something more ontological still lying underneath and between these areas of curiosity rather than a focus on ontic aspects of workplace support to ALiP.

ALiP as having evidence and research in practice

In bringing together the parts and the whole, the offerings revealed participants' experiences of having and using evidence and research to create opportunities to have a heard voice to challenge, change or transform workplace cultures and practice. In considering the whole, 'application' of learning became

illuminated as an active process of PGNS having and using understanding of evidence and research to individually act and influence wider workplace practices. I found myself dwelling with a notion of PGNS actively building internal and external connecting bridges to move forward with applying learning in practice in varied ways for different means. Subsequently, I was becoming drawn to assumed modes of knowledge associated with phronesis.

The philosophical work of Aristotle (1976) is considered a seminal influence in the historic development of phronesis set within assumed modes of knowledge. Aristotle positioned that scientific knowledge (episteme) is a necessary mode of knowledge focused on knowing that or knowing why (Aristotle, 1976; Grint, 2007). Furthermore, it is assumed that objects of scientific knowledge are capable of being demonstrated, taught and learnt (Aristotle, 1976; Grint, 2007). Contrastingly, art or technical skills knowledge (techne) is focused on knowing how, and the craft that can be produced or made by a producer (Aristotle, 1976; Stenberg and Maaranen, 2022). Phronesis is assumed to be grounded within both episteme and techne modes of knowledge, as a practical intellectual virtue (Aristotle, 1976). Furthermore, Aristotle (1976) positioned that phronesis cannot exclusively be grounded in scientific knowledge due to variability of deliberation and actions. However, phronesis is neither purely techne due to the difference between production and action. Production in the context of techne is assumed to have an end other than itself, whereas phronesis is associated with action that has the end of doing well. The term 'phronimos' is also grounded within the Aristotelian notion of phronesis. The translation of the term phronimos being assumed to relate to a prudent or practically wise person and their ability to deliberate and action towards a good life for themselves and others (Aristotle, 1976).

I felt it was important to acknowledge the philosophical Aristotelian roots and terms in coming to explore the notion of phronesis surfacing within my research. However, I was becoming increasingly aware of the vast philosophical depth of Aristotle's (1976) modes of knowledge, phronesis and phronimos from intellectual, moral and ethical perspectives. I was also aware of the breadth and complexity of philosophical critiques, interpretations and development of Aristotle's (1976) notion of phronesis by further philosophers such as Hannah Arendt, Hans-George Gadamer and Jürgen Habermas (Dunne, 1993). Gadamer's (2004/1960) notion of effective historicity brought my awareness to drawing upon the Aristotelian notion of phronesis and subsequent philosophical interpretations set within diverse socio-historic, cultures and times from that of my research. Similarly, resonating with my positioning of Heidegger's (1962/1927) work and Heideggerian approaches within the contemporary, present context of my research. Reflexively, this guided my exploration into the notion of phronesis towards contemporary literature and perspectives.

The term phronesis is commonly translated or used interchangeably with practical wisdom, prudence or practical rationality (Aristotle, 1976; Sellman, 2012). Sellman (2012) positioned a preference towards the term practical wisdom based on phronesis extending beyond reasoning to being a practical virtue

associated with phronimos. Kinsella and Pitman (2012) also highlight that rationality alone may not lead to phronetic action and the importance of lived experiences in practice. Therefore, from a contemporary perspective, phronesis may encompass moral and intellectual judgments as well as being a virtue embodied in social practice and complex interactions (Ellett, 2012; Kinsella and Pitman, 2012). Reflexively, these contemporary perspectives called to thinking the underpinning ontological assumptions of PGNS being in a socio-historic world inseparable from '*being-with-others*' (Heidegger, 1996/1927). Subsequently, based on these contemporary perspectives I decided to refer to the term practical wisdom when exploring what might be surfacing about this notion in bringing together the parts of my research. However, the terms phronesis and prudence are also used interchangeable within my discussion to reflect the position of an author's work, historic literature or context relating to phronesis. Furthermore, debates also exist relating to the Aristotelian notion of phronesis and action towards rightness, goodness, living well and human good and the meaning of these terms to current times (Aristotle, 1976). Within the context of contemporary professional practice, Sellman (2012) positions actions with reference to being towards human betterment. Setting the context of phronesis and action towards human betterment within my thesis was also assumed to align to aspects of my professional values, code of practice (NMC, 2018e) and research aims as opposed to a focus on rightness.

Following on from my initial exploration of phronesis from Aristotelian and contemporary perspectives, I returned to dwell with the notion of PGNS actively building internal and external connecting bridges to move forward with ALiP in varied ways for different means. Dunne's (1993) philosophical conversation study of Aristotle's notion of phronesis evoked further thinking about the *techne* mode of knowledge and PGNS experiences of ALiP. The *techne* mode of knowledge assumes production involving the maker objectively and impersonally bringing a product to an end or to the achievement of the final product (Aristotle, 1976; Dunne, 1993). In contrast, phronesis is concerned with a person's own actions relating to living well or human betterment (Aristotle, 1976; Dunne, 1993; Sellman, 2012). Furthermore, such actions are assumed to be bound by an interdependent relationship of being with others (Dunne, 1993). This surfaced meaning about PGNS experiences of ALiP not being bound by PGNS individual objectives focused on ontic, end products of ALiP or purely *techne* outcomes of knowing how. Consideration of phronesis as assumed moral actions with others towards human betterment, illuminated broader possibilities for PGNS and workplace supporters to engage, explore and action what it means to live well or better within their interdependent relationship of support to ALiP. Reflexively, this also continued to highlight PGNS experiences of ALiP extending and being interdependent and relational in being with workplace colleagues, and the socio-historic, cultural contexts of being a PGNS in practice.

Understanding Aristotle's (1976) notions of *techne*, phronesis and *episteme* also evoked curiosity about a potential disconnect or separation between PGNS experiences of having evidence and research, self-reflection, thinking, and analysis as ALiP. Aristotle (1976) positioned that prudence (phronesis, practical wisdom) relates to a true state of reasoned and capable of action for human good. Considering

phronesis within contemporary professional practice, Kinsella and Pitman (2012) argue that thinking about action is not enough and that phronetic action is required. Furthermore, Kristjánsson *et al.* (2021) position phronesis as a virtue that operates within the sphere of praxis action. Praxis being assumed as the thinking about action that is focused on doing rather than making (techne) (Kristjánsson *et al.*, 2021). Kinsella and Pitman (2012) suggest that professionals in everyday practice may need to decide actions within a complex sphere of uncertainty and certainty, drawing upon the assumed certainty of evidence-based practice. Reflexively, these perspectives brought awareness to why I may be grappling with a disconnect and a sense of something missing between the participants' experiences of having evidence and research to create opportunities to have a heard voice to challenge, change or transform workplace cultures and practice.

Significantly, this understanding led me to surface practical wisdom being a concealed notion lying underneath PGNS experiences of ALiP and an unconscious or forgotten part of being a PGNS. The notion of practical wisdom illuminated PGNS potentially being with unseen, complex moral judgements, thinking and decisions providing a connecting bridge between PGNS having evidence and research to living out professional and personal motivations and actions towards change, challenge or transform of workplace practices and cultures. Further surfacing the lived experience of being a PGNS, being grounded by individual practical wisdom bound by praxis and being with others. Suddenly it was as if a bright light had been switched on, magnifying a tiny shard of ice as part of a vast, surfaced iceberg. The light illuminating interconnected fragments between practical wisdom, praxis and the curious parts of my research offerings that I felt had been fragmented. In considering the notions of phronesis and praxis threads started to surface and link between the previously identified areas of curiosity.

Threads between everydayness, disorientating dilemmas, self-evaluation and growth

The notion of practical wisdom called to thinking something more surfacing from PGNS accepting the everydayness of practice and the participants' experiences of an in betweenness of workplace support to ALiP. Aristotle (1976) positioned that a person with practical wisdom discovers and chooses the 'mean' between extremes of excess and deficiency to what is right or best to live well. Aristotle's (1976) use of the term the 'mean' is different from statistical use of the term and set within complex philosophical and socio-historic interpretation and critique of phronesis. However, this furthered my thinking towards PGNS internal and external sense of self trying to discover, choose or influence a point of harmony relating to in-between experiences of workplace support to ALiP. Furthermore, extending to situations in which PGNS may experience deliberation between personal and professional motivations, thinking, actions and the realities of living out their best to ALiP. Burbules (2019) suggests that experiences in which people may become stuck, fosters attitudes towards tolerating uncertainty and adapting to circumstances. Dwelling with the notion of practical wisdom, it is assumed that the wise person living

through uncertain situations strives for what is best, with a willingness to confront and learn from the consequences (Kemmis, 2012). Furthermore, Sellman (2012) draws upon the notion of 'professional phronesis' requiring the uncertainties, complexities and aporias of practice to be embraced rather than being unacknowledged. However, Sellman (2012) positions the notion of 'professional phronesis' as different from phronesis in everyday life. Reflexively, I was aware of the participants' experiences within my research becoming unbound by being a PGNS and professional to influencing wider experiences of self and personal growth.

I returned to dwell with the call of something more surfacing from PGNS accepting the everydayness of practice and experiences of an in betweenness of workplace support to ALiP with these emerging perspectives of practical wisdom. Of significance is that a broader horizon of understanding illuminated beyond PGNS being with a sense of giving up or accepting the everyday uncontrolled or uncertain aspects of practice influencing workplace support to ALiP. The notion of practical wisdom surfaced PGNS being internally and externally in between complex moral workplace dilemmas and responsibilities, and a personal and professional willingness to actively act and to do the best towards ALiP. This meaning also brought curiosity to further areas of research enquiry relating to what it means to PGNS to live out the best or become the best through the experience of PGNS and ALiP.

Subsequently, this extended my thinking beyond a perspective of practical wisdom involving the willingness of an individual person to stand behind their actions and take moral responsibility. Kemmis (2012) suggests that individuals are not the sole authors of their actions or the practical situations in which they may find themselves. Reflexively, leading me to Gadamer's (2004/1960) discussion about the hermeneutic relevance of Aristotle and the notion of phronesis and moral knowledge. Gadamer (2004/1960) positioned that a person with understanding does not stand apart from others but thinks along with others. Gadamer's (2004/1960) translated text relates to an 'insightful person' however, significantly Gadamer (2004/1960) drew upon the insightful person being prepared to consider the situation of another person. Within contemporary literature, phronesis is also positioned as an individual's preparedness to deliberate a situation in different ways or already available ways of understanding from the perspectives of others and self (Kemmis, 2012; Jenkins, Kinsella and DeLuca, 2018). This surfaced further meaning concealed underneath the participants' experiences of an in betweenness of workplace support to ALiP and accepting of the everydayness of practice.

Subsequently, illuminating the potential for PGNS developing practical wisdom in coming to an understanding of workplace situations, actions, responsibilities and consequences, as part of the being and becoming a PGNS in practice. Furthermore, highlighting the ontological assumption that our individual being in the world is inseparable from the socio-historic contexts of being with others and a complex interplay of past, present and future experiences (Heidegger, 1996/1927; Gadamer, 2004/1960).

This led me to also contemplate whether there was something further to surface from the participants' experiences of coming to consciously question taken for granted or absorbed ways of being leading to self-evaluation, change and transformation as a PGNS and person. Dwelling with the notion of phronesis, it is assumed that a wise person develops perceptual acuity to re-evaluate unfolding situations (Jenkins, Kinsella and DeLuca, 2018). Tiberius and Swartwood (2011) suggest that a wise person's actions may also be guided by their values and influence refinement of values. Significantly, Kinsella (2012) also suggests that practitioners coming from a place of practical wisdom contemplate and examine taken-for-granted aspects of practice. However, Kinsella (2012) positions that as part of phronetic judgement a practitioner oriented towards practical wisdom and justice also engages in the transformative potential of the situation. This surfaced meaning about PGNS re-evaluation of self being part of a broader horizon of PGNS developing practical wisdom. Furthermore, illuminating the potential for PGNS lived experiences of disorientating dilemmas influencing being and becoming a practically wise practitioner, PGNS and person. This furthered insight into PGNS re-evaluation of self being part of a complex interplay of evaluating morals and values and creating possibilities to re-evaluate or refine personal and professional values while also considering the perspectives of others.

Dwelling with Kinsella's (2012) notion of a transformative potential and the possibility for PGNS developing practical wisdom as part of coming to an understanding of workplace situations and colleagues. Furthered insight into PGNS experiences being situated within part of a complex interplay of evaluating and re-evaluating morals and values from the perspective of self and others. This called to thinking the potential for disorientating dilemmas to also create transformative opportunities beyond self to workplace colleagues.

The research offerings also revealed reflection as part of PGNS coming to evaluate or question being a PGNS and ALiP. Sellman (2012) suggests that phronimos requires critical self-reflection to be valued. Reflection may also be associated with critically disrupting the flow of thinking to consider what happens next (Frank, 2012). However, Grint (2011) argues that phronesis requires more than reflection for phronesis to be grounded in the process of thinking and the doing of actions in practice (praxis). Subsequently, this led to curiosity about the processes of thinking and acting as part of PGNS experiences of reflection, disorientating dilemmas and evaluation of self.

I found myself being drawn to the notion of reflexivity as opposed to reflection. Jenkins, Kinsella and DeLuca (2018) propose that reflexivity as part of phronesis offers a place for practitioners to critically deliberate, examine and explore beliefs, values and pre-understandings within the sphere of nursing practice. Further suggesting a place of reflexivity provides an opportunity to pay attention to the everydayness of practice that can be oppressive (Jenkins, Kinsella and DeLuca, 2018). Initially, this drew me to a deepening insight of the active, reflexive thinking processes that may be invisible (or unseen) as part of PGNS experiences of questioning or re-evaluating being PGNS. Furthermore, such

reflexivity may potentially be concealed by PGNS experiences of disheartenment, demotivation, resistance or acceptance of the everydayness of practice. However, the everydayness of practice may not always be experienced as one of oppression. Particularly, considering the offerings of PGNS experiences being between positive and not so positive experiences of workplace support and ALiP.

Jenkins, Kinsella and DeLuca's (2018) concept of a reflexive place furthered my thinking towards Heidegger's (1962/1927) notion of coming into a clearing. I found myself being drawn to the offerings relating to PGNS experiencing a clearing providing space and time for thinking between past, present and future possibilities of workplace support to ALiP. Heidegger (1962/1927) proposed that a person must clear away concealments in order to not block or prevent the way to discovering '*authentic Self-being*'. Suddenly, the notions of phronesis and clearing surfaced further meaning about the ways in which PGNS may experience an active, reflexive clearing space. This illuminated the possibilities for PGNS to come into a clearing space with practical wisdom. Such space providing PGNS with an opportunity to be present with disorientating dilemmas to acknowledge and explore underlying or unsurfaced thoughts and feelings for example disheartenment, motivation and acceptance. Subsequently, PGNS may also come to awareness of presuppositions and deliberate and re-evaluate the socio-historic, cultural practice situations, morals and values that may guide an internal and visible sense of being a PGNS and actions to ALiP. However, this understanding evoked further curiosity about PGNS conscious self-awareness of disorientating dilemmas, developing practical wisdom and reflexivity in order to find such clearing spaces.

Of significance is that a hidden, binding thread between phronesis, reflexivity and praxis surfaced from continuing to dwell with something that felt fragmented about the participants' experiences of disorientating dilemmas, re-evaluation and self-adaptation to change, challenge or transform practice. However, I had a feeling that there was still something more ontological to surface about PGNS coming to, being with and moving through a clearing space. I found myself being drawn to Aristotle's (1976) assumption that the intellectual virtue of practical wisdom is inseparable or interdependent with moral virtues. This called to thinking the participants' experiences revealing willingness and motivations to do their best to ALiP and being with socio-historic, cultural experiences of resistance, questioning of identity and acceptance of the everyday unpredictable nature of practice. Subsequently, these further calls to thinking significantly illuminated the potential for PGNS developing practical wisdom with ontological attitudes of courage and commitment as a PGNS, professional and person. Furthermore, such ontological ways of being supporting phronetic actions towards bettering aspects of workplace and nursing practice and wider self-being.

However, I grappled with Aristotle's (1976) moral virtue of courage within the context of my research. This was influenced by the socio-historic contexts of this virtue within Aristotle's (1976) seminal translated text 'The Nicomachean Ethics' and the virtue relating to the practical wise person aiming to

live well between the extremes of fear and confidence. Reflexively, this brought me back to the context of courage within contemporary nursing practice and the participants' experiences. Particularly, the ontological attitude of courage surfacing through participants' experiences of workplace support to ALiP and professional and personal motivations and actions towards changing, challenging or transforming workplace practices and cultures in being with others and the everydayness of practice.

The spiral of being and becoming the practically wise workplace supporter

The offerings surfaced a notion of some workplace supporters having historic, learning experiences of PGNE and supporting PGNS through shared personal knowing and understanding of PGNE. Subsequently, this led me to question whether there was a hidden, ontological meaning about what it means to be a PGNS supported by workplace colleagues that have experience of PGNE. Such questioning called to thinking my previous experiences as a pre-registration nursing student and being supported by role model mentors in practice that I aspired to be like as a future nurse. At the time, I could identify the professional attributes associated with my positive influential role models relating to knowledge, person-centredness, being present with people, commitment, kindness and compassion. However, there was also something that remained awe inspiring and mysterious that I could not quite articulate about such positive role model mentors, their ways of being and supporting me to ALiP as a student nurse.

Jenkins, Kinsella and DeLuca's (2018) interpretation of Aristotle's virtue of phronesis suggest that learning from the experiences of wise people involves paying attention to the wise person. Furthermore, learning from wise individuals is fundamentally underpinned by seeking understanding. However, the wise person may not always know the correct course of action (Jenkins, Kinsella and DeLuca, 2018). Grint's (2007) exploration of Aristotle's concept of wisdom within contemporary leadership practice, positioned that practical wisdom must be lived through and cannot be taught. Subsequently, practical wisdom is assumed to be learned indirectly through practice, guided by the experiences of self and others as opposed to being directly taught (Grint, 2007; Kemmis, 2012). This called to thinking Jenkins, Kinsella and DeLuca's (2018) contemporary perspective of phronesis being inclusive of the dimension of perceptiveness. Such perceptiveness involves the wise person drawing upon aesthetic ways of knowing to bring meaning and understanding from experiences in professional practice (Jenkins, Kinsella and DeLuca, 2018).

Subsequently, the notion of practical wisdom revealed a hidden connecting thread between workplace supporters' socio-historic learning experiences of PGNE and the outcomes of sharing personal knowing and understanding as workplace support. Ontologically, this surfaced the significance of PGNS experiences of workplace support being experienced through unseen, aesthetic ways of workplace supporters being with practical wisdom. Particularly, to guide PGNS through their experiences of being a

PGNS. Furthermore, this surfaced that the practical wisdom of workplace supporters may influence workplace supporters being comfortable with indirect ways of guiding PGNS and the uncertainty of opportunities that may arise for PGNS to ALiP, as a course of workplace support action.

Reflexively, these insights brought awareness to the potentially concealed pedagogical and philosophical assumptions of my research question. This led me to question whether the context of the workplace supporter may have been assumed as a facilitator of ontic, pragmatic, prescribed courses of action or directions for PGNS to ALiP. Subsequently, this illuminated a broader horizon relating to the practical wisdom of workplace supporter being an invisible, ontological connecting thread between their previous experiences of PGNE and their actions in guiding PGNS through their experiences and ALiP.

Particularly, considering the perspective that deep ways of knowing through practical wisdom are influenced by experiences, learning, critical dialogue and reflection (Higgs, 2012).

The research offerings also illuminated PGNS becoming workplace supporters to others. Particularly, through the situational contexts of supporting the learning of students and workplace colleagues CPD. Considering the notion of practical wisdom further surfaced the potential for PGNS to be unaware of developing practical wisdom through their own experiences of PGNE and being a PGNS. Subsequently, influencing PGNS being and becoming workplace supporters with practical wisdom themselves to support other learners in practice. This further illuminating practical wisdom extending beyond PGNS experiences of their own workplace supporters to being a workplace supporter with practical wisdom for others.

Higgs (2012) suggests that in aspiring to be wise like others, a person must accept the challenge of phronesis as part of becoming a wise practitioner. This evoked a further thread of curiosity relating to PGNS self-awareness of aspirations and phronesis in being and becoming a wise practitioner. However, my thinking was also drawn to an ontological attitude surfacing of PGNS being committed in both values, virtues and actions to workplace support for other learners in the workplace. PGNS perhaps being unaware of hidden interplay of practical wisdom developing from their own experiences of workplace support to ALiP which may have been positive or not so positive, and their own commitment and generosity to support the learning of others in practice. Reflexively, this called to thinking the perspective that phronesis encompasses moral and intellectual judgments as well as being a virtue embodied in social practice and complex interactions (Ellett, 2012; Kinsella and Pitman, 2012). The participants' experiences surfaced PGNS being unconscious or explicitly unaware of their own being and becoming as a wise workplace supporter to colleagues due to their assumed socio-historic, reflexive learning experiences of being a PGNS. Furthermore, illuminating this potentially being a hidden, untaught aspect of being a PGNS and experiencing PGNE.

Synthesis of following the thread

In bringing the notions of phronesis and praxis to the parts and the whole of my research, hidden interconnected threads and bridges became visible. Significantly, this surfaced further meaning and insights relating to the areas that I felt were fragmented. Reflexively, this led to a sense of reaching an acceptance in bringing the offerings about PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP together as a whole within my research.

Dwelling with the notion of phronesis and praxis surfaced PGNS developing practical wisdom and ontological ways of being through lived experiences of disorientating dilemmas, the everydayness of practice and workplace support to ALiP. The notions of phronesis and praxis also bound the fragmented areas and curious questions together and surfaced the previously concealed phenomenon of PGNS being and becoming practically wise.

Aristotle (1976) positioned practical wisdom being interdependent with moral virtues. Such moral virtues considered as the 'mean' which lies between deficiency and the extreme of what is right or best (Aristotle, 1976). Exploration into contemporary, professional perspectives of virtues surfaced PGNS being with ontological attitudes or qualities of courage, generosity and commitment within my research. This further illuminated a complex interplay of practical wisdom with diverse socio-historic, cultural experiences of being a PGNS, ontological ways of being and acting in practice. Subsequently, ontological attitudes or qualities of generosity and commitment became visible through PGNS being and becoming a wise workplace supporter to others even though PGNS may experience in-between support themselves. The notion of developing practical wisdom as part of living through disorientating dilemmas and the everydayness of practice also illuminated PGNS being with ontological attitudes of courage and commitment. Furthermore, this surfaced PGNS unconsciously or consciously embracing reflexive thinking, action and an ongoing attitude of commitment and willingness to doing the best to challenge, change or transform practice. Kemmis (2012) argued the need for professional practitioners with qualities beyond theoretical, scientific and craft knowledge towards wisdom. Significantly, my research illuminated PGNS experiences of developing professional wisdom and these experiences being grounded and interwoven with individual ontological ways of being, attitudes or qualities. Furthermore, providing an opportunity for an authentic sense of self, being a PGNS and professional identity to become visible through practice.

The surfacing of PGNS developing practical wisdom as part of being a PGNS also furthered insights into wider professional and personal growth and transformation. Kristjánsson *et al.* (2021) positions that phronesis enables a person to deliberate values, actions and emotions through a lens of promoting living well. If it is assumed that individual practical wisdom continues evolving and is interdependent with ongoing socio-historic, cultural lived experiences as a PGNS, person and learner (Aristotle, 1976; Gadamer, 2004/1960; Sandvik and Hilli, 2021). The notion of living well could be perceived from an ontic

or outcome perspective. For example living well in the context of maintaining evidence of professional standards of practice or achieving PGNS learning outcomes following course completion.

However, my curiosity was drawn towards future ontological enquiry to further understanding about what it means to live well or flourish as a PGNS and what is the lived experience of developing practical wisdom as a PGNS. Furthermore, leading me question how this is meaningful to the experience of flourishing and understanding PGNE considering assumed links with living a good professional life, self-identity and self-esteem (Ellett, 2012). These questions could also be extended to the wider context of being a registered nurse. Reflexively, this called to thinking PGNS experiencing a questioning from others about professional, academic or clinical identity in being a PGNS and the valuing of learning experiences within socio-cultural contexts of practice. Based on the assumed interconnected relationship between phronesis and praxis, my curiosity has extended to wondering about professional and workplace valuing of praxis and acting in practice. Particularly, if practical wisdom is made possible through a readiness and openness to learn from individual experiences and that of others (Aristotle, 1976; Gadamer, 2004/1960). Kemmis (2012) positioned that phronesis can only be indirectly learned through a valuing and commitment to praxis and acting in practice. Of significance is that the research offerings surfaced PGNS developing practical wisdom being interwoven with values and an ontological attitude of commitment. However, Kemmis (2012) suggests that a commitment to praxis is not solely dependent on an individual. This brought to my awareness the interdependent socio-cultural contexts of PGNS and nurses being with colleagues in the workplace and wider professional practice. Subsequently, as a nurse, research student and nurse educator this furthered curiosity about what it means to value, learn and support phronesis and praxis as part of workplace support and to enable PGNS to flourish. Reflexively, I also realised that I was coming towards a new horizon of understanding ALiP through the lens of phronesis and praxis.

I also found myself being drawn to Kemmis (2012) positioning of the 'happening-ness of practice'. This relates to the changes in practice or praxis that unfold in socio-historic ways that may be uncontrolled or unconceived by an individual practitioner (Kemmis, 2012). Further requiring individuals to understand and confront the consequences of the happening-ness of practice and praxis. Furthermore, Higgs (2012) suggests that practice cannot be wise if it is not known or authentic to self and wider professional contexts. Based on the philosophical assumption that our '*being-in-the-world*' is inseparable from others (Heidegger, 1962/1927). This called to thinking PGNS and workplace colleagues consciously coming to a place together to understand, confront and learn from changes in practice and praxis. Additionally, I wondered whether such actions may provide opportunities for PGNS developing practical wisdom and ontological attitudes of courage, generosity and commitment to become conscious or visible to themselves and workplace colleagues. Reflexively, this illuminated why I perhaps grappled with PGNS being seen and present as a PGNS to self and others. Furthermore, this revealed complex ontological views and ways of PGNS being with workplace colleagues. This also surfaced an ongoing inseparable

cycle of learning experiences, practical wisdom and praxis opening workplace possibilities for individual and collective personal and professional growth.

As I reached this understanding, questions surfaced whether developing practical wisdom as a PGNS is assumed to be experienced and intertwined with praxis. Particularly, considering the positions that phronesis cannot be directly taught but comes from experiences with others (Schwartz, 2011; Kemmis, 2012; Jenkins, Kinsella and DeLuca, 2018). Kinsella and Pitman (2012) previously proposed phronesis, phronetic action and praxis becoming part of language and core dimensions of professional practice and education. Dwelling with the context of my own professional experiences, insights, landscapes and code of practice (NMC, 2018e) the terms practical wisdom, phronesis and praxis are not frequently experienced. Although, aspects and ways of being resonated with my professional experiences of active learning communities, workplace projects, participatory action research, person-centred practice, reflection and reflexivity. Subsequently, the invisible, connecting threads of practical wisdom that surfaced from my research called to thinking the curious questions raised. These questions offer an opportunity to surface further understanding and meaning about PGNS experiences of practical wisdom and praxis.

Personal reflexive synthesis

Initially it felt daunting but necessary to follow a sense of something further calling and mattering through the participants lived PGNS experiences. As I followed a flow of extended hermeneutic phenomenological conversations, this importantly led me towards exploring the notions of practical wisdom and praxis. Subsequently, these notions significantly revealed as connecting threads binding the areas that I was curious about and that previously felt fragmented to bring together the parts and whole of my research offerings. Significantly these notions also surfaced a concealed phenomenon of PGNS being and becoming practically wise through experiences of workplace support to ALiP.

As a professional doctorate student in following these further calls to thinking, there were times when I felt like I was in a dense fog of uncertainty, not knowing where these calls to thinking would lead. It was during one of these experiences that I was drawn to Dunne's (1993) philosophical conservation about Gadamer's fusion of horizons. Reflexively, this brought self-awareness to the importance of not remaining static within the same, momentary horizon but creating an openness within my being, thinking and research to allow for new or recombined horizons of understanding to overtake (Dunne, 1993; Gadamer, 2004/1960). Enquiry into phronesis and praxis provided an invaluable personal research experience of my own horizons being stretched and broadened. Particularly, in coming to an understanding of the meaning of PGNS lived experiences of workplace support to ALiP unfolding. The appearance of practical wisdom and praxis within my research was beyond the horizons that I could have anticipated or envisioned. In bringing the notions of practical wisdom and praxis to the areas that I

had considered to be fragmented or still called for something further to be revealed, I came to a sense of the offerings of my research coming together as a whole. This evoked a sense of acceptance and harmony in bringing together the things that mattered within the context and boundaries of my research, and my journey of being a professional doctorate research student. I felt a sense that the fog had lifted to illuminate new horizons of understanding about my research. However, a light also shone on new paths of enquiry to be discovered and curiously followed. I felt an ongoing sense of being indirectly guided by the notions of practical wisdom and praxis towards an unfolding question to myself and others within the context of nursing practice and education. The question being to continue to consider what are my thoughts and actions in coming to understand the offering presented.

10.3 Strengths and limitations

To support transparency and rigour within my research, discussion of strengths and limitations associated with my study aimed to demonstrate trustworthiness and openness, prior to discussing how the offerings may influence future research and practice (C11). This section also reflexively shares my methodological learning which illuminated opportunities for furthering research approaches and development as a future researching professional.

Following two phases of recruitment for my study from a HEI, a total of four voluntary PGNS participants were recruited, fewer than the initially proposed sample of 6-10 participants. It was beyond the scope and timeframes of my study to extensively explore factors that may have influenced the smaller sample of participants. However, aspects of my research may have been influenced by changing COVID-19 pandemic contexts e.g. national government and local guidelines influencing professional, educational and research practices, and personal lived experiences at the time of my research (UWS, no date). As a professional doctorate student, I was aware that the smaller sample size may influence criticism of my research and the significance and credibility of my research offerings. Particularly, in view of contrasting positivist research paradigms that pose challenge to smaller, subjective qualitative studies and hermeneutic phenomenological research methodologies, rigour and outcomes. Potentially, the smaller sample size might also influence opportunities to disseminate my research outcomes via journal publication depending on specific publication guidelines or criteria for qualitative research studies and sample sizes. To mitigate concerns regarding the sample size and ensure rigour and credibility prior to completing the recruitment stage of research, I critically discussed the perceived issues with my Professional Doctorate Supervisory Team including my associated academic Professor and the Chair of the relevant Ethics Committee. As the smaller sample size was still deemed relevant to yield rich, in-depth subjective data to realistically explore PGNS experience of workplace support to ALIP, agreement

was given from my Supervisory Team and the Chair of the Ethics Committee to proceed with my professional doctorate research (EoR: Balanced integration, openness).

In consideration of the sample size of my study, I reflexively learned about the richness of hermeneutic phenomenological data and the great depth of interpretation from the things that mattered from four participants' experience of workplace support to ALiP. This evoked significant learning and considerations for future research relating to sample sizes when using methodologies that involve in-depth interpretation. Particularly, being cognisant of the aims of research studies with consideration of ethical issues relating to the potential volume of data that might be collected and feasibly used, interpreted and presented.

Within the context of my professional role, CPD towards the end of my professional doctorate focused on person-centred and participatory approaches to research. Such CPD activities and learning furthered critical awareness of different ways in which my methodology could have been approached. In furthering my understanding and surfacing pronesis the connection with embodiment opened a potential new way of approaching future theoretical and lived experience research enquiry (Jenkins, Kinsella and DeLuca, 2018). Particularly, person-centred research approaches associated with human flourishing and participant empowerment through participant inclusion, participation and collaboration within research (McCormack *et al.*, 2017; Dewing, McCormack and McCance, 2021). This learning called to thinking whether there may have been opportunities to consider the ability of the participants to flourish as part of their participation within my study, particularly considering the participants being PGNS and the focus on supporting ALiP. Reflecting on my experiences of hermeneutic phenomenological data interpretation, also evoked curiosity about extending creative approaches to crafting stories interwoven with participatory, person-centred approaches. This called to question whether weaving such approaches may further ways of meaningfully presenting and calling others to listen, wonder and think about peoples lived experiences.

In alignment with my philosophical and methodological framework, the offerings did not aim to provide a definitive answer to the research question or be generalisable to all PGNS. Alternatively, the offerings aimed to provide the reader with a plausible understanding to surface meaning about PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP, relevant to the contemporary contexts of PGNE. However, this presented challenges to convey meaningful understanding of the offerings in relevant professional contexts whilst demonstrating philosophical and methodological congruence to hermeneutic phenomenology, and the work of Heidegger (1962/1927; 1996/1927) and Gadamer (2004/1960). While these aspects were considered essential to maintain rigour within my research and meet professional doctorate requirements seeking to address both aspects may have limited a logical flow within the writing style of the offerings chapters. Further influencing meaningful understanding for the reader who is invited into complex philosophical interpretation, perhaps introduced to new philosophical terms and presented with

research offerings as parts of a whole that invite further thinking rather than concluding definitive answers or findings. Therefore, throughout the offerings chapters, I transparently integrated my understanding of the key philosophical terms used to deepen interpretation of the participants' experiences and set meaningful context for the reader associated with contemporary PGNE.

The development of analytical discussion to come to a deeper understanding of the research offerings or further explore phenomenon revealed was limited in some areas due to the availability of specific, relevant contemporary literature following focused literature searches. It was beyond the scope, timeframes and remit of this thesis to conduct wider systematic literature reviews for some aspects of the offerings that invited further thinking. However, these areas have been highlighted within the offerings chapters to support transparency and discussed within Chapter 11 to illuminate future areas for further literature and research enquiry.

Based on the philosophical underpinnings of my research, understanding is assumed to be historically effected and influenced by being in a socio-cultural world with others (Heidegger, 1962/1927; Gadamer, 2004/1960). Therefore, my research offerings reflect the temporal nature of the participants and my own '*fore-structures*' of understanding. Gadamer's (2004/1960) concept of historicity and fusion of horizons also assumes that as a horizon of understanding is projected it is simultaneously superseded. This philosophical perspective resonated with the research offerings presented being contextualised to one specific group of PGNS participants' experiences of workplace support to ALiP at the time of my research. Subsequently, an assumed outcome of my research is that readers will make:

... their own meaning, when the knowledge and experience they bring fuses with the new text, and it is for the reader to decide how applicable and transferable the new meanings are. (Dibley *et al.*, 2020, p. 129)

Therefore, readers are invited to lean in to the strengths and limitations of my research while considering the interpretation, context and relevance of the offerings at the time of reading.

10.4 Reflexive synthesis

In the context of my research, reflexivity was understood and approached as an essential, active process interwoven through my research, thesis and studies (Gadamer, 2004/1960; UWS, 2019b; Dibley *et al.*, 2020). In aiming to provide a reflexive synthesis of my experiences through my professional doctorate, I was drawn to a quote about the context of hermeneutic phenomenological approaches to research; 'one must love the experience, drawing from who one is and is becoming' (Smythe *et al.*, 2008, p. 1391). Reflexively, this resonated with my experiences of being and becoming a professional doctorate student, a researching professional and person during my studies. Particularly, as this illuminated my collective,

temporal experiences of transformational learning, and professional and personal growth undertaking a professional doctorate underpinned by hermeneutic phenomenological approaches. Subsequently, this called to thinking an opportunity to synthesise my reflexive learning through poetry.

Poem 1: A reflexive, temporal synthesis of my professional doctorate at the time of writing

This journey has changed me, I am not who I was.
I didn't realise the longevity.
A personal plight,
a passion for learning, and my profession.
COVID Hit,
I struggle to explain.
Trying to hold on,
but then others came,
a gratitude, how do I explain.
Leaping into vulnerability, with writing and interpretive leaps,
what if isn't not right,
but they say there's no right.
Not any easier though.
Think about holistic being,
bring mind, body, heart and soul.
Block out the ticking clock.
Step into that clearing,
find safety to dwell.
Maybe I could, bring something to give.

Offerings now shared,
bring opportunities for others to step in,
and further possibilities, well beyond within.

Keep looking and moving with openness to the horizon,
follow the way with commitment and courage.
Don't forget to bring your wise self and others along.
Chat and discover as you go,
share experiences of the past and the present,
be curious about the future.
I just then wonder,
what might happen,
and unfold ...

Not the end! (but an encouraging call to further thinking and action)

Chapter 11 - Calls to further thinking and enquiry

11.1 Introduction

In bringing together the research offerings as a whole, my interpretation continued to illuminate possibilities to further understanding beyond my initial research question. Therefore, this final chapter aims to extend the relevance, meaning and transferability of my research offerings across professional landscapes by calling to thinking the questions that emerged from my interpretation of the participants' experiences of workplace support to ALiP.

This chapter invites relevant professional peers to consider future possibilities for learning, enquiry, and research to further understanding of PGNE, being a PGNS and workplace support for PGNS to ALiP across research, nursing and HEI contexts (UWS, 2019b). Furthermore, providing an opportunity to contemplate different philosophical, research and practice development approaches in seeking to extend and deepen knowledge and understanding in these areas.

Throughout this thesis, professional landscapes focused on the context of nursing, nurse education and HE. It is not the purpose of hermeneutic phenomenology or my research to provide generalisable findings or extend enquiry beyond the scope of these landscapes. However, some of the calls to further enquiry within this chapter may further thinking for readers across wider professional landscapes and contexts in which PG students may be situated in broader healthcare roles or contexts of workplace support to ALiP.

11.2 Reconnecting with PGNE landscapes

To support rigour and contextual currency of my research at the final stages of my professional doctorate I returned to scope the landscape of literature relating to PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP. This involved scoping key strategic nursing, HE and research literature published in the past two years to further literature previously reviewed (C2-3). Activities included scoping relevant strategic nursing and HE literature across the four UK CNOD, HEE, NHS, NHSScotland, NES, AdvanceHE, QAA and QAAS website resources. The scoping activities identified no further policies, frameworks or initiatives specifically influencing the current context of PGNE and / or workplace support for PGNS to ALiP. Furthermore, an overarching scope of research literature using the CINAHL database focused on PGNE, PGN, workplace support and learning identified no further published literature relevant to the specific context of my research.

A further development related to the NMC (2022c) publishing new standards for post-registration programmes which specifically apply to PGNS undertaking SCPHN and Community Nursing Specialist

practice qualifications at a minimum of PG masters level. The NMC (2022c) standards set that AEI and PLP must ensure employer support and protected learning time to enable students to be appropriately supported. Subsequently this may influence some PGNS future experiences of workplace support to ALiP.

The findings of my scoping activities may have related to previously reviewed strategic policies, visions and frameworks remaining within the associated strategic timeframes. Additionally, it was assumed that the context of the pandemic may have influenced a limited focus on strategic and relevant research literature across nursing and HE. Particularly considering the ICN (2021) and NMC (2022a) published statements acknowledging the wider current and future issues influencing the nursing workforce. However, the ICN (2021) in the context of the pandemic highlighted the continued need for investment in nurse education to address retention and nursing workforce shortages. Furthermore the ICN (2021) acknowledged the unprecedented challenges regarding the acquisition of CPD and acknowledged disruptions to PGNE potentially influencing APN.

11.3 Calls to further thinking and enquiry

11.3.1 Being a PGNS

The research offerings revealed the potential for PGNS relational and situational experiences of being with workplace colleagues, cultures and everyday practice to create or inhibit opportunities for workplace support to ALiP. Further illuminating the potential for workplace support for PGNS to ALiP to provide a conduit for PGNS to contribute to changing, challenging and transforming aspects of workplace and nursing practices. Therefore, it is proposed that further in-depth exploration into these complex aspects influencing workplace support for PGNS to ALiP is essential across nursing and HE landscapes. Based on the assumption that a deeper understanding of these aspects may inform and support opportunities for workplace support for PGNS to ALiP and contribute to wider aspects of workplace or nursing practices.

In coming to a deeper understanding of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP. The research offerings significantly illuminated that PGNS may experience or become aware of complex tensions between self and professional motivations towards PGNE and actual application of workplace support to apply learning within temporal, situational and everyday constructs of workplace practice. Subsequently, revealing the possibility that PGNS may experience dilemmas or disjuncture which call to question aspects of self-being, being a PGNS and being with colleagues in workplace cultures. Pedagogically, such dilemmas or disjuncture may be associated as being part of transformative learning. Furthermore, providing learning opportunities for PGNS to experience personal and professional growth, and authentic

and autonomous ways of becoming their own conduit in creating possibilities for workplace support to ALiP (Mezirow, 2000; Mezirow and Taylor, 2010; Jarvis, 2018). Potentially further contributing to challenging or transforming aspects of workplace practice. However, the participants' experiences of workplace support to ALiP significantly furthered insight into contrasting PGNS experiences of disheartenment, demotivation, acceptance of everyday workplaces and cultures to encouragement and empowerment influencing ALiP. This illuminated the possibilities of PGNS experiencing critical questioning of previously accepted ways of *'Being'* or disorientating dilemmas within workplace practices.

Dwelling with the participants' experiences of disorientating dilemmas, self-evaluation and adaptation to change, challenge or transform practice surfaced a hidden, binding thread between practical wisdom, reflexivity and praxis. The notion of practical wisdom illuminated PGNS being internally and externally in between complex moral workplace dilemmas and responsibilities in being a PGNS, and a personal and professional willingness to act and do the best towards ALiP. Furthermore this revealed a notion of PGNS coming into a clearing space to deliberate and re-evaluate socio-historic, cultural experiences of practice, morals and values in order to guide being and becoming a PGNS and actions to ALiP.

My research offerings invite nurses and nurse educators to further explore PGNS experiences of dilemmas, disjuncture, developing practical wisdom and transformative learning through a lens of workplace, professional and HE support. This is considered essential from the collective perspective of nursing practice and nurse education communities supporting PGNS. Particularly, in view of PGNS experiences of personal and professional growth and flourishing creating further opportunities for PGNS to feel empowered and enabled to effectively contribute to PGNE, ALiP, learning communities and the improvement of practice. Such enquiry may further understanding whether such dilemmas, disjuncture, phronesis or transformation are part of the context of experiencing PGNE. Furthermore, providing an important opportunity to consider the potential impact on PGNS and the preparation that may be required to support PGNS, workplace supporters and nurse educators. Particularly, in view of wider current and future issues influencing the nursing workforce including the sustained demands across all sectors, staff shortages and significant increases in national pressures (NMC, 2022a).

Subsequently, my research offerings relating to being and becoming a PGNS influenced and informed the proposed areas for future research and enquiry, across nursing and nurse education landscapes. Particularly to further understanding of:

- Professional attitudes, beliefs and values towards PGNE within workplace practices; to further understand contexts and opportunities for workplace support for PGNS to ALiP.
- PGNS experiences of transformational learning and developing practical wisdom across workplace, nursing and HE contexts.

- PGNS awareness and experiences of coming to, being in and moving through disorientating dilemmas in the context of developing practical wisdom and reflexivity.
- How is the lived experience of being a PGNS from perspectives of phronesis and transformation considered within PGNE curriculums, philosophies and pedagogies.
- How PGNS are supported through transformational learning experiences to grow and flourish within the contexts of nursing practice and PGNE.
- PGNS learning and support needs relating to potential experiences of dilemmas, disjuncture, transformative learning and developing practical wisdom.
- Wider transformative expectations, outcomes and experiences of being a PGNS from professional and HE perspectives; to further insight into the contribution of PGNE.
- Workplace colleague and nurse educator needs to prepare and support PGNS experiencing dilemmas, disjuncture, developing practical wisdom and transformative learning through PGNE.

11.3.2 Furthering workplace support for PGNS to ALiP

The context of my research focused on PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP. However, the research offerings illuminated PGNS experiences of peer support from PGNS within the HEI environment potentially influencing PGNS expectations, experiences and needs for workplace support from colleagues. Subsequently, my research invites a reflexive opportunity for PGN educators to consider, review and explore existing PGNS peer support infrastructures. Particularly, across HE and nursing practices, through a lens of seeking to further understand and support PGNS to ALiP.

From collective HE and nursing practice perspectives further research into PGNS experiences of peer support within PGNE may deepen understanding of PGNS experiences, expectations and ways of workplace and HE peer support. Research into this area may provide a significant opportunity for those within nurse education contexts to gain insight into PGNS experiences and needs for peer support across workplace and HEI landscapes. This may also provide an opportunity for nurse educators to consider existing PGNE curriculum design and content to support PGNS to explore; their workplace support needs, contexts of asking for workplace support and approaches to sharing knowledge and understanding of PGNE. Such opportunities and exploration may then contribute to informed, effective approaches to support workplace support and ALiP. Particularly, given the identified limited workplace support infrastructures for PGNS on non-NMC AEI specialist post-registration programmes (NMC, 2018d; 2022c) and contrasting practice education infrastructures that exist to support; PRNE following the NMC (2018d) Standards for supervision and assessment, and potential approaches to preceptorship for newly registered nurses following the collaborative UK CNO and NMC (no dated) Principles for Preceptorship.

A further consideration is whether existing practice education infrastructures or those with roles and remits for supporting learning in practice, may provide opportunities to explore existing and potential supporting infrastructure specifically for PGNS within nursing practice in collaboration with PGNS and PGNE educators in HEI. The revealing of PGNS being and becoming workplace supporters for students and colleagues potentially influenced by colleagues' background experiences of PGNS or equivalent practice. Furthermore, calls to thinking opportunities to explore workplace support infrastructures and communities between PGNS and PGN.

The research offerings significantly revealed the possibility of the application of workplace support for PGNS being a prerequisite prior to ALiP. However, my research revealed PGNS experiencing dilemmas in the actual application of workplace support. This potentially being influenced by a constant movement of workplace support being available or unavailable within situational, temporal contexts of being a PGNS and being with workplace colleagues in everyday nursing practice. If workplace support is assumed as a potential conduit or prerequisite for PGNS to ALiP within immediate or wider workplace contexts. Further research is recommended to explore pedagogical understanding of the application of workplace support as a prerequisite or conduit to application of PGNE learning to practice. Research into this area may then contribute to a deeper understanding of ALiP. Particularly the significance of workplace support influencing outcomes of PGNE, application of PGNS attributes in practice and being a PGNS in the workplace.

Although my research was focused on an ontological approach to enquiry. Further research into the complex pragmatic factors influencing the availability of workplace support is also recommended. Particularly, to deepen insight into PGNS workplace support needs and resources to support ALiP. From joint nursing practice and nurse education perspectives, this may further pragmatic ways of workplace support being available or more consistently available to PGNS to apply learning within everyday nursing practice. Further research to explore the beliefs, values, experiences and needs of colleagues in providing workplace support for PGNS to ALiP may also help to inform and enhance effective, realistic and meaningful ways of PGNS being with workplace support and supportive colleagues within everyday nursing practice. Additionally, research into these areas may bring opportunities to explore how workplace colleagues are supported in their roles and which roles may be best placed to support PGNS.

My research offerings revealed that workplace colleagues with previous experiences of PGNE may provide different approaches or ways of being with workplace support through personal knowing, practical wisdom and understanding of PGNE. This further surfaced PGNS being and becoming workplace supporters with practical wisdom to support other learners in practice. This illuminated a potential relational cycle of PGNS coming into PGNE, being a PGNS and becoming a workplace supporter for PGNS and other learners in the workplace. Practical wisdom is associated with being learned indirectly through practice, guided by the experiences of self and others as opposed to being

directly taught (Grint, 2007; Kemmis, 2012). Furthermore, Higg's (2012) positioned that in becoming a wise practitioner a person accepts the challenge of phronesis. Reflectively, this called to thinking whether it is assumed that PGNS are consciously aware that such experiences may influence the development of practical wisdom and being or becoming a wise practitioner. Therefore the notions of phronesis and the person with practical wisdom (phronimos) are suggested as offering a different ontological lens to explore further areas of enquiry relating to:

- PGNS awareness of their ontological attitudes, socio-historic experiences in developing practical wisdom, and being and becoming a wise workplace supporter to other learners.
- PGNS experiences of hidden or untaught aspects of PGNE and being a PGNS.
- What is the lived individual and shared experience of developing practical wisdom as a PGNS, nurse and community of professionals. Furthermore, how is this meaningful to nursing communities, the profession and nurse education.

It is suggested that further research into the notion of PGNS becoming workplace supporters for other PGNS may offer relevant nurse educators an opportunity to consider wider PGNS outcomes, ontological ways of being and contribution to workplace learning communities. Creating an opportunity to inform the further development of effective and available workplace support infrastructures, networks and ways of PGNS being with workplace support specific to PGNE and wider learners within nursing practice.

11.3.3 A call to wider professional considerations

The research offerings highlighted the potential of complex situational, relational and temporal aspects influencing the asking of workplace support by PGNS and workplace colleagues including those within senior managerial roles. The participants' experiences also revealed the potential for active and authentic approaches to asking for support, professional attitudes and background experiences to influence approaches to asking about workplace support. Given the identified limited research literature specifically focused on PGNS asking for workplace support, the following areas of research are suggested to further understanding into:

- PGNS, workplace colleagues' and managers' experiences, attitudes, beliefs and values about the asking of workplace support to ALiP.
- Whether the specific notion of asking for workplace support may influence ALiP.

The research offerings also evoked questions about workplace colleagues knowing and understanding of PGNE and PGNS workplace support needs. Particularly, whether the abstract nature of some PGNS attributes and characteristics may influence how workplace support and ALiP is understood, known or

demonstrated by PGNS with workplace colleagues. Therefore, from nursing and HE contexts further enquiry is recommended to explore:

- Understanding of PGNE among PGNS, workplace colleagues and professional nursing communities, and how this might influence the presence of PGNS within workplace communities.
- Approaches to authentic, meaningful and relevant discussions between PGNS and workplace colleagues as a conduit to understanding individual PGNS workplace support and learning needs to ALiP.
- HEI engagement practices with PGNS and workplaces to further understanding and knowing of PGNE, PGNS workplace support / learning needs and ALiP.

It is assumed that further understanding about the asking and knowing of workplace support for PGNS may then contribute to strengthened approaches and cultures for PGNS to ALiP. Research into these areas may provide HEI with an opportunity to consider how PGNS can be supported in asking for workplace support. Furthermore, providing an opportunity to extend knowledge and understanding of PGNE across professional landscapes. Subsequently, bringing possibilities to further professional understanding and visibility of workplace support, PGNE and application of PG learning within workplace learning communities and nursing practice.

Of wider professional significance is that the research offerings illuminated the potential for PGNS to experience an inbetweenness of workplace support to ALiP. Revealing complexities surrounding resistance, allowance, and the giving and taking of workplace support to ALiP within the context of everyday nursing practice. The research offerings also illuminated the potential for PGNS to seek self and professional validation and affirmation of being a PGNS, including a sense of PGNS knowing and doing the right thing in undertaking PGNE and ALiP. This surfaced the notion of PGNS developing practical wisdom with ontological attitudes of courage, commitment and generosity, as a PGNS, professional and person. These offerings importantly surfaced what mattered within the PGNS individual experience of workplace support to ALiP and ontological ways of being a PGNS. In considering the strategic visions and policies towards nurses with levels of PGNE as part of the nursing workforce (WHO, 2016a; HEE, 2017; CNOD, 2018); it is suggested that further enquiry and exploration beyond the context of workplace support to ALiP is required to further professional understanding of:

- How PGNS may be faring in the wider context of CPD, post-registration education and professional learning.
- PGNS professional identity within workplace, professional learning communities and the wider nursing profession.
- Wider self and professional beliefs, values and attitudes may influence workplace support for PGNS to ALiP across workplace and professional learning communities.

Further enquiry into these areas may provide opportunities across nursing practice and nurse education to further post-registration and PGNE workplace support, learning infrastructures and communities.

In considering the individual experiences for PGNS and the wider contexts of nursing practice, nurse education and the nursing profession. The research offerings illuminated the potential for PGNS becoming their own conduit to creating opportunities for change and transformation across context of self-being, being a PGNS and workplace practice. Jarvis (2018) called for philosophical perspectives within studies of learning to further understand the person – the learner. Subsequently, PGNS, nurses, nurse educators, researchers and leaders are invited to consider within their individual professional roles and as a collective profession, opportunities to engage in authentic conversations at individual, workplace or strategic levels about the asking, knowing and values of workplace support for PGNS to ALiP. In addition to continuing to further understanding of the everyday experiences of being a PGNS and nurse in the context of professional learning, workplace support to ALiP and flourishing.

Human flourishing focuses on maximizing individuals' achievement of their potential for growth and development as they change the circumstances and relations of their lives. People are helped to flourish (i.e. grow, develop, thrive) during the change experience in addition to an intended outcome of wellbeing for the beneficiaries of the work. (Titchen and McCormack, 2010, p. 532)

11.3.4 Continuing to explore the thread of phronesis within PGNE, nursing practice and nurse education

Practical wisdom is assumed to enable individuals to evolve from ongoing, complex socio-historic experiences and deliberating values, actions and emotions through a lens of promoting living well (Aristotle, 1976; Gadamer, 2004/1960; Kristjánsson *et al.*, 2021; Sandvik and Hilli, 2021). Ellet (2012) highlighted that living a good professional life within the context of contemporary phronesis is interrelated with self-identity and self-esteem. Phronesis is also assumed to be indirectly learned through individual and social experiences, values and commitments to praxis and action in practice (Schwartz, 2011; Kemmis, 2012; Jenkins, Kinsella and DeLuca, 2018). Reflexively, my research offerings revealed notions of PGNS experiencing an in betweenness of workplace support to ALiP and questioning about the value of learning experiences within socio-cultural contexts of practice. Significantly, this surfaced PGNS developing practical wisdom, and this being interwoven with individual values and ontological attitudes of commitment, courage and generosity. This further illuminated PGNS experiencing wider professional and personal growth, transformation and flourishing through the experience of being a PGNS. Subsequently, the research offerings called to thinking further areas for ontological and philosophical enquiry to further understand:

- What is the lived experience of developing practical wisdom as a PGNS and how is this meaningful to the experience of flourishing as a PGNS and to PGNE.
- What does it mean to live well or flourish as a PGNS within the contemporary context of practical wisdom and praxis.
- What does it mean to value, learn and support phronesis and praxis as part of workplace support to enable PGNS to flourish.

In the context of nursing, there are calls towards phronesis and phronetic action being part of language, core dimensions, inherent structures and authentic approaches within practice and education (Kinsella and Pitman, 2012; Jenkins, Kinsella and DeLuca, 2018; Sandvik and Hilli, 2021). Reflexively, within my research the notion of phronesis was something concealed underneath PGNS experience of workplace support to ALiP. In the context of my professional experiences, insights and code of practice (NMC, 2018e) the specific terms practical wisdom, phronesis and praxis do not appear to be frequently or explicitly used. Coming to this understanding brought curiosity and questioning as educator, nurse and professional doctorate student whether phronesis is something inherently assumed to happen within pedagogical and professional experiences of practice. Furthermore, whether PGNS development of practical wisdom is an assumed way of PGNS bridging learning between PGNE theory, practice and phronetic actions. Particularly, acknowledging the debate that phronesis cannot be taught and therefore indirectly learned through individual and social experiences, values and commitments to praxis (Schwartz, 2011; Kemmis, 2012; Jenkins, Kinsella and DeLuca, 2018). Subsequently, the following further areas of research and enquiry are proposed from pedagogical and practice perspectives:

- How is practical wisdom and praxis understood and valued by PGNS, nurses, nurse educators and professional leaders in the context of nursing practice, education and strategic visions.
- What is the lived experience of practical wisdom and praxis for nurses, nurse educators and professional leaders.
- How are the notions of phronesis and praxis approached within PGNE pedagogy, curriculums and teaching, learning and assessment activities.

11.4 Concluding statement

This thesis demonstrates a significant and original contribution to furthering understanding and meaning of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP across professional nursing, nurse education and HE practices through my professional doctorate hermeneutic phenomenological research study (UWS, 2019b). Particularly, as this was an area associated with limited literature and research prior to my study.

Following the submission of my thesis, I aim to seek professional opportunities to authentically engage with relevant others to share the research offerings, methodological insights and learning experiences as a professional doctorate student, nurse and nurse educator. The advanced professional research knowledge and skills that I have developed will also be used to further learning as a future researching professional. Through applying professional doctorate attributes, I also aim to make a meaningful contribution to professional communities and practices across contemporary nursing, healthcare, education and research landscapes.

Reflexively, I learned that in asking participants to share their experiences, the depth and breadth of their PGNS experiences offered far more insights beyond workplace support to ALiP and the remit of my professional doctorate research thesis. This learning called to thinking Gadamer's (2004/1960) hermeneutic assumptions that meaning is an infinite process, never finished and that new understanding will continually emerge. This resonated with my lived experience and insight into the potential for hermeneutic phenomenological interpretation to be endless. Particularly, in offering further possibilities for myself and professional peers to extend horizons of understanding about what it means to be a PGNS, PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP and PGNE across professional nursing, research and HE landscapes.

In coming to conclude my thesis, I was drawn back to Smythe's (2012) positioning of lived experience research within the initial chapter of my thesis:

...always it is to remember what matters; to strive to enhance the experiences of those we go on to walk with through similar experiences. Yes, phenomenon has been articulated, but always it comes back to people, like you and me. Life is only ever lived as 'my experience'. (Smythe, 2011, p. 51)

Reflexively, this emphasised the importance of conveying the things that mattered from the participant's experiences of workplace support to ALiP as a PGNS, professional and person within my research. However, this also highlighted the temporal contexts of the PGNS lived experiences and my research. In the context of phronesis, Kemmis (2012) positions that experience also teaches the limits of what we know and have learned, calling further towards new practical deliberation and action. This resonated with my experiences of concluding this thesis which illuminated an opening towards a continuing research journey. I was also drawn to Gadamer's (2004/1960) position that a person with understanding does not stand apart from others but thinks along with others. My research offerings open a call to myself and communities of nurses, educators, researchers and professional leaders to come with challenge, courage and commitment to further explore philosophical and ontological ways of being a PGNS and nurse. Particularly, to consider what further, could be known, understood and learned about being a postgraduate nursing student, nurse and nurse educator through the notions of practical wisdom, praxis and human flourishing.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: HEI Masters Degree Aims

The QAA (2020b) recommend that any HEI master degrees should offer students at least one of the following aims:

- a focus on a particular aspect of a broader subject area
- a focus on a particular subject area or field of study in greater depth
- undertaking a research project on a topic within the area of interest
- learning how to conduct research and undertake training in research methods
- specialising in an area of employment or practice related to a particular profession
- progression towards professional registration in a particular profession. (QAA, 2020b, pp. 2-3)

Appendix 2: Generic themes relating to UK strategic postgraduate level descriptors

Table 5 presents the generic themes identified from a scoping activity of UK strategic PG level descriptors to support understanding the context of PGNE prior to research implementation.

Table 5: Generic themes relating to UK strategic postgraduate level descriptors

Source	QAA (2014)	SCQF Partnership (2012)	QAAHE (2013); QAAS (no date)	Common themes identified across the PG descriptors
Context	Quality Code descriptor masters degree education	Key generic characteristics associated level 11 descriptor	Definitive statements for the seven facets of masters level study	
Associated description	<p>Upon achievement of qualification the student will:</p> <p>Demonstrate;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Systematic understanding of knowledge, critical awareness and insight at the forefront of academic or professional practice • Comprehensive understanding of techniques and critical evaluation to support research and advanced scholarship • Originality applied to the context of knowledge, practice and research <p>Be able to;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deal systematically and creatively with complex issues • Problem solve with self-direction, originality and autonomy • Further advance high level knowledge, understanding and skills <p>Hold employment qualities and transferable skills e.g.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Initiative • Complex decision-making • Independent approach to learning and CPD 	<p>Key characteristics associated with application to theory, research, practice and, unpredictable, complex and abstract issues</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Critical awareness and understanding • Extensive, detailed knowledge • Originality • Creativity • Critically reflect, analyse, evaluate and synthesise • Advanced skills and techniques • Exercise initiative, autonomy and significant responsibility • Contribute to change • Manage and lead 	<p>Abstraction – extracting and construct new knowledge or meaning</p> <p>Depth of learning</p> <p>Critical research and enquiry skills and attributes</p> <p>Recognising, dealing complexity and unpredictability e.g. to creatively resolve issues</p> <p>Autonomy and responsibility for learning</p> <p>Professionalism, integrity and reflection</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Critical knowledge and understanding • Unpredictable, complex issues • Critical awareness / insight • Originality • Creativity • Critical approaches; knowledge, understanding, reflection, research • Autonomous approach to professional learning • Forefront of practice and change • Professionalism

Appendix 3: Key attributes and characteristics associated with ALNP

Table 6 summarises the key attributes and characteristics associated with the broad concepts of ALNP from professional and HEI perspectives from a scope of associated UK ANP and ALNP strategic frameworks and policies (SCQF Partnership, 2012; QAA, 2014; NICEP, 2016a; RCN, 2018a; 2018c; 2018d; QAA, 2020b; International Council of Nurses Nurse Practitioner / Advanced Practice Nursing Network (ICN NP/APNN), no date; NES, no date; QAAS, no date).

Table 6: Key attributes and characteristics associated with ALNP

ALNP					Key characteristics across ALNP and PGNE
Career Framework Level	Expected qualifications	SCQF (FHEQ) level	Capability across practice	Professional Attributes	Synthesised attributes, themes, characteristics and attributes (Cross mapped with Appendix 2)
Level 7	PG Certificate, Diploma OR Masters' Degree	Level 11 (Level 7)	Clinical, Leadership, Facilitation of learning, Evidence, research and development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experienced • High level of skills and theoretical knowledge • Critical awareness of field knowledge • Interface between fields • Innovative • Responsible for developing and changing practice • Works within a complex and unpredictable environment • Autonomy to manage workload and complex decision-making 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A critical approach to academic and professional nursing practice • Being situated at the forefront of academic, research and professional nursing practice • Applying advanced knowledge, skills and approaches to recognise and creatively address complex and unpredictable nursing / health care issues and decision-making • Being an autonomous professional using integrity, originality, reflection and learning within academic and nursing practice

Appendix 4: Synthesis of background contexts

Figure 20 was developed to support a synthesis of key findings from exploring the context of PGNE within Chapter 2. This figure was also viewed as a potentially reflexive resource that may be helpful to return to deepen understanding of factors which may influence how registered nurses may become situated within PGNE as part of further pre-research enquiry activities.

Figure 20: Strategic contexts towards PGNE

Appendix 5: Supporting literature search strategy implementation

Table 7: Application of the PEO model to identify key search terms for parts one and two literature search strategies

*-Truncation applied to word endings.

Part one literature review		Part two literature review
Aim: To critically explore the state of knowledge relating to workplace support for PGNS to translate or apply their learning in practice.		Aim: To deepen specific understanding of PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP.
Key search terms	Key associated words	Key search terms
1.PG nurs* students (Population)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Masters nursing students • Post-registration nursing students • PG nursing learner • Masters programme(s)/ module(s) • PG programme(s)/module(s) 	PG (or masters) nursing students
2.Experience* (Exposure)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lived experience/s • Perception/s • Understanding • Encounters • Attitudes • Opinions 	Experiences
3.Support* (Exposure)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opportunities • Enablement • Facilitation • Preparation • Staff Support 	Workplace support
4.In practice (Exposure)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work • Workplace • Work-based environment • Employment • Job • Occupation • Clinical practice 	
5.Trans* learning (Outcome)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transferring/Transfer/Transitional/Transition/Translate/Translation of learning • Use of learning • Utilisation of learning • Appl* learning • Implementation of learning 	Appl* learning (and / or) in practice

Table 8: The inclusion and exclusion criteria applied to parts one and two literature search strategies

Search Criteria	Applied to part literature search / review	Inclusion or exclusion criteria	Rationale
Domain	Part 1 & 2	Include only the domain of: Nurs*(Nurse, Nursing, Nurses)	To align to my subject area, literature review, research aim and the context of nursing practice.
Key search terms and associated key words	Part 1	Literature matching the key search terms and/or associated key words (Table 7)	To allow broader, relevant search to be conducted using associated key search words to mitigate search results being too limited by key search words depending on the initial yield of search findings.
	Part 2	Literature matching key search terms only (Table 7)	To ensure the yield of findings most closely aligned to the aim of my literature review.
Publication dates	Part 1	Inclusion of search findings published between: 1 st January 2007 to 31 st December 2017. With the exception of books/eBooks published between: 1 st January 1997 to current date.	To establish an understanding of contemporary, relevant literature associated with my subject area within report timeframes. Publication period broadened for book sources to allow a broader insight into theoretical contexts while maintaining relevance and currency to the context of nursing practice and nurse education.
	Part 2	Inclusion of search findings published between 1 st January 2018 and time of search implementation (anticipated Jan /Feb 2020).	To support; an efficient literature search strategy, iterative literature review and currency of the knowledge to inform justification and originality for my area of research.
Language	Part 1 & 2	Include English language only.	Due to my language being limited to English and timeframes of the review.
Search screen	Part 1 & 2	Inclusion of advanced screen search only.	To support the application of the full search criteria and yield the most relevant search results.
Limiters	Part 1 & 2	Include full text only.	To support the review of literature within my report timeframes.
Expanders	Part 1 & 2	Include also search within full text.	To support a wider identification of relevant literature as part of my search strategy.

Table 9: Data sources used for parts one and two literature search strategies

Data Source / Data Search Engine	Associated type of literature	Rationale
Review of my previous doctorate work reference lists	Journal articles, organisational literature	To build upon understanding the structure and context of my subject area and ensure that any previous seminal findings were included if they remained relevant throughout my iterative review of the literature (Randolph, 2009).
British Library e-theses online service (EThOS)	Doctoral theses (grey literature)	Provided full text access to doctoral theses from UK HEI to identify previous research undertaken relating to my research area (UWS, 2020).
Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL)	Journal articles	CINAHL provided an extensive database of full text articles from global credible published nursing and allied health professional journals to yield journal articles relevant to my subject area and the domain of nursing.
Education Source database	Journal articles	Education Source provided a large database of full text journal articles focused on education including health education which allowed for the identification of findings relevant to PGNE and translation of learning (UWS, 2020).
One Search database	a. Books/eBooks b. Journal articles	The associated university's search database of books and eBooks which aimed to support the identification and exploration of theoretical concepts associated with my subject area (part one search strategy only due to scoping approach).
Organisational websites	Grey literature	Identification of grey literature from relevant organisations aimed to inform the strategic and professional context of my subject area e.g. policies, standards, strategies.
Web of Science database	Conference literature	A citation indexing service recommended for identifying conference literature, journal articles and eBook citations (UWS, 2020). Potentially the findings yield aimed to inform an understanding of existing research, scholarly activity, projects surrounding my subject area (part one review only due to scoping approach).
Additional data sources used for part two literature search strategy		

Data Source / Data Search Engine	Associated type of literature	Rationale
American Doctoral Dissertations	e-Dissertations	An American electronic doctoral dissertation database (UWS, 2020). Used to potentially identify existing body of US doctoral research that may relate to specific aim of literature review and deepen understanding and broaden context of practice.
DART-Europe e-thesis portal	e-Thesis	To identify existing body of European doctoral research that may relate to specific aim of literature review and deepen understanding across broader contexts of practice. A European e-thesis portal in partnership with national and university library providing access to electronic research theses from 567 universities across 29 countries (DART-Europe, no date).
Education Resources Information Center (ERIC)	Journal articles	To identify and explore research within the specific context of education. The database is associated with a US based focused, potentially supporting international research enquiry (UWS, 2020).

Table 10: Key abbreviations used within the example literature search implementation templates

The abbreviations used relate to Tables 11-12.

Abbreviation Used	Meaning
C	Key search term
B	Boolean operator
✓	Applied
X	Not applied
Y	Yes
N	No
P	Partially
U	Unknown
NA	Not applicable
JA	Journal article
Filled grey background section	Search findings deemed appropriate for stage one or two review.

Table 11: Example of literature search implementation template

Example template developed to initially record parts one and two literature search findings.

Part One: Literature search A															
Search data source	CINAHL (EBSCO host research databases)														
Type of literature	Journal articles														
Domain	Nurs*														
Publication inclusion dates	01/01/2007 – 31/12/2017														
Language	English														
Search screen	Advanced														
Limiters	Full text only														
Expander	Also search within full text														
Search Code for literature source e.g. article	Key search term and/or Boolean phrase applied to search													Total number of search findings (including duplicates)	
	C1	B	C2	B	C3	B	C4	B	C5	B	C6	B	C7		
A1	√	and	√	and	√	and	√								1,071
A2	√	and	√	and	√	and	√				and	√			959 (all criteria applied)
A2.1	√	and	√	and	√	and	√	-	X	-	√				967(English language limit not applied)
A2.2	√	and	√	and	√	and	√	-	X	-	√				1,292 (inclusion date not applied)
A3	√	and	√	and	√	and	√	and	√	and	√	√			205
A3.1	√	not	X	and	√	and	√	and	√	and	√	√			221
A3.2	√	not	X	and	√	and	√	not	X	and	√	√			1,260
A3.2.1	√	not	X	and	√	and	√	not	X	and	√	√			1,271 (English language limit not applied)
A3.2.2	√	not	X	and	√	and	√	not	X	and	√	√			1,676 (inclusion date not applied)
A3.3	√	and	√	not	X	and	√	and	√	and	√	√			229
A3.3.1	√	and	√	not	X	and	√	and	√	and	√	√			230 (English language limit not applied)
A4	√	and	√	and	√	and	√	not	X	and	√	√			754
A5	√	not	X	not	X	not	X	and	√	and	√	√			258
A5.1	√	not	X	not	X	not	X	and	√	and	√	√			266 (English language limit not applied)
A6	√	and	√	and	√	and	√	and	√	and	√	and	√	√	196
Total														Inserted on completion of searches	

Table 12: Example of stage one literature search implementation template

Example template used for parts one and two literature search strategies.

Part One: Literature search A					
Search Code and Item Number (I) for personal referencing management	Automatic search item reference used within electronic results record	Search criteria met	Title and/ or abstract review	Material type or brief description	Deemed relevant for Stage 2 review
A6.I1 A6.I2	College & Association of Registered Nurses of Alberta (2008a; 2008b)	Y	N	Summary of professional awardees. Duplicate result shorten version of A6.1	N
A6.I3	End of Life Care Journal (2009)	Y	Y	Conference abstracts 3 relevant to subject area; presentation numbers 1, 20, 102	Y
A6.I4	16th International Social Pharmacy Workshop (2010)	N	N	Conference titles and abstracts. Domain of pharmacy, no specifically relevant conference titles/abstracts to justify reviewing beyond nursing domain	N
A6.I5	Abstracts from the health professional and health sciences educational research symposium (2010)	Y	Y	Conference abstracts; Abstract 8 for further review due to relevance to subject area	Y
A6.I6	Oral presentations (2010)	N	N	Conference abstracts within medical domain, no abstracts of sufficient relevance to go beyond nursing domain	N
A6.I7	Poster presentations (in alphabetical order by first author) (2010)	Y	N	Poster abstracts focused on physiological and mental health	N
A6.I8	Noticeboard (2011)	Y	N	Journal new update, although highlighted NMC review of education	N
A6.I9	Improving nurses skills through e-learning (2012)	Y	N	JA	N
A6.I10	Meeting abstracts (2012)	Y	N	Meeting abstracts, domain of pharmaceutical medicine	N

Table 13: Key abbreviations used within the example literature search implementation template

The abbreviations used relate to Table 14.

Area	Full Term	Abbreviation used in table
Origin	Europe	E
	International	I
	United Kingdom	UK
Domain	Education	Ed
	Nursing	Nurs
	Other	O
Type of Literature	Dissertation / Thesis	D / T
	Journal Article	JA
	Other to be stated e.g. Discussion piece, Strategy	o
Type of Study	Mixed	M
	Qualitative	Ql
	Quantitative	Qn
Action from stage two review	Yes, relevant for stage three critical review	YCR
	Potential for critical review in the future if literature review needs to be widened	PCR
	Not relevant for stage three critical review	NCR
	Not for stage three critical review but provides background context	NCR - BC
Inclusion Criteria	Met	X
-	Not applicable	NA

Table 14: Example of stage two literature search implementation template

Example template developed and used for parts one and two literature search strategies. Slight amendments were made to the template depending on the specific parts one or two search strategy inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Search Code and Item Identifier	A6.I3	A.I5	A6.I20 /B2.I23	A6.I22	A6.I37
Origin	UK		UK		UK
Domain	Nurs	Nurs	Medicine	Nurs	Nurs
Specialist area	Palliative Care	International Nurs educ	Medical graduates	Mid – Senior career	Paediatrics
Type of literature	Conference: oral (No.1, 20) and poster presentation abstracts (No.102)	Conference abstract No.8: Summary of study as part of larger study	Conference abstract No.31	JA: Career pathway stories	JA: Research
Type of study	1 and 20: N.A 102: Hermetic phenomenology, interviews	Exploratory, interviews	Questionnaires	N.A	Practice Project; Literature review, survey, interviews
PG nurs* students				X	
Masters nursing students		X		X	
Post-registration nursing students					
PG nursing learner					
Other:	MSc Multi professionals including Nurs		Medical graduates		
Experienc*, lived experienc*	X No.102	X		X	X
Perception/s Understanding		X	X		
Attitudes					
Opinions					
Other:					
Support*				X	
Opportunities				X	
Enablement					
Facilitation					
Preparation					
Staff Support					X
Other:					
In practice	X	X			
Work, Workplace Work-based environment	X				
Employment, Job Occupation					
Clinical practice					
Other:					
Trans* learning					
Use learning					
Utilisation of learning					
Appl* learning		X			
Implementation of learning					
Other:					
Significance of findings	Mixed practice projects and research	Research	Research limited to abstract	Non research, professional stories	Research; practice project
Additional Information	No.1 focus on competences No.20 focus in research in palliative care No.102 including focus on theory practice gap	Smaller study limited information as abstract only, identified as linking to larger study D.113 code reference	Focus on medical role transitions	Highlights person values of MSc studies to career pathway	Focus on development of learning and development policy and practice
Action	No. 102 if can source primary paper	NCR as full reference to D.113	NCR	PCR	NCR

Table 15: Summary of part one literature search findings

Brief description of search strategy (+ = and)	Total number of search findings (including potential duplicates)	Total number of relevant findings from stage one review of title and abstract	Total number of relevant findings from stage two review of full text relevant against criteria checklist
Part One Search Strategy			
Search terms applied: PG nurs + Experienc* + Support* + In practice + Trans* learning, Nurs* + Research Full inclusion criteria applied Search source: CINAHL Source type: Journal articles	196	24	2
Search terms applied: PG nurs + Experienc*+ Support* + In practice + Trans* learning Full inclusion criteria applied Search source: Education Source Source type: Journal articles	242	16 (1 duplicate from A6 search)	1
Search terms applied: PG nurs + Experienc*+ Support* + In practice + Trans* learning Full inclusion criteria applied Search source: Web of Science Source type: Conference literature	40	7	1
Limited search engine functionality influencing search strategy Search terms applied: PG nurs* + Nurs* Partial search criteria applied: No full text option Search source: One Search Source type: Journal articles	71	18	5
Limited search engine functionality influencing search strategy Search terms applied: PG nurs*+ Nurs* + Trans* learning or associated terms Partial search criteria applied: No full text option, extended publication period due to source type Search source: One Search Source type: Books	114	5	4
Limited search engine functionality influencing search strategy Search terms applied: PG nurs*+ Nurs* Partial search criteria applied: No full text option Search source: eThOS Source type: e-thesis	14	1	1
Limited search engine functionality influencing search strategy Search terms applied: PG nurs*+ Nurs* Partial search criteria applied: Reduced publication period to support currency Search source: Organisational websites Source type: Grey literature, policy and professional	28	28	18
Search terms applied: PG nurs + Experienc* Inclusion criteria applied manually Search source: Previous doctorate work Source type: Journal articles	6	4 (as one duplicate of A6)	2
Total results part one	711	103	34 (29 critically reviewed as books excluded due to timeframes and aim of review)

Table 16: Summary of part two literature search findings

Brief description of search strategy (+ = and)	Total number of search findings (including potential duplicates)	Total number of relevant findings from stage one review of title and abstract	Total number of relevant findings from stage two review of full text relevant against criteria checklist
Search terms applied: PG nursing student*, Masters nursing student*, Experience* (experiences or perceptions or attitudes or views or feelings or qualitative or perspective), Work* Support (work* or workplace or support or strategies), Appl* learning, In practice (or clinical setting) with additional Subject Heading search (2) Full inclusion criteria applied Search source: CINAHL Source type: Journal articles	293	10	4
Search terms applied: PG nursing student*, Masters nursing student*, Experience* (experiences or perceptions or attitudes or views or feelings or qualitative or perspective), Work* Support (work* or workplace or support or strategies), Appl* learning, In practice (or clinical setting) Full inclusion criteria applied Search source: Education Source Source type: Journal articles	37	5	2
Search terms applied: PG nursing student*, Masters nursing student*, Experience* (experiences or perceptions or attitudes or views or feelings or qualitative or perspective), Work* Support (work* or workplace or support or strategies), Appl* learning, In practice (or clinical setting) Full inclusion criteria applied Search source: ERIC Source type: Journal articles	2	1	0
Search terms applied: Combined terms due to search limitation including: PG nursing student*, Masters nursing student*, Experience* Work*support, Appl* learning, In practice Full inclusion criteria applied - Manually due to search options available Search source: eThOS Source type: Published thesis	17	1	1
Search terms applied: PG nursing student*, Masters nursing student* as no results for full terms Full inclusion criteria applied – Manually due to search options available Search source: DART-Europe Source type: Published thesis	17	0	0
Search terms applied: PG nursing student*, Masters nursing student*, Experience* Work* support, Application of learning, In practice Full inclusion criteria applied – Manually due to search option available Search source: American Doctoral Dissertations Source type: Published dissertations / thesis	34	0	0
Total part two review	589	17	7
Total parts one and two reviews	1300	120	36

Figure 21: Example critical analysis tool template

Figure 21 provides an example of a qualitative critical analysis template developed to support the process of critical appraisal within the part one and two literature search and review strategies (Letts *et al.*, 2007a; 2007b; Caldwell, Henshaw and Taylor, 2011). I developed and used similar critical analysis tool templates specifically for quantitative research (Law *et al.*, 1998a; 1998b; Caldwell, Henshaw and Taylor, 2011), grey literature (Weber, 2010; Greenhalgh, 2014) and other sources e.g. non research, discussion or opinion journal articles (Hek and Langton, 2000).

Colour codes and themes were applied to each of the completed templates as part of critical synthesis and analysis processes of the part one and two literature reviews. The content of the colour codes was then further analysed to support the development of overarching, main and sub themes as per Table 17 example guided by principles of Braun and Clarke (2006; 2020a) thematic and reflexive thematic analysis.

Search Code, Item Identifier (1) and Paper Number (P)	Sections completed with critique of article / source	
Citation		
Author Background		
Area of review	Key considerations guidance	Data extraction from literature source - Sections completed with critique of article / source
Study Purpose		
Was the purpose/aim and/or research question stated clearly? Yes / No	Summary of purpose: Was the purpose / rationale of the study relevant to the chosen subject area? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key considerations: research, professional, knowledge, current issue contexts. How was the purpose relevant to the chosen subject area?	
Literature		
Was relevant background literature reviewed? Yes / No	What was the justification for the study? Was the justification clear and compelling? Key considerations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sources • Synthesis of key/relevant literature and discussion • Currency / relevance of literature • Inclusive of qualitative and quantitative evidence 	

Search Code, Item Identifier (1) and Paper Number (P)	Sections completed with critique of article / source	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Were there gaps associated with knowledge, literature and/or research? • Is the study applicable to practice? 	
Continue review	Is the study still relevant for further review? Yes / No	
Study Design		
What was the design? Were advantages and disadvantages of the design acknowledged? Yes / No / Not addressed / Not applicable	Description of the advantages and disadvantages of the design and potential implications? Was the design appropriate based on the study aim, purpose or question? Why?	
Was a theoretical perspective identified? Yes / No	Description of the theoretical or philosophical background and rationale for the study inclusive of the researcher's perspective (Caldwell, Henshaw and Taylor, 2011). Key considerations: researcher worldview, beliefs, nature of the results, depth and involvement of participants, type of reasoning (inductive, theory construction)	
Method used?	Description of the method used to answer the research aim / purpose/ questions? Did the methods align with the philosophical approach and purpose? Yes / No Explanation:	
Sampling		
Was the purposeful process of sampling described? Yes / No/ Limited	Description of the sampling method? Was the sampling method appropriate and align to the aim / purpose or question?	
Was sampling undertaken until redundancy/ theoretical saturation in data was reached? Yes / No / Not addressed	Were the participants described in adequate detail including participant characteristics? How is the sample applicable to the chosen subject area?	
Continue review	Is the study still relevant for further review? Yes / No	
Ethical Considerations		
Was ethical approval achieved? Yes / No Was informed consent gained? Yes / No / Not addressed (Unknown)	Description the ethical considerations and associated actions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Was ethical approval sought from appropriate organisations or committees? • Were there any ethical considerations in view of the chosen methodology? If so, what were these and how were they addressed? • Describe whether any of the ethical issues had implications to the research process or on the research findings? (Caldwell, Henshaw and Taylor, 2011) How was consent obtained and recorded? Description if any ethical considerations / issues had implication to the research process / findings:	

Search Code, Item Identifier (1) and Paper Number (P)	Sections completed with critique of article / source	
Data Collection		
<u>Descriptive Clarity</u> Clear and complete description of : Site: Yes / No Participants: Yes / No Role of researcher and relationship with participants addressed: Yes / No Identification of researcher assumptions and / or biases: Yes / No	Description of the context of the study (should be clear): Sufficient understanding of the 'whole picture'? Descriptions of the role and relationship of the researcher? Was it appropriate and aligned to the study? Describe the identified assumptions and biases? What was missing? How does this influence your understanding of the research?	
<u>Procedural Rigour</u> Was used in data collection strategies? Yes / No / Not addressed (unstated)	Was adequate information provided about data collection? Key considerations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researcher's role • Access, collection method, time, amount, training Description of flexibility in design and data collection methods?	
Data Analysis		
<u>Analytical Rigour</u> Data analysis was inductive? Yes / No / Not addressed (unstated) Findings were consistent and reflective of the data? Yes/No	Description of data analysis method: Key considerations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How did the findings emerge from the data? Analysis methods used, organised, managed Methods appropriate? Yes / No / Partial Why? What were the findings? How were the findings presented? E.g. clear, logical and relevant way?	
<u>Auditability</u> <u>Decision Trail</u> developed? Yes / No / Not addressed (unstated) Process of data analysis was adequately described? Yes / No / Not addressed (unstated)	Description of research decisions / audit process? Description of rationale given for development of themes?	
Theoretical Connections		

Search Code, Item Identifier (1) and Paper Number (P)	Sections completed with critique of article / source	
Did a meaningful picture of the phenomenon under study emerge? Yes / No	How were the concepts clarified and refined? Where relationships made clear? Description of the conceptual frameworks that emerged? Implications to practice / chosen area:	
Overall Rigour		
Evidence of the 4 components of trustworthiness? Credibility: Yes / No Transferability: Yes / No Dependability: Yes / No Confirmability: Yes / No	Description of the actions taken to ensure / address: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Credibility • Transferability • Dependability • Confirmability Describe the meaning and relevance: does the study have to practice / chosen subject area?	
Conclusion and Implications		
Conclusions were appropriate / aligned to the study findings? Yes / No The findings contributed to theory development and / or future practice / research? Yes / No Limitations were acknowledged? Yes / No	What did the study conclude? What are the implication to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practice • Theory • Research • Subject area Describe the main limitations of the study? Describe any other influencing factors?	
Key researcher thoughts and considerations to subject area / literature review process		

Appendix 6: Theme development supporting literature review

Table 17: Example of theme development from thematic and reflexive thematic analysis of the part one literature review findings

Following initial theming into coloured codes, the colour code themes were then reviewed to identify specific overarching, main and sub themes as illustrated within the example table below.

P = Paper Number

Overarching Theme 1:	Policy Context			
Main themes	1.Current and Future Context of Healthcare	2.Current and Future Context of the Nursing Workforce	3.Influence of Professional Regulation	4.Current and Future Context of Nurse Education
Sub themes	<p>Global, UK and Scottish influencing factors (largely commonalities across)</p> <p><u>Population demographics:</u></p> <p>Increasing aging population (P11,14)</p> <p><u>Meeting healthcare needs:</u></p> <p>Meet healthcare system needs (P11,15,26)</p> <p>Meet universal health needs (P11)</p> <p>Meet sustainable health goals (P11)</p> <p>Address health inequalities (P15,21)</p> <p>Increasing public expectations, confidence, protection, standards (P16,17,18)</p> <p>Provision of the best possible evidence-based care and treatment (P12,18)</p> <p>Safe, effective, quality, person-centred (compassionate) care (P15,21,25,26,27)</p>	<p><u>Association with current and future context of healthcare:</u></p> <p>-Current and future nursing workforce is (critically) associated with addressing, meeting and providing a response to future population health needs/goals healthcare systems and workforce needs, models of care (P11,14,21,22,23,25,26)</p> <p>-Link with transforming roles (nursing) agenda (P14,21,26)</p> <p>-Link with provision and maintenance of quality care, safe, effective, person-centred care (P11,16,18,19,21,25,26,27)</p> <p><u>Current nursing workforce:</u></p> <p>Aging workforce / declining workforce (P11,14,15)</p> <p>Staffing levels/ Stress (P14,26)</p> <p>A required graduate level of education, diversity/ attitudes amongst existing workforce (P26)</p> <p>Maintain knowledge, skills through continuing processes, learning and reflection (P16,18)</p>	<p>Potential difference / variation globally.</p> <p><u>UK perspective</u></p> <p><u>Purpose:</u></p> <p>Public standards, safety & expectations; Maintaining: professional standards (P18,19)</p> <p>Adherence to the Code of Practice (P16)</p> <p>Revalidation requirements (P18,19)</p> <p>Regulation, maintenance and monitoring of NMC approved programmes and standards that AEs must meet (P17)</p> <p><u>Influencing factors:</u></p> <p>Revalidation / Code requirements: Up to date, share professional knowledge, skills, development and practice (P16,18)</p> <p>Improve practice & develop new skills (P16)</p> <p>Response to changes & advanced in nursing (P16)</p>	<p><u>Global nurse education developments:</u></p> <p>Shift to all graduate profession (P26)</p> <p>High quality education (graduate/advanced levels) associated as an enabler of quality or better care/outcomes (P14,25,26)</p> <p><u>UK and Scottish practice:</u></p> <p><u>policy focus on:</u></p> <p>Education commission and design aligning with health care and service needs e.g. flexible, effective, right support (P14,17,21,25,26)</p> <p><u>Current and future issues:</u></p> <p>Commissioning particularly relating to (consistency, agreement) advanced levels of practice (P13)</p> <p>Fit for purpose models of education (P26)</p> <p>Funding/ support/ Preceptorship (P26)</p> <p>Need for structured, sustainable coordinated and focused models of education, (commissioning and funding – P25) but also flexible and effective professional education (P17,22)</p> <p>Level 7 associated with advanced practice and MSc level 11 education requirement (P19)</p>

Table 18: Extraction of theme data to support literature review

Table 18 relates to development of Figure 5 to bringing together identified components relating to the concept of support for PGNS within Chapter 2.

Support Concept (Need)	System	Emotional and Moral	Facilitative
Support Factor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academic ability (Drennan and Hyde, 2008a; Millberg <i>et al.</i>, 2014; Rooney, 2015) • Costs; fees, funding, time (Black and Bonner, 2011; Rooney, 2015; Ng, Eley and Tuckett, 2016; HEE, no date) Employer and Managerial role (Drennan and Hyde, 2008b; Richardson, 2013; Millberg <i>et al.</i>, 2014; Rooney, 2015; Ng, Eley and Tuckett, 2016) • Mentorship and Preceptorship (Lofmark and Mamhidir, 2010; Black and Bonner, 2011; Shearer and Adams, 2012; Illingworth <i>et al.</i>, 2013; Richardson, 2013; Millberg <i>et al.</i>, 2014; Rooney, 2015; HEE, no date) • Placement Learning Support (Black and Bonner, 2011; Illingworth <i>et al.</i>, 2013) • Programme Choice (Drennan and Hyde, 2008b; Rooney, 2015) • Renumeration; pay, workload, role (Drennan, 2008a; Drennan and Hyde, 2008b; Millberg <i>et al.</i>, 2014) Time: Learning, study, role release (Drennan and Hyde, 2008b; Black and Bonner, 2011; Millberg <i>et al.</i>, 2014; Rooney, 2015; Ng, Eley and Tuckett, 2016) • Workplace culture (Black and Bonner, 2011; Millberg <i>et al.</i>, 2014) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moral and emotional actions; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ consultation, affirmation, respect, understanding and appreciation (Millberg <i>et al.</i>, 2014) ○ encouragement (Millberg <i>et al.</i>, 2014; Rooney, 2015) ○ support (Black and Bonner, 2011); managerial/employer (Rooney, 2015; Ng, Eley and Tuckett, 2016) • Professional attitudes (Illingworth <i>et al.</i>, 2013; Millberg <i>et al.</i>, 2014; Rooney, 2015) • Professional recognition, status and role legitimacy (Illingworth <i>et al.</i>, 2013; Millberg <i>et al.</i>, 2014; Ng, Eley and Tuckett, 2016) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opportunities to utilise learning and knowledge in practice towards role development and change (Illingworth <i>et al.</i>, 2013; Richardson, 2013; Millberg <i>et al.</i>, 2014; Rooney, 2015; HEE, no date) • Contribution to patient care (Millberg <i>et al.</i>, 2014) • Contribution and use of academic skills, competence and advanced roles (Illingworth <i>et al.</i>, 2013; Millberg <i>et al.</i>, 2014) Career development and enhancement opportunities (Shearer and Adams, 2012; Millberg <i>et al.</i>, 2014; Rooney, 2015; Ng, Eley and Tuckett, 2016) • Encouragement towards further learning (Millberg <i>et al.</i>, 2014) • Job satisfaction (Shearer and Adams, 2012; Ng, Eley and Tuckett, 2016)

Appendix 7: Evidence of ethical approval

10/07/2019 ([REDACTED] ethics co-chair)

Dear Anna Buckby,

Your application 8408: A hermeneutic phenomenology study to explore postgraduate nursing students' lived experiences of workplace support to apply learning in practice., submission reference 6805, has been approved, with conditions, by the Health and Life Sciences SEC. Please work closely with your supervisor to complete these changes to their satisfaction. I also ask that the supervisor contacts the co-chair to confirm that the changes have been made. **You may proceed with your study provided you meet the conditions outlined below:**

All the conditions outlined were met and approved by my Professional Doctorate Supervisory Team prior to the implementation of the research study.

Appendix 8: Gatekeeper permission request

Dear [*Gatekeeper details inserted*],

My name is (*name inserted*) and I am a Professional Doctorate Student within the School of Health and Life Sciences. I am writing to ask for your permission to conduct a hermeneutic phenomenology study to explore postgraduate nursing students' experiences of workplace support to apply learning in practice.

In due course, the study will require voluntary recruitment of 6-10 continuing postgraduate nursing students' from SCQF level 11 programmes and modules under the remit of (*details inserted*); including the (*specific PG programme details inserted*) programme.

If this is possible, please could you arrange for a (*specific details inserted*) Administrator / Coordinator to send students an invite to participate in my study. Please note personal and research data from participants will be securely stored and destroyed in line with UWS data protection and management guidelines (UWS, 2015; 2019), GDPR regulations (EPCEU, 2016) and actions within my ethics application. The study has been approved by the UWS Ethics Committee and will be supervised by (*Names and roles of professional doctorate supervisory team inserted*) within the (*Details of associated area and HEI inserted*). If you are willing to support this request, could you send me an email to confirm that you permit me to access the students.

The specific timeframes for recruitment activities to commence are still to be confirmed. If you wish to receive an update regarding anticipated timeframes for recruiting participants, please also include this within your email reply. Please note that your details will be anonymised when including gatekeeper information within my thesis.

Please email me if I can provide any information or if you have any questions.

Thank you for your time in reading this request.

Yours sincerely,

(*Name inserted*)

Professional Doctorate Student

School of Health and Life Sciences, University of the West of Scotland (full address details inserted)

Email: (*email contact details inserted*)

Please note that email is the best way of contacting me and my supervisory team.

Supervisory Team Contact Details and Information (inserted below)

(Adapted from: Coventry University, no date)

Appendix 9: Evidence of gatekeeper permissions

[Redacted]

To: Anna Buckby

Mon 19/07/2021 14:35

Hi Anna,

Thank you for getting in touch, your study sounds very interesting. I am happy for you to contact the students on the MSc [Redacted] programme, I am sure some of them would be interested in supporting you with this.

Good luck with your study and if you require anything else from me, please let me know.

Kind regards,

[Redacted]

[Redacted]

Lecturer / Programme Leader (MSc : [Redacted])

[Redacted]

To: Anna Buckby

Mon 19/07/2021 08:15

Yes that's fine

Get [Outlook for Android](#)

Appendix 10: Recruitment email

Version 4

Email sent on behalf of Professional Doctorate Student: Invite to Participate in Professional Doctorate Study.

Dear Postgraduate Student,

***Are you a postgraduate nursing student working in practice?
Would you be interested in sharing your experiences of workplace support to apply your
learning in practice?***

Hello, my name is (*inserted here*) and I am a professional doctorate student at UWS. I would like to invite continuing postgraduate nursing students' (those that have completed one full term) and practising as professionally registered nurses to take part in a research study.

The research study aims to explore postgraduate nursing students' experiences of workplace support to apply learning in practice. Voluntary participation in the study would include receiving a telephone interview call from me at a time convenient to you, to share your experiences of workplace support to apply your postgraduate learning in practice.

If you are interested in taking part, please read the attached Participant Information Sheet including the Privacy Notice that explains the purpose of the study and what would be involved.

If you would like to volunteer to participate, please email me (*email: email details inserted*) by the (*date inserted*) using your student email address.

Please also email me if you have any questions.

Thank you for your time in reading this email.

Kind regards,

Professional Doctorate Student, School of Health and Life Sciences, UWS

Email: (*email contact details inserted*)

Please note that email is the best way of contacting me.

Appendix 11: Participant information sheet

Version 6

Participant Information Sheet

(Date version inserted here)

Are you a postgraduate nursing student working in practice?

Would you be interested in sharing your experiences of workplace support to apply your learning in practice?

My name is (*name inserted*) and I am a professional doctorate student at the University of the West of Scotland (UWS). I would like to invite continuing postgraduate nursing students (those that have completed one full term) and practising as professionally registered nurses to take part in a research study.

The research study aims to explore postgraduate nursing students' experiences of workplace support to apply learning in practice.

Before you decide whether you would like to participate in the study, it is important, that I explain why this study is being undertaken and what your participation would involve.

Do I need to take part in this study?

No, participation is voluntary, this means it is your choice whether or not you participate in this study.

Why take part in this study?

By sharing your experiences as a postgraduate nursing student, you will contribute to the body of knowledge surrounding workplace support for postgraduate nursing students (PGNS) to apply learning in practice.

Collectively, anonymised findings will be used, published, and disseminated. This may inform future approaches and research to further workplace support for PGNS to apply learning in practice, and potentially contribute to workplace development to support PGNS to apply learning in practice.

The study has received ethical approval from the UWS Ethics Committee and will be overseen by my Professional Doctorate Supervisory Team.

What will you need to do if you choose to take part?

- Please email me by the (*date inserted here*) to confirm that you would like to participate. I will then email you to organise a convenient interview date and time and provide you with an electronic informed consent form. Once you have read the forms, please email me a copy of your completed consent form to confirm that you wish to be interviewed prior to our agreed interview date.
- I will make the telephone call to you so that you do not incur any costs for the call.
- I will conduct our interview from a private, individual room from a UWS campus location. It is recommended that you participate in the interview from an individual, private location, free from disruption to support confidentiality, anonymity, and provide you with a safe and comfortable interview environment.
- During the audio recorded telephone interview, I will ask you as a postgraduate nursing student to share your experiences of workplace support to apply your learning in practice. The interview is anticipated to last around 60 minutes. However, the duration of the interview will be dependent on the time that you feel you need to share your experiences or the time that you have available.
- Please note you are free to withdraw from the interview at any time, without any explanation required.
- If the number of potential participants exceeds those required for the study you will receive an email to inform you that your participation will not be required, however if a participant withdraws from the study, you may be asked if you still wish to take part.

What will happen to the information that you give?

- Your personal data e.g. name, telephone number and student email address will be held only by myself. Any personal and research data e.g. anonymised interview transcripts will be securely stored and destroyed in adherence to; Doctoral College (UWS, 2019a), the General Data Protection Regulations (EPCEU, 2016) and University Ethics Committee (UWS, 2016, 2020).
- To support anonymity, pseudonymation and random participant codes e.g. Participant E will be used when presenting and disseminating the research findings (raw data) or discussing the findings with my supervisory team.

Interested in taking part? Any questions?

If you would like to ask questions about the study or participate in the interviews, please contact me by email (*email contact detailed inserted here*) using your student email address by the (*date inserted here*).

If you wish to contact a member of my supervisory team or an independent person in relation to this research study, please email:

(Professional doctorate supervisor names, roles and email contact details inserted here).

Or Independent contact *(Independent contact name, role and email details inserted here).*

Please note that email is the best way to contact me or a member of my supervisory team. Please email using your student email address.

Thank you for taking the time to read this invitation, the participant information and privacy notice (included below).

Kind regards,

(Name inserted)

Professional Doctorate Student

Email: *(Contact student email address inserted)*

School of Health and Life Sciences, University of the West of Scotland

Stephenson Place, Hamilton International Technology Park, South Lanarkshire

G72 0LH, Scotland, UK.

Privacy Notice

The University of the West of Scotland (the "University" or "we") is the sponsor for this study based in the United Kingdom. The University is committed to looking after any information that you make available to us and we aim to be clear about what we will do with your data. This privacy notice explains when and why we collect personal information about you and how we will use this information.

We will use the information you have provided to us in order to carry out the research study and our basis for doing this is that [universities and their researchers have a legitimate interest in carrying out such research projects OR it is in the public interest for us to do so]. We will act as the data controller in relation to the information you provide. Will we not share your information with any third parties that are not part of the research group mentioned in this Participant Information Notice. We will keep identifiable information about you for the minimal period required e.g. on completion of the study or 10 years after the study has finished.

The information you have provided to us will not be transferred out of the EEA.

You can find information about:-

- The details of our data protection officer
- How we will keep your information safe
- What choices you have in relation to your information
- How you can complain about the use of your information.

in our privacy notice which you can read here - <https://www.uws.ac.uk/about-our-website/privacy/>

Some of the rights you have in relation to your information that are set out in the privacy notice are limited, as we need to manage your information in specific ways in order for the research to be reliable and accurate. If you withdraw from the study, we will delete the information about you that we have already obtained, where it is possible for us to do so. To safeguard, your rights, we will use the minimum personally-identifiable information possible.

References supporting the development of the participant information sheet

Smythe (2011); EPCEU (2016); UEC (2016; 2020); NHS HRA (no datea; no dateb); University of the West of Scotland (no dateb; no datec).

Appendix 12: Potential response emails

Version 4

Option 1: Initial response email

Dear (*Responding postgraduate nursing students name to be inserted*),

Thank you for your interest in participating in the research study.

Once you have read the Participant Information Sheet including the Privacy Notice information as attached. Please complete and return the attached electronic consent form via your student email address to me by email (*email contact details inserted*) by the (*date inserted – based on two week decision-making / response timeframe*).

I will then email you to organise a convenient interview date and time.

Please could you also provide your contact telephone number so that I can contact you on the agreed date and time of the interview.

Please email me if you have any questions.

Thank you.

Kind regards,

(*Name inserted*)

Professional Doctorate Student, School of Health and Life Sciences, University of the West of Scotland

Email: (*Email contact details inserted*)

Please note that email is the best way to contact me.

Option 2: Response email if email received with completed consent form

Dear (*Responding postgraduate students name to be inserted*),

Thank you for your email and returning the completed consent form (*option to be selected*: and contact information or: Please could you also provide your contact telephone number so that I can contact you on the agreed date and time of the interview.)

Please could you email me via your student email address to confirm if any of the following dates below would be convenient to participate in the telephone interview. Please also let me know what time would be convenient to you.

(*Potential dates to be inserted*)

Please email me if you have any questions too.

Thank you.

Kind regards,

(*Name inserted*)

Professional Doctorate Student, School of Health and Life Sciences, University of the West of Scotland.

Email: (*Email contact details inserted*)

Option 3: Response email if further recruitment not required

Dear (*Responding postgraduate nursing students name to be inserted*),

Thank you for your interest in participating in the research study. Your interest is appreciated however, as the sample for the study has now been met your participation is not required at this time. However, if a participant withdraws from the study, you may be asked if you still wish to take part.

Please note if further recruitment to the study is undertaken this will be communicated by a standardised email.

Thank you for your interest and taking time to respond.

Kind regards,

(*Name inserted*)

Professional Doctorate Student, School of Health and Life Sciences, University of the West of Scotland.

Email: (*Email contact details inserted*)

(Please note that email is the best way to contact me)

Appendix 13: Informed consent form

Version 1.09

School of Health and Life Sciences

Stephenson Place
Hamilton International Park
South Lanarkshire
G72 0LH
01698 283 100

(Relevant date inserted)

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Title of Project: A hermeneutic phenomenology study of postgraduate nursing students' lived experiences of workplace support to apply learning in practice.

Name of Researcher: *(Name Inserted)*, Professional Doctorate Student.

Name of School: *(Name inserted)*

This form can be completed:

- Option 1: By saving an electronic copy of the consent form. Then type your initials inside the boxes. Then type your full name or add your electronic signature in the sections entitled 'name of the participant' and 'signature' section.
- Option 2: By downloading and printing the attached consent form. Then completing in handwritten text to be scanned.

Once the form has been completed by Option 1 or 2. Please send me an email via your student email address with your consent form attached confirming that you wish to take part in the interview.

Insert initials into the
box below

1. I confirm that I have read and understood the participant information sheet dated (*date inserted here*) for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.

2. I confirm that I have read and understood the Privacy Notice and understand how my personal information / data will be used and what will happen to it e.g. secure storage and destruction processes.

3. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, up to the point of interview completion without giving any reason and without any consequences.

4. I consent to providing the researcher, (*name inserted*) with my contact telephone number and student email address so that I can be contacted to participate in the research interview.

5. I consent to the telephone interview being digitally audio recorded as part of the project.

6. I understand that anonymised data cannot be withdrawn once included in the study e.g. data analysis has commenced.

7. I understand that anonymous quotes will be sensitively used to present, share and disseminate the study findings.

8. I understand that there may be risks to privacy, confidentiality and anonymity if;
- I self-disclose my participation to others.
 - A professional or care concern is raised during the interview or debriefing process. Concerns raised may be discussed with the researcher's supervisory team and appropriately reported based on the researcher's professional duty of care.
9. I understand that I will be offered a debrief conversation and signposted to potential support and wellbeing services should any sensitive issues arise, and there are no known harmful risks associated with participating in the study.
10. I understand that the information held and maintained by *(Name of Professional Doctorate Student and associated HEI details inserted)* may be used to help contact me.
11. I agree to take part in the above study.

Name of Participant [Please insert your first name and surname as electronic type text or handwritten capitalised text after the ' : ']:

Date [Please insert the date of completing this form as electronic type text or handwritten text after the ' : ']:

Signature [Please insert your signature as electronic type text or handwritten signature after the ' : ' If you have access to an electronic signature you can alternatively insert this after the ' : ']:

References supporting the development of informed consent form:

Health and Care Research Wales., Health and Social Care., NHS Health Research Authority., NHS Scotland and Regulating Medicines and Medical Devices (2018); University of Strathclyde, (2018); NHS HRA, (no dateb).

Appendix 14: Supporting outline interview guide

Version 2

Completed electronic consent form to be checked by myself prior to interview.

Telephone call made to participant at agreed date and time with participant telephone details.

Initial checks including; convenient time for participant, participants full name, telephone number and student email address to support communication if needed. Further question regarding participants preferred name.

1. Welcome and introduction including: thank you for participation, introductions (self and participant) and clarification of my role as a professional doctorate student and purpose of conversation at time of interview.
2. Overview of the aim and purpose of my research study.
3. Overview of interview process including; duration, use of broad open and prompt questions, respect to participants right to reply to questions, anonymity and confidentiality including that of others as per NMC (2018e) Code e.g. reference to practice, place of work, colleagues.
4. Overview of health and safety procedures: e.g. privacy, fire safety (in view of potential HEI requirements), participant comfort break.
5. Invite an opportunity for any participant questions which may include; participant information, right to withdraw, researcher role, confidentiality, anonymity, storage of data, presentation and dissemination of the study findings.
6. Confirmation of completed electronic informed consent form.

Interview commences: start of audio interview recording and researcher notes (non-verbal data e.g. silent pause) guided by the interview questions and prompts below.

Key open question:

- As a postgraduate nursing student, can you please tell me about your experiences of workplace support to apply your learning in practice?

Prompt questions used to clarify words or phrases:

- Can you tell me a bit more about your experience of ... e.g. workplace support, applying your learning?

Prompt questions used to seek in-depth understanding in response to an emerging experience or conversation relating to workplace support to apply learning in practice:

- Hypothetically, if you had a colleague / peer who was a PGNS what would you say to them about workplace support to apply learning in practice?
- I noticed that you mentioned ... e.g. that you felt supported / unsupported...
 - Tell me what happened when ...?
 - And what happened next ...?
- Tell me about an experience that went really well ...?
- Tell me about a challenging experience ...?
- Tell me about the first, last or most recent experience of workplace support to apply your learning in practice?
- How was that experience for you?
- What was that experience like for you?
- Is there anything important to you about your experiences of workplace support to apply your learning in practice?

Allow for silence, observations of non-verbal chronemic and paralinguistic data (Benner, Tanner and Chesla, 1996; Healy, 2011).

7. Interview close: Verbal check-in with the participant to confirm they have reached an end point of sharing / telling their experience. On confirmation of the end point, the participant will be informed that the recorded interview and researcher notes will be stopped, ending data collection and the interview process.
8. The participant will be invited to engage in a debrief conversation or given the opportunity to ask any questions. If appropriate, the participant will be signposted to any support or wellbeing services if required.
9. The participant will be informed of subsequent stages of the research process e.g. storage and use of transcription, presentation and dissemination of findings.
10. Final participant check-in opportunity for any further questions.
11. The participant will be thanked for; their time, sharing their experience and contribution to my research study.
12. Close of telephone interview meeting, telephone call ends.
13. Secure storage of data processes undertaken e.g. personal data, electronic notes, audio interview recording.

Appendix 15: Being with the hermeneutic spiral

Collectively Appendix 15-16 outline application of the hermeneutic spiral and my data interpretation framework (Heidegger, 1962/1927) (F11). I used a combination of phases, principles, templates and frameworks to support pragmatically interpreting the data, ensure rigour and alignment to philosophical principles.

Being with data transcription

This section outlines the data transcription processes that I undertook as part of my research supported by my developed data transcription template.

Figure 22: Example data transcription template

Column A	Column B	Column C	Column D
Any line numbers	Data transcription - initial	Initial reflections or aspects that call out during transcription	Any coding (may not be required at initial stage)
Interviewer (IV)			
Participant (P)			

- 1a. Initially listened and transcribed the data (F22 – Column B).
- 1b. Listened to the data for a second time, checking accuracy of transcription.
- 1c. Listened to each question-and-answer section to check the accuracy of transcription.
- 1d. Returned to listened to the data recording as a whole to check accuracy of transcription.
- 1e. Listen to the data as a whole to see if anything further announced.

For each of the above stages, I took a reflexive and interpretive approach as data interpretation commenced as data transcription occurred. This included use of Column C (F22) to capture initial reflections relating to the research question that called out during transcription or notes relating to a critical evaluation of the interview questions, challenges to presuppositions, shifting temporality, or any curious questions. Reflexive notes were highlighted in a different colour of text to ensure distinction between the transcribed data.

To support clarity and context of the transcribed text the following aspects were also completed to support working towards crafting stories:

- Bracketed areas were used to indicate tone e.g. laughter, pauses, words such as 'um'.
- Codes were used to reflect unfinished sentences, de-identify or remove potentially detailed information and inaudible words.
- Spell check of the transcript (Crowther *et al.*, 2016).

The chosen framework for rigour and ethical aspects were also considered throughout the transcription processes (F8-9; F11).

Application of reduction of data to support crafting stories

Following transcription, each transcript was transferred with initial reflexive and interpretive notes into a phase 1-2 data interpretation template (F23) prior to reduction of some textual data which I coded as hermeneutic phenomenological reduction of the data (HPRD) as part of the process of crafting stories.

The reduction of some text (F23 - Column B) of the anonymised transcripts was undertaken to openly remove irrelevant details as part of the process of showing the phenomenon being revealed (Crowther *et al.*, 2016). The phase 1-2 data interpretation template developed also aimed to support application of the hermeneutic spiral and my data interpretation framework (Heidegger, 1962/1927) (F11).

The reduction of the text within transcripts was an iterative process, initially reduction did not result in significant removal of text. Justification for this initial approach to reduction aimed to mitigate initial assumptions of irrelevant details or sections being significantly reduced prior to further interpretation which may have limited future interpretation of parts and whole of the text and the reveal of the concealed phenomenon through the crafted stories. However, this was in a balance with sustaining orientation to the research question and a focus on what was the experience for the participant (EoR: Openness). To support openness an audit trail and records of pre-HPRD and HPRD transcripts were kept as per ethical approval processes. As part of developing the crafted stories participants' conversational pauses or intonations were stated denoted as '(...)' and '...' used to denote aspects of text reduction to remove incomplete words, sentences, irrelevant repeated word or to support anonymity.

Figure 23: Phase 1-2 data interpretation template

Column A	Column B	Column C	Column D	Column E	Column F
Code link to any further notes	Hermeneutic phenomenological reduction of data (HPRD)	<p>Initial callings – Early focused lines of enquiry (including those from initial transcription)</p> <p>Does anything appear, announce, reveal, conceal? Are there any tensions, disturbances, breakdowns. What is the mood / attunement. Thrownness.</p>	<p>Central concerns or alternative ‘meanings’</p> <p>Plus, naming of conceptualisation and coding of central concerns / inviting’s for findings – the things that matter.</p>	<p>Initial links with philosophical notions, frameworks or literature</p>	<p>Shared connections and meanings.</p> <p>Within and across (mapping reference) parts and whole</p> <p>Including acknowledgement of reflexivity – fore understandings</p>
E.g. Interviewer Question					
E.g. Participants (P) response					

Appendix 16: Being present and applying the data interpretation framework

Phase 1: Early focused lines of enquiry and critical evaluation

Subsequently, I reviewed the HPRD with a focus on early lines of enquiry and critical evaluation of the data (F23 - Column C). Further using the data interpretation framework to support a reflexive approach and sustained orientation to the research question (F11). Key phase included:

1a. A focus on initial callings and early focused lines of enquiry from reading the whole HPRD from the start to finish capturing notes based on any initial callings (Dibley *et al.*, 2020) (F23). Captured early lines of enquiry were highlighted with a different colour of text in the HPRD and initial callings columns.

1b. The above process was repeated for each of data interpretation templates (F23) with a focus on reading the HPRD line by line (the parts) and capturing any further initial callings or early focused lines of enquiry. Again, I captured notes based on any initial callings applying my data interpretation framework within Column C (F23). Early lines of enquiry were highlighted with the same colour of text as phase 1a.

Phase 2: Central concerns and meanings; the 'things that matter'

Phase 2 involved continuing to use each phase 1-2 data interpretation template to interpret central concerns, alternative meanings and invitings. The naming of conceptualisation related to naming 'meanings' to support understanding of the things that mattered from the HPRD within the developing crafted stories as opposed to frequency-based themes (Smythe *et al.*, 2008). Key phases included:

2a. Making notes in column D (F23) to capture any central concerns or alternative meanings from the HPRD and initial calling notes. Once completed, any text relating to central concerns and alternative meanings across the columns were highlighted in yellow.

2b. I then reviewed the text within the HPRD, initial callings and central concerns columns (F23). Bold text was used to highlight any 'naming' of conceptualisation, invitings or the things that mattered in relation to the research question. As part of this process meanings (namings) from the templates were extracted into an initial meanings list with brackets used to provide an audit trail back to the associated section of the template (F23). At this phase, the list of meanings was not systematically ordered or grouped to sustain openness and clarity of shared meanings prior to phase 3 of data interpretation.

Figure 24 provides an example to demonstrate application of my data interpretation framework through phase 1 and phase 2 of data interpretation.

Figure 24: Example of working with the Phase 1-2 data interpretation template

Phase 2a to 2b of Data Interpretation					
Phase 1 of Data Interpretation					
Column A	Column B	Column C	Column D	Column E	Column F
Code link to any further notes	HPRD	Initial Callings – Early focused lines of enquiry - including those from initial transcription Does anything ...	Central concerns or alternative ' meanings. Plus, ...	Initial links with philosophical notions, frameworks of literature	Shared connections and meanings
IV – Section number X	As a postgraduate nursing student could you please tell me about your experiences of workplace support to apply learning in practice?				
P – section number X	Okay, (short pause) erm (sigh) so luckily some of my colleagues have already done some postgrad courses already . So, I, I think that the kind of procedure for supporting sort of nurses doing that was already in place which was good (IV: erm). Erm, I think (slight pause) one of the main things has been trying to give me time to have ?... It takes time to actually attend lectures if they're during the day or erm, even just have the time to (slight pause) sort of do some course work or, or essays or things like that. So, that was kind of the first thing that was sort of layout when I first started the course (IV: Uhum). Erm, (slight pause) some of my colleagues and also some of my ? allowed me to have time to sort of debrief and speak about like even just workload or things like that generally (IV – uhum) rather than just actually applying it to practice . Erm, but also some of the more set up sort of sessions to ...	Luck colleagues – situational experience of WPS Others already done / doing – same PG experience Already in place – procedure for support but what was this? Main things – trying - Give / Giving time – course takes time – attending Colleagues – others - Allow / Allowed / Permission – for time / voice (speaking experience) Support - opportunity to speak / talk with others - how can use in practice Speaking rather than just applying to practice- Challenge in my assumptions beyond application of learning (reflexive note)	Being with others – colleagues – others having done PGNE WPS colleagues 'Giving' time – The pragmatic, main thing support? Equipment – Others 'allowing' / permissions time WPS colleagues - 'Talking' with others – conduit ALiP – the 'before' of the ALiP.	? Already to hand ? Equipment	

Examples of developing naming's / meanings – the things that matter (Phase 2b) - Initial meanings (with numerical code link / column A reference in brackets)

1. Being with others (Associated section numbers X); 11. 'Giving time' versus 'taking time' others and self (Associated section numbers X)
17. Others allowing (Associated section numbers X); 22. Talking with others (Associated section numbers X)

Phase 3: Working with initial meanings (central concerns) becoming clearer towards shared meanings

The list of developing namings/ meanings from each of the phase 1-2 data interpretation templates were transferred into a phase 3a data interpretation template (F25). The initial meanings included code references to the phase 1-2 data interpretation templates to support return to the parts and bring together interpretive summaries as part of phase 4 -5 data interpretation. The coding also aimed to strengthen rigour by providing an audit trail relating to transparent data interpretation and crafted stories. Key phases included:

3a. I read the initial meanings columns and moved across the parts and whole of the columns to support central concerns becoming clearer across the data. Central concerns were then captured within the emerging shared meanings across and within column (F25).

Figure 25: Example of working with the Phase 3a data interpretation template

Phase 3a working with initial meanings (parts – Phase 2b) towards shared meanings (whole, phase 3a) of the ‘Things that Matter’ about: Postgraduate Nursing Students Experiences of WPS to ALiP across and within the data					
Brackets: Provide numerical code audit trail to Phase 2b data interpretation.					
Emerging shared meaning column text colour codes reflective of emerging shared meanings from initial meanings columns					
Initial Meanings from Phase 2b (5v)	Initial Meaning from Phase 2b (7t)	Initial Meanings from Phase 2b (9r)	Initial Meanings from Phase 2b (11p)	Emerging Shared Meanings across and within	Expressions of Shared Connections ‘The ‘ings / offerings’
Phase 3a of Data Interpretation					
<p>1. Being with others (1, 7, 8, 11, 12, 13)</p> <p>2. WP being there, being back (8, 10, 13)</p> <p>3. Not being there (13)</p> <p>4. Fore-havings (2, overarching, 12 ‘the helper’)</p> <p>5. WPS before PGNE begins or pre ALiP (12, 17, 18)</p> <p>6. WP supporter(s) – Colleagues, individuals (1, 2, 12, 13)</p> <p>7. The giving / offerings of support by others (12, 13)</p>	<p>1. Positive experiences (1, 9, 10, 12 (enjoyment), 19 (not having))</p> <p>2. Temporality of PGNE / experiences (1, 3, 5, 9, 12, 13, 17, 18)</p> <p>3. Mastersness; level, challenge, overwhelm (1, 2, 8, 12)</p> <p>4. Going back to university (9, 17)</p> <p>5. Private self / being (2, 6, 19)</p> <p>6. WPS not great (2, 19)</p> <p>7. Situational, everyday WP context (2)</p>	<p>1. Experiences of ‘having or not having’ WPS (1, 4, 5, 7, 8, 13, 20)</p> <p>2. WPS and WPS ALiP, others being there, not being there (5, 6, 7, 8, 10, 12, 15, 18, 20, 21, 22)</p> <p>3. WPSupporters only colleagues (20)</p> <p>4. Self-Doing and Asking (1, 4, 7, 10, 13, 20, 21)</p> <p>5. WPS others being there - direct and indirect (20)</p>	<p>1. PGNS and temporality of WP, role, banding (1)</p> <p>2. ALiP as ideas to improve practice (1)</p> <p>3. Meeting resistance to ideas by others (1, 2, 9, 11, 12)</p> <p>4. The challenges of resistance to change (11, 12)</p> <p>5. Questioning motivations of others; PGNS self ‘academic’ self wants versus impact on team (11)</p> <p>6. Looking for reasoning for resistance by others; duration of being with/in team, different values (1, 7)</p>	<p>A. WPS being there or not being there.</p> <p>B. Temporality of self-experiences</p> <p>C. The before of WPS and ALiP (fore-havings)</p> <p>D. Self being and being PGNS (fore-havings / situational tensions)</p> <p>E. Situational Everydayness (as thread through meaning too)</p> <p>F. Having and not having</p> <p>G. Giving and taking</p> <p>H. Time mattering</p> <p>I. The WP Supporters ...</p>	<p>Column returned to and completed at end of Phase 3b interpretation</p>

3b. I then reviewed the ‘emerging shared meanings’ with the previous initial meanings columns going back across the parts and whole of the phase 3a data interpretation template to identify any expressions of shared connections / offerings.

3c. Subsequently, I extracted the emerging shared meaning into a phase 3b data interpretation template and diagrammatic list (F26). This provided a further opportunity to consider the things that matter in relation to the research question and identified expressions of shared connections. I then used the diagrammatic list to develop key offering headings that would inform the presentation of the crafted stories within the written research findings termed as research offerings (F27).

Figure 26: Example of working with the Phase 3b data interpretation template

Phase 3b working with shared meanings (whole) of the 'Things that Matter' towards expressions of shared connections: Postgraduate Nursing Students Experiences of WPS to ALiP across and within the data	
Emerging Shared Meaning across and within (extracted from Phase 3a template to develop expressions of shared connections)	Expressions of Shared Connections (any callings to philosophical notions): 'The 'ings' or offerings'
<p>A. WPS being there or not being there.</p> <p>B. Temporality of self-experiences</p> <p>C. The before of WPS and ALiP (fore-havings)</p> <p>D. Self being and being PGNS (fore-havings / situational tensions)</p> <p>E. Situational Everydayness (as thread through meaning too)</p> <p>F. Having and not having</p> <p>G. Giving and taking</p> <p>H. Time mattering</p> <p>I. The WP Supporters (WP Supporting)</p> <p>J. Expecting's; Mangers versus Peer</p> <p>K. Being with 'resistance'</p> <p>L. Moods towards possibilities</p> <p>M. Temporal and situational acceptance</p> <p>N. Revealing or concealing being a PGNS influencing WPS possibilities (inviting a curious question)</p> <p>O. 'The PGNS as the WPS' / influencer in being with others (opening to new possibilities of the question revealed)</p> <p>P. Understanding ALiP and the 'doing' of PGNE from the telling of experiences.</p> <p>Q. The 'could be possibilities'</p> <p>R. Affirming being PGNS</p> <p>S. WPS from self or Self WPS</p> <p>T. Moods and actions of 'the they' WPS / WPS to ALiP</p> <p>U. Being there of WPS cultures</p> <p>V. Self reflections and changing of being a PGNS</p> <p>W. Asking (listening and hearing, responding of WPS)</p> <p>X. Bringing and Contributing ALiP</p> <p>Y. Inbetweenness of the 'tive' experience (not positive not negative)</p>	<p>1. Contextualising 'being'</p> <p>D. Self being and being PGNS (fore-havings / situational tensions); B. Temporality of self-experiences</p> <p>2. Understandings from PGNS experiences of WPS to apply learning in practice</p> <p>2a. Reflexing pre-understandings; C. The before of WPS and ALiP (fore-havings)</p> <p>2b. Workplace Supporting; I. The WP Supporters (WP Supporting); J. Expecting's; Mangers versus Peer; A. WPS being there or not being there; F. Having and not having; W. Asking (listening and hearing, responding of WPS); G. Giving and taking; H. Time mattering; ? S. WPS from self or Self WPS</p> <p>2c. Furthering understanding PGNS application of learning to practice; P. Understanding ALiP and the 'doing' of PGNE from the telling of experiences; X. Bringing and Contributing ALiP</p> <p>2d. WPS to Apply Learning to Practice; T. Moods and actions of 'the they' WPS / WPS to ALiP; K. Being with 'resistance'; Q. The 'could be possibilities'; U. Being there of WPS cultures</p> <p>2e. Accepting temporality and situational being (or being with temporal and situational acceptance); E. Situational Everydayness (as thread through meaning too); M. Temporal and situational acceptance; Y. Inbetweenness of the 'tive' experience (not positive not negative)</p> <p>3. Self-being; V. Self reflections and changing of being a PGNS; R. Affirming being PGNS; L. Moods towards future possibilities</p> <p>4. Inviting curiosity; N. Revealing or concealing being a PGNS influencing WPS and ALiP possibilities (inviting a curious question) O. 'The PGNS as the WPS' / influencer in being with others (opening to new possibilities of the question revealed); P. Understanding ALiP and the 'doing' of PGNE from the telling of experiences (challenge to pre-suppositions and ALiP back into PGNE; Professional being and time (T, U)</p>

Figure 27: Working with the emerging shared meanings and expressions of shared connections

Working with the phase 3b data interpretation template as parts and whole towards the development of thesis chapters, crafted stories and offerings across shared meanings and expressions of shared connections (F28).

3d. I then returned to complete the phase 3a data interpretation template to capture and demonstrate the identified 'expressions of shared connections – offerings'.

Figure 28: Example of returning to the Phase 3a data interpretation template

Phase 3a working with initial meanings (parts) towards shared meanings (whole, Phase 3b) of the 'Things that Matter' about: Postgraduate Nursing Students Experiences of WPS to ALiP across and within the data					
Brackets: Provide numerical code audit trail to Phase 2b data interpretation					
Emerging shared meaning column text colour codes reflective of emerging shared meanings from initial meanings columns					
Initial Meanings from Phase 2b (5v)	Initial Meaning from Phase 2b (7t)	Initial Meanings from Phase 2b (9r)	Initial Meanings from Phase 2b (11p)	Emerging Shared Meanings across and within	Expressions of Shared Connections 'The 'ings / offerings'
Phase 3a into Phase 3b 'Expressions of Shared Connections'					
<p>1. Being with others (1, 7, 8, 11, 12, 13)</p> <p>2. WP being there, being back (8, 10, 13)</p> <p>3. Not being there (13)</p> <p>4. Fore-havings (2, overarching, 12 'the helper')</p> <p>5. WPS before PGNE begins or pre ALiP (12, 17, 18)</p> <p>6. WP supporter(s) – Colleagues, individuals (1, 2, 12, 13)</p> <p>7. The giving / offerings of support by others (12, 13)</p>	<p>1. Positive experiences (1, 9, 10, 12 (enjoyment), 19 (not having))</p> <p>2. Temporality of PGNE / experiences (1, 3, 5, 9, 12, 13, 17, 18)</p> <p>3. Mastersness; level, challenge, overwhelm (1, 2, 8, 12)</p> <p>4. Going back to university (9, 17)</p> <p>5. Private self / being (2, 6, 19)</p> <p>6. WPS not great (2, 19)</p> <p>7. Situational, everyday WP context (2)</p>	<p>1. Experiences of 'having or not having' WPS (1, 4, 5, 7, 8, 13, 20)</p> <p>2. WPS and WPS ALiP, others being there, not being there (5, 6, 7, 8, 10, 12, 15, 18, 20, 21, 22)</p> <p>3. WPSupporters only colleagues (20)</p> <p>4. Self-Doing and Asking (1, 4, 7, 10, 13, 20, 21)</p> <p>5. WPS others being there - direct and indirect (20)</p>	<p>1. PGNS and temporality of WP, role, banding (1)</p> <p>2. ALiP as ideas to improve practice (1)</p> <p>3. Meeting resistance to ideas by others (1, 2, 9, 11, 12)</p> <p>4. The challenges of resistance to change (11, 12)</p> <p>5. Questioning motivations of others; PGNS self 'academic' self wants versus impact on team (11)</p> <p>6. Looking for reasoning for resistance by others; duration of being with/in team, different values (1,7)</p>	<p>A. WPS being there or not being there.</p> <p>B. Temporality of self-experiences</p> <p>C. The before of WPS and ALiP (fore-havings)</p> <p>D. Self being and being PGNS (fore-havings / situational tensions)</p> <p>E. Situational Everydayness (as thread through meaning too)</p> <p>F. Having and not having</p> <p>G. Giving and taking</p> <p>H. Time mattering</p>	<p>1. Contextualising 'being'</p> <p>D. Self being and being PGNS (fore-havings / situational tensions)</p> <p>B. Temporality of self-experiences</p> <p>2. Understandings from PGNS experiences of WPS to ALiP</p> <p>2a. Reflexing pre-understandings</p> <p>C. The before of WPS and ALiP (fore-havings)</p>

3e. Before moving onto phase 4 of data interpretation I took time to be present and dwell with interpretation of the data. This included reflexively dwelling with the phase 3a and 3b data interpretation templates to consider any further emerging meanings or expressions of shared connections. I also returned to the phase 1 and 2 data interpretation templates to critically consider whether the shared connections reflected the essence of the HPRD, demonstrating application of the hermeneutic spiral and use of the parts and whole text (Heidegger, 1962/1927; Gadamer, 2004/1960).

3f. I then presented and critically discussed the proposed expressions of shared connections relating to the crafted stories of the participants' experiences of workplace support to ALiP to my supervisory team. The supervisory team undertook the role of critical conversation partners to challenge the ways in which I came to the expressions of shared connections. I requested that my supervisory team underpinned critical conversation and challenge using aspects of Madison's (1988 cited in Benner, 1994) Principles of Evaluation, De Witt and Ploeg (2006) Expression of Rigour (F11; F29). The purpose being to support application of my data interpretation framework, methodological rigour and to mitigate misinterpretation e.g. by challenging my potential presuppositions. This also provided an opportunity for my supervisory team to critically bring their professional, research and supervisory expertise to this phase of the research process, prior to the next phase of developing interpretive summaries.

Figure 29: Prompt questions used to support supervisory team critical conversations and challenge through data interpretation

Critical conversations and supervisor challenge

Overall, does the sample of draft work align and demonstrate application of my chosen methodological and data interpretation frameworks?

At this stage,

- Is there **clear and visible sustained orientation and alignment** to hermeneutic phenomenology, the research question, and the participants sharing of experiences (balanced integration, openness, thoroughness)?
- Does data interpretation reflect **richness and emerging understandings of the phenomenon / question** (resonance)?
- Does data interpretation **reflect a sense of the whole, situatedness and temporality** (comprehensiveness)?
- Do any **emerging question** reflect those raised through data interpretation / text (appropriateness / suggestiveness)?
- Is **contextuality** reflected through interpretation (e.g. historic, fore-having and context)?
- Have I kept an **openness to possibilities of alternative meanings and explanations**?

Feedback and feedforward on draft and presentation:

- **What are the key aspects that I need to work towards** e.g. any supervisory concerns, strengths, limitations.
- Views of the level of detail **required for thesis** methodology and appendix.

Critical conversations and challenges to move forward

- How does the feedback and feedforward inform progression to Phase 4 and 5 data interpretation e.g. agreement of shared meanings / connections, starting to write draft structured chapters underpinned by interpretive summaries of shared meanings / connections.

Phase 4: Coming to final interpretations

All data interpretation templates were then used to inform phase 4 and 5 with a focus on the revealing the things that mattered within and across the data about the participants' PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP. I worked across and within all data interpretation tables, going back to the transcripts to further the crafted stories and written interpretive summaries. These activities aimed to show connections, reveal the phenomenon and illuminate meaning relating to the things that mattered orientated to PGNS experiences of workplace support to ALiP.

During this phase I sought ongoing input for my supervisory team as critically challenging partners through the submission of draft crafted stories, interpretive summaries and supervision discussion. This aimed to further application of my data interpretation framework, rigour and reflexivity within my research. For example, through the challenge of any presuppositions and my supervisory team bringing

critical and curious questions to support an openness to alternative meanings as part of data interpretation. Figure 30 provides an overview of the activities and connections as part of phase 4 and 5 data interpretation.

Figure 30: Guide developed to support Phase 4 and 5 data interpretation

Phase 5: Creating an invite to offerings from data interpretation

Phase 5 provided an opportunity to further enhance meaning and offerings from the crafted stories, interpretation summaries and development of the offering’s chapters. I approached this by exploring and integrating relevant literature to enhance the richness of understanding shared connections (F30). Continued supervisory review of the developed crafted stories and interpretative summaries also aimed to support the development of insights, depth of interpretation and rigour through the Offerings Chapters (C6-9).

Appendix 17: Communities of practice framework

In considering my community of practice, Wenger Traynor's (2015) foundational components of communities of practice Figure 31 provides an outline of the foundational components of my community of practice. My community of practice is underpinned by the context of my research study and being a professional doctorate student, registered nurse and nurse educator.

Figure 31: Identifying the foundational components of my community of practice

Adapted from: Wenger-Traynor and Wenger-Traynor (2015).

Figure 31 was also used to develop an iterative vision for a community of practice framework (F32) based on Wenger-Traynor's (2015) levels of participation. My community of practice framework was used reflexively to support opportunities for professional enquiry and learning in relation to my research topic throughout my professional doctorate. The framework also aimed to support purposeful and targeted dissemination of my research outcomes. However, it is anticipated the communities of practice will continue to evolve through further dissemination activities.

Figure 32: Community of practice framework

(SHNMSEC – School of Health, Nursing and Midwifery associated ethics committees)

Adapted from: Wenger-Traynor and Wenger-Traynor (2015).